

Towards Countering the Insider Reconnaissance Using a Combination of Shuffling and Diversity Moving Target Defense Techniques

Muhammad Faraz Hyder

Department of Software Engineering
NED University of Engineering & Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
farazh@neduet.edu.pk

Waseemullah

Department of Computer Science and IT
NED University of Engineering & Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
waseemu@neduet.edu.pk

Muhammad Umer Farooq

Department of Computer Science and IT
NED University of Engineering & Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
umer@neduet.edu.pk

Abstract-Moving Target Defense (MTD) has recently emerged as a significant cybersecurity technique. Software-Defined Networking (SDN) has the capability to design efficient network architecture due to its programmability and centralized control management. In this paper, a mechanism for the protection against insider reconnaissance has been proposed using a combination of diversity and a shuffling-based approach of MTD. In order to implement the shuffling technique, IP shuffling is used in the insider network. The IP addresses of internal hosts are mapped via real to virtual IP mapping through random IP generation from a pseudo-random mechanism. For the diversity, a multiple servers' platform is incorporated for different critical LAN services like Domain Name System (DNS), internal web services, etc. This combined diversity and shuffling approach significantly counters the insider reconnaissance targeting critical LAN services. The proposed scheme also exploited open-source IDS to block insider reconnaissance. The proposed solution was implemented using ONOS SDN controller, Mininet simulator, Snort IDS systems. The experimental results substantiate effective protection against insider network reconnaissance at a low computational cost.

Keywords-diversity; IP shuffling; insider reconicance moving target defense; software defined networking; virtual IP

I. INTRODUCTION

Threats emerging from malicious insiders that have quite a clear picture of the internal resources are becoming more and more common [1]. Network reconnaissance is the initial stage of the cyber kill chain [2]. The notion is to collect information about the system and its attributes. Many different solutions have been proposed for the protection against these types of attack [3]. However, the existing work for protection against the network reconnaissance is mainly focused on the external attackers and subsequently the reconnaissance traffic generated

from outsiders. Moving target is a cyber defense technique with the goal of constantly changing the attack surface in order to incommode the attacker to exploit the system [4-6]. This active cybersecurity has already drawn the attention of the research community in different domains including the security of cyber-physical systems [7, 8], network security [4], cloud security [9], IoT security [10], etc. Software-Defined Networking (SDN) [11] augments the MTD-based solution development due to its centralized network control, visibility, and separation of control and data planes. Therefore, several MTD solutions are based on SDN [5, 12, 13].

In this paper, a mechanism for protecting the critical DNS and Web Servers from reconnaissance attacks generating from inside the network has been developed. The notion of the work is the exploitation of the MTD mechanism for the protection of resources from insider reconnaissance. Moreover, we have adopted a combination of two different MTD techniques, i.e. Diversity and Shuffling. The work provides a three-layer protection against insider reconnaissance. In the first line of defense, the IP addresses of the nodes are periodically mapped to virtual IP addresses. These addresses are generated using pseudo-random number generators in order to enhance the randomness. The mechanism provides the functionality of all internal communication happening via a virtual IP address. The second line of defense is the platform-level diversity of DNS and Web Services. The third protection mechanism is the use of IDS to detect and block malicious insiders generating reconnaissance traffic. These three approaches substantially counter the internal reconnaissance while ensuring that the information gained by the insider during the reconnaissance is not correct as it changes after a specific period.

The fundamental motivation behind the MTD based system is to increase the uncertainty and confusion regarding the

Corresponding author: Muhammad Faraz Hyder

information collected by attackers through constantly changing the attack surface [14]. It is an active cybersecurity technique with the objective of making cybersecurity an equal playing field for both the attacker and the defender. There are three broad categories of MTD, namely diversity, redundancy, and shuffling [15]. The diversity technique provides different platforms, software, programming languages, and networks. In the case of shuffling techniques, different system parameters are shuffled either periodically or on the basis of certain events. In redundancy, replicas of the resources are created. These replicated and redundant resources substantially increase the uncertainty for the attacker. Most of the work in the domain of MTD exploits one of the basic three approaches. However, a combination of these approaches has not been exploited in detail. The amalgamations of these techniques will enhance the performance of the MTD solution and increase attacker uncertainty. SDN is getting popular in designing security solutions [16]. The centralized controlling attributes enable greater ease for designing the MTD solution. It's also popular to design MTD for network security [17, 18], cyber-physical systems [7], ad hoc networks [19, 20], cloud security [9, 19], etc.

Insider attacks are gaining momentum [1, 20]. There is an initial level of work for the protection of the first stage of the cyber kill chain, i.e. reconnaissance [21]. Authors in [22] proposed a scheme to counter external reconnaissance using SDN-based virtual topologies. In [23], the authors suggested a bio-inspired technique to mitigate insider reconnaissance attacks. Insider threat detection based upon a reality game-based approach was proposed in [24].

II. THE PROPOSED SCHEME

The proposed scheme has three levels of defense. The first one is the IP shuffling approach for different nodes and servers. The second one is based upon the diversity of platforms for Web and DNS servers. The third level of defense is the detection of insider reconnaissance via open-source IDS solution and subsequently blocking the malicious hosts generating such traffic. The high-level diagram is depicted in Figure 1.

The MTD is created using the ONOS SDN controller that consists of multiple switches and different hosts connected. Figure 2 depicts the communication between two hosts. It also presents the network flow between these hosts. The communication inside the network is happening via virtual IP addresses that are constantly changing. When a host initiates the traffic to other hosts in the network, then communication is mapped to their corresponding virtual IPs. There are several steps involved in this communication. The application running in the controller will modify the IP address of the host to convert it into a virtual IP address. The frequency for IP shuffling is set to be 30 seconds for attaining a time-based MTD mechanism. The SDN controller injects the necessary flows based upon the new IP addresses for smooth communication inside the network.

The second line of defense counters insider reconnaissance targeting specific services like DNS and Web servers. To protect against this type of attack, multiple platforms are used.

In the case of DNS, the server was prepared using Bind9 and Unbound DNS. Similarly, there are different platforms for web servers, like Apache, Nginx, and IIS. Within these platforms, different versions are also used to increase the uncertainty for the attackers. When the insider performs reconnaissance to gather information about the DNS or the Web servers, then they will get diversified platform information.

Fig. 1. The multi-layered defense approach against insider reconnaissance attacks.

Fig. 2. Traffic flow sequence during IP mapping from real to virtual and vice versa.

Fig. 3. Server platform diversification.

The proposed solution also utilized the open-source IDS Snort to detect and block the insider generating the reconnaissance traffic. This is the third line of defense against insider threats. Figure 3 depicts the server platform diversification for DNS and Web Servers. The attacker performing scanning will get different results of specific web and DNS platforms. Figure 4 represents the Snort platform analyzing the traffic for detection of reconnaissance traffic. The graphical interface of the Snort platform is depicted in Figure 5.

Fig. 4. Snort IDS platform analyzing packets.

Fig. 5. Graphical interface of the Snort IDS platform.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We used ONOS SDN Controller [25], Mininet simulator [26], and Snort IDS [27]. Regarding the server machines, we used different platforms for webserver implementation including Apache [28], Nginx [29], and IIS [30], while DNS implementation BIND9 [31], Unbound DNS [32], and PowerDNS [33] packages were selected. On the SDN network, class A IP addresses were assigned. sFlow [34] was used for collecting different statistical parameters of the network. The experimental setup was implemented on a Dell server having 32GB RAM. To generate the reconnaissance traffic, we have used Nmap [35]. The experimental topology is depicted in Figure 6. The attacker first generates the reconnaissance traffic against the other internal hosts. However, all internal transmission is based upon the mapping from real to virtual IP addresses mapping. This mapping also uses pseudo-random number generators to produce virtual IPs. The information gained by the attacker in one iteration gets invalidated due to virtual IP randomization. In the second phase, the attacker targets the DNS and Web servers' platforms.

Fig. 6. The experimental topology.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We assumed that the attacker can perform a maximum of 10 scan probes at a time. Table I represents the IP addresses on the network as observed by the attacker in different iterations. The attackers perform multiple reconnaissance attacks. The attackers observed different IP schemes and addresses due to the IP randomization through the proposed MTD scheme. This substantially increases the confusion for the attackers, because the knowledge gained in each iteration becomes void in the next. Figure 7 illustrates the IP shuffling results for different iterations. The attackers discovered different number of IP addresses in different iterations. However, in different iterations attackers may correctly identify the previous IP addresses. The percentage of getting the same IP addresses in consecutive iterations is below 5%. We considered the generic case of i^{th} and i^{th+1} iterations.

TABLE I. IP ADDRESSES DISCOVERED IN DIFFERENT ITERATIONS OF RECONNAISSANCE BY THE INSIDER ATTACKER

IP addresses discovered in:			
1 st iteration	2 nd iteration	3 rd iteration	4 th iteration
192.168.10.4	10.5.7.9	172.16.12.5	10.6.7.3
192.168.10.5	10.5.7.10	172.16.12.6	10.6.7.4
192.168.10.6	10.5.7.11	172.16.12.7	10.6.7.5
192.168.10.7	10.5.7.12	172.16.12.8	10.6.7.6
192.168.10.8	10.5.7.13	172.16.12.9	10.6.7.7
192.168.10.9	10.5.7.14	172.16.12.10	10.6.7.8
192.168.10.10	10.5.7.15	172.16.12.11	10.6.7.9
192.168.10.11	10.5.7.16	172.16.12.12	10.6.7.10
192.168.10.12	10.5.7.17	172.16.12.13	10.6.7.11
192.168.10.13	10.5.7.18	172.16.12.14	10.6.7.12

Table II depicts the diversified DNS and Web servers' platform observed by the attackers while running probing traffic against these servers. Since our scheme deploys diversified platforms, the attackers observe multiple platforms. This substantially increased the attacker confusion.

Fig. 7. IP Shuffling to counter insider reconnaissance.

Table III indicates the IP addresses of the malicious insiders generating reconnaissance traffic being blocked by the third line of defense of our scheme i.e., the IDS Snort. The first column in Table III is the number of distinct attackers, the second column indicates the maximum number of probes generated by the attacker. The third column is the multiple of the first two, i.e. the total generated probes. The IDS is able to detect and blocked on average approximately 85% of malicious attackers. Overall, the proposed scheme successfully counters the insider reconnaissance using the three-level defense level MTD technique.

TABLE II. PLATFORM DIVERSITY FOR WEB AND DNS SERVICES

Web server IP addresses	Web server platform detected	DNS server IP addresses	DNS server platform detected
192.168.10.10 10.5.7.15	Apache 2.4.48	192.168.10.13 10.5.7.18	Bind 9.12
172.16.12.11 10.6.7.9	nginx-1.21.1. IIS 10.0 Express	172.16.12.14 10.6.7.12	Unbound 1.13.2 PowerDNS 4.5.1

TABLE III. ATTACKER IP ADDRESSES BLOCKED BY IDS

No. of malicious IP addresses generating scans	No. of scans generated by an individual attacker	Total No. of insider reconnaissance attempts	Malicious IP addresses detected and blocked by the IDS	Malicious IP addresses detected and blocked by the IDS (%)
N	M	T=N×M	B	%
10	10	100	8	80%
20	10	200	17	85%
30	10	300	26	87%
40	10	400	35	88%
50	10	500	42	84%
60	10	600	53	88%
70	10	700	60	86%
80	10	800	69	86%
90	10	900	76	84%
100	10	1000	86	86%

V. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED SCHEME WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART TECHNIQUES

Table IV summarizes the comparison of the proposed scheme with the state-of-the-art existing solutions. The first advantage of our scheme is the exploitation of MTD for insider reconnaissance protection. The existing work in the literature [22-24] focuses on the protection of external reconnaissance. The second advantage of our technique is the combination of

MTD techniques for insider reconnaissance protection. Moreover, our scheme is based upon SDN which provides greater flexibility in designing MTD solutions. Only the work presented in [22] exploited SDN-based MTD for probing traffic protection. However, their work focused on external reconnaissance protection only. Hence our proposed SDN-based combination of MTD technique is quite an efficient one.

TABLE IV. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED IMPLEMENTATION WITH EXISTING SOLUTIONS

	Insider reconnaissance protection	Multiple MTD techniques	SDN-based MTD solution
Proposed	✓	✓	✓
[22]	×	×	✓
[23]	×	×	×
[24]	×	×	×

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, a protection mechanism against insider reconnaissance traffic has been developed by combining the Randomization and Diversification MTD approaches inside an SDN-based network along with IDS-based detection. The work elaborated the effectiveness of the scheme for two important services, i.e. DNS and Web. The proposed scheme provides three levels of defense: IP randomization and platform diversity for DNS and Web Servers and IDS-based detection and blockage. The developed solution effectively throttles the insider probing traffic with minimal computational cost.

In the future, we will extend our technique for privacy enhancement for critical services. An adversary while observing the DNS traffic can cause privacy disclosure by identifying the URLs visited by the users. The proposed approach can be extended to protect against such attacks.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Liu, O. De Vel, Q.-L. Han, J. Zhang, and Y. Xiang, "Detecting and Preventing Cyber Insider Threats: A Survey," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 1397–1417, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2018.2800740>.
- [2] T. Yadav and A. M. Rao, "Technical Aspects of Cyber Kill Chain," in *International Symposium on Security in Computing and Communication Systems*, Kochi, India, Aug. 2015, pp. 438–452, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-22915-7_40.
- [3] M. I. Al-Saleh, Z. A. Al-Sharif, and L. Alawneh, "Network Reconnaissance Investigation: A Memory Forensics Approach," in *10th International Conference on Information and Communication Systems*, Irbid, Jordan, Jun. 2019, pp. 36–40, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IACS.2019.8809084>.
- [4] S. Sengupta, A. Chowdhary, A. Sabur, A. Alshamrani, D. Huang, and S. Kambhampati, "A Survey of Moving Target Defenses for Network Security," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 1909–1941, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2020.2982955>.
- [5] M. F. Hyder and M. A. Ismail, "INMTD: Intent-based Moving Target Defense Framework using Software Defined Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5142–5147, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3266>.
- [6] M. H. H. Khairi, S. H. S. Ariffin, N. M. A. Latiff, A. S. Abdullah, and M. K. Hassan, "A Review of Anomaly Detection Techniques and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) on Software Defined Network (SDN)," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2724–2730, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1840>.

- [7] B. Potteiger, Z. Zhang, and X. Koutsoukos, "Integrated moving target defense and control reconfiguration for securing Cyber-Physical systems," *Microprocessors and Microsystems*, vol. 73, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 102954, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpro.2019.102954>.
- [8] M. Higgins, K. Mayes, and F. Teng, "Enhanced Cyber-Physical Security Using Attack-resistant Cyber Nodes and Event-triggered Moving Target Defence," *arXiv:2010.14173 [cs, eess]*, Oct. 2020, Accessed: Oct. 03, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2010.14173>.
- [9] M. Torquato and M. Vieira, "Moving target defense in cloud computing: A systematic mapping study," *Computers & Security*, vol. 92, May 2020, Art. no. 101742, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2020.101742>.
- [10] R. E. Navas, F. Cuppens, N. Boulahia Cuppens, L. Toutain, and G. Z. Papadopoulos, "MTD, Where Art Thou? A Systematic Review of Moving Target Defense Techniques for IoT," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 7818–7832, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.3040358>.
- [11] Y. Djeldjeli and M. Zoubir, "CP-SDN: A New Approach for the Control Operation of 5G Mobile Networks to Improve QoS," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6857–6863, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4016>.
- [12] S. Debroy *et al.*, "Frequency-Minimal Utility-Maximal Moving Target Defense Against DDoS in SDN-Based Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 890–903, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNSM.2020.2978425>.
- [13] D. P. Sharma *et al.*, "Dynamic Security Metrics for Software-Defined Network-based Moving Target Defense," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 170, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 102805, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2020.102805>.
- [14] R. Zhuang, S. A. DeLoach, and X. Ou, "Towards a Theory of Moving Target Defense," in *First ACM Workshop on Moving Target Defense*, Scottsdale, AR, USA, Nov. 2014, pp. 31–40, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2663474.2663479>.
- [15] J.-H. Cho *et al.*, "Toward Proactive, Adaptive Defense: A Survey on Moving Target Defense," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 709–745, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2019.2963791>.
- [16] O. Yurekten and M. Demirci, "SDN-based cyber defense: A survey," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 115, pp. 126–149, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2020.09.006>.
- [17] A. Chowdhary, A. Alshamrani, D. Huang, and H. Liang, "MTD Analysis and evaluation framework in Software Defined Network (MASON)," in *ACM International Workshop on Security in Software Defined Networks & Network Function Virtualization*, New York, NY, USA, Mar. 2018, pp. 43–48, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3180465.3180473>.
- [18] A. Chowdhary, S. Pisharody, and D. Huang, "SDN based Scalable MTD solution in Cloud Network," in *ACM Workshop on Moving Target Defense*, Vienna, Austria, Oct. 2016, pp. 27–36, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2995272.2995274>.
- [19] H. Alavizadeh, J. Jang-Jaccard, and D. S. Kim, "Evaluation for Combination of Shuffle and Diversity on Moving Target Defense Strategy for Cloud Computing," in *17th IEEE International Conference On Trust, Security And Privacy In Computing And Communications/ 12th IEEE International Conference On Big Data Science And Engineering (TrustCom/BigDataSE)*, New York, NY, USA, Aug. 2018, pp. 573–578, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TrustCom/BigDataSE.2018.00087>.
- [20] D. C. Le and N. Zincir-Heywood, "Anomaly Detection for Insider Threats Using Unsupervised Ensembles," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 1152–1164, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNSM.2021.3071928>.
- [21] K. Park, S. Woo, D. Moon, and H. Choi, "Secure Cyber Deception Architecture and Decoy Injection to Mitigate the Insider Threat," *Symmetry*, vol. 10, no. 1, Jan. 2018, Art. no. 14, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym10010014>.
- [22] S. Achleitner, T. F. La Porta, P. McDaniel, S. Sugrim, S. V. Krishnamurthy, and R. Chadha, "Deceiving Network Reconnaissance Using SDN-Based Virtual Topologies," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1098–1112, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNSM.2017.2724239>.
- [23] A. Nicolaou, S. Shiaeles, and N. Savage, "Mitigating Insider Threats Using Bio-Inspired Models," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 15, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 5046, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10155046>.
- [24] S. Wasko *et al.*, "Using alternate reality games to find a needle in a haystack: An approach for testing insider threat detection methods," *Computers & Security*, vol. 107, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 102314, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2021.102314>.
- [25] P. Berde *et al.*, "ONOS: towards an open, distributed SDN OS," in *3rd workshop on Hot topics in software defined networking*, Chicago, IL, USA, Aug. 2014, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2620728.2620744>.
- [26] R. L. S. de Oliveira, C. M. Schweitzer, A. A. Shinoda, and L. R. Prete, "Using Mininet for emulation and prototyping Software-Defined Networks," in *IEEE Colombian Conference on Communications and Computing*, Bogota, Colombia, Jun. 2014, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ColComCon.2014.6860404>.
- [27] M. Roesch, "Snort – Lightweight Intrusion Detection for Networks," in *Lisa*, Washington, DC, USA, Nov. 1999, pp. 229–238.
- [28] R. R. Zebari, S. R. M. Zeebaree, and K. Jacksi, "Impact Analysis of HTTP and SYN Flood DDoS Attacks on Apache 2 and IIS 10.0 Web Servers," in *International Conference on Advanced Science and Engineering*, Duhok, Iraq, Oct. 2018, pp. 156–161, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOASE.2018.8548783>.
- [29] C. Nedelcu, *Nginx HTTP Server*, Second edition. Birmingham, UK: Packt Publishing, 2013.
- [30] Y. Yan, P. Guo, B. Cheng, and Z. Zheng, "An experimental case study on the relationship between workload and resource consumption in a commercial web server," *Journal of Computational Science*, vol. 25, pp. 183–192, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2017.05.019>.
- [31] T. Jinmei and P. Vixie, "Implementation and evaluation of moderate parallelism in the BIND9 DNS server," in *USENIX Annual Technical Conference*, Berkeley, CA, United States, Jun. 2006, pp. 115–128.
- [32] S. Son and V. Shmatikov, "The Hitchhiker's Guide to DNS Cache Poisoning," in *International Conference on Security and Privacy in Communication Systems*, Singapore, Singapore, Sep. 2010, pp. 466–483, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16161-2_27.
- [33] G. Lencse and S. Repas, "Performance analysis and comparison of four DNS64 implementations under different free operating systems," *Telecommunication Systems*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 557–577, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11235-016-0142-x>.
- [34] K. Giotis, C. Argyropoulos, G. Androulidakis, D. Kalogeras, and V. Maglaris, "Combining OpenFlow and sFlow for an effective and scalable anomaly detection and mitigation mechanism on SDN environments," *Computer Networks*, vol. 62, pp. 122–136, Apr. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjp.2013.10.014>.
- [35] G. F. Lyon, *Nmap network scanning: Official Nmap project guide to network discovery and security scanning*. Sunnyvale, CA, USA: Insecure. Com LLC, 2008.

A Contribution to the Thermal Field Evaluation at the Tool-Part Interface for the Optimization of Machining Conditions

Nasreddine Benhadji Serradj
 Department of Mechanical Engineering
 University of Tlemcen
 Tlemcen, Algeria
 kawther4499@yahoo.fr

Abdelillah Djamel Kara Ali
 Department of Mechanical Engineering
 University of Tlemcen
 Tlemcen, Algeria
 dj_kara_ali@yahoo.fr

Mohamed El Amine Ghernaout
 Department of Mechanical Engineering
 University of Tlemcen
 Tlemcen, Algeria
 e_amine2001@yahoo.fr

Abstract-In this study, an experimental measurement methodology is implemented that allows obtaining consistent temperature data during the turning operation of semi-hard C20 steel using SNMG carbide insert, allowing us to have better control at the tool-part interface. The interactions of the phenomena influencing the cut led our choices on the development of a correlation model for the analysis and prediction of the relationships between the machining parameters by measurement of the temperature. The measurement procedure implemented for the temperature estimate is based on the use of an FLIR A325sc type infrared camera mounted and protected by a device on the machine tool. The Taguchi method was chosen to find the relationships between the input factors (cutting speed (V_c), feed rate (a), depth of cut (p)), and the output factor (temperature (T)). In the future, we will develop a numerical validation model to simulate the machining process in order to predict temperatures.

Keywords-machining conditions; temperature measurement; infrared camera; thermal transfer; Taguchi plan; emissivity

I. INTRODUCTION

During machining, maximum heat occurs at the tool-part interface. It affects, among others, tool life, surface finish, and cutting forces. At the heart of the process, two main phenomena interact: a very strong plastic deformation in the shear zones and the friction of the chip on the cutting face of the tool. We can also add the friction of the draft face on the newly generated surface (Figure 1). Since the first experimental work of Taylor (1905-1907) on the influence of temperature in machining, significant progress has been made in improving knowledge about metal cutting. The bibliographic research carried out in [1] on the different thermal aspects during machining shows the difficulties of direct measurement.

Authors in [2] showed that several methods are possible for measuring temperatures during the cutting process:

- Measurement by metallurgical analysis of the cutting insert after machining. Authors in [3] showed that it is possible to determine the temperature map in the cutting tool as a function of the phase transformations detected during a metallographic analysis of a high speed steel tool. This is an a posteriori measurement method.
- Measurement by thermocouples implanted in the cutting insert. In [4], it was shown that for this type of thermal measurement, the temperature mapping is carried out from point readings obtained by thermocouples implanted in the insert of the cutting tool.
- Temperature evaluation by thermocouples directly in contact with the tool-part pair. In this particular case, only an average value of the temperature can be obtained. Authors in [5] proposed the use of the tool-part contact as a hot junction for the thermocouple. The two preceding methods present major hazards relating to the installation of thermocouples.

Fig. 1. Sources of heat generation in machining.

Our job focused on taking the temperature with an infrared camera without contact. The response time is fast, thus allowing the capture of the intermittent heat generation. This capture can allow us to regulate the cutting parameters if there is a sudden increase in temperature. The camera is mounted and protected by a device on the machine tool.

II. THERMAL FLOWS

Almost all of the chip formation work is degraded in the form of heat. This results in a high temperature rise in the chip formation zone. The correlation between cutting conditions and temperature is shown in Figure 2, with regard particular to the primary influence of the cutting speed factor.

Fig. 2. Correlation between cutting conditions and temperature.

In this section, we will recall the modes of heat transfer and the influence factors expressed in this method of measurement. Surface temperature measurements implement three heat transfer modes that we briefly recall below along with the relationships of the listed laws.

- Conduction: corresponds to the transfer of heat within an opaque medium, without displacement of matter, under the influence of a temperature difference. Fourier's law (1) describes this transfer mechanism [9-10]:

$$\phi = \lambda \cdot S \cdot \frac{T_1 - T_2}{\Delta x} \quad (1)$$

- Convection: corresponds to the transfer of heat between a solid and a moving fluid (liquid or gas). Newton's law (2) describes this transfer mechanism [9-10]:

$$\phi = h \cdot S \cdot (T_p - T_a) \quad (2)$$

- Radiation: corresponds to the transfer of heat in the form of an electromagnetic wave, emitted by a surface. Stefan's law (3) describes this transfer mechanism [9-10]:

$$\phi = \sigma \cdot S \cdot \epsilon_p \cdot (T_p^4 - T_a^4) \quad (3)$$

To obtain consistent temperature data at the tool-part interface, an experimental measurement methodology is proposed using acquisition instrumentation, equipped with an infrared camera and a unit for processing the measured values.

III. MEASUREMENT BY INFRARED RADIATION

The large amount of heat released in the chip formation zone and the difficulties of evacuation of this generated energy, result in very high and localized temperatures. These in turn have a significant impact on the dimensional and geometric precision of the produced surfaces and the lifetime of the cutting tools. The knowledge of the thermal field is therefore an essential element in the analysis and control of these phenomena.

A. Infrared Thermography

Thermal imaging is a contactless technology that converts infrared waves into a temperature image. Figure 3 shows schematically the overall principle of this method.

Fig. 3. Radiometric chain of the camera.

B. Theoretical Elements

Increase in temperature due to machining causes electromagnetic radiation described by Planck's law. This law, for a black body, is the basis of temperature measurement by radiation analysis. It has a spectral distribution, which depends on the material. Its intensity or its luminance can be measured and its analysis allows finding the temperature [6].

$$L_\lambda = \frac{C_1}{\lambda^5 (e^{\lambda T} - 1)} \quad (4)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are constants: $C_1 = 1.191 \times 10^{-16} \text{W} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{sr}^{-1}$ and $C_2 = 1.438 \times 10^{-2} \text{m} \cdot \text{K}$, h is the Planck constant, k the Boltzmann constant, c the speed of light, T the absolute temperature in Kelvin degrees, and λ the wavelength in m [9-10].

Emissivity ϵ is a property of surfaces depending on the nature of the material, its surface quality, the wavelength and the angle of observation. Its prior evaluation is essential to determine the absolute value of the temperature from the light flux signal [7].

$$\epsilon = \frac{L_\alpha}{L_\beta} \quad (5)$$

where L_α is the luminance of the measured object and L_β the luminance of the black body [9-10].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Although the undertaken studies so far in the area of cutting (mechanism of chip formation, behavior of tools, thermal appearance, and damage of the cutting edges) have made significant progress in the understanding of the process, it is necessary to update and continue them, in order to meet the

new conditions of the industrial context. The complexity and interactions of the many factors involved in the cutting phenomena require specific experiments for each material, in order to define the best choice of tools and corresponding optimal cutting conditions, based on the analysis of their wear behaviors.

A. Means of Realization

In order to take into account the dominant elements of machining, the current analysis was restricted to steel and conventional machining processes.

- Machine tool used: The machining was carried out on a conventional parallel lathe made by TOS TRENCIN (Figure 4). It is a rigid, powerful, precise and well-sealed machine. The main motor of the machine is asynchronous type.
- Machined material: The material used for these tests is the C20 non-alloy steel for heat treatments frequently used in industry. The chemical composition and physic properties are presented in Tables I and II.

Fig. 4. Radiometric chain of the camera.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION

Element	C	Fe	Mn	P	S
%	0.138	98.11	1.062	0.013	0.011

TABLE II. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Property	Value	Units
Elastic modulus	2.049999984e+011	N/m ²
Mass density	7850	Kg/m ³
Thermal conductivity	52	W/(m*K)
Specific heat	486	J/(kg*K)

- Insert and tool holders: The insert used in our tests were chosen according to the machining conditions and a small beak radius ($r = 0,8$ mm). The reference selected is SNMG 12-04-08 (Figure 5). The choice of the tool holder was oriented on a PCLN R 20-20 K12. The properties of the insert are shown in Table III.
- Measurement process used: The objective of this contribution is to measure temperatures in the chip formation zone in order to collect thermal data from the cutting mechanism. The quality of the information sought

requires that it be captured as close as possible to the chip creation area. Temperatures were recorded using the FLIR A325sc thermal camera (Figure 6). The camera is coupled with FLIR Research IR Max measuring software for maximum intuitiveness in display, recording and advanced thermal data processing (Figure 7) [8].

TABLE III. INSERT PROPERTIES

Wafer shape	SNMG
Insert size	120408
Matter	Carbide
Insert thickness (mm)	4.76
Edge length (mm)	12
Insert radius (mm)	0.8
Draft angle (°)	0
Number of cutting edges	8

Fig. 5. Pad and its diagram of the range of applications.

Fig. 6. (a) Thermal camera FLIR A325sc, (b) the experimental device.

Fig. 7. Chain of acquisition and processing of the thermal data.

- Calibration of the camera: The camera is calibrated in the factory to make accurate measurements and thermal images. However, knowledge of the calibration curve (Figure 8) is essential for advanced control of radiometric measurement.

Fig. 8. Calibration curves for the FLIR A325sc.

- Influence of emissivity: When making an infrared measurement, we record the energy ϕ emitted by the studied body and refer to Stefan's law of radiation of the black body:

$$\phi = \sigma T^4 \quad (6)$$

where σ is the Boltzmann constant and T the temperature of the studied body, identified with an ideal black body [9-10].

In addition, the measurement requires knowledge of the emissivity coefficient of the studied body. For this, we put the tool (insert) in an oven whose temperature is known thanks to a standard thermometer. After reaching thermal equilibrium, in situ measurements were taken with the camera. Knowing the temperature in the oven, the temperature measured during machining, and the emissivity coefficient displayed on the camera, the actual coefficient of emissivity of the tool is deduced during machining using (6) [9]. We have taken the same approach to determine the emissivity of the machined material.

B. Preliminary Tests

In order to verify the possibility of recording the influence and the variability of the thermal fluctuations during the machining, a first series of tests was conducted to control the sensitivity and the capacity of our measuring system to capture and analyze the thermograms (Figure 9). These preliminary tests were carried out under the variability conditions summarized in Table IV, in which the results of the experiment for the qualification and validation of the measurement method are grouped. Over the length of the machining, we chose 10 positions for the temperature reading, using the camera software. These points are taken during the machining stabilization period. The experimental results illustrated in Figure 10 allow us to conclude that the temperature variations are very small in the steady state for invariant cutting parameters. On the other hand, the heat flux generated during machining is largely evacuated by the chip.

In Figure 11, the curves represent the temperatures of the chip, the machined surface and the cutting edge of the tool. Two curves (tool-part) have practically the same shape and very close temperature thresholds (near 100°C). On the other

hand, the chip temperature curve shows a marked increase in temperature (around 300°C), which confirms the theoretical results which state that the chip evacuates the most important temperature flow.

Fig. 9. Thermograms: tool-part.

TABLE IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Position	Part	Tool	Chip
1	114.6	79.2	300.7
2	117.6	89.02	298.7
3	117.5	93.3	299.5
4	114.9	95.5	302
5	117.6	96.2	295.5
6	122	96.3	288.3
7	118	97	299.3
8	120.1	97.3	288
9	113.3	99.9	291.3
10	113.4	98.6	289.2
Average	116.90	94.23	295.25

Fig. 10. Temperature variations (quickplot).

Fig. 11. Temperature variations.

V. REFERENCE TESTS

The large number of variables controlling the manufacturing process requires mathematical models to represent this process. These models should be developed using only the most significant parameters. Tests are used to build first and second order models by multiple regression methods. The aim of developing mathematical models is to understand the combined effect of the parameters involved and to facilitate the optimization of the machining process. During the carried out tests, various machining parameters such as cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut, vary according to the design of experiments as independent variables in order to be linked to the response, namely the cutting temperature [T = f(v, f, p)], by prediction equations of the type:

$$T = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 \quad (7)$$

The choice of cutting conditions was conditioned by the range of rotational speeds of the machine and the temperature measurement range of the infrared camera. Table V summarizes the results of the experiments. Figure 12 shows the effect of cutting conditions on temperature variation. Changing the depth of cut has a very high effect on the cutting temperature while the cutting speed and feed rate have a moderate effect on the cutting temperature.

TABLE V. CUTTING PARAMETERS

Parameter	Code	Levels			
		1	2	3	4
Cutting speed Vc (m/min)	X ₁	78	112	157	220
Feed rate a (mm/rev)	X ₂	0.08	0.11	0.14	0.20
Depth of cut P (mm)	X ₃	0.25	0.5	0.75	1
Turning conditions	Machining without lubrication				

Fig. 12. The effects of cutting conditions on temperature.

After treatment and elimination upstream of the insignificant terms of the model, we obtain the following prediction equation that relates the input and output parameters:

$$T_{\text{tool}} = 9.7 + 0.0877 V_c + 139.7 a + 74.96 P \quad (8)$$

A. Effects of Cutting Speed on Temperature

We can see the different levels of the temperature curves according to the cutting speed in Figure 13. They increase with the evolution of the depth of cut. At 112m/min cutting speed (point A) a temperature peak can be observed which can be

explained by unfavorable cutting conditions, generating entanglement of the chip around the cutting edge, as shown by the thermogram of Figure 14. At high cutting speed (point B), the chip flow is restored, the cutting temperature drops shown by the thermogram (Figure 15).

Fig. 13. Temperature according to cutting speed.

Fig. 14. Thermogram at point A.

Fig. 15. Thermogram at point B.

Fig. 16. Temperature according to the feed rate.

B. Effects of Feed Rate on Temperature

Figure 16 shows the different levels of the temperature curves depending on the feed rate. They increase with increasing depth of cut. At the feed rate of 0.11tr/min (Point C) a lower temperature can be observed which can be explained by cutting conditions which favor the flow of the chip around the cutting edge, as shown in the thermogram in Figure 18. At high cutting speed (Point D), the chip remains at the cutting edge, which generates an increase in temperature shown by the thermograms in Figures 17 and 18.

Fig. 17. Thermogram at point C.

Fig. 18. Thermogram at point D.

C. Effects of Depth of Cut on Temperature

The different levels of the temperature curves according to the depth of cut are exhibited in Figure 19. They increase with the evolution of the cutting speed.

Fig. 19. Temperature as a function of depth of cut.

At the 0.5mm depth of cut (point E) a temperature peak can be observed which can be explained by cutting conditions favoring the flow of the chip around the cutting edge, as shown

by the thermogram of Figure 20. With a depth of 0.75mm (point F), the chip is evacuated more easily, which generates a decrease in temperature (thermogram Figure 21).

Fig. 20. Thermogram at point E.

Fig. 21. Thermogram at point F.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Knowledge of the distribution of the temperature flow between the cutting tool, the chip and the workpiece provides useful information for optimizing manufacturing conditions. Therefore, it is essential to determine the relationship between the cutting parameters and the temperature distribution. The current paper focuses on the infrared thermography procedure for establishing an experimental methodology, which allows the evaluation of the cutting temperature during the machining operations for different cutting parameters. The experimentation allowed us to evaluate the distribution of the temperature flow on the machined surface of the part, the chip, and the cutting edge. For a large cutting penetration, the friction increases for both the tool and the chip and generates an increase in temperature, so we took (from thermograms) the maximum temperatures of the tool and the chip which were 112.63°C and 275.1°C. The optimal conditions for the good quality of the part are moderate temperatures for high cutting speeds and small depths of cut. The chosen infrared camera used in the experiments has many advantages such as the ability to take measurements without contact with a very little disturbance between the surface of the studied object and its surrounding environment, its measurement capacity in real time, a wide range of operating temperatures, and the ability to adapt to all types of materials. The obtained results during our tests allowed concluding on one hand that the temperature variations are very weak in permanent regimes for invariant cutting parameters and on the other that the heat flux generated during machining is largely evacuated by the chip. The major difficulty in taking the machining sequence by the camera is the winding of the chip, hence the need to choose good cutting

conditions and to have good protection and fixation of the camera.

In the future, our work will be extended to other materials. We will also try to define a correlation between the cutting temperature and the wear of the tool during machining. We are encouraged by the results of this work to extend to higher speeds (UGV) and to use a more efficient infrared camera for larger measurement range.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. F. Brito, S. R. Carvalho, and S. M. M. Lima E Silva, "Experimental investigation of thermal aspects in a cutting tool using comsol and inverse problem," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 86, pp. 60–68, Jul. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2015.03.083>.
- [2] O. Pantalé, R. Rakotomalala, and M. Touratier, "An ALE three-dimensional model of orthogonal, oblique metal cutting processes," *International Journal of Forming Processes*, vol. vol.1, pp. 371–388, Sep. 1998.
- [3] P. K. Wright and E. M. Trent, "Metallographic methods of determining temperatures gradients in cutting tools," 1973.
- [4] W. Bouzid, "Etude expérimentale et numérique de la coupe orthogonale," Ph.D. dissertation, Arts et Métiers ParisTech, Paris, France, 1993.
- [5] D. A. Stephenson, "Tool-Work Thermocouple Temperature Measurements—Theory and Implementation Issues," *Journal of Engineering for Industry*, vol. 115, no. 4, pp. 432–437, Nov. 1993, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2901786>.
- [6] I. Bonnet and J. Gabelli, "Probing Planck's law at home," *European Journal of Physics*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 1463–1471, 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0143-0807/31/6/012>.
- [7] N. M. Ravindra, S. Rajyalaxmi Marthi, and A. Bañobre, "Introduction to radiative properties," in *Radiative Properties of Semiconductors*, Morgan & Claypool Publishers, 2017, <http://doi.org/10.1088/978-1-6817-4112-3ch1>.
- [8] FLIR, "FLIR SC325 Datasheet." FLIR, 2010.
- [9] D. Kara Ali, N. Benhadji Serradj, and M. E. A. Ghernaout, "Qualification and Validation of an in-situ Measurement Method of the Machining Temperature," in *Mechanism, Machine, Robotics and Mechatronics Sciences*, vol. 58, R. Rizk and M. Awad, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2019, pp. 15–27, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-89911-4_2.
- [10] J.-L. Battaglia, A. Kusiak, and C. Pradere, *Introduction aux transferts thermiques: cours et exercices corrigés*. Paris, France: Dunod, 2020.
- [11] M. H. El-Axir, M. M. Elkhabeery, and M. M. Okasha, "Modeling and Parameter Optimization for Surface Roughness and Residual Stress in Dry Turning Process," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 2047–2055, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1560>.
- [12] N. M. M. Reddy and P. K. Chaganti, "Investigating Optimum SiO₂ Nanolubrication During Turning of AISI 420 SS," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3822–3825, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2537>.
- [13] M. PradeepKumar, K. Amarnath, and M. SunilKumar, "A Review on Heat Generation in Metal Cutting," *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 193–197, Aug. 2015.
- [14] G. Sidebotham, "Heat Transfer Modes: Conduction, Convection, and Radiation," in *Heat Transfer Modeling: An Inductive Approach*, G. Sidebotham, Ed. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 61–93, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14514-3_3.
- [15] D. Pajani and L. Audaire, "Thermographie - Technologies et applications: Thermographie et utilisation des caméras thermiques," *Techniques de l'Ingénieur*, Mar. 2013, Accessed: Oct. 06, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.techniques-ingenieur.fr/base-documentaire/genie-industriel-th6/mise-en-uvre-de-la-maintenance-42136210/thermographie-r2741/thermographie-et-utilisation-des-cameras-thermiques-r2741v2niv10002.html>.
- [16] O. Riou, P.-O. Logerais, and J.-F. Durastanti, "Quantitative study of the temperature dependence of normal LWIR apparent emissivity," *Infrared Physics & Technology*, vol. 60, pp. 244–250, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infrared.2013.05.012>.
- [17] J. Goupy and L. Creighton, *Introduction aux plans d'expériences*, 3rd ed. Paris, France: Dunod, 2006.
- [18] S. Atlati, "Développement d'une nouvelle approche hybride pour la modélisation des échanges thermiques à l'interface outil-copeau: application à l'usinage de l'alliage d'aluminium aéronautique AA2024-T351," Ph.D. dissertation, Université de Lorraine, Lorraine, France, 2012.

A Deep Learning Approach for Malware and Software Piracy Threat Detection

Khalid Aldriwish

Department of Computer Science
College of Science and Humanities
Majmaah University
Majmaah, Saudi Arabia
k.aldrish@mu.edu.sa

Abstract-Internet of Things (IoT) -based systems need to be up to date on cybersecurity threats. The security of IoT networks is challenged by software piracy and malware attacks, and much important information can be stolen and used for cybercrimes. This paper attempts to improve IoT cybersecurity by proposing a combined model based on deep learning to detect malware and software piracy across the IoT network. The malware's model is based on Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs). Apart from this, TensorFlow Deep Neural Networks (TFDNNs) are introduced to detect software piracy threats according to source code plagiarism. The investigation is conducted on the Google Code Jam (GCJ) dataset. The conducted experiments prove that the classification performance achieves high accuracy of about 98%.

Keywords-cybersecurity; malware; software piracy; deep learning; Internet of Things

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) approaches are overgrowing through machine learning and deep learning technologies. Using AI in applications improves accuracy and efficiency. The AI approach supports innovations in various fields [1-10]. The Internet of Things (IoT), as an interconnection of device-based sensors through the Internet, requests a safety mechanism based on AI methods to prevent attacks and intrusion. IoT devices are defined by unique Radio Frequency Identifier (RFID) tags and are connected via nodes. The IoT interconnection mechanism ensures distant monitoring and controlling [9]. The IoT connectivity is a universal mechanism to support cloud computing, service industries, and innovative applications. With the number of connected devices via the Internet exceeding 50 billion by 2021 [10], data security becomes a significant challenge. The IoT technology faces a massive amount of data due to the growth of communication networks. Attackers benefit from the IoT architecture to handle attacks through IoT devices. Pirated software and malware infection have been used to affect the security of the industrial IoT cloud [11]. These methods attempt to reuse source code illegally and to use the system as a regular user. The attacker writes a malware code based on reverse engineering through the logic of the original code [12]. This kind of attack is a severe threat because it allows unlimited downloads of pirated

software. This issue is solved by using an intelligent software plagiarism technique that finds the stolen source code in the illegal software. Intelligent software plagiarisms are based mainly on test-based analysis and structure. The proposed techniques use many methods: similarity identification, clone detection, software birthmark investigation, and software bug analysis [12]. Software plagiarism based on structure technique focuses on the basic structure of the source code, graph behavior, function call graph, and syntax trees. These methods do not catch the attack if another type of programming can preserve the same behavior as the original software.

Providing secure IoT networks is the purpose of many malware detection and intelligent software plagiarism techniques. Infecting the privacy of IoT nodes, smartphones, and computer systems is the goal of malware attacks. The different ways to detect malware are: Statistic identification analysis and dynamic identification analysis. The second one learns malware patterns when the code is executed in real-time. The malware is detected considering function parameters' exploration, function calls, visual investigation of codes, dataflow, and instruction traces. Some detection tools based on the dynamic behavior of malicious codes such as Anubis, TT analyzer, and CW Sandbox [13] are provided online. These tools, characterized by the monitoring of every dynamic behavior, suffer from the time-consuming issue. Statistic methods attempt to capture the layout information without real-time execution. As a statistic method, the signature identification technique detects windows-based malware via specification signatures as opcode frequency, string signature, and control flowgraph. Statistic methods are supported by disassembling tools to extract the hidden patterns from binary executables [14]. Byte sequence technique is considered a statistic method and removes n-byte sequences from patterns.

A. Software Piracy Detection

In most software plagiarism cases, the software is written on a single programming language and crackers change the control flow using a similar programming language. Authors in [15] proposed a method-based software benchmark to detect threats in java source code. The authors retrieved structural features by extracting the control flow of source codes. Then the similarity is computed between benchmarks of two source

codes. Authors in [16] attempted to acquire the similarity between codes through a hybrid approach. The compiler level features technique was considered. The authors performed an unsupervised learning approach to detect plagiarism. The proposed method computes the similar functionalities of different sources codes. Authors in [17] introduced an approach to achieve the similarity features between C++ and C source codes. The proposed method was based on a source forager search engine to extract features of every code. The control flow of the source code is identified based on the shape functionalities of the code. Authors in [18] computed the difference between two source codes using a logic-based approach. The semantics for differences were captured using symbolic execution and preconditions techniques. Authors in [19] tried to detect plagiarism related to student's assignments using the Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) method. The authors aimed to compare source codes with regard to syntactic structures. This objective was achieved by combining LSA with PlaGate to identify the similarity. Then, the syntax tree detected the syntactic view and the abstract of the source code. Authors in [20] attempted to detect similar source code fragments using the parse tree kernel. The authors focused on Java files and proved that the achieved results were inaccurate. Therefore, a fingerprinting method was proposed instead of the parse tree kernel. Authors in [21] introduced a behavioral approach called BPlag to detect source code plagiarism. The behavior was extracted using symbolic execution. Then, the code was assimilated to a novel graph-based format. The plagiarism was computed according to these graphs. The authors proved that their approach was more accurate and more robust to plagiarism-hiding than 5 source code plagiarism tools. Authors in [22] presented a combined approach, using a Greedy String Tiling and Explicit Semantic Analysis method named EsaGst. The proposed method supported the detection of source code plagiarism independently from the programming language. The evaluation was conducted using different languages, including Java, C++, Python, PHP, and Java-Script. The results proved the good performance of the EsaGst approach.

B. Malware Detection

Malware detection is an open scientific topic. Authors in [23] used a machine learning approach to classify worms from the binaries of benign files based on a sequence of variable length instructions. The authors built a dataset including 1330 benign files and 1444 worms. The experimental results achieved a classification accuracy of around 96%. Authors in [24] combined the SVM-based machine learning and N-opcode sequences to detect malware. The detection process included the critical instruction sequence and cosine similarity. Findings demonstrated that similar malware possessed common core signatures. The proposed malware detection method achieved an accuracy around 98%. Authors in [25] introduced a method based on the dynamic analysis approach to highlight the limits of the static analysis approach. The author proposed an obfuscation model to execute binary samples and identify significant behavioral features within a virtual machine. The evaluation proved the insufficiency of the static analysis approach in the case the malware is obfuscated. Authors in [26] attempted to automate malware detection by identifying

abnormal behavior within the program. The proposed idea provides little information about malicious behavior. Authors in [27] applied a classification approach based on the clustering method. The aim was to classify malware samples based on behavioral features. The proposed method was added to the Anubis system to track malware samples. The tracking report detailed the in-depth activities of the malware samples. Authors in [28] aggregated between statistic and dynamic analysis to detect malware accurately. The statistical analysis managed the operational codes based on frequency occurrences. The dynamical analysis executed traces of system calls and executable files. Tacking the advantages of each approach, the authors achieved a better result than statistic or dynamic case separately. Authors in [29] utilized Convolutional Neural Networks for malware detection. The announced purpose was to reduce time, size, and resource overhead. The proposed method used image-based malware for classification with 98.5% accuracy. Authors in [30] tried to detect malware using the image similarity technique. The authors employed benign and vision research lab datasets to evaluate their method. Samples from executable files were converted to binary code. In the testing phase, the accuracy reached 98%. Authors in [31] established an enhanced method to detect malware variants based on the deep learning approach. The authors intended to obtain high accuracy at a low time cost. The suggested process transformed the malicious code into a grayscale image, then classified samples using the CNN based on significant features. The authors overcame the imbalance of data by applying the bat algorithm. According to the experimental results based on the research lab dataset, the computed accuracy and speed were sufficient. Authors in [32] applied a machine learning method with processor core events to detect malware with a hardware event counter to ensure the detection. The purpose was to detect the SPECTRE using on-chip hardware on time. The proposed hardware architecture was based on software agents. To predict malicious activity, the authors used several machine learning classifiers. The predictive results achieved an accurate detection.

The current paper's contributions can be summarized as follows:

- A Deep Learning approach based on the TensorFlow Deep Neural Network is proposed to detect software piracy through source code plagiarism.
- A Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) is proposed to detect malware through binary visualization.
- The two models are combined into the same architecture for the IoT case.
- The proposed architecture is evaluated according to adequate datasets.

II. THE PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Figure 1 describes the proposed architecture, which is composed of malware and software piracy detection. Cloud data storage faces many kinds of attacks. Cyber security threat samples are stored in 4 databases. Database 1 contains network traffic data. Database 2 stores a list of earlier known malware data. Database 3 comprises new signatures and features of

detected malware. Database 4 includes pirated software via IoT devices. These databases contain a massive amount of data and request a lot of computational time and cost. Firstly, the network traffic data database (D1) transmits raw data to the

detection module, which identifies the kind of attack (malware or software piracy). The classification is ensured based on learning signatures stored in databases D2 and D4.

Fig. 1. The proposed architecture for malware and software piracy.

A. Software Piracy Threat Detection Model

The proposed software piracy attack detection is based on deep learning. The detection based on plagiarism methodology is captured through different types of source codes. The pirated version uses the same logic as the original software. Once the traffic data are classified as software piracy, the source codes are tokenized to decrease the dimensions of the data. In that step, significant features are extracted using the TensorFlow framework. The Keras API for deep learning is applied to capture source code plagiarism. The first database (D1) includes the network traffic data collected from Google Code Jam (GCJ) database. The D1 data are built from 100 programmers and contain about 400 source code documents. Software piracy threat detection is preceded by a preprocessing step. The purpose of this step is to divide the source code into small pieces. Then, the semi-code is converted into useful information, and noise is removed. Meaningful tokens are obtained during the tokenization step. Finally, the contribution of each token is zoomed through a weighting mechanism, see (1), based on the Logarithm of Term Frequency algorithm [33] and the Term Frequency and Inverses Document Frequency (TFIDF).

$$W(t, Doc, DS) = TF(t, Doc) \times IDF(t, DS) \quad (1)$$

where t defines the token, Doc defines a document, DS represent all the documents used in the dataset, TF defines the Term Frequency function, and IDF defines the Inverse Document Frequency function.

Deep learning is conducted by Tensorflow, which is used for high-level computations. The pirated software is identified through extracted similar codes. A fully connected network with dense layers is utilized for input and output data. The first layer, which contains 100 neurons, receives the data. The second layer is composed of 50 neurons. The third layer consists of 30 neurons. The output variable uses the fourth dense layer to identify the target of the plagiarized code. Deep learning is able to solve the overfitting problem using the drop out layer. The pattern is computed based on the rectifier (ReLU) activation method [34]:

$$f(x) = x^+ = \max(0, x) \quad (2)$$

where x defines the input of the equivalent neurons.

The multi-class problem is conducted using the sigmoid method defined by:

$$S(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \quad (3)$$

The deep learning approach used to detect software piracy provides the following benefits: (1) the model is trained automatically, (2) the design supports various computational types, (3) services are reliable while updating and extending the model, and (4) the proposed model supports big networks.

B. Malware Threat Detection Model

The proposed malware threat detection model consists of two steps: preprocessing and deep convolutional neural network. Raw binary files generate the color images and the problem is becoming an image classification problem. The adopted color system is grayscale, and features are extracted from the color image. A feature reduction method is used to enhance the classification performance. It aims to reduce the feature set. The generation of the color image from a binary file proceeds as follows: (1) generate the hexadecimal strings, (2) divide the hexadecimal strings into a chunk of 8-bit vector, (3) convert each 8-bit vector to a two-dimensional matrix, and (4) plot the two-dimensional space. Then, the Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) is utilized to identify the malware. The DCNN receives training images. The Convolution layer's purpose is to reduce noise and enhance signal features. It reduces the over-fitting problem. The convolutional layer performs the computations using (4):

$$x_j^n = f(\sum_{i \in M_j} x_j^{n-1} * k_{ij}^n + b_j^n) \quad (4)$$

where f defines the activation function, M is the cluster of given maps, b_j^n presents the bias consistent, and k_{ij}^n denotes the convolution kernel.

The accuracy of the proposed DCNN is improved through the convolutional kernel width. The pooling layer ensures the reduction of the data overhead and selects useful information. It minimizes the consequence of image distortion using (5):

$$x_j^n = f(Pool(x_j^{n-1}) + b_j^n) \quad (5)$$

where $Pool()$ ensures the pooling task.

The classification of the output of the pooling layer is performed at the fully connected layer. It aims to enhance the model by reducing the over-fitting issue. The noise is removed using filters. Then, the training of the proposed DCNN is performed using Softmax-Cross-Entropy loss [35], as defined by:

$$L = -\log\left(\frac{e^{r_k}}{\sum_k e^{r_k}}\right) \quad (6)$$

where r_k denotes the rank of the k class. The learning of the parameters attempted to minimize the loss is conducted with the use of the Adam optimizer.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PART

A. Software Piracy Detection Performance Evaluation

The evaluation is based on the code similarity between the pirated software and the source software using the GCJ dataset [36]. The similarity is checked using Codeleaks plagiarism tool [12]. The dataset is proceeded by the preprocessing step to

provide the valuable tokens of each source code as root word, stemming, token's length, and token's frequency. Then, the TFIDF and LogTF algorithms are applied to conduct token weighting. The accuracy of the classification is improved according to the number of neurons. The evaluation is shown in Figure 2 based on validation accuracy, validation loss, and loss.

Fig. 2. (a) Loss and (b) accuracy results for source codes.

The loss curves (Figure 2) start from 0.75 and follow the same trend until 0.3. A fluctuation can be seen in the loss curve, but both curves are reduced in a similar way. From the accuracy curves, we can see that the proposed software piracy threat detection model achieved an accuracy of about 98%.

B. Malware Detection Performance Evaluation

The proposed model measures the effect of malware image ratios. The image size is taken as 180×180 and 196×196. We used the Leopard Mobile dataset [37], which is composed of 2486 benign and 14733 malware samples for evaluation. The training phase uses 15219 samples, and the testing phase employs 2000 samples. According to the experiments, the 196×196 dimension reached better accuracy than the 180×180 dimension. Therefore, the 196×196 ratio is more suitable for the proposed model. Table I highlights the comparison between the different dimensions based on the classification results. The image size of 196×196 achieves 98.12% testing accuracy. The computation time is about 18s. Figure 3 presents the performance evaluation related to the 196×196 image size based on training accuracy, training loss, test accuracy, and test loss metrics. A comparison with previous works is presented in Table II.

TABLE I. CLASSIFICATION RESULTS

Ratio	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	Accuracy (%)	Time (s)
180×180	94.15	94.68	94.47	16s
196×196	98.02	97.88	98.12	18s

Fig. 3. Loss and accuracy results for malware detection.

TABLE II. MALWARE DETECTION APPROACHES COMPARISON

Ref	Method	Year	Approach	Accuracy (%)	Time (s)
[38]	SVM+GIST	2017	ML	86.1	46
[39]	SVM+LBP	2018	ML	78.05	27
[40]	SVM+CLGM	2019	ML	92.06	21
Proposed	DCNN	2021	DL	98	18

The comparison in Table II proves that the proposed malware threat detection model is more accurate than previous studies that are based only on the machine learning approach. The proposed method requires only 18s of computation time.

IV. CONCLUSION

Recent industrial systems migrate to industrial-based IoT to support new network services. Many security issues are related to IoT networks, especially malware threats and software piracy. Accurate cyber security defending IoT big data is needed. In this paper, a new security architecture based on the deep learning approach is proposed. The attempt aims to detect malware attacks and pirated software. The proposed approach is a combined methodology to detect threats. A Deep Learning approach based on the TensorFlow Deep Neural Network is introduced to detect software piracy through source code plagiarism. Then, a DCNN is utilized to detect malware through binary visualization. The findings prove that the proposed combined approach of DCNN and TFDNN achieves a classification accuracy of about 98%. The results of the proposed approach are better than the results obtained by related works. Speeding up the computation time to support real-time systems can be the purpose of future work. This target could be reached by proposing a high-security level hardware accelerator.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Huang, J. Chai, and S. Cho, "Deep learning in finance and banking: A literature review and classification," *Frontiers of Business Research in China*, vol. 14, no. 1, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 13, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11782-020-00082-6>.
- [2] M. B. Ayed, "Balanced Communication-Avoiding Support Vector Machine when Detecting Epilepsy based on EEG Signals," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6462–6468, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3878>.
- [3] M. Ben Ayed, A. Massaoudi, and S. A. Alshaya, "Smart Recognition COVID-19 System to Predict Suspicious Persons Based on Face Features," *Journal of Electrical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 1601–1606, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42835-021-00671-2>.
- [4] M. Ramzan, M. S. Farooq, A. Zamir, W. Akhtar, M. Ilyas, and H. U. Khan, "An Analysis of Issues for Adoption of Cloud Computing in Telecom Industries," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3157–3161, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2101>.
- [5] H. E. Fazazi, M. Elgarej, M. Qbadou, and K. Mansouri, "Design of an Adaptive e-Learning System based on Multi-Agent Approach and Reinforcement Learning," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6637–6644, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3905>.
- [6] S. S. T. Alatawi *et al.*, "A New Model for Enhancing Student Portal Usage in Saudi Arabia Universities," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7158–7171, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4132>.
- [7] T. Brito, J. Queiroz, L. Piardi, L. A. Fernandes, J. Lima, and P. Leitão, "A Machine Learning Approach for Collaborative Robot Smart Manufacturing Inspection for Quality Control Systems," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 51, pp. 11–18, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2020.10.003>.
- [8] F. Musumeci *et al.*, "An Overview on Application of Machine Learning Techniques in Optical Networks," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 1383–1408, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2018.2880039>.
- [9] C. R. Srinivasan, B. Rajesh, P. Saikalyan, K. Premsagar, and E. S. Yadav, "A Review on the Different Types of Internet of Things (IoT)," *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamic and Control Systems*, vol. Volume 11, no. 1, pp. 154–158, 2019.
- [10] Y. B. Zikria, R. Ali, M. K. Afzal, and S. W. Kim, "Next-Generation Internet of Things (IoT): Opportunities, Challenges, and Solutions," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 4, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 1174, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21041174>.
- [11] E. B. Karbab, M. Debbabi, A. Derhab, and D. Mouheb, "Android Malware Detection using Deep Learning on API Method Sequences," *arXiv:1712.08996 [cs]*, Dec. 2017, Accessed: Oct. 07, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1712.08996>.
- [12] F. Ullah, J. Wang, M. Farhan, M. Habib, and S. Khalid, "Software plagiarism detection in multiprogramming languages using machine learning approach," *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, vol. 33, no. 4, 2021, Art. no. e5000, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.5000>.
- [13] A. Orgah, A. Case, and G. Richard, "MemForC: Memory Forensics Corpus Creation for Malware Analysis," in *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security*, Jan. 2021.
- [14] V. Raja, "Introduction to Reverse Engineering," in *Reverse Engineering: An Industrial Perspective*, V. Raja and K. J. Fernandes, Eds. London, UK: Springer, 2008, pp. 1–9.
- [15] H. Lim, H. Park, S. Choi, and T. Han, "A method for detecting the theft of Java programs through analysis of the control flow information," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 51, no. 9, pp. 1338–1350, Sep. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2009.04.011>.
- [16] J. Yasaswi, S. Kailash, A. Chilupuri, S. Purini, and C. V. Jawahar, "Unsupervised Learning Based Approach for Plagiarism Detection in Programming Assignments," in *Proceedings of the 10th Innovations in Software Engineering Conference*, Feb. 2017, pp. 117–121, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3021460.3021473>.
- [17] V. Kashyap, D. B. Brown, B. Liblit, D. Melski, and T. Reps, "Source Forager: A Search Engine for Similar Source Code," *arXiv:1706.02769 [cs]*, Jun. 2017, Accessed: Oct. 07, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1706.02769>.
- [18] F. Zhang, D. Wu, P. Liu, and S. Zhu, "Program Logic Based Software Plagiarism Detection," in *2014 IEEE 25th International Symposium on*

- Software Reliability Engineering*, Naples, Italy, Nov. 2014, pp. 66–77, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISSRE.2014.18>.
- [19] G. Cosma and M. Joy, "An Approach to Source-Code Plagiarism Detection and Investigation Using Latent Semantic Analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol. 61, no. 3, pp. 379–394, Mar. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TC.2011.223>.
- [20] J.-W. Son, T.-G. Noh, H.-J. Song, and S.-B. Park, "An application for plagiarized source code detection based on a parse tree kernel," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 26, no. 8, pp. 1911–1918, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2013.06.007>.
- [21] H. Cheers, Y. Lin, and S. P. Smith, "Academic Source Code Plagiarism Detection by Measuring Program Behavioral Similarity," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 50391–50412, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3069367>.
- [22] T. Foltýnek, R. Všíanský, N. Meuschke, D. Dlabolová, and B. Gipp, "Cross-Language Source Code Plagiarism Detection using Explicit Semantic Analysis and Scored Greedy String Tiling," in *Proceedings of the ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries in 2020*, New York, NY, USA, Aug. 2020, pp. 523–524, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3383583.3398594>.
- [23] M. Siddiqui and M. C. Wang, "Detecting Internet Worms Using Data Mining Techniques," *Journal of Systemics, Cybernetics and Informatics*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 48–53, 2008.
- [24] B. Kang, S. Y. Yerima, K. McLaughlin, and S. Sezer, "N-opcode analysis for android malware classification and categorization," in *2016 International Conference On Cyber Security And Protection Of Digital Services (Cyber Security)*, London, UK, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CyberSecPODS.2016.7502343>.
- [25] A. Moser, C. Kruegel, and E. Kirda, "Limits of Static Analysis for Malware Detection," in *Twenty-Third Annual Computer Security Applications Conference (ACSAC 2007)*, Miami Beach, FL, USA, Dec. 2007, pp. 421–430, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACSAC.2007.21>.
- [26] M. Christodorescu, S. Jha, and C. Kruegel, "Mining specifications of malicious behavior," in *Proceedings of the the 6th joint meeting of the European software engineering conference and the ACM SIGSOFT symposium on The foundations of software engineering*, New York, NY, USA, Sep. 2007, pp. 5–14, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1287624.1287628>.
- [27] U. Bayer, P. M. Comparetti, C. Hlauschek, C. Kruegel, and E. Kirda, "Scalable, Behavior-Based Malware Clustering," 2009.
- [28] I. Santos, J. Nieves, and P. G. Bringas, "Semi-supervised Learning for Unknown Malware Detection," in *International Symposium on Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence*, 2011, pp. 415–422, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-19934-9_53.
- [29] M. Kalash, M. Rochan, N. Mohammed, N. D. B. Bruce, Y. Wang, and F. Iqbal, "Malware Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks," in *2018 9th IFIP International Conference on New Technologies, Mobility and Security (NTMS)*, Paris, France, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NTMS.2018.8328749>.
- [30] R. Kumar, Z. Xiaosong, R. U. Khan, I. Ahad, and J. Kumar, "Malicious Code Detection based on Image Processing Using Deep Learning," in *Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Computing and Artificial Intelligence*, New York, NY, USA, Mar. 2018, pp. 81–85, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3194452.3194459>.
- [31] Z. Cui, F. Xue, X. Cai, Y. Cao, G. Wang, and J. Chen, "Detection of Malicious Code Variants Based on Deep Learning," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 3187–3196, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2018.2822680>.
- [32] R. Oshana, M. A. Thornton, E. C. Larson, and X. Roumégue, "Real-Time Edge Processing Detection of Malicious Attacks Using Machine Learning and Processor Core Events," in *2021 IEEE International Systems Conference (SysCon)*, Vancouver, Canada, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SysCon48628.2021.9447078>.
- [33] J. H. Paik, "A novel TF-IDF weighting scheme for effective ranking," in *Proceedings of the 36th international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval*, New York, NY, USA, Jul. 2013, pp. 343–352, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2484028.2484070>.
- [34] T. Georgiou, Y. Liu, W. Chen, and M. Lew, "A survey of traditional and deep learning-based feature descriptors for high dimensional data in computer vision," *International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 135–170, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13735-019-00183-w>.
- [35] M. Ben Ayed, S. A. Alshaya, and A. Alshammari, "Enhanced heart rate estimation based on face features," in *2021 18th International Multi-Conference on Systems, Signals Devices (SSD)*, Monastir, Tunisia, Mar. 2021, pp. 840–844, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SSD52085.2021.9429508>.
- [36] A. Back and E. Westman, "Comparing programming languages in google code jam," Chalmers University of Technology, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden, 2017.
- [37] T. H.-D. Huang and H.-Y. Kao, "R2-D2: ColoR-inspired Convolutional NeuRal Network (CNN)-based Android Malware Detections," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*, Seattle, WA, USA, Dec. 2018, pp. 2633–2642, <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData.2018.8622324>.
- [38] A. D. Moore, *Intellectual Property and Information Control: Philosophic Foundations and Contemporary Issues*. New Brunswick, NJ, USA: Routledge, 2004.
- [39] S. Elfving, E. Uchibe, and K. Doya, "Sigmoid-weighted linear units for neural network function approximation in reinforcement learning," *Neural Networks*, vol. 107, pp. 3–11, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2017.12.012>.
- [40] Z. Cui, L. Du, P. Wang, X. Cai, and W. Zhang, "Malicious code detection based on CNNs and multi-objective algorithm," *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, vol. 129, pp. 50–58, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpdc.2019.03.010>.

Post-Fire Behavior of Non-Prismatic Beams with Multiple Rectangular Openings Monotonically Loaded

Bashar F. Abdulkareem

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
bashar.faisal@muc.edu.iq

Amer F. Izzet

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
amer.f@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Nazar Oukaili

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
nazar.oukaili@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract—The main objective of this paper is to study the behavior of Non-Prismatic Reinforced Concrete (NPRC) beams with and without rectangular openings either when exposed to fire or not. The experimental program involves casting and testing 9 NPRC beams divided into 3 main groups. These groups were categorized according to heating temperature (ambient temperature, 400°C, and 700°C), with each group containing 3 NPRC beams (solid beams and beams with 6 and 8 trapezoidal openings). For beams with similar geometry, increasing the burning temperature results in their deterioration as reflected in their increasing mid-span deflection throughout the fire exposure period and their residual deflection after cooling. Meanwhile, the existing openings situation was compounded. The burned NPRC beams were left to gradually cool down under ambient laboratory conditions, and afterward, they were loaded until failure. The influence of temperature on the residual ultimate load-carrying capacity of each beam was studied by comparing these beams with unburned reference beams. Increasing exposure temperature reduces the ultimate strength of solid NPRC beams exposed to temperatures of 400°C and 700°C by about 5.7% and 10.84% respectively. Meanwhile, NPRC beams with trapezoidal openings showed ultimate strength reductions of 21.13% and 32.8% (for beams with 8 openings) and 28% and 34.4% (for beams with 6 openings) under the same burning conditions. The excessive mid-span deflections for these three types of beams were 2%–30.8%, 1.33%–21.8%, and 1.5%–17.4% under the same burning conditions.

Keywords—burning temperature; non-prismatic beams; openings number

I. INTRODUCTION

Reinforced Concrete (RC) is often used in high-rise structures and other buildings. Ensuring the fire safety of structural components is an important part of building design because fires are among the most dangerous environmental phenomena that may affect a structure during its life cycle. This requirement can be attributed to the fact that when other fire control measures fail, structural integrity becomes the last line of defense of a building. Experimental investigations have been conducted in the past to highlight the effect of fires on the material characteristics of concrete with several mix

proportions under different fire scenarios [1-4]. High temperature has been reported to reduce the material characteristics of concrete, including strength [5]. Reinforcing steel is more sensitive than concrete at high temperatures [6]. While concrete and steel show a similar thermal expansion at temperatures up to 400°C, the latter significantly expands at higher temperatures. In addition, at 700°C, the steel bearing capacity of these materials reduces by about 20% [7]. Structural failure mostly occurs when the reinforcement loses its effective strength via heating. Therefore, researchers argue that a reinforcement with adequate cover has a sufficient fire resistance [8]. Authors in [9] designed a numerical model in the form of a computer program to track the fire behavior of RC beams over the entire load range from pre-fire conditions to fire collapse. Three stages were examined in their analysis, namely establishing the fire temperature–time development, calculating the heat transfer of fire through the structure, and interpreting the structural analysis results. Authors in [10] studied the fire resistance of 6 RC beams and found that the fire resistance of HSC beams is lower than that of NSC beams. Moreover, HSC beams exhibit a high level of spalling, which is largely affected by concrete permeability, fire exposure type, load level, and restraint conditions. Similarly, the type of fire scenario, axial restraint, and load level significantly affect the overall fire resistance of RC beams.

Authors in [11] tested 9 rectangular beams to study the effect of multiple web openings along the span length of RC beams on their bending behavior. The plastic failure mechanism for beams having multiple openings is much longer than those for beams with a single opening. Authors in [12] studied experimentally and theoretically the effect of strengthening on improving the flexural and shear strength of 12 simply supported, high-strength Non-Prismatic RC (NPRC) beams with openings. Experimental results show that when NPRC beams are strengthened by a carbon fiber bar, the ultimate load for flexural and shear strengths increases by 16% and 15% respectively. Authors in [13] investigated 4 RC beams with a rectangular cross-section under 3-point load until failure and found that perforating an RC beam with small web openings slightly reduces its ultimate load and increases its

Corresponding author: Bashar F. Abdulkareem

ultimate deflection. Authors in [14] studied the serviceability of reinforced concrete gable roof beams with openings under static loads obtaining good agreement between the analytical and the experimental results. Authors in [15] investigated the structural behavior of RC beams with Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) bars and large rectangular openings and found that the presence of openings leads to the early formation of cracks at the locations of these openings. However, no study thus far has examined the high temperature resistance of NPRC solid beams or beams with openings.

II. BEAM SETUP

The experimental part was executed by manufacturing 9 scaled down (1/4) simply supported non-prismatic archetype roof beams. As shown in Figure 1, these beams have a width of 10cm, an overall horizontal lower chord length of 300cm, and inclined upper chord heights of 40cm and 25cm at the mid-span and ends respectively. All beams were reinforced identically with 4-Ø6mm arranged by 2 layers in the top chord and 2-Ø6+2-Ø 12mm arranged by 2 layers in the bottom chord (Figures 2-4). Transverse steel bars made of 6mm steel bars were provided at the solid ends of the solid beam GB and the other test specimens, and the openings were equally spaced at 10cm. Closed shear stirrups made of 4mm ordinary steel bars were provided over the entire span of the upper and lower chords of the test sample with 5cm spacing. Each beam was tested using a simple scheme with an effective span of 280cm. The tested beams were divided into 3 groups depending on the heating temperature (ambient, 400°C, and 700°C). Each of these groups has 3 NPRC beams (solid beam, and beams with 6 and 8 trapezoidal openings).

Fig. 1. Schematic layout of NPRC beams (all dimensions are in mm). (a) Solid NPRC beams GB, GB-400, and GB-700, (b) NPRC beams with trapezoid openings GT6, GT6-400, and GT6-700, (c) NPRC beams with trapezoid openings GT8, GT8-400, and GT8-700.

Table I and Figure 1 show the parametric details of the tested beams, where G denotes the NPRC beams, B denotes the beams without openings, and T denotes the ones with trapezoidal openings. The number that follows each symbol represents the number of openings in each specimen. Figures 2-4 show the configuration of the test beams and the reinforcement arrangement of the control and other NPRC beams. In all beams with openings, the length of solid ends ranges from 40cm to 50cm to override shear or end bearing failure. Meanwhile, a 20cm wide column was directly realized under mid-span load.

Fig. 2. Steel reinforcement of GB, GB-400, and GB-700. Section A-A (all dimensions are in mm).

Fig. 3. Details of steel reinforcement of GT6, GT6-400, and GT6-700. Sections B-B and C-C/

Fig. 4. Details of steel reinforcement of GT8, GT8-400, and GT8-700.

Normal concrete was used in the beams. The characteristics of concrete (e.g. modulus of elasticity, compressive and splitting tensile strength) were measured using steel cylindrical molds with 300mm height and 150mm diameter. The reinforcing steel bars had diameters of 4, 6, and 12mm, and the average yield, ultimate strength, and modulus of elasticity were determined by performing standard tests on the steel bars. The characteristics of the normal concrete and steel reinforcements used in this work are shown in Tables II and III.

TABLE I. DETAILS OF TESTED NPRC BEAMS

Group ID	Beams ID	Openings shape	Number of openings	Total area of openings (mm ²)	Width of openings (mm)	$\frac{\text{weight}_{\text{rafter}}}{\text{weight}_{\text{GB}}}$	Fire Temperature (°C)
I	GB	-	-	0	-	1.0	Amb.
	GT6	Trapezoid	6	180000	200	0.81	Amb.
	GT8	Trapezoid	8	174000	150	0.81	Amb.
II	GB-400	-	-	0	-	1.00	400
	GT6-400	Trapezoid	6	180000	200	0.81	400
	GT8-400	Trapezoid	8	174000	150	0.81	400
III	GB-700	-	-	0	-	1.00	700
	GT6-700	Trapezoid	6	180000	200	0.81	700
	GT8-700	Trapezoid	8	174000	150	0.81	700

TABLE II. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Material	Ø (mm)	Yield stress (MPa)			Compressive strength (MPa)			Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)		
		Amb.	400	700	Amb.	400	700	Amb.	400	700
Conc.	--	--	--	--	32.6	25	12.6	--	--	--
Steel	4	390	352	262	--	--	--	590	547	456
	6	580	524	390	--	--	--	650	602	503
	12	610	570	496	--	--	--	722	657	549

TABLE III. MODULUS OF ELASTICITY

Material	Ø (mm)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)		
		Amb.	400	700
Concrete	--	26.86	20.1	13.1
Steel	4	200	200	194
	6	200	200	194
	12	200	200	194

III. TESTING PROCEDURE

The experimental program involved casting and testing of the NPRC beams. They were monotonically loaded after exposure to high temperatures, as follows:

A. Burning Stage

The burning process was conducted in a furnace manufactured with a 4mm thick box-shaped steel plate to restrict heat and to burn one or more NPRC beams simultaneously (Figure 5). The furnace had an inner clear space of 0.8m height, 2m width, and 3.5m length and had the capability of maintaining 20 methane flames (nozzles). Eight compressed air nozzles were positioned at the lower furnace level near the base to maintain enough space underneath the NPRC beams, so the flames from the methane would be able to reach the NPRC beams, simulating the burning of simply supported NPRC beams. The upper level of the furnace had many small openings for thermocouple wires (K-type). The burning stage involved positioning each NPRC beam above its idealized simply supported ends and reading the mid-span deflection from dial gauges. The NPRC beams and control specimens were exposed to burning temperatures of 400°C or 700°C following the fire standard rate of ASTM E-119 [16]. The flame was supplied at the lower level of the furnace for an exposure period of 1h after reaching the target temperature. After this period, the flame was turned off, the furnace cover was removed, and the NPRC beams were gradually cooled down under ambient air.

Fig. 5. Furnace and burning process.

B. Load Test Stage

Figure 6 presents a schematic of the test setup. The NPRC beams were simply supported by steel rollers with a solid steel plate. The left roller was welded to the bearing plate to simulate hinge support, whereas the right roller was not welded. To eliminate the difference in load due to the variations in the sizes and locations of the openings, the load was applied on a thick 10cm × 10cm steel plate positioned at the tapered crest end of a non-prismatic beam that was flatted horizontally. A hydraulic jack with a 50-ton capacity was used to apply load on the beams. The applied load was controlled using a load cell with a digital load reader. The load was applied with 2.5kN increments. A dial indicator was used to measure the vertical deflection at 150mm from the support, under each post, and at the mid-span. The beam was loaded until failure. Deflection and the resulting strain were measured, the crack propagation

was marked, and the crack width was measured at different load levels.

Fig. 6. Test setup.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Deflection at Burning and Cooling Stages

The target temperatures of 400°C and 700°C were reached after 7 and 10min respectively. They are approximately similar to those specified in ASTM E-119 [15] as shown in Figure 7. After removing the furnace cover, the NPRC beams were gradually cooled under ambient laboratory conditions.

Fig. 7. Fire scenarios used in the burning test.

Fig. 8. History of mid span deflection Group 400.

Figures 8 and 9 present the mid-span deflection versus time history of groups exposed to similar burning conditions. Groups 400 and 700 correspond to the burning temperatures of

400°C and 700°C respectively. The mid-span deflection rate caused by heating increased through the burning periods of rising and target temperatures. Thereafter, some of this deflection was restored during the cooling (third) period. Meanwhile, the NPRC beams with openings demonstrated a higher deflection increase rate after heat exposure. The recovery rate of GT6 was slightly greater than that of GT8. Table IV presents the effect of openings, burning temperatures, and residual deflection of NPRC beams at each exposure period.

Fig. 9. History of mid span deflection Group 700.

TABLE IV. RESIDUAL DEFLECTION AT THE END OF THE BURNING PERIOD AND THE COOLING CYCLE.

Group	Beam ID	Residual deflection		
		At the third period (mm)	NPRC beams (with/ without openings) (%)	NPRC beams exposed to (700/400) °C (%)
400	GB-400	2.31	100	159
	GT8-400	3.32	143	148
	GT6-400	3.43	148	154
700	GB-700	3.67	100	
	GT8-700	4.92	134	
	GT6-700	5.27	143	

B. Monotonic Load Test Post Fire Results

1) Cracking and Failure Loads and Modes of Failure

Visible or not, most NPRC beams cracked evenly during the fire exposure test stage. The first crack load is indicative of two things, the flexural crack load or the widening of post-fire cracks. All NPRC beams cracked during the loading stage for loads varying between 17.5% and 23.5% of the corresponding load of failure. Such disparity between cracking and the ultimate loads was clear for the unburned NPRC beams (17.5%–20%) and decreased along with increasing temperature (20%–23.2% and 19.9%–23.5% at 400°C and 700°C respectively) as shown in Table V. Figure 12 shows the crack patterns of the tested beams. In all NPRC beams, cracking occurred at loads below their respective service loads, although the ultimate load decreased with increasing temperature. Therefore, the trustworthy design of these structural elements may be controlled by serviceability requirements. The average crack spacing was 60mm to 75mm for the NPRC beams in the unburned group, 55mm to 70mm for the NPRC beams exposed to 400°C, and 50mm to 65mm for the beams exposed to 700°C.

TABLE V. CRACKING AND ULTIMATE LOADS OF THE TESTED NPRC BEAMS

Group	Beam ID	No. of openings	Net area of the beam A_{net} (mm ²)	First cracking load P_{cr} (kN)	$\frac{A_{net}}{A_{net,GB}}$ (%)	$\frac{P_{cr}}{P_{cr,GB}}$ (%)	Failure load P_{ult} (kN)	$\frac{P_{cr}}{P_{ult}}$ (%)
Unburned	GB	-----	982500	18	-----	-----	90	20
	GT6	6	802500	14	81.7	77.8	77.8	18
	GT8	8	808500	14	82.3	77.8	80.2	17.5
400	GB-400	-----	982500	17	-----	-----	84.91	20
	GT6-400	6	802500	13	81.7	76.5	56	23.2
	GT8-400	8	808500	13	82.3	76.5	63.25	20.6
700	GB-700	-----	982500	16	-----	-----	80.24	19.9
	GT6-700	6	802500	12	81.7	75	51.06	23.5
	GT8-700	8	808500	12	82.3	75	53.9	22.3

Relatively short surface hairline cracks began to form at 400°C and became very obvious at 700°C. Apart from the effect of temperature, Figures 10-11 show the correlation between the savings in concrete used in producing the tested NPRC beams with openings and the percentage reduction in the load carrying capacity of these members. The maximum ratio of reduction in concrete consumption to the reduction in load-carrying capacity for NPRC beams with openings was 1.72 for GT8 at ambient temperature, whereas the minimum ratio was 0.45 for GT6 exposed to 700°C. Meanwhile, the ratio of reduction in concrete consumption to the reduction in load-carrying capacity decreased along with increasing burning temperature. Due to the exposure circumstance, the denominator (load-carrying capacity) showed a greater reduction than the numerator (concrete consumption). Comparing the NPRC beams with 8 openings with those having 6 openings reveals that the ultimate load-carrying capacity increased by 3.1%, 13%, and 5.5% at ambient temperature of 400°C, and 700°C respectively.

Fig. 10. Effect of openings and the temperature on the ultimate capacity.

Fig. 11. Failure load vs. exposure temperatures.

Fig. 12. Crack patterns. (a) GB, (b) GT6, (c) GT8, (d) GB-400, (e) GT6-400, (f) GT8-400, (g) GB-700, (h) GT6-700, (i) GT8-700.

2) Load-Deflection Relationship

Tables VI, VII and Figures 13-15 show the mid-span deflection at different loading stages (20kN, 40kN, and ultimate load). At the ultimate load, the excessive mid-span deflection increased for the NPRC beams with openings. The mid-span deflections of beams exposed to ambient temperature, 400°C, and 700°C ranged from 42.3% to 57.7%, 41.6% to 57%, and 32.4% to 41.5% respectively, depending on the number of posts between the openings and their total area. The stiffness of all NPRC beams decreased with increasing burning temperature due to the deterioration of concrete during its exposure to fire, which in turn led to the increased deflection of these beams. A high rate of defects was observed at 700°C.

TABLE VI. LOAD FOR TESTED NPRC BEAMS AT ULTIMATE STAGE

Group	Beam ID	Openings number	Failure load P_{ult} (kN)	Percentage of reduction (%)
GB	GB	---	90.0	----
	GB-400	---	84.9	5.7
	GB-700	---	80.24	10.8
GT8	GT8	8	80.2	----
	GT8-400	8	63.25	21.13
	GT8-700	8	53.9	32.8
GT6	GT6	6	77.8	----
	GT6-400	6	56.0	28
	GT6-700	6	51.1	34.3

TABLE VII. LOAD AND CORRESPONDING DEFLECTION FOR THE TESTED NPRC BEAMS AT DIFFERENT LOADING STAGES AND FIRE EXPOSURE CONDITIONS

Group	Beam ID	At 20 kN		At 40 kN		At ultimate load		Failure load P_{ult} (kN)	Percentage of reduction (%)
		Deflection (mm)	Percentage of increase (%)	Deflection (mm)	Percentage of increase (%)	Deflection (mm)	Percentage of increase (%)		
Unburned	GB	2.62	-----	6.4	----	16.8	----	90.0	----
	GT6	4.02	53.4	9.96	55.6	26.5	57.7	77.8	13.6
	GT8	2.76	5.3	8.36	30.6	23.9	42.3	80.2	10.9
400	GB-400	4.43	----	8.32	----	17.1	----	84.9	----
	GT6-400	6.28	41.8	13.76	65.4	26.9	57.0	56.0	34
	GT8-400	5.11	15.3	11.61	39.5	24.2	41.6	63.25	25.5
700	GB-700	5.43	----	10.4	----	21.9	----	80.24	----
	GT6-700	10.1	86.3	19.8	90	31.1	41.5	51.1	36.4
	GT8-700	7.43	36.8	18.1	74	29.1	32.4	53.9	32.8

Fig. 13. Load-deflection curves, GB group.

Fig. 14. Load-deflection curves, GT8 group.

Fig. 15. Load-deflection curves, GT6 group.

V. CONCLUSIONS

- Increase in the burning temperature increased the mid-span deflection of NPRC beams at all burning and cooling cycle periods. A similar increase was reported for residual deflection, which amounted to 143% and 148% for beams with 8 and 6 openings, respectively, at 400°C and to 134% and 143% at 700°C.
- Cracks began to form on the concrete surfaces of NPRC beams after the burning and cooling processes. The number and width of cracks increased with burning temperature.
- All NPRC beams cracked during the loading stage at 17.5% to 23.5% of the corresponding failure load. The disparity between cracking and ultimate loads was obvious among the unburned NPRC beams (17.5% to 20%) and decreased with increasing temperature (20%–23.2% and 19.9%–23.5% at 400°C and 700°C burning temperatures).

- Increase in the exposure temperature reduced the ultimate strength of solid NPRC beams by about 5.7% and 10.84% after exposure to 400°C and 700°C. The corresponding reductions for NPRC beams with 8 and 6 trapezoidal openings were 21.13%–32.8% and 28%–34.4% respectively. Under these same conditions, the excessive mid-span deflections for these beams were 2%–30.4%, 1.3%–21.8%, and 1.5%–17.4% for ambient temperature, 400°C, and 700°C respectively.
- For the same length of extended beams, increasing the number of openings with a small area, which coincides with reducing the total area of openings by increasing the number of posts, improved the flexural behavior of NPRC beams. Relative to that of beams with 6 openings, the load-carrying capacity of NPRC beams with 8 openings increased by 3.1%, 13.0%, and 5.5% when exposed to ambient temperature, 400°C, and 700°C respectively.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. F. Chang, Y. H. Chen, M. S. Sheu, and G. C. Yao, "Residual stress-strain relationship for concrete after exposure to high temperatures," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 1999–2005, Oct. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2006.05.029>.
- [2] S. K. Handoo, S. Agarwal, and S. K. Agarwal, "Physicochemical, mineralogical, and morphological characteristics of concrete exposed to elevated temperatures," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 1009–1018, Jul. 2002, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-8846\(01\)00736-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-8846(01)00736-0).
- [3] J. Lee, Y. Xi, and K. Willam, "Properties of Concrete after High-Temperature Heating and Cooling," *Materials Journal*, vol. 105, no. 4, pp. 334–341, Jul. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.14359/19894>.
- [4] M. Tufail, K. Shahzada, B. Gencturk, and J. Wei, "Effect of Elevated Temperature on Mechanical Properties of Limestone, Quartzite and Granite Concrete," *International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 17–28, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40069-016-0175-2>.
- [5] H. S. Al-Nimry and A. M. Ghanem, "FRP Confinement of Heat-Damaged Circular RC Columns," *International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 115–133, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40069-016-0181-4>.
- [6] D. N. Bilow and M. E. Kamara, "Fire and Concrete Structures," presented at the Structures Congress 2008, Apr. 2012, pp. 1–10, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2005\)131:1\(34\)299](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2005)131:1(34)299).
- [7] I. A. Fletcher, S. Welch, J. L. Torero, R. O. Carvel, and A. Usmani, "Behaviour of concrete structures in fire," *Thermal Science*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 37–52, 2007.
- [8] V. K. R. Kodur and L. A. Bisby, "Evaluation of Fire Endurance of Concrete Slabs Reinforced with Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Bars," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 131, no. 1, pp. 34–43, Jan. 2005, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2005\)131:1\(34\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2005)131:1(34)).
- [9] V. K. R. Kodur and M. Dwaikat, "Performance-based Fire Safety Design of Reinforced Concrete Beams," *Journal of Fire Protection Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 293–320, Nov. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1042391507077198>.
- [10] V. K. R. Kodur and M. B. Dwaikat, "Effect of Fire Induced Spalling on the Response of Reinforced Concrete Beams," *International Journal of Computing Science and Mathematics*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 71–81, Dec. 2008.
- [11] B. Aykac, I. Kalkan, S. Aykac, and Y. E. Egriboz, "Flexural behavior of RC beams with regular square or circular web openings," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 56, pp. 2165–2174, Nov. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2013.08.043>.
- [12] M. B. Dawood and R. A. A. Nabbat, "Flexural and shear strength of non-prismatic reinforced high strength concrete beams with openings and strengthened with NSM-CFPR bars," *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, vol. 6, no. 9, pp. 93–103, Sep. 2015.
- [13] M. a. J. Hassan and A. F. Izzet, "Experimental and Numerical Comparison of Reinforced Concrete Gable Roof Beams with Openings of Different Configurations," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5066–5073, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3188>.
- [14] M. a. J. Hassan and A. F. Izzet, "Serviceability of Reinforced Concrete Gable Roof Beams with Openings under Static Loads," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4813–4817, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3110>.
- [15] S. Yehia, A. Ibrahim, and B. Faihan, "Experimental Study on Steel-FRP Reinforced Concrete Beams with Large Rectangular Openings," *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 657–661, Jan. 2021.
- [16] E05 Committee, "Test Methods for Fire Tests of Building Construction and Materials," ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, USA, ASTM E119-16a, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1520/E0119-16A>.
- [17] A. H. Buller, M. Oad, and B. A. Memon, "Flexural Strength of Reinforced Concrete RAC Beams Exposed to 6-hour Fire – Part 2: Rich Mix," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3814–3817, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2494>.

Genetic Algorithm-Based Multi-Hop Routing to Improve the Lifetime of Wireless Sensor Networks

Adel Rajab

College of Computer Science and Information Systems
Najran University
Najran, Saudi Arabia
77adel.rajab@gmail.com

Abstract-Wireless sensor networks are known for their monitoring and tracking application-specific operations. These operations diversely demand improvement in existing strategies and their parameters. One key parameter is energy usage during operations. Energy plays a vital role in each application, as the wireless sensor networks lack battery lifetime and energy resources. So, there is a need for an optimized and efficient routing method with regard to energy consumption in wireless sensor networks. For multi-hop routing, the genetic algorithm serves as a robust algorithm with diverse optimized routing plans to improve the lifespan for large-scale wireless sensor networks. In this paper, the genetic algorithm provides the optimized routes for data operations and improves the lifetime of wireless sensor networks by saving energy. The performance of the genetic algorithm is compared with the TEEN algorithm.

Keywords-wireless sensor networks; multi-hop; genetic algorithm; optimization; lifetime durability

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are constructed by many self-organized and multifunctional mobile or non-mobile sensor nodes operating wirelessly in an area [1-4]. These sensor nodes possess inherited abilities to sense and transmit the gathered data towards the sink or base station. Therefore, the process of the data transmission towards the sink consumes more energy than the other processes such as data collection and data processing [5]. Since the sensor nodes have small-sized batteries, the overall performance of the sensor network depends on their lifetime. Additionally, the WSNs are prone to failure and can be deployed randomly in hard-to-reach areas. To counter this problem, multi-hop communication plays an essential role in improving network lifetime [6-8]. In the multi-hop communication paradigm, the source node transmits the data through the intermediate sensor nodes. These intermediate sensor nodes relay the data towards the sink as depicted in Figure 1. Multi-hops minimize the energy consumption by consuming a tiny amount of energy to relay the data towards the neighbor and the nearest sensor nodes [9, 10], which are hard to find in the WSNs if the optimal routing path is not determined. The optimal path towards the nearest sensor nodes is the key to save the extra consumption of the energy of the node.

The Genetic Algorithm (GA) is used to save energy and determine all the possible paths in the WSNs. The multi-hop communication paradigm with a focus on reduction of energy usage and optimal paths towards the nearest relay nodes is based on the distance among them. So, the distance among the sensor nodes from the source node towards the sink, all relay sensor nodes, and a possible number of multiple hops are determined by the GA in order to select the most optimal path for the data transmission. The results with the utilization of the GA prove that the multi-hop communication paradigm improves the WSNs lifetime [11-15].

Fig. 1. Hop-to-hop communication.

II. RELATED WORK

There is abundant research literature in the field of WSNs with regard to routing mechanisms and the improvement of energy utilization. Multipath routing schemes have been proposed to replace the single path routing paradigms. Replacing the single path or direct communication paradigms provides better performance of the network [8-11]. Multipath routing provides the benefit to transmit the packets by more than two paths, thus the packet loss rate is minimized [11, 12]. On the other hand, the multipath technique reduces the chance

of malicious attacks and any kind of packet tempering [13]. Multipath routing schemes for WSNs based on the next hop have been proposed in [14-16]. The sensor nodes are deployed in a hierarchical form and the algorithms are set to send the message according to the pre-determined loop of the hierarchical form. The authors claimed that this resulted in better network performance and more saved energy. Additionally, the routing schemes involving multiple paths reduced fault tolerance including error detection and error recovery. Authors in [17] presents a solution to the problem of the unbalanced energy expenditure in WSNs for multipath routing. The multiple-path routing scheme has been carried out in 3-D space and regional co-evolution. A protocol was designed to divide the one-hop path of the neighbor sensor node into many subspaces by partitions of the region. Then the source node selects the optimal node and path to transmit the data. The co-evolution algorithm helps to find out the next hop. A multipath cost function model for the statistical estimation of the overall network, namely the total energy of the nodes and the energy used in relaying the data was proposed in [18-20]. Multipath routing for the directional diffusion routing protocol from the source to the destination node with a certain probability of selecting one path among all possible paths was proposed in [19, 21-24]. Authors in [25, 27] advocated load-balancing energy schemes for WSNs and energy harvesting for the overall network. They utilized ACO (Ant Colony Optimization) for multiple path finding and claimed satisfying results. The study used an electromagnetic antenna-based approach for energy harvesting to gain high performance of IoT and WSNs. Numerous studies have been carried out on minimum energy consumption. The efficient usage of energy has been claimed as an important part to maximize the WSNs lifetime through optimization [28-30]. The optimization also reduces the complexity of the overall network and provides many possible options for routing the data from source to destination.

III. GENETIC ALGORITHM

GAs are meta-heuristic algorithms. The GA mimics the natural selection process [21] and has been used in various computer and AI applications. Due to its robustness, many research scholars adopted GA for solving optimization problems. Optimization finds the possible solutions to the problems and potential methods to tackle complications. As the GA mimics the natural selection process it follows the selection of healthy chromosomes. These chromosomes are selected by the fitness function, and are subjected to crossover and mutation [22-24]. The working mechanism of GA in this research is utilized with some modifications. All the operators of GA are used for selecting the best individuals from the population. The population comprises of all sensor nodes and sinks deployed in the area. After the selection of the best population, the GA finds fit individuals by applying the fitness function as shown in Figure 2. Each individual passes on the basis of their energy. Then, other operators, namely crossover and mutation, are applied to select the best chromosome as shown in Figure 3(a)-(b). For this research, the mutation probability is set to 0.8 [2, 24]. The process of mutation is depicted in Figure 3(c). After the mutation operator, the best

individual and the new fit individual are re-evaluated on the basis of their energy and only the fit individual can be obtained.

Fig. 2. Operator utilization of GA.

Fig. 3. (a), (b) Crossover and (c) mutation.

IV. PERFORMANCE AND SIMULATION

The experimental setup includes a dual-core Intel processor with a CPU of 3.5GHz and 32GB RAM. Simulations have been carried out using MATLAB R2020b in Windows 10. The sensor nodes are simulated as non-mobile but randomly deployed in a 100×100m² area with 4 sinks deployed at the corners. The multi-hop communication paradigm where the source node transmits the data through the relay nodes towards the nearest sink is shown in Figure 4. All possible routing paths towards all sinks are determined by the GA. When a node gathers and transmits the data by the optimal path towards the

nearest sink, it follows the already optimized route from multiple possible routes determined by the GA. The multiple hop distance is evaluated and determined by the GA. All sinks broadcast their locations to all sensor nodes and the nodes only transmit the data towards the nearest sink as illustrated in Figure 4. The simulation results comprise 40 and 50 sensor nodes deployed in a static manner along with static sinks [26]. The results of alive nodes, dead nodes, and overall packet transmission are compared with the standard TEEN algorithm's and they fairly outperform it in terms of energy expenditure and WSNs lifetime maximization.

A. Simulation Parameters

The studied WSN parameters are given in Table I. Each sink is responsible to collect the data from the nodes efficiently through optimized routes. Route optimization and determination are done with the help of GA. The evaluation of the route is done in two manners, namely the direct distance evaluation and the multiple hop distance evaluation. The evaluation of the distance is based upon the energy consumption. It is observed that the nearest nodes have the least energy consumption in comparison with the more remote nodes. During the simulations, the most remote nodes died in a few rounds because of the long routes and direct distances.

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameters	Value
Size of the network	100×100m ²
Number of nodes	40 and 50
Initial energy	0.9 Joules
Rounds	4000
Dissipation of energy	50 nJ/bit
Increase of energy $d_i < d_j$	10 pJ/bit/m
Increase of energy $d_i > d_j$	0.0015 pJ/bit/m

B. Simulation Algorithm

The proposed algorithm provides the routing mechanism among all sensor nodes and all sinks. It initially provides all the sensor nodes with a number of trial rounds. These trials are based on the energy levels of every sensor node and the distance among the sensor nodes and respective sinks. Therefore, the distance and their selection of routes strictly depend upon their physical location, where they are deployed, and the nearest sink.

Pseudo code for the optimization.

Input: All Nodes:	$Sensor_{Total}$
Total trials:	\emptyset
Battery life of each node:	\emptyset_{first}
Network area:	100×100m ²
Selected route and every route i :	∂_i
Path optimization:	P_{optim}
for i from 0 until ∂ do	
for j from 1 until \emptyset do	
$Sensor_{Total}$	Produce random network
$Sink_{Loc}$	Sink locations are broadcasted.
$Initial_{Route} = 0$	for every new network
\aleph_{Routes}	Route determining from/to sink(s)

end if

$\pi_{Optimized Routes}$ Obtaining optimized routes
 $\beta_{Most Optimal Route}$ reservation of optimal route
do while $\partial \emptyset_{first} > 0$ operation of nodes until battery dies
 $\beta_{Most Optimal Route}$ save the optimal route
 $\beta_{Most Optimal Route}$ copy it for every iteration.
end and return with $\beta_{Most Optimal Route}$

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

The WSN is constructed with 40 and 50 sensor nodes and 4 sink stations located at the corners of the network area as illustrated in Figures 5-6. The evaluation and simulation results of the randomly and static deployed sensor nodes and sinks show that the route distance is covered by multiple hop routing. That enhances the sensor node's battery lifetime and improves the network's lifetime. In other words, the network lifetime has, extensively, been increased by the use of the optimized multiple hop routes as depicted in Figure 7. Therefore, it has been experimentally proved that the network lifetime can be improved through optimum data transmission. Although there are a number of routes in multiple hop routing mechanism the source sensor node only opts to transmit the data through the optimal one.

Fig. 4. Deployment of 40 sensor nodes and sinks.

Fig. 5. Deployment of 50 sensor nodes and sinks.

Fig. 6. Data transmission to (a) Sink 1 (b) Sink 2, (c) Sink 3, and (d) Sink 4.

The localization of 40 sensor and multi-hop relay sensor nodes is shown in Figure 7. Multiple paths are determined by the GA among all the sensor nodes and sinks. The sensor nodes in the nearest sensor node towards the sink receive the data and perform the execution. The source sends the data towards the nearest sink with the help of relay sensor nodes. The optimal distance towards Sink 1 and Sink 2 is 114.647ms and 107.225m respectively. Sink 3 with 134.815m and Sink 4 with 131.194m have optimal routes towards the farthest node.

Fig. 8. Comparison of packets to sinks.

Fig. 7. Number of rounds vs. number of alive nodes for the proposed scheme and the TEEN algorithm.

The result comparison of this research with the standard TEEN algorithm [26] shows that the proposed scheme performs significantly better. The results show that the number of rounds vs. the number of alive nodes of the proposed scheme is bigger than the respective number of the TEEN standard algorithm as shown in Figure 8. The data transmission towards the sinks and the comparison of the results with the standard TEEN algorithm are shown in Figure 9. The packets with the proposed scheme at the rounds 1500, 2000, 2500, 3000, and 3700 have been received successfully at the end of

the sink. Also, the proposed scheme maximized the WSN's life durability and improved network performance. Additionally, the comparison results show that the standard TEEN algorithm has significantly more dead nodes as the packet transmission increases, while the proposed algorithm performs better and increases network durability [26].

VI. DISCUSSION

The proposed scheme improves the lifetime of the WSNs. The GA determines all possible routes for data transmission and optimizes each route for efficient data delivery with minimum energy cost. The GA determines an optimized route for each sensor node. The simulation results are more compromising than the standard TEEN [26] algorithm's. The proposed work performed very well on 500, 1000, 2000, and 3700 rounds and enhanced network lifetime.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, a multi-hop routing scheme for wireless sensor networks, based on the energy optimization by GA for network lifetime maximization, has been proposed and examined. The GA provides the optimized routes for data operations and improves the lifetime of WSNs by saving energy. The simulation results demonstrate the robust performance of the GA resulting in improved network lifetime. Also, the proposed algorithm achieves a significant performance gain over the standard TEEN protocol. Networks with a significant number of sensor nodes were simulated as non-mobile WSNs. Comparatively, the GA lost less nodes in 2000, 3000, and 4000 rounds, than the standard TEEN algorithm. In simulation results, the GA performed fairly better than the standard TEEN algorithm. Regarding future work, the current study can be extended to mobile and hybrid optimization schemes.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Zhang, "Wireless Sensor Networks: Lecture 1," Norrköping, Sweden, Jan. 17, 2014.
- [2] C. Li, J. Hailing, M. Yong, L. Tianpu, L. Wei, and Z. Ze, "Overview of Wireless Sensor Networks," *Journal of Computer Research and Development*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 163–174, Jan. 2005.
- [3] F. Samad, Q. Abu Ahmed, A. Shaikh, and A. Aziz, "JAM: Mitigating Jellyfish Attacks in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks," in *Emerging Trends and Applications in Information Communication Technologies*, 2012, pp. 432–444, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-28962-0_41.
- [4] A. Shaikh, N. Anjum, F. Samad, and A. Shah, "Building Wireless Sensor Networks Application Using Sun SPOTS," in *Emerging Trends and Applications in Information Communication Technologies*, 2012, pp. 466–477, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-28962-0_44.
- [5] M. A. Elmagzoub, A. Shaikh, A. Alghamdi, and K. Rajab, "A Review on MIMO Wireless Signals over Fibre for Next Generation Fibre Wireless (FiWi) Broadband Networks," *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 12, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics9122014>.
- [6] S. Solangi, D. Hakro, A. Lashari, K.-U.-R. Khoumbati, Z. Bhutto, and M. Hameed, "Genetic Algorithm Applications in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN): A Review," *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 152–166, Apr. 2017.
- [7] S. P. Singh and S. C. Sharma, "A Novel Energy Efficient Clustering Algorithm for Wireless Sensor Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1775–1780, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1277>.
- [8] G. Huang, W. Tao, P. Liu, and S. Liu, "Multipath ring Routing in Wireless Sensor Networks," presented at the 2nd International Symposium on Computer, Communication, Control and Automation (ISCCCA 2013), Feb. 2013, pp. 768–771, <https://doi.org/10.2991/isccca.2013.193>.
- [9] I. F. Akyildiz and M. C. Vuran, *Wireless Sensor Networks*, 1st ed. Chichester, West Sussex, UK; Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2010.
- [10] P. Chanak and I. Banerjee, "Energy efficient fault-tolerant multipath routing scheme for wireless sensor networks," *The Journal of China Universities of Posts and Telecommunications*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 42–61, Dec. 2013, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1005-8885\(13\)60107-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1005-8885(13)60107-7).
- [11] S. Wang, "Multipath Routing Based on Genetic Algorithm in Wireless Sensor Networks," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2021, Jun. 2021, Art. no. e4815711, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/4815711>.
- [12] N. A. Alrajeh, M. S. Alabed, and M. S. Elwahiby, "Secure Ant-Based Routing Protocol for Wireless Sensor Network," *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, vol. 9, no. 6, Jun. 2013, Art. no. 326295, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/326295>.
- [13] L. J. and J. Huo, "Uneven Clustering Routing Algorithm Based on Optimal Clustering for Wireless Sensor Networks," *Journal of Communications*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 132–142, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.12720/jcm.11.2.132-142>.
- [14] S. Md Zin, N. Badrul Anuar, M. L. Mat Kiah, and I. Ahmady, "Survey of secure multipath routing protocols for WSNs," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 55, pp. 123–153, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2015.04.018>.
- [15] P. J. Morrissey, K. S. Vunna, J. N. Potts, J. W. Ehm, and R. P. Singh, "Multi-path routing control for an encrypted tunnel," US9755953B1, Sep. 05, 2017.
- [16] T. Murakami, E. Kohno, and Y. Kakuda, "Radio Overlapping Reduced Multipath Routing Method by Utilizing Control Packet Overhearing to Counter Eavesdropping on Data Packets for Ad Hoc Networks," in *2015 Third International Symposium on Computing and Networking (CANDAR)*, Sapporo, Japan, Dec. 2015, pp. 167–173, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CANDAR.2015.56>.
- [17] W. Bai, H. Wang, X. Shen, R. Zhao, and Y. Zhang, "Minimum Delay Multipath Routing Based on TDMA for Underwater Acoustic Sensor Network," *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, vol. 12, no. 2, Feb. 2016, Art. no. 1394340, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/1394340>.
- [18] K. B. Wand and L. L. Cheng, "Wireless sensor network redundancy sensor node state schedule method," *Application Research of Computers*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 1227–1230, 2018.
- [19] M. Zhou, Y. Wang, Y. Liu, and Z. Tian, "An Information-Theoretic View of WLAN Localization Error Bound in GPS-Denied Environment," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 4089–4093, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2019.2896482>.
- [20] Z. Y. Zhang, Y. J. Liu, and X. D. Wang, "Multi-path routing in multi-factor wireless sensor monitoring network," *Computer Engineering & Science*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 1064–1071, Jun. 2014.
- [21] W. Ma, F. Yan, X. Zuo, L. Ren, W. Xia, and L. Shen, "Coverage hole detection algorithm without location information in wireless sensor networks," in *2017 3rd IEEE International Conference on Computer and Communications (ICCC)*, Chengdu, China, Dec. 2017, pp. 357–361, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CompComm.2017.8322571>.
- [22] M. Zhou, Y. Wang, Z. Tian, Y. Lian, Y. Wang, and B. Wang, "Calibrated Data Simplification for Energy-Efficient Location Sensing in Internet of Things," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 6125–6133, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2018.2869671>.
- [23] M. Zhou, X. Li, Y. Wang, S. Li, Y. Ding, and W. Nie, "6G Multisource-Information-Fusion-Based Indoor Positioning via Gaussian Kernel Density Estimation," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 20, pp. 15117–15125, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.3031639>.
- [24] W. R. Heinzelman, A. Chandrakasan, and H. Balakrishnan, "Energy-efficient communication protocol for wireless microsensor networks," in *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, Maui, HI, USA, Jan. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2000.926982>.

-
- [25] A. Nayyar and R. Singh, "IEEMARP- a novel energy efficient multipath routing protocol based on ant Colony optimization (ACO) for dynamic sensor networks," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 79, no. 47, pp. 35221–35252, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-019-7627-z>.
- [26] A. Manjeshwar and D. P. Agrawal, "TEEN: a routing protocol for enhanced efficiency in wireless sensor networks," in *Proceedings 15th International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium. IPDPS 2001*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Apr. 2001, pp. 2009–2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPDPS.2001.925197>.
- [27] I. Mujahidin and A. Kitagawa, "The Novel CPW 2.4 GHz Antenna with Parallel Hybrid Electromagnetic Solar for IoT Energy Harvesting and Wireless Sensors," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 393–400, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2021.0120845>.
- [28] J. O. Obira and R. Sinde, "Development of a Sensor-Based Heartbeat and Body Temperature Monitoring System for Remote Chronic Patients," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7375–7380, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4216>.
- [29] M. K. Sastry, A. A. K. Mohammad, and A. M. Abdul, "Optimized Energy-efficient Load Balance Routing Protocol for Wireless Mesh Networks," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)*, vol. 12, no. 8, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2021.0120871>.
- [30] M. B. Apsara, P. Dayananda, and C. N. Sowmyarani, "A Review on Secure Group Key Management Schemes for Data Gathering in Wireless Sensor Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5108–5112, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3213>.

A Novel MPPT Design for a Partially Shaded PV System Using Spotted Hyena Optimization Algorithm

Belkacem Korich
LAADI Laboratory
Department of Sciences and Technology
Ziane Achour University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
kor_belkacem@yahoo.fr

Amar Benaissa
LAADI Laboratory
Department of Sciences and Technology
Ziane Achour University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
benaissa_am@yahoo.fr

Boualaga Rabhi
LMSE Laboratory
Department of Sciences and Technology
University of Biskra
Biskra, Algeria
boualaga@yahoo.fr

Derradji Bakria
LAADI Laboratory
Department of Sciences and Technology
Ziane Achour University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
bakriaderradji@gmail.com

Abstract—Partial shading is a common problem in photovoltaic (PV) systems, known for its difficulty. Numerous attempts have been conducted to mitigate this problem. Some of these efforts deploy metaheuristic optimization with a view to tracking the multiple-peak P–V curve in a partial shading PV system. Hence, this paper proposes a novel metaheuristic algorithm to track the maximum power point of PV systems using the Spotted Hyena Optimization (SHO) algorithm. When evaluated, the SHO algorithm proved to be very fast, robust, and accurate in standard conditions, Partial Shading Conditions (PSCs), and irradiance variations. Also, the results reveal a remarkable improvement in the performance when we compare the SHO algorithm with the Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) algorithm and the Perturb and Observe (P&O) algorithm.

Keywords—*photovoltaic system; maximum power point tracking; partial shading condition; SHO optimization*

I. INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic solar energy is a renewable energy that is characterized by great development potential. Some of the advantages of this energy that it comes from an inexhaustible, clean source and the great safety it offers when used. Nevertheless, the two main problems that limit the use of PV systems are the high cost of installation and the low efficiency in energy conversion. We can only get up to 20% efficiency when we convert solar energy into electrical energy. Hence, the remaining of the solar energy is lost in the environment as it is not converted into useful electrical energy. As in many renewable energy systems, maintaining maximum efficiency remains a big challenge, especially when rapid changes occur in weather conditions.

Researchers have concentrated on three basic topics in order to increase the efficiency of PV systems [1]: designing

solar irradiance tracking systems, implementing efficient power converters, and developing Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms. The latter has the advantage that it can be deployed in both new and existing PV systems, whereas the two first can be implemented only during the design and installation of new PV systems [2]. To increase the output electrical power of a PV system, an MPPT algorithm must be adjusted to the operating point, whereas the connection of the PV system to the load is done by a DC-DC boost converter [2]. The output of MPPT algorithms can be the reference voltage, the reference current, or the duty cycle of the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) controller, and the PV systems' operating point can be controlled and adjusted via these parameters.

Under uniform irradiance, there is a unique MPP in the power-voltage curve that changes according to temperature and irradiance variations and the MPPT algorithm is responsible to find new optimal operating points according to these changes. Part of the conventional MPPT algorithms involve the Perturb and Observe (P&O) algorithm [3], the incremental conductance algorithm, and the extremum-seeking control algorithm [4, 5]. Cloud movement, big buildings, and tree shadows may generate lower irradiance received by some elements of the PV systems. Such a condition is called a Partial Shading Condition (PSC). Under PSC, there are various MPPs in the P-V curve of the system: a cluster of Local Maximum Power Points (LMPPs) with one Global Maximum Power Point (GMPP) [6]. Under PSC, it was discovered that the conventional MPPT algorithms have low performance, especially when assuming just one MPP on the P-V curve. In reality, due to their poor global search performance, methods such as the P&O method are often trapped in LMPPs and they cannot guarantee the convergence to the GMPP [7]. Due to the limitations of the classical MPPT algorithms, several algorithms based on

Corresponding author: Belkacem Korich

artificial intelligence and stochastic optimization, have been presented, many of which have been reviewed in [8, 9].

In this paper, the Spotted Hyena Optimization (SHO) algorithm is utilized to design a fast, robust, and precise MPPT algorithm for PV systems [10, 11]. The SHO algorithm is a new and powerful method that proved to be efficient in solving different optimization problems with many local optimum points. A PV system was simulated, and the performance of the suggested method was examined in various environmental conditions.

II. SYSTEM MODELING AND DESCRIPTION

A. The PV System Model

The PV cell is the principal element of a PV system that directly products electrical power from sunlight. We can represent this device by a single diode model because of its simple structure. The mathematical model for the current-voltage characteristic of a PV cell is [13, 14]:

$$I_{PV} = N_{pp} \left\{ I_{pvn} - I_o \left[\exp \left(\frac{V+R_s I}{N_{ss} V_t} \right) - 1 \right] \right\} - \frac{V+R_s I}{R_p} \quad (1)$$

where I_{pv} is the PV current source, R_s is the series equivalent resistance, R_p is the equivalent parallel resistance, I_{pvn} is the photocurrent, I is the difference between I_{pvn} and I_D , I_D is the diode current, I_o is the saturation current, V_t is the thermal voltage, N_{ss} is the number of cells connected in series, and N_{pp} is the number of cell connected in parallel. In the present article, we used the KC200GT module (Table I) to examine the simulation [15] and a DC-DC boost converter (Table II).

TABLE I. KC200GT MODULE CHARACTERISTICS

Parameter	Value
Model	KC200GT
Maximum power	200.143W
MPP Voltage	26.3V
MPP Current	7.61A
Open-circuit voltage	32.9V
Short-circuit current	8.21A
Kv	-0.123V/°C
Ki	0.003A/°C
Cells per module	54

TABLE II. PARAMETERS OF THE DC-DC BOOST CONVERTER

Element	Value
Inductance	300μH
Output capacitor	100μF (μF)
Load	100Ω
Switching frequency	10kHz

Figure 1 displays the P-V characteristic of the KC200GT PV panel obtained through simulation at changing irradiation and constant temperature. We notice the effect of insolation on the efficiency of the PV module whenever the value of insolation decreases. The extracted power from the PV module also diminishes.

Fig. 1. P-V characteristics of the KC200GT PV module at changing irradiation and constant temperature.

Fig. 2. The structure of the studied system.

B. System Description

PV modules are grouped in series and in parallel in order to increase the power of the PV system according to the demand requirements. A rapid and dynamic insolation change may appear on the panels during PSCs or in cloudy days. Then, multiple peaks are viewed in the curve of P-V characteristic as shown in Figure 3 (local and global MPPs) because of the bypass diodes' existence [8]. During PSCs, the existence of the bypass diode aids to reduce the possibility of hot-spot occurrence. This makes the shaded module to behave like as if it is loading power instead of generating it.

Fig. 3. P-V characteristics for shade patterns.

More importantly, the GMPP is changing, mainly depending on the shade pattern (Figure 3). Therefore, under

partial shading, GMPP tracking is important in order to improve the power generation efficiency. As shown in Figure 2, in our operating scenario of the PV system, an array of 3 KC200GT PV modules in series is simulated in Matlab/Simulink. We remark the immense effect of insolation on the extracted power of the three modules (Figure 3). The first case (pattern 1) shows that the insolation applied on the three modules was the same (1000W/m²) and the outcome of the global power was estimated as 600.42W. In the two other cases, the insolation changed (pattern 2: 1000/800/400, pattern 3: 900/700/300) and new LMPPs and GMPP occurred for each case. The power of GMPP was estimated as 333.4W and 291.7W respectively. In all these patterns, the temperature did not change.

III. A REVIEW OF P&O AND GWO ALGORITHMS

A. P&O Algorithm

The MPPT that can be generated from a PV system is maintained due to the use of the P&O MPPT algorithm [16]. This method is considered as the most useful technique due to its simple simulation and easy implementation [4]. Firstly, the P&O algorithm senses the voltage and current, and after it calculates the power. Based on the change of the power, this algorithm generates a variation in the DC-DC converter's duty cycle as presented in (2):

$$\begin{cases} D_{new} = D_{old} + \Delta D & (if P > P_{old}) \\ D_{new} = D_{old} - \Delta D & (if P < P_{old}) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The flowchart of P&O is presented in Figure 4 [4].

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the P&O algorithm.

B. GWO Algorithm

In 2014, Mirjalili formulated the social hierarchy and the hunting behavior of the grey wolf packs as an optimizer to deal with many optimization problems [17, 18]. A pack of grey

wolves is composed of an alpha (α), a beta (β), and a delta (δ) wolf, while the rest of the pack are omega wolves. α , β , and δ are the dominating wolves. They are responsible for decision making and discipline in the pack. During the hunt, the omega wolves update their locations and surround the area determined by α , β , and δ . The hunt will continue until the prey stops moving, and finally the hunt will end by attacking the prey. The mathematical model of the aforementioned behaviors is detailed in [17, 18]. GWO-based MPPT design for PV system has been presented in [18, 19]. The duty cycle has been considered as a grey wolf that tries to find the optimum solution related to the MPP. The flow chart of the GWO-based algorithm is presented in Figure 5 [18].

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the GWO algorithm.

IV. THE SHO ALGORITHM

A. Spotted Hyena Optimizer (SHO)

The SHO was first presented in 2017 [11]. This bio-inspired optimization technique imitates the social hierarchy and the group hunting behavior of the spotted hyenas in the purpose of solving various optimization problems. For more details see [11, 12, 20]. The pack of spotted hyenas can contain more than 100 members working together in an organized way. It is a hunting technique that can be divided into 4 main behaviors which are:

- Searching for prey
- Encircling prey
- Hunting
- Attacking prey

B. Application of SHO for MPPT

Figure 6 represents the diagram of the SHO algorithm. Our optimization problem is the maximization of PV output power. The duty cycle (D) of the PWM signal (which controls the switch of the boost converter) is defined as a hyena [12]. The SHO algorithm, which is used for the first time in this field in the current paper, is proved to be applicable when racking the GMPP in the case of partial shading fault in PV systems.

Fig. 6. Flowchart of the SHO algorithm.

V. SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS

To examine the performance of the proposed SHO MPPT algorithm, we compared its performance with the P&O and GWO algorithms'. The structure of the PV system under study (Figure 2), has been simulated in MATLAB/Simulink. The KC200GT PV model module was used in the simulations.

A. Performance Under Standard Conditions

In this situation, the proposed method's performance is evaluated throughout the PV system simulations under standard conditions. The levels of irradiance of the 3 PV modules are set as 1000W/m². The modules' temperature is 25°C as shown in Figure 3 (pattern 1). Figures 7-9 show PV output's power, voltage, and current of the 3 algorithms. P&O, GWO, and SHO took approximately 0.53s, 0.58s, and 0.50s respectively, to arrive at the MPP. We note that the time response of SHO is better than that of P&O and GWO. Moreover, the steady-state output power of the SHO algorithm is about 600.41W which is closer to the PV's maximum power, i.e. 200.143×3=600.43W when compared to the other methods.

Fig. 7. Performance of P&O algorithm under standard conditions.

Fig. 8. Performance of GWO algorithm under standard conditions.

Fig. 9. Performance of SHO algorithm under standard conditions.

Thus, we can conclude that the SHO algorithm is more efficient than the formerly mentioned algorithms.

B. Performance Under PSCs

In this test, the PV modules have 3 irradiance values, set as follows: 900, 700, and 300W/m². Their temperature is at 25°C as shown in Figure 3 (pattern 3). We observe the existence of a GMPP at 291.78W and two LMPPs at 168.35W and 201.29W. Figures 10-12 show the PV output power, PV output voltage, and PV output current of the three algorithms. In this state of shading condition, both SHO and GWO algorithms are able to find the GMPP. The SHO algorithm came to 291.7W while GWO reached 291.06W. Hence, it is affirmed that for reaching the GMPP (291.78W), the SHO proved to be more valid than the GWO. It should be noted that the P&O algorithm converges to an LMPP (201.22W). This result shows that power losses due to wrong tracking of the GMPP are significant. To arrive at the GMPP, GWO takes 0.6s and SHO 0.5s. As a result, the SHO algorithm proved to be more effective than the GWO algorithm.

Fig. 10. P&O algorithm under PSC.

Fig. 11. GWO algorithm under PSC.

Fig. 12. SHO algorithm under PSC.

C. Performance Under Fast Changing Solar Irradiance

In this condition, all 3 modules of the simulated array are used under standard conditions (T=25°C, G=1000W/m²). At 1s, we applied a step variation to the solar irradiance (the irradiances of the second and third modules are decreased to 800 and 400W/m² (see Figure 3, pattern 2) respectively, while the irradiance of the first module remains as before to test and examine the performance and precision of the SHO in comparison with the GWO algorithm, when solar irradiance changes rapidly. In this case, at 1s we got a new curve that involves a GMPP at 333.41W and two LMPPs (187.94W and 269.94W). In Figures 13, 14, the trajectories of the solar array for GWO and SHO algorithms are displayed.

Fig. 13. GWO tracking trajectories under rapid solar irradiance change.

As can be seen in Figures 13 and 14, after applying a step change of the solar irradiance, the presented SHO algorithm has absolutely detected the GMPP (333.24W) and converged with a proper speed, while GWO reached it satisfactorily (332.1W). The time of convergence has increased by about 0.48s after a fast change of solar insolation. When observing

the obtained simulations results, it can be noted that the GMPP tracking can be reached with more accuracy with the proposed SHO algorithm than with other literature results [6-8].

Fig. 14. SHO tracking trajectories under rapid solar irradiance change.

VI. CONCLUSION

With the aim of designing an MPP tracker for PV systems, SHO has been presented in this research paper and it is proposed for working under PSCs. The performance of the SHO algorithm was tested and compared with GWO and P&O algorithms. According to the test results, it was concluded that SHO proved to be efficient in tracking the GMPP with high fidelity, mainly under PSCs. The proposed algorithm exhibits fast, robust, and accurate performance. As a final result, this work confirmed that this optimization exhibited superior performance when compared with the two other tested methods, especially in terms of tracking ability.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Yatimi and E. Aroudam, "Assessment and control of a photovoltaic energy storage system based on the robust sliding mode MPPT controller," *Solar Energy*, vol. 139, pp. 557–568, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2016.10.038>.
- [2] R. Aghaie and M. Farshad, "Maximum Power Point Tracker for Photovoltaic Systems Based on Moth-Flame Optimization Considering Partial Shading Conditions," *Journal of Operation and Automation in Power Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 176–186, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.22098/joape.2019.5360.1401>.
- [3] S. Saad, "Enhancement of Solar Cell Modeling with MPPT Command Practice with an Electronic Edge Filter," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7501–7507, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4304>.
- [4] A. Ghelam, M. Boudiaf, and Y. Derouiche, "Correction of the Photovoltaic System Control by the Addition of a Voltage Regulator in the Electrical Conversion Chain," *Majlesi Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 45–52, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.29252/mjee.14.3.5>.
- [5] P. Lei, Y. Li, and J. E. Seem, "Sequential ESC-Based Global MPPT Control for Photovoltaic Array With Variable Shading," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 348–358, Jul. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSTE.2011.2141692>.
- [6] D. A. Nugraha, K. L. Lian, and Suwarno, "A Novel MPPT Method Based on Cuckoo Search Algorithm and Golden Section Search Algorithm for Partially Shaded PV System," *Canadian Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 173–182, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CJECE.2019.2914723>.
- [7] P. S. Gavhane, S. Krishnamurthy, R. Dixit, J. P. Ram, and N. Rajasekar, "EL-PSO based MPPT for Solar PV under Partial Shaded Condition," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 117, pp. 1047–1053, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.05.227>.
- [8] H. Rezk, A. Fathy, and A. Y. Abdelaziz, "A comparison of different global MPPT techniques based on meta-heuristic algorithms for photovoltaic system subjected to partial shading conditions," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 74, pp. 377–386, Jul. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.02.051>.
- [9] L. L. Jiang, R. Srivatsan, and D. L. Maskell, "Computational intelligence techniques for maximum power point tracking in PV systems: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 85, pp. 14–45, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.01.006>.
- [10] H. Jia, J. Li, W. Song, X. Peng, C. Lang, and Y. Li, "Spotted Hyena Optimization Algorithm With Simulated Annealing for Feature Selection," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 71943–71962, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2919991>.
- [11] G. Dhiman and A. Kaur, "Spotted Hyena Optimizer for Solving Engineering Design Problems," in *2017 International Conference on Machine Learning and Data Science (MLDS)*, Noida, India, Dec. 2017, pp. 114–119, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MLDS.2017.5>.
- [12] G. Dhiman and V. Kumar, "Spotted hyena optimizer: A novel bio-inspired based metaheuristic technique for engineering applications," *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 114, pp. 48–70, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2017.05.014>.
- [13] A. A. Djalab, M. M. Rezaoui, L. Mazouz, A. Teta, and N. Sabri, "Robust Method for Diagnosis and Detection of Faults in Photovoltaic Systems Using Artificial Neural Networks," *Periodica Polytechnica Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 64, no. 3, pp. 291–302, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.3311/PPee.14828>.
- [14] S. Hota, M. K. Sahu, and J. M. R. Malla, "A Standalone PV System with a Hybrid P&O MPPT Optimization Technique," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2109–2112, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1374>.
- [15] "KC200GT High Efficiency Multi-Crystal Photovoltaic Module Datasheet." Kyocera, 2011.
- [16] S. Latreche, A. E. Badoud, and M. Khemliche, "Implementation of MPPT Algorithm and Supervision of Shading on Photovoltaic Module," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3541–3544, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2354>.
- [17] S. Mirjalili, S. M. Mirjalili, and A. Lewis, "Grey Wolf Optimizer," *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 69, pp. 46–61, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2013.12.007>.
- [18] S. Mohanty, B. Subudhi, and P. K. Ray, "A New MPPT Design Using Grey Wolf Optimization Technique for Photovoltaic System Under Partial Shading Conditions," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 181–188, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSTE.2015.2482120>.
- [19] M. Valan Rajkumar, M. Mahakumar, M. Manojkumar, M. Hemaraj, and E. Kumaravel, "A New DC-DC Converter Topology with Grey Wolf MPPT Algorithm for Photovoltaic System," *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Engineering Research*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 54–59, Apr. 2017.
- [20] G. Dhiman and V. Kumar, "Spotted Hyena Optimizer for Solving Complex and Non-linear Constrained Engineering Problems," in *Harmony Search and Nature Inspired Optimization Algorithms*, Singapore, 2019, pp. 857–867, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-0761-4_81.

Behavior of RC Beams Strengthened with NSM-CFRP Strips Subjected to Fire Exposure

A Numerical Study

Hayder A. Al-Baghdadi
Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
baghdadi.hayder@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Anwer Sabah
Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
anwer.ali1801m@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract—The use of Near-Surface Mounted (NSM) Carbon-Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) strips is an efficient technology for increasing flexural and shear strength or for repairing damaged Reinforced Concrete (RC) members. This strengthening method is a promising technology. However, the thin layer of concrete covering the NSM-CFRP strips is not adequate to resist heat effect when directly exposed to a fire or at a high temperature. There is clear evidence that the strength and stiffness of CFRPs severely deteriorate at high temperatures. Therefore, in terms of fire resistance, the NSM technique has a significant defect. Thus, it is very important to develop a set of efficient fire protection systems to overcome these disadvantages. This paper presents a numerical study that investigates the fire behavior of thermally insulated RC beams flexurally strengthened with NSM-CFRP strips and subjected to fire exposure according to the ISO 834 standard. The numerical study considered three-dimensional finite element models in the ABAQUS software that have been developed to simulate and predict the performance (thermal and structural response) of fire endurance tests on strengthened, uninsulated strengthened, and thermally insulated beams strengthened with NSM-CFRP strips, which were exposed to fire and had different fire insulation schemes. The insulation used was plaster from local material with a thickness range of 25 to 50mm. The variation of the thermal and mechanical properties with the temperature of the constituent materials was considered. All beams' mechanical and thermal responses were adequately simulated using numerical models. The results of the numerical simulations were in good agreement with the experimental data. The fire behavior of the NSM-CFRP strengthened RC beams was examined and particularly the efficiency of the NSM strengthening system during the fire. The behavior in the fire of the NSM-CFRP strengthening system on the RC beams thermally protected with different fire insulation schemes was assessed. Finally, the effectiveness of fire insulation was studied.

Keywords—Near-Surface Mounted (NSM); Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP); RC beams; fire exposure

I. INTRODUCTION

Strengthening technologies based on Fiber-Reinforced-Polymer (FRP) composites have recently emerged as a possible alternative to infrastructure issues. FRP materials are appealing

to civil engineers because of their resistance to electrochemical corrosion, their high ratio of strength to weight, and their fabrication pliability. FRP is a modern type of building material made up of resin-saturated fibers (polymeric matrix). FRPs have high tensile strength, low thermal conductivity, corrosion resistance, residual stress strength, availability in a variety of configurations, lower maintenance costs, ease of installation, and mechanical fixing. Since the '90s the FRPs have seen widespread use in civil constructions [1].

FRP materials are highly susceptible to the consequences of high temperatures. At a temperature close to the polymer adhesive matrix's glass transition temperature (T_g) substantial mechanical and/or bonding degradation can be predicted. This raises the possibility of a sudden and disastrous collapse during a burn. Furthermore, the majority of organic polymer matrix products are flammable. Also flame spread, smoke production, and toxicity must be considered [2]. Near-Surface Mounted (NSM) FRP reinforcement is used in a growing number of applications. This system is based on the concept of embedding FRP reinforcements (e.g. bars or laminates) into grooves created by slotting the concrete members' surface with an adhesive (organic or inorganic) in the concrete cover of the elements to be strengthened. Externally Bonded FRP Reinforcement (EBR FRP) has several advantages over the NSM system: (a) It is possible to reduce the needed amount of site installation work. (b) NSM bars can be easily anchored into adjacent members to prevent debonding failures. (c) NSM reinforcement can be pre-stressed more easily. This feature is particularly appealing in the flexural strength. The FRP reinforcement in NSM is slitted instead of being externally bonded. This provides additional fire safety opportunities. (g) The NSM system has better bonding properties and protects the FRP bars or strips from accidental impact, mechanical damage, fire, and vandalism, due to the concrete cover. The polymer binder in these composites does not have the same fire resistance as the fibers used in FRPs. As a result, fires damage concrete buildings reinforced with FRPs. In reality, when compared to the EBR, the NSM technique provides better effectiveness and anchoring capacity because the strengthening material is within the concrete cover [3-9].

Corresponding author: Hayder A. Al-Baghdadi

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

A. Geometry and Element Types

The studied three-dimensional (3D) Finite Element (FE) models simply support RC beams flexurally strengthened with NSM-CFRP strips. An NSM-CFRP strip strengthened RC beam was modeled as a reference. The geometry, dimensions, and configuration of the beams were identical to the tested specimens. The insulated modeled RC beam is 1850mm in length and has a rectangular cross-section of 225mm and 130mm in depth and width respectively, and a concrete cover of 20mm. Two 8mm diameter steel rebars were used to model the top and bottom internal steel reinforcement. The transverse stirrups were identical, made from steel with 8mm diameter and the distance between stirrups kept constant at 60mm. The beam was strengthened with two CFRP strips that have a cross-section of 15mm (width)× 1.2mm (thickness) and a total length of 1450mm was applied on the beams' grooves according to the NSM technique. The adhesive layer was modeled as a fully bonded model. Plaster with a thickness ranging from 25mm to 50mm was used to insulate the three sides and ends of the RC beam as shown in Figure 1. It should be noted that an anchorage length of approximately 550mm was determined [10]. Two concentrated static loads, spaced 550mm apart, were applied to the beam, giving it a shear span of 500mm.

The FE models included unburned and burned beams. The unburned beam comprised of 4 parts. These parts were concrete, longitudinal and stirrup steel reinforcements, the steel rods of loading and the supports, and the CFRP strips. Concrete, steel rods of loading, and supports, were modeled with the C3D8R 3D 8-node linear brick solid element with reduced integration (R), whereas steel reinforcement bar and stirrup elements were modeled using the 3-D 2-node truss element T3D2. The CFRP was modeled using the 3D 4-node shell element termed S4R.

Fig. 1. Assembly of the whole insulated and strengthening RC beam parts, FEM analysis.

For the burned uninsulated beam, concrete was modeled using the 3D 8-node linear heat transfer brick solid element titled DC3D8, while the heat transfer 2-node DC1D2 was the selected link element as the steel reinforcement. The CFRP was modeled using the heat transfer quadrilateral DS4 3D 4-node shell element. For the burned insulated beams, an additional part was modeled: the linear3D 8-node hexahedral heat transfer brick DC3D8 element was selected as the insulation element. The overall brick element mesh is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Meshing for brick elements, FEM analysis.

B. Material Properties at Ambient Temperature

Concrete was modeled as an elastic and isotropic material. ABAQUS requires the identification of 2 parameters: modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio. Equation (1) in [11] was used to determine the modulus of elasticity of concrete. A value between 0.15 and 0.2 was used for the Poisson's ratio for concrete based on [12]. Moreover, to simulate the inelastic behavior of concrete, the Concrete Damage Plasticity Model (CDPM) is used. Five parameters are required for CDPM to be defined: the dilation angle (ψ), the flow potential eccentricity (e), the ratio of initial equibiaxial compressive yield stress to the initial uniaxial compressive yield stress (f_{b0}/f_{c0}), the parameter (K) which is used to define the multi-axial behavior of concrete, and the viscosity (μ).

$$E_c = 4700\sqrt{f'_c} \quad (1)$$

Table I lists the CDPM parameters adopted in this study. The data for the compressive and tensile behavior of concrete come from the uniaxial compression and uniaxial tension tests in [12].

TABLE I. CDPM PARAMETERS ADOPTED IN THIS STUDY

Specimen description	Reinforced concrete beams strengthened with CFRP				
	ψ	e	f_{b0}/f_{c0}	K	μ
Parameters					
Values	40	0.1	1.16	0.667	1e-4
Specimen description	Reinforced concrete beams strengthened with CFRP (loading after burned)				
	ψ	e	f_{b0}/f_{c0}	K	μ
Parameters					
Values	50	0.1	1.16	0.667	1e-4

The steel reinforcement and stirrups were modeled using an elastic-perfectly plastic material, with modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio of 200000MPa and 0.3 respectively, which defined the linear isotropic part, while yield stress and plastic strain determine the bilinear isotropic part. Steel bearing rods and support rods were modeled as isotropic linear materials. The linear isotropic part is specified by the steel rods' modulus of elasticity and the Poisson's ratio, which are 200000MPa and 0.3 for each rod. As facilitation, the CFRP strips were modeled as a linear elastic isotropic brittle material. The Poisson's ratio of 0.3 was assigned to CFRP components at an ambient temperature [13], σ_{pu} was 2800MPa, the modulus of elasticity E_{CFRP} was 160GPa according to the manufacturer's specifications of Sika® CarboDur® plates. The adhesive was also treated as a linear elastic isotropic brittle material [14]. A plaster made from local materials was used as the fire

insulation system, with a thickness ranging from 25 to 50mm. It was applied on the three surfaces of the beam. The fire insulation system presents variable thickness along the beam's length, being typically thicker at the anchorage zones of the CFRP strips. The thermal conductivity and the specific heat capacity of the plaster at room temperature are $\lambda = 0.15\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$, and $C_p = 1000\text{J}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$ respectively [15].

C. Temperature-Dependent Material Properties

Due to the considerable effect of temperature on the structural and thermal response of the CFRP-strengthened RC beams subjected to fire, the dependency of all material properties on temperature was taken into account in the models. The variation of concrete specific heat capacity, density, and thermal conductivity with temperature was provided in [15]. The concrete's density is taken to have a constant value of $2400\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$, and a constant emissivity value of 0.7 was considered. Classical concrete was adopted in simulations. The mechanical properties of concrete at room temperature were: average cylinders' compressive strength: $f'_c = 21\text{MPa}$, maximum tensile strength: $f'_{tc} = 1.512\text{MPa}$, and average modulus of elasticity: $E_c = 21538\text{MPa}$. It was assumed that the reduction of these properties with temperature would follow the relationships indicated in [16]. The reduction with temperature of reinforcement steel mechanical properties suggested in [15] was included in the present models. The steel's density was taken as $7800\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$. The variation of the thermal properties of CFRP strips with temperature was determined by the data provided by [17]. According to [18], a constant with temperature CFRP emissivity of 0.7 was assumed. The CFRP bonding adhesive was modeled as a fully bonded model. The variation of the plaster properties with temperature was considered as reported in [16]. The variation of the plaster density and specific heat with temperature was determined according to [16] and a constant with temperature emissivity value of 0.7 was considered. The mechanical contribution of the fire protection schemes is expected to be negligible, consequently, it was not considered.

III. THERMAL AND STRUCTURAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

A. Temperature-Dependent Material Properties

1) Thermal Boundaries

To closely match the environments occurring during fire, the bottom face and the two lateral faces of the beams' models were directly exposed to fire according to the heating rate of ISO 834 standard fire curve. Figure 3 shows the thermal applied loads on the models, which represent the furnace temperature measured at the fire test, whereas the top face was submitted to the temperature of the air above the top face of the beam. The lateral faces were thermally insulated during the tests. The boundary conditions correspond to the thermal exposure of beams (adopted in the tests). Radiation and convection heat transfer modes were considered on top, bottom, and the two lateral faces, a convection coefficient (h_c) of $25\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{C}$ (constant with temperature) was adopted, as suggested in [16]. The initial temperatures of the models were defined according to the recorded data of the beams test ranging between 10 and 20°C .

Fig. 3. Thermal applied loads on BSHP-25 and BSHP-50 beams' models.

2) Structural Boundaries

The beams were subjected to a mechanical load applied in a 4-point bending configuration. Simply supported boundary conditions were assigned to the beam-ends. These supports were simulated by elastic supports. One support provided restraint to both vertical and longitudinal displacements (directions y and z), while it permitted rotations around the (x -axis), (pinned support). The second support provided restraint to only vertical displacements, (direction y) while still enabling longitudinal displacements and rotations about the x -plane axis, (roller support). These supports were initially applied on concrete beams subjected to concentrated load. An identical simplification was adopted for the applied load, each rod has equal to $(1/2)$ of the actual applied load (P). For all beams, the same increment of the experimentally applied load was adopted. It is worth pointing out that the beams' self-weight was not considered.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several comparisons between the numerical and the experimental findings are presented. These comprise the effect of elevated temperature, load-deflection relation under the applied load of the references, and post-fire reinforced beams. The temperature of the NSM-CFRP strengthened RC beams subjected to fire exposure was recorded at the opposite anchorage zone (thermocouples T1 and T2) and the mid-span section (thermocouple T3).

A. Thermal Response (Temperature vs Duration of Fire Exposure)

The comparison of the predicted (numerical) and recorded (experimental) temperatures as a function of the duration of fire exposure at various places are shown in Figures 4-6. For the uninsulated beam, it was noted that the FE model underestimated the temperatures along the central zone of the bonded interface. The differences are most likely due to the high difficulty of simulating the behavior of NSM-CFRP-strengthened RC members in fire (because of the thermal gradient that exists along the depth of the slits causing non-uniform thermal deterioration throughout its depth) and because the effect of concrete spalling on heat transfer in-depth, which was not considered by the models. For the insulated beams, it was also found that the numerical model underestimated the temperatures along the center zone of the bonded interface. These variations are most likely the result of

modeling without taking into account the impacts of plaster cracks and fall-off (which were seen in the experimental fire test) in simulations due to their high complexity. Falling off is an outcome of the formation of diverse discrete cracks in the gypsum. Gypsum fall-off in fire strongly influences the fire resistance of the insulated beams. However, modeling this phenomenon is exceedingly complex, and no scientific effort has yet been published that uses numerical methods to solve this problem [15].

Fig. 4. Comparison of temperatures recorded at various locations of the BSH beam.

Fig. 5. Comparison of temperatures recorded at various locations of the BSHP-25 beam.

In comparison to their experimental counterparts, the predicted time-temperature curves show a more uniform temperature rise. The predicted temperature curves did not show any plateau (such as those recorded on the time-temperature curves in actual tests). This means that the influence of moisture content was not entirely captured by the thermal characteristics. There are some differences between the measured and the predicted temperatures. This might have occurred because the actual thermal characteristics of concrete and plaster utilized in the beams at increased temperatures differ from those included in the FE models. Despite the abovementioned deviations, generally all models gave a satisfying accuracy of the temperature development in the respective beams, demonstrating the FE models' capacity to correctly predict the thermal behavior of uninsulated and

insulated NSM-CFRP beams exposed to fire. The comparison of the time the epoxy adhesive required to reach T_g is listed in Table II and shown in Figures 7 and 8.

Fig. 6. Comparison of temperatures recorded at various locations of the BSHP-50 beam.

TABLE II. REQUIRED TIME COMPARISON FOR EPOXY ADHESIVE TO REACH T_g

Beam code	Time required to reach T_g of epoxy adhesive (min.)			
	Central zone		Anchorage zones	
	Exp.	Num.	Exp.	Num.
BSH	3	6	7	7
BSHP-25	20	13	21	14
BSHP-50	44	26	56	35

Fig. 7. Comparison of the time required to reach T_g of epoxy adhesive at the central zone.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the time required to reach T_g of epoxy adhesive at the anchorage zones.

B. Structural Response (Load vs Mid-Span Displacement)

Figures 9-12 show the measured and predicted mid-span displacement increments of all beams. From the FE analysis result, it can be seen that the models are stiffer than the experimental specimens. Some influences may be the cause for higher stiffness in FE analysis results. Micro-cracks resulting from the drying shrinkage and curing are found in the concrete during the experiment and after burning and cooling. These would decrease the actual specimens' stiffness. Modeling of these micro-cracks hasn't been conducted in FE models. Also, the bond between concrete and steel reinforcing or CFRP in the FE analysis is assumed perfect. This assumption is not totally true for real specimens. When bond-slip happens, composite work is lost between concrete and steel reinforcing. Therefore, the overall stiffness of the real specimens can be lower than the one expected from FE analysis.

Fig. 9. Comparison of load vs deflection curves for BSR beam.

Fig. 10. Comparison of load vs deflection curves for BSH beam.

Fig. 11. Comparison of load vs deflection curves for BSHP-25 beam.

Fig. 12. Comparison of load vs deflection curves for BSHP-50 beam.

There are differences between the real temperature effects on materials' mechanical properties and those included in the models. All beams' mechanical responses were adequately simulated using numerical models. In terms of load versus deflection curves, strength, and stiffness, the results of numerical simulations were in good agreement with the experimental data. Table III lists the ultimate load and deflection, as found in FE analysis and the experimental work for all specimens under static test. All failure loads obtained from FE analysis (except BSR and BSHP-50) show an overestimation of the real experimental values.

TABLE III. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ULTIMATE LOAD AND DEFLECTION OF THE TESTED SPECIMENS

Beam code	Ultimate load(kN)		Ultimate deflection (kN)	
	Exp.	Num.	Exp.	Num.
BSR	73.72	70.46	16.21	16.75
BSH	53.71	54.37	16.68	17.79
BSHP-25	57.73	59.85	14.25	15.59
BSHP-50	68.82	65.16	16.81	17.32

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusions from the findings of the current study can be summarized as:

- The numerical models were able to estimate the thermal behavior of the insulated RC beams that strengthened NSM-CFRP that were exposed to fire adequately. In addition, the flextural responses of the FE models for all beams were in good agreement with the experimental findings.
- The structural performance of reference beams, uninsulated and insulated NSM CFRP-strengthened RC beams subjected to static load after being exposed to fire according to the standard fire curve was adequately predicted.
- From the FE analysis result, it can be seen that the models are stiffer than the experimental specimens.
- The numerical results indicate that using thicker insulation in the CFRP anchoring zones (applied using NSM methods) reduced the required time the adhesive temperature needs to reach glass transition temperature T_g .

- The predicted time-temperature curves show a uniform temperature rise, while the predicted temperature curves did not show any plateau (such as those recorded on the time-temperature curves in actual tests). This shows that the influence of moisture content is not entirely captured by the thermal characteristics.
- The numerical models underestimated the temperatures along the center zone of the bonded interface. These variations are most likely the result of modeling without taking into account the impacts of plaster cracks and fall-off (which were seen in the experimental fire test) in simulations due to their higher complexity.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the staff of the Civil Engineering Department of the University of Baghdad for their scientific and professional help. The authors would also like to thank the staff of the Civil Engineering Department's Structural Laboratory of the University of Baghdad for their support.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. T. K. Al-Saadi, A. Mohammed, R. Al-Mahaidi, and J. Sanjayan, "A state-of-the-art review: Near-surface mounted FRP composites for reinforced concrete structures," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 209, pp. 748–769, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.03.121>.
- [2] V. K. R. Kodur, L. A. Bisby, and M. F. Green, "Preliminary Guidance for the Design of FRP-strengthened Concrete Members Exposed to Fire," *Journal of Fire Protection Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 5–26, Feb. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1042391507061956>.
- [3] R. El-Hach, S. Rizkalla, and R. Kotynia, "Modelling of Reinforced Concrete Flexural Members Strengthened with Near-Surface Mounted FRP Reinforcement," in *7th Int. Symp. on Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Reinforcement for Concrete Structures*, Jan. 2005, pp. 1681–1700.
- [4] J. A. O. Barros, S. J. E. Dias, and J. L. T. Lima, "Efficacy of CFRP-based techniques for the flexural and shear strengthening of concrete beams," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 203–217, Mar. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2006.09.001>.
- [5] R. Seracino, N. M. Jones, M. S. Ali, M. W. Page, and D. J. Oehlers, "Bond Strength of Near-Surface Mounted FRP Strip-to-Concrete Joints," *Journal of Composites for Construction*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 401–409, Aug. 2007, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0268\(2007\)11:4\(401\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0268(2007)11:4(401)).
- [6] L. De Lorenzis and J. G. Teng, "Near-surface mounted FRP reinforcement: An emerging technique for strengthening structures," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 119–143, Mar. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2006.08.003>.
- [7] M. a. J. Hassan and A. F. Izzet, "Experimental and Numerical Comparison of Reinforced Concrete Gable Roof Beams with Openings of Different Configurations," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5066–5073, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3188>.
- [8] H. M. Hekmet and A. F. Izzet, "Numerical Analysis of Segmental Post Tensioned Concrete Beams Exposed to High Fire Temperature," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4759–4768, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3059>.
- [9] A. H. Buller, M. Oad, B. A. Memon, and S. Sohu, "24-hour Fire Produced Effect on Reinforced Recycled Aggregates Concrete Beams," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4213–4217, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2764>.
- [10] ACI-Committee-440.2R-17, *ACI PRC-440.2-17: Guide for the Design and Construction of Externally Bonded FRP Systems for Strengthening Concrete Structures*. West Conshohocken, PA, USA: ACI, 2017.
- [11] ACI-Committee-318-19, *ACI 318-19: Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete*. West Conshohocken, PA, USA: ACI, 2019.
- [12] Y. Dere, "Nonlinear FE Modeling of Reinforced Concrete," *International Journal of Structural and Civil Engineering Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 71–74, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijscer.6.1.71-74>.
- [13] J. P. Firmo and J. R. Correia, "Fire behaviour of thermally insulated RC beams strengthened with EBR-CFRP strips: Experimental study," *Composite Structures*, vol. 122, pp. 144–154, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.11.063>.
- [14] Z. S., "Behaviour, and modelling of RC beams strengthened in flexure with near-surface mounted FRP strips," Ph.D. dissertation, Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong, China, 2012.
- [15] I. Rahmanian, "Thermal and Mechanical Properties of Gypsum Boards and Their Influences on Fire Resistance of Gypsum Board Based Systems," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Manchester, Manchester, UK, 2011.
- [16] *UNE EN 1992-1-2:2011/A1:2021 Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures - Part 1-2: General rules - Structural fire design*. 1992.
- [17] C. A. Griffis, R. A. Masumura, and C. I. Chang, "Thermal Response of Graphite Epoxy Composite Subjected to Rapid Heating," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 427–442, Sep. 1981, <https://doi.org/10.1177/002199838101500503>.
- [18] J. R. Miller and P. M. Weaver, "Temperature profiles in composite plates subject to time-dependent complex boundary conditions," *Composite Structures*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 267–278, Feb. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0263-8223\(02\)00054-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0263-8223(02)00054-5).

Analysis of the Physicochemical Characteristics of Distillery Wastewater at Habib Sugar Mills, Nawabshah

Nasir Hussain Jakhrani
Environment Engineering
Department
QUEST
Nawabshah, Pakistan
engrnasirhussain@gmail.com

Kishan Chand Mukwana
Environment Engineering
Department
QUEST
Nawabshah, Pakistan
kcmukwana@quest.edu.pk

Muhammad Aslam Bhutto
Civil Engineering Department
NED University of Engineering and
Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
mabhutto@neduet.edu.pk

Dur Muhammad Mangi
Environment Engineering Department
QUEST
Nawabshah, Pakistan
dm_mangi@yahoo.com

Memoona Hafeez
Institute of Chemistry
University of Sindh
Jamshoro, Pakistan
memoonahafeez88@gmail.com

Abstract—The aim of this study is to perceive the level of significant physicochemical characteristics of Distillery Wastewater (DWW) at Habib Sugar Mills, Nawabshah, Pakistan. Five locations in the mill namely spent wash, digester tank, distillery, primary treatment, and secondary treatment were selected for analysis of pH, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) of the samples. The samples were taken on a weekly basis for four succeeding months, from January 2021 to April 2021 and the experiments were carried out in the laboratory by adopting standard procedures. The results revealed that the pH of the samples from spent wash was the lowest, whereas secondary treatment samples had the highest. On the contrary, the highest concentrations of TDS, TSS, and COD were found in the samples taken from the spent wash and the lowest from the secondary treatment. The pH values were found abruptly increasing in the digester tank due to the addition of calcium carbonate in the stream of wastewater after the spent wash. The COD concentration was found to rapidly decrease, from more than 106000mg/l in the spent wash to around 35000mg/l in the digester tank samples, and then to gradually decrease up to the final point of disposal. Overall, TDS, TSS, and COD values were higher during April, January, and February and lower during March. The level of pH was extremely low in the spent wash and did not meet the lower limits of standards and the other examined parameters exceeded the upper limits of WHO standards.

Keywords—chemical oxygen demand; distillery wastewater; sugar mill effluents; physicochemical characteristics

I. INTRODUCTION

Around 75% of the earth's crust is covered with water. About 97% of the total available water is saline, which is confined in oceans, 2% is entwined in glaciers, ice caps, mud

and air. The remaining less than 1% is usable freshwater for the general public [1, 2]. The quality and quantity of water has great importance as a basic need [3, 4]. The discharge of untreated effluents should be within the safety limits [5]. Water is used for many purposes such as drinking, washing, bathing, cooking, agriculture, industry, and generation of electricity. In average, global agricultural withdrawals of all freshwater sources is about 70%. Agricultural inputs, especially fertilizers, pesticides, and other chemicals used for increasing the production of crops deteriorate the quality of water [6, 7]. Moreover, industries and municipal sewage pollute water sources when discharged directly into the water bodies without treatment. Polluted water causes many ailments, which are either direct or indirect [8].

Sugar industries are quite common globally due to their availability in more than 65% of sovereign countries. They are processing cane to produce raw sugar [9]. These industries generate byproducts such as bagasse, press mud, molasses and wastewater [10]. The production of 1kg sugarcane crop requires about 210lt of water. Besides crop requirements, water is also needed to run different processes in sugar mills and generates varying quantities and qualities of wastewater. In the sugar industry, water is normally obtained during the cane processing and the refinery processes [11]. Sugarcane crop contains about 70–80% moisture and approximately 1m³ of wastewater is generated when 1 ton of sugarcane is processed in sugar industry [9, 12].

A. Distillery Industry

Sugar industries can be categorized into three main groups, namely those that produce only raw table sugar, those that produce only ethanol, and those that produce a combination of

Corresponding author: Nasir Hussain Jakhrani

both [9, 13]. Approximately 90% of sugar industries belong to the third category, whereas, 7% produce only ethanol and 3% only sugar [14]. The increasing population has forced the enhancement of the development of distillery industry that produces ethanol, industrial chemicals, and bio-fuels. The processes used in distillery industry leads to the generation of Distillery Wastewater (DWW), stillage, or spent wash. On average, 1lt of alcohol production generates about 13lt of DWW depending on the used methods of distillation and waste treatment [15]. Thus, typical large distillery plants produce about 1950m³ of DWW.

B. Characteristics of Distillery Wastewater

The sugar mill DWW is highly polluted wastewater due to the presence of various organic compounds. It has dark color, low pH, high temperature, and extreme level of Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), BOD, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), sludge, press mud, and bagasse [16]. DWW has a pH of 4.0–4.6, BOD 25,000–35,000ppm TDS 85,000–110,000ppm and COD 85,000–110,000ppm [17]. Authors in [18] found the ratio of BOD and COD index in sugar industry to be 0.60 and 0.25. Authors in [10] found that DWW has a pH of 4.0 to 4.3 with high rates of BOD (52-58kg/m³), COD (92-100 kg/m³), and Total Suspended Solids (TSS) (2.0-2.5kg/m³). Authors in [19, 20] reported the characteristics of DWW as dark brown color, 5.4-4.5 pH, 40,000 to 50,000mg/L BOD, and 80,000 to 100,000mg/L COD. The high concentration of COD and BOD of DWW were attributed to the composition of input material used for the production of ethanol [21, 22]. High pollution load and the volume of DWW cause significant environmental issues [23] but now due to statutory restrictions, it cannot be used without meeting standards [24], as it may lead to alteration of the soil structure and can cause eutrophication of water bodies [21, 25, 26].

From the literature review, it is perceived that DWW is one of the most polluted waste materials and must be disposed of with care as it is of low pH, dark brown color, high content TDS, TSS, and COD. If DWW is disposed of without proper treatment, it can deteriorate the receiving water bodies and affect the general environment. This study was conducted in order to analyze the physicochemical characteristics of DWW and to check the level of pollutants in DWW and whether it meets standards or not.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area

Habib Sugar Mills was selected for this case study. It is located in the Nawabshah city. The sugarcane crushing capability of the mill is around 11,000ton per day. The refine productions of the mill are sugar and methanol, and the raw wastes are bagasse and molasses [27].

B. Sampling and Collection

A total of 5 wastewater sampling locations, namely spent wash, digester tank, distillery unit, primary treatment, and secondary treatment plant were selected in order to investigate the characteristics of sugar mill DWW. The samples were collected weekly for a period of four months. The samples were kept in cleaned plastic bottles. All bottles were washed

properly with distilled water. The capacity of each bottle was 5lt. The samples were collected from the exit points of each location. Precaution and standard protocols were adopted during the entire sampling period.

C. Analysis of the Physicochemical Characteristics of Sugar Mill Distillery Wastewater

Some physicochemical parameters of DWW were measured on the spot, while others were examined in the laboratory using the standard protocols. The instruments and methods used for the analysis of the physicochemical characteristics of DWW are tabulated in Table I.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Four physicochemical parameters, namely pH, TDS, TSS, and COD of sugar mill DWW were analyzed as per ASTM standards from January 2021 to April 2021. The results obtained from the experimental work are presented in Figures 1-8.

TABLE I. METHODS USED FOR THE ANALYSIS OF PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DWW

S. No.	Parameter	Instrument	Method
1	pH	pH meter, HI 2211 pH/ORP meter	ASTM E70-19 ASTM D1293-18
2	TDS (mg/L)	TDS Digital meter	ASTM D5907-18 ASTM D5907-10
3	TSS (mg/L)	TSS Digital meter	ASTM D5907-18 ASTM D5907-10
4	COD (mg/L)	Titration method	ASTM D1252-06 (2020)

A. pH Level

The determined pH value of the samples taken from different locations and the monthly average values are presented in Figures 1 and 2. The pH value of spent wash wastewater samples was 4.3, 4.5, 4.3, and 4.3 for each month from January to April respectively with an average value of 4.3. Similarly, the pH value of digester tank was 7.6, 7.9, 7.8, and 7.6 with an average value of 7.7. Likewise, the pH level of distillery wastewater sample was 8.0, 8.0, 8.0, and 7.9 with an average of 7.9. The pH of the samples taken from primary treatment was 8.1, 8.1, 8.1, and 8.1 with an average of 8.1 and from secondary treatment it was 8.3, 8.2, 8.2 and 8.2 with an average value of 8.2. The maximum and minimum pH values of spent wash, digester tank, distillery wastewater, primary treatment and secondary treatment were 4.5 and 4.4, 7.9 and 7.6, 8.0 and 7.9, and 8.3 and 8.2 respectively. The mean monthly average values of pH from all sampling locations were 7.3, 7.3, 7.3, and 7.2 from January to April respectively. The maximum and minimum mean monthly average values of pH were 7.3 and 7.2 in February and April respectively. Overall, the maximum pH values were observed in the secondary treatment samples, and the minimum from the spent wash wastewater samples. It was observed that 4 wastewater samples were slightly closer to the upper limit of the standard and only 1 sample was highly acidic which was taken from the spent wash.

B. TDS Concentration

The levels of TDS in DWW samples are shown in Figure 3 and the monthly average in Figure 4. The TDS of spent wash wastewater was 34525, 34400, 34050, and 34675mg/l each month from January to April with an average of 34412mg/l. The TDS of the digester tank samples was 26775, 27150, 26890 and 27062mg/l respectively with an average of 26969mg/l. Similarly, the TDS concentration of distillery wastewater was 20675, 21962, 21420 and 21825mg/l with an average of 21470mg/l and from the primary treatment 14637, 14837, 14550, and 14887mg/l with an average of 14728mg/l. The TDS concentration of the samples taken from the secondary treatment was 11775, 11250, 11230, and 11362mg/l with an average value of 11404mg/l. The maximum and minimum TDS concentration of spent wash, digester tank, distillery wastewater, primary treatment, and secondary treatment was 34675 and 34050, 27150 and 26775, 21962 and 20675, 14887 and 14550, and 11775 and 11230mg/l respectively. The monthly mean values of TDS from all sampling locations were 21677, 21920, 21628, and 21962mg/l from January to April respectively.

Fig. 1. pH values.

Fig. 2. Average monthly pH level.

The monthly maximum average value of TDS was 21962mg/l during April and the minimum was 21628mg/l in March. The higher TDS values were shown in spent wash samples and the lower values in secondary treatment water

samples. All wastewater samples were higher than the WHO standards.

Fig. 3. TDS values of all samples from different locations.

Fig. 4. Average monthly level of TDS in different months

C. Total Suspended Solids Concentration

The concentrations of TSS in the samples taken from different locations are given in Figure 5 and their average monthly level is displayed in Figure 6. The level of TSS in spent wash wastewater samples was 11630, 11370, 11246, and 11315mg/l for each months from January to April respectively with an average of 11390mg/l. The respective TSS level of digester tank samples was 8292, 8337, 8264, and 8305mg/l with a monthly average of 8300mg/l. The TSS concentration of distillery wastewater samples was 6822, 6852, 6808, and 6695mg/l with an average of 6794 mg/l. Similarly, the primary treatment samples had TSS level of 2917, 2970, 2968, and 2990mg/l with a monthly average of 2961mg/l. The TSS level in the samples taken from the secondary treatment was 1892, 1872, 1854, and 1847mg/l with an average of 1866mg/l. The higher and lower TSS concentrations of spent wash, digester tank, distillery wastewater, primary treatment, and secondary treatment were 11630 and 11246, 8337 and 8264, 6852 and 6695, 2990 and 2917, and 1892 and 1847mg/l respectively. The monthly mean values of TSS from all sampling locations were 6311, 6280, 6228, and 6230mg/l from January to April respectively. The highest observed monthly mean of TSS was 6311mg/l in January and the lowest was 6228mg/l in March. Overall, the higher TSS concentrations were found in spent

wash samples and the lower in the samples taken from the secondary treatment location. It was also observed that all examined samples showed higher values than the WHO standards.

D. COD Concentration

The levels of COD in the examined samples are shown in Figure 7 and their average monthly values in Figure 8. The COD value of spent wash samples for the months from January to April were 104763, 108370, 106052, and 106112mg/l respectively with an average of 106324mg/l. The COD values of the samples taken from the digester tank were 36250, 34448, 34510, and 34375mg/l respectively with an average of 34896mg/l. The monthly values of the samples taken from the distillery were 23175, 23225, 22640, and 23750mg/l respectively with an average of 23197.50mg/l. Likewise, the primary treatment samples values were 14012, 13982, 14270, and 14700mg/l respectively with an average of 14241mg/l. Correspondingly, the COD of secondary treatment samples for the months from January to April were 8400, 8705, 8320, and 8375mg/l respectively with an average of 8450mg/l.

average value of COD was 37746mg/l in February and the minimum 37158.4 mg/l in March. Generally, it was found from the analysis that the spent wash samples showed the highest COD concentration, whereas the samples taken from secondary treatment location displayed the lowest values. However, all examined samples showed higher COD values than the WHO standards.

Fig. 5. TSS values of all samples.

Fig. 6. Average monthly level of TSS.

The maximum and minimum COD concentration in spent wash, digester tank, distillery wastewater, primary treatment, and secondary treatment were recorded as 108370 and 104763, 36250 and 34375, 23750 and 22640, 14700 and 13982, and 8705 and 8320mg/l respectively. The maximum mean monthly

Fig. 7. COD values of all samples.

Fig. 8. Average monthly level of COD.

IV. CONCLUSION

Weekly samples of sugar mill DWW were taken from 5 locations, namely spent wash, digester tank, distillery wastewater, primary and secondary treatment, and analyzed for four consecutive months from January 2021 to April 2021 by observing 4 physicochemical characteristics, namely pH, TDS, TSS, and COD. It was found from the analysis that the pH values of spent wash samples were the lowest, whereas the values from the secondary treatment samples were the highest. The highest concentrations of TDS, TSS, and COD were found from the samples taken from the spent wash and the lowest from the secondary treatment location. The authorities of Sugar Mill add calcium carbonate to increase the level of pH up to standards, thus its values were sharply increased in the next sampling place, i.e. in the digester tank, and then were slowly increasing up to the final disposal point. The concentration of COD was found to quickly decrease from 106000mg/l in the spent wash samples to around 35000mg/l in the next sampling

location, and then gradually decreased up to the final disposal point. Overall, TDS, TSS, and COD values were found lower in March and higher during the other months. The levels of almost all examined parameters were higher than WHO standards, except from pH which was extremely low in the spent wash.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Q. Jakhriani, S. R. Samo, H. R. Sobuz, A. Uddin, and N. S. Hasan, "Assessment of Dissolved Salts Concentration of Seawater in the Vicinity of Karachi," *International Journal of Structural and Civil Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 61–69, Feb. 2012.
- [2] K. Mullen, "Information on Earth's Water," *NGWA*. <https://www.ngwa.org/what-is-groundwater/About-groundwater/information-on-earths-water> (accessed Oct. 16, 2021).
- [3] A. N. Laghari, Z. A. Siyal, D. K. Bangwar, M. A. Soomro, G. D. Walasai, and F. A. Shaikh, "Groundwater Quality Analysis for Human Consumption: A Case Study of Sukkur City, Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2616–2620, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1768>.
- [4] A. A. Mahessar, A. L. Qureshi, A. N. Laghari, S. Qureshi, S. F. Shah, and F. A. Shaikh, "Impact of Hairdin, Miro Khan and Shahdad Kot Drainage on Hamal Dhand, Sindh," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3652–3656, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2389>.
- [5] A. N. Laghari, Z. A. Siyal, M. A. Soomro, D. K. Bangwar, A. J. Khokhar, and H. L. Soni, "Quality Analysis of Urea Plant Wastewater and its Impact on Surface Water Bodies," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2699–2703, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1767>.
- [6] J.-M. Faurès, J. Hoogeveen, and J. Bruinsma, "The FAO irrigated area forecast for 2030." FAO, 2002.
- [7] D. Pimentel *et al.*, "Water Resources: Agricultural and Environmental Issues," *BioScience*, vol. 54, no. 10, pp. 909–918, Oct. 2004, [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2004\)054\[0909:WRAAEI\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2004)054[0909:WRAAEI]2.0.CO;2).
- [8] P. Chowdhary, R. N. Bharagava, S. Mishra, and N. Khan, "Role of Industries in Water Scarcity and Its Adverse Effects on Environment and Human Health," in *Environmental Concerns and Sustainable Development: Volume 1: Air, Water and Energy Resources*, V. Shukla and N. Kumar, Eds. Singapore: Springer, 2020, pp. 235–256.
- [9] P. K. Poddar and O. Sahu, "Quality and management of wastewater in sugar industry," *Applied Water Science*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 461–468, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-015-0264-4>.
- [10] T. Nandy, S. Shastry, and S. N. Kaul, "Wastewater management in a cane molasses distillery involving bioresource recovery," *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 25–38, May 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1006/jema.2001.0505>.
- [11] A. Ingaramo, H. Heluane, M. Colombo, and M. Cesca, "Water and wastewater eco-efficiency indicators for the sugar cane industry," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 487–495, Mar. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2008.08.018>.
- [12] O. P. Sahu and P. K. Chaudhari, "Electrochemical treatment of sugar industry wastewater: COD and color removal," *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry*, vol. 739, pp. 122–129, Feb. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelechem.2014.11.037>.
- [13] K. Sriroth, W. Vanichsriratana, and J. Sunthornvarabhas, "The Current Status of Sugar Industry and By-products in Thailand," *Sugar Tech*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 576–582, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12355-016-0491-5>.
- [14] L. A. Martinelli *et al.*, "Water Use in Sugar and Ethanol Industry in the State of São Paulo (Southeast Brazil)," vol. 2013, Jun. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jsbs.2013.32019>.
- [15] A. M. de Lima and R. R. de Souza, "Use of Sugar Cane Vinasse as Substrate for Biosurfactant Production Using *Bacillus subtilis* PC," *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, vol. 37, pp. 673–678, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1437113>.
- [16] P. K. Singh, M. Tripathi, R. P. Singh, and P. Singh, "Treatment and Recycling of Wastewater from Sugar Mill," in *Advances in Biological Treatment of Industrial Waste Water and their Recycling for a Sustainable Future*, R. L. Singh and R. P. Singh, Eds. Singapore: Springer, 2019, pp. 199–223.
- [17] S. Krishnamoorthy, M. Premalatha, and M. Vijayasekaran, "Characterization of distillery wastewater – An approach to retrofit existing effluent treatment plant operation with phytoremediation," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 148, pp. 735–750, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.02.045>.
- [18] J. Fito, N. Tefera, H. Kloos, and S. W. H. Van Hulle, "Physicochemical Properties of the Sugar Industry and Ethanol Distillery Wastewater and Their Impact on the Environment," *Sugar Tech*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 265–277, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12355-018-0633-z>.
- [19] R. Chowdhary, A. Yadav, G. Kaithwas, and R. N. Bharagava, "Distillery Wastewater: A Major Source of Environmental Pollution and Its Biological Treatment for Environmental Safety," in *Green Technologies and Environmental Sustainability*, R. Singh and S. Kumar, Eds. Singapore: Springer International Publishing, 2017.
- [20] P. Chowdhary, A. Raj, and R. N. Bharagava, "Environmental pollution and health hazards from distillery wastewater and treatment approaches to combat the environmental threats: A review," *Chemosphere*, vol. 194, pp. 229–246, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.11.163>.
- [21] A. C. Wilkie, K. J. Riedesel, and J. M. Owens, "Stillage characterization and anaerobic treatment of ethanol stillage from conventional and cellulosic feedstocks," *Biomass and Bioenergy*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 63–102, Aug. 2000, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0961-9534\(00\)00017-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0961-9534(00)00017-9).
- [22] A. K. Prajapati and P. K. Chaudhari, "Physicochemical Treatment of Distillery Wastewater—A Review," *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 202, no. 8, pp. 1098–1117, Aug. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00986445.2014.1002560>.
- [23] A. K. Biswas, M. Mohanty, K. M. Hati, and A. K. Misra, "Distillery effluents effect on soil organic carbon and aggregate stability of a Vertisol in India," *Soil and Tillage Research*, vol. 104, no. 2, pp. 241–246, Jul. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2009.02.012>.
- [24] F. Ansari, "Environmental Impact of Distillery Effluent on Vertical Soil Horizon due to Leaching Effect: An Experimental Approach," *International Journal of Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 223–231, Aug. 2014.
- [25] D. Pant and A. Adholeya, "Biological approaches for treatment of distillery wastewater: A review," *Bioresour. Technol.*, vol. 98, no. 12, pp. 2321–2334, Sep. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2006.09.027>.
- [26] P. A. Shivajirao, "Treatment of distillery wastewater using membrane technologies," *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Studies*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 275–283, 2012.
- [27] "Company History," *Habib Sugar Mills Ltd.* <http://www.habibsugar.com/company-history> (accessed Oct. 16, 2021).

Analysis of a Multilevel Voltage-Based Coordinating Controller for Solar-Wind Energy Generator: A Simulation, Development and Validation Approach

Thilagawathy Lachumanan

Faculty of Electronics and Computer Engineering
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Melaka, Malaysia
thilagaal@hotmail.com

Ranjit Singh Sarban Singh

Advanced Sensors and Embedded Controls
Centre for Telecommunication Research and Innovation
Faculty of Electronics and Computer Engineering
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Melaka, Malaysia
ranjit.singh@utem.edu.my

Mohd Ibrahim Shapiai

Centre of Artificial Intelligence and Robotic iKohza
Malaysia – Japan International Institute of Technology
Universiti Teknologi Malaysia
Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
md_ibrahim83@utm.my

T. Joseph Sahaya Anand

Faculty of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering
Technology
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Melaka, Malaysia
anand@utem.edu.my

Abstract-This paper presents the development and the performance analysis of the developed model of a voltage-based coordinating controller. This model is developed to perform activities such as sensing, measuring, switching, coordinating, and effectively managing the output voltages produced by the solar-wind renewable energy sources in order to supply the connected load or/and charge the battery storage system. The developed model has different tasks to perform when solar-wind energy sources both produce output voltages simultaneously, also contributing to solving the requirements of different synchronization algorithms for a multi-agent renewable energy system. The sensed and measured output voltages of the solar-wind energy sources are used as directive information to allow the developed model's controller to supply the available power to the connected load or/and charge the battery storage system. Also, the produced information at the model's controller input is used to individually control the other sub-system, which directly assists in achieving the aim of simultaneous operation when both solar and wind energy sources produce output voltages. The model is developed and simulated in Matlab/Simulink. The simulation results are used to validate the developed methodology and the aims of the developed model.

Keywords-voltage-based; coordinating controller; renewable energy sources; Matlab/Simulink; solar-wind

I. INTRODUCTION

Irregularity of energy production and generation by Renewable Energy Sources (RESs) [1] makes it necessary for the microgrid system to integrate an energy storage system to stabilize the overall performance of the DC-based microgrid systems [2-5]. Reviewing the evolution of DC-based microgrid

systems [6] and their complexity, Energy Management Systems (EMSs) [7-12] have been introduced. The EMS technology for microgrid-based systems is divided into two categories: (i) Centralized EMS (CEMS) [8] and (ii) Decentralized EMS (DEMS) [12]. A CEMS is also known as the AC-based system, a microgrid connected to a transmission grid while the DEMS is a DC-based system where the microgrid is a standalone system.

Systems that have employed the EMSs into the Distributed Generation (DG) sources such as solar photovoltaic (PV) panels [13], wind turbine systems [14], hydropower systems [15], etc., into DC-based microgrid systems provide a reliable solution able to supply electrical power to rural communities where the national grid is not reachable [16]. Systems proposed in [8, 17, 18] deploy a centralized agent which transfers and shares information and electricity with the other agents' controllers. The other agents are RESs, the grid network, load consumption, and the battery storage system. The centralized agent acts as the master, and it is responsible for managing the data and sending the action to agents based on the real-time information. In [9], the decentralized multi agent was introduced. Each agent in the proposed system works by receiving information through sensors. The disadvantage of this method is that each agent has its own algorithm and needs to be synchronized with complicated coding. Authors in [19] suggested a voltage divider switching technique as the sensing and measuring of output voltages of RESs. The voltage divider switching configuration is proposed for self-intervention of a hybrid renewable energy system.

Corresponding author: Ranjit Singh Sarban Singh

The disadvantage found in [9] and the advantage of having EMS DC-based microgrid systems for the rural communities encouraged the development of the VBCC (Voltage-Based Coordinating Controller) model for the DC-based solar-wind RES microgrid system. With the development of VBCC, a single mechanism was used instead of different algorithms for each agent. In terms of contribution, the developed VBCC can strategically contribute, control, and manage the connected sources via its multilevel voltage sensing and measurement mechanism. Besides that, the integration of multilevel voltage sensing reduces the impact on the system, when the voltage is low. The voltage is used to charge the battery energy storage and at the same time discharge the battery to the connected load.

The proposed VBCC senses, measures, coordinates, controls, and effectively manages the output voltages from the distributed generators for the connected load and charge battery energy system.

II. SYSTEM COMPONENTS

The developed VBCC consists of:

- Electronic Stateflow Condition Circuit (ESCC)
- Electronic Logic "AND" Gate Circuit (ELGC)
- Electronic Conditions Switching Circuit (ECSC)
- DC Boost Converter (DC-BC)
- Current Conversion Circuit (CCC)

The VBCC is responsible for sensing, measuring, coordinating, switching, and effectively managing the generated energies from solar-wind RESs which generate output simultaneously while performing different roles when the VBCC is operating. Figure 1 shows the modeled block diagram of the integrated VBCC. Solar energy is produced from solar PV panels and wind energy is produced from a wind turbine generator as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The VBCC developed model.

TABLE I. SOLAR-WIND GROUPED CONDITIONS

No.	Grouped conditions
1	$0V \leq V_{solar} < 10V$ and $0V \leq V_{wind} < 10V$
2	$0V \leq V_{solar} < 10V$ and $10V \geq V_{wind} > 12V$
3	$0V \leq V_{solar} < 10V$ and $12V \geq V_{wind} \geq 15V$
4	$10V \geq V_{solar} > 12V$ and $0V \leq V_{wind} < 10V$
5	$10V \geq V_{solar} > 12V$ and $10V \geq V_{wind} > 12V$
6	$10V \geq V_{solar} > 12V$ and $12V \geq V_{wind} \geq 15V$
7	$12V \geq V_{solar} \geq 15V$ and $0V \leq V_{wind} < 10V$
8	$12V \geq V_{solar} \geq 15V$ and $10V \geq V_{wind} > 12V$
9	$12V \geq V_{solar} \geq 15V$ and $12V \geq V_{wind} \geq 15V$

The solar and wind stateflow condition charts are categorized into 3 divisions which are:

- $0 \text{ Volt} \leq VR < 10 \text{ Volt}$
- $10 \text{ Volt} \leq VR < 12 \text{ Volt}$
- $12 \text{ Volt} \leq VR \leq 15 \text{ Volt}$

where R is the solar or wind RESs shown in Figure 1. The ranges of output voltages for the solar – wind RESs are summarized in Table I.

III. WORKING PRINCIPLE OF THE COMPONENTS OF THE VBCC SYSTEM

A. Electronic Stateflow Condition Circuit (ESCC)

The ESCC senses the total output analogue voltage amount of the individual solar - wind RES based on the primary division voltage ranges shown in Figure 2. For example, if the solar source produces voltage 9V and the wind produces 9V, then solar10 and wind10 in Figure 2 will produce a logic 1. This logic 1 then will be sent into the electronic logic "AND" gate circuit.

Fig. 2. Solar - wind primary voltage division ranges.

B. Electronic Logic "AND" Gate Circuit (ELGC)

The ELGC is combinational of 9 AND gates and is shown in Figure 3. Each of the 9 AND gates takes an individual logic from each primary division range from the ESCC shown in Figure 2. The 2 inputs of the AND gate produce a single logic output which is used to switch ON any respective switching circuit in the electronic conditions switching circuits shown in

Figure 1. When solar0 and wind0 are equal to logic 1, the S0W0 outputs a logic 1 too. The S10W10 logic 1 is sent to switch ON S10W10 of electronic conditions switching circuits. The other combinational AND gate circuits also have their decision-making roles based on the combinational input logics from the stateflow condition charts of solar - wind primary voltage division ranges.

Fig. 3. The 9 AND gate combinational circuit.

C. Electronic Conditions Switching Circuit (ECSC)

The ECSC of 9 conditional switching circuits is shown in Figure 4(a). Figure 4(b) shows the S10W10 condition switching circuit which is integrated as one conditional switching circuit in Figure 4(a). The S10W10 output logic 1 mentioned in Section B is sent into S10W10 of the conditional switching circuit of electronic conditions switching circuit in Figure 4(a). The S10W10 logic 1 then turns ON the relays shown in Figure 4(b). When the relays are turned ON, the output from the switches is sent to the SPDT relays to turn ON the SPDT relays from Normally Open (NO) to Normally Closed (NC). When the SPDT relays are at NC, the solar and wind input voltages are connected to S10W10/S and S10W10/W as shown in Figure 1. The S10W10/S and S10W10/W will output voltages in the range of 10V to 12V to next respective system component.

D. DC Boost Converter

The Direct Current (DC) Boost Converter (BC) is shown in Figure 5. In an explained example, the S10W10/S and S10W10/W will output voltage of 10V to 12V. Then the output voltage of S10W10/W is connected to S10W10/W. The 10V to 12V from S10W10/W is sent into the DC-BC Input as shown in Figure 6. The DC_BC Output will output an increased voltage compared to the input voltage at the DC_BC Input. The increased voltage output at the DC_BC Output is used to perform the battery energy system charging process as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 4. (a) 9 conditional switching circuits, (b) S10W10 condition switching circuit.

The S10W10/S will output voltage between 10V and 12V which is sent into S10W10/S as shown in Figure 1. The input 10V-12V at S10W10/S is sent into the DC BC input shown in Figure 7. From there, it is sent to the DC BC at both Voltage inputs as shown in Figure 8. But only one DC BC is activated which is the volt10 DC BC. Logic 1 of S10W10/S is sent into volt10 port to switch the SPDT relay from NO to NC and allow the 10V to 12V incoming voltage to be increased.

Fig. 5. DC – DC boost converters.

Fig. 6. The DC boost converter circuit.

Fig. 7. DC to AC voltage output.

Fig. 8. DC boost converter and DC to AC inverter system.

The increased output voltage from the DC BC is supplied into Converter volt10 which is a DC to AC inverter. The inverter will invert the DC input voltage to an AC voltage which is used to supply to any connected LOAD.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed VBCC model was fully developed in Matlab/Simulink. Voltage sensing and measuring method was used to assist the controller in coordinating, switching, and effectively managing the respective tasks such as supplying the inverted DC voltage into AC for connected LOAD or boosting the DC voltage to perform charging on the battery energy system. At in the beginning of this paper, we used the condition S10W10 to depict the developed VBCC's system methodology. Thus, the condition S10W10 will also be used to present the results of each stage of the developed VBCC to validate the developed system's overall performance and to analyze the respective required generated signals.

A. Solar – Wind Renewable Energy Sources

Figure 9 shows the solar - wind RESs input voltages captured based on the preset value shown in Figure 1. Hence, the 11V voltage captured is an amount of the voltage that the connected solar – wind RESs are producing. These voltages are then sent into the ESCC as shown in Figure 1. In the ESCC, these voltages are captured by the individual solar and wind stateflow chart shown in Figure 10. Hence, when the solar and wind stateflow condition charts capture the output voltages of the solar – wind RESs, a logic 1 is produced by each stateflow condition chart. Referring to Figure 10, solar and wind stateflow condition charts give a logic 1 for 11V sensed and measured voltage.

Fig. 9. Solar – wind RESs input voltages.

Fig. 10. 11V of solar – wind stateflow condition chart.

Both logics are sent into the electronic logic "AND" gate circuit through the ports solar10 and wind10 as shown in Figure 1. Figure 11 shows the solar10 and wind10 logic output based on the sensed and measured output voltage shown in Figure 10. The solar10 and wind10 logic 1 is sent into the AND gate LO6 shown in Figure 3 for an output of logic 1.

TABLE II. AND GATES COMBINATIONAL OUTPUT – S10W10

AND gates combinations	Output
S0W0	0
S0W10	0
S0W12	0
S10W0	0
S10W10	1
S10W12	0
S12W0	0
S12W10	0
S12W12	0

Based on Table II, the combinational output of the S10W10 AND gates shown in Figure 3 is the logic 1. This S10W10 logic 1 is sent to the S10W10 port of electronic condition switching circuit as shown in Figure 1. The S10W10 logic 1 connects the port 7 S10W10 of the 9 Conditional Switching Circuits shown in Figure 4(a) to activate the S10W10 Condition Switching Circuit shown in Figure 4(b). The S10W10 logic 1 will switch the relays from NO to NC to allow the SOLAR Input 11V and WIND Input 11V to flow into port 1 (S10W10/S) and 2 (S10W10/W) as shown in Figure 4. Figure 12 shows the 11V voltage output captured at ports S10W10/S and S10W10/W as shown in Figure 4(a).

Fig. 11. Solar stateflow condition chart – (a) solar10 Logic Output and (b) wind10 Logic Output.

Referring to Figure 1, the 11V voltage at S10W10/S is connected to the current conversion circuit, while the 11V voltage at S10W10/W is connected to the DC BC. Figure 13 shows the input 11V voltage at S10W10/W – DC-BC Input and the approximately 16V voltage output at the DC_BC Output as shown in Figure 6. The 16V voltage output at the DC_BC Output is connected to the battery energy system as shown in Figure 5 to charge the batteries used as an energy storage system. Figure 14 shows the results captured when the 16V voltage output at the DC_BC Output is connected as input to the DC to AC Inverter. The 16V voltage is inverted into 240V AC Voltage Output at the DC to AC Inverter, which is then used to supply the connected load.

Fig. 12. Voltage output at S10W10/S and S10W10/W.

Fig. 13. Input and output voltage – DC boost converter.

Fig. 14. 16V voltage input and 240V AC output at the DC to AC inverter.

The presented results are for condition S10W10, while the results for all the other conditions were compiled and are presented in Tables III and IV.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the presented literature review, a VBCC for solar – wind RES was proposed, modeled, and developed in this paper. The modeling and development of the VBCC was conducted in order to sense and measure the incoming voltages from the solar and wind RES. The other aims of VBCC are to coordinate, switch, and effectively manage the produced energy from the available voltages. The presented research

methodology has successfully developed the VBCC. The obtained results show that the developed VBCC can coordinate, switch, and effectively manage the available energy for connected load and battery energy system charging.

TABLE III. ESCC OUTPUT LOGIC CONDITIONS

ESCC Output Logic Conditions					
S0	S10	S12	W0	W10	W12
1			1		
1				1	
1					1
	1		1		
	1			1	
	1				1
		1	1		
		1		1	
		1			1

TABLE IV. ELGC COMBINATIONAL OUTPUT LOGICS

ELGC Combinational Output Logics								
C9	C8	C7	C6	C5	C4	C3	C2	C12
S0W0	S0W10	S0W12	S10W0	S10W10	S10W12	S12W0	S12W10	S12W12
1								
	1							
		1						
			1					
				1				
					1			
						1		
							1	
								1

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support by the Centre of Telecommunication Research & Innovation (CeTRI), Fakulti Kejuruteraan Elektronik dan Kejuruteraan Komputer (FKEKK), and Faculty of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering Technology (FTKMP), Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka, and the Ministry of Higher Education, Malaysia. Also, the authors thank the Centre of Artificial Intelligence and Robotic iKohza Malaysia-Japan International Institute of Technology, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM).

REFERENCES

[1] Md. S. Alam, F. S. Al-Ismail, A. Salem, and M. A. Abido, "High-Level Penetration of Renewable Energy Sources Into Grid Utility: Challenges and Solutions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 190277–190299, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3031481>.

[2] Md. S. Alam, F. S. Al-Ismail, A. Salem, and M. A. Abido, "High-Level Penetration of Renewable Energy Sources Into Grid Utility: Challenges and Solutions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 190277–190299, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3031481>.

[3] P. S. Gotekar, S. P. Muley, and D. P. Kothari, "A Single Phase Grid Connected PV System working in Different Modes," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6374–6379, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3746>.

[4] Y. Kassem, H. Camur, and O. a. M. Abughinda, "Solar Energy Potential and Feasibility Study of a 10MW Grid-connected Solar Plant in Libya," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 5358–5366, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3607>.

[5] S. A. Dayo, S. H. Memon, M. A. Uqaili, and Z. A. Memon, "LVRT Enhancement of a Grid-tied PMSG-based Wind Farm using Static VAR

Compensator," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7146–7151, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4147>.

[6] A. Al-Quraan and M. Al-Qaisi, "Modelling, Design and Control of a Standalone Hybrid PV-Wind Micro-Grid System," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 16, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 4849, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14164849>.

[7] M. F. Zia, E. Elbouchikhi, and M. Benbouzid, "Microgrids energy management systems: A critical review on methods, solutions, and prospects," *Applied Energy*, vol. 222, pp. 1033–1055, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.04.103>.

[8] A. Anvari-Moghaddam, A. Rahimi-Kian, M. S. Mirian, and J. M. Guerrero, "A multi-agent based energy management solution for integrated buildings and microgrid system," *Applied Energy*, vol. 203, pp. 41–56, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.06.007>.

[9] C.-S. Karavas, G. Kyriakarakos, K. G. Arvanitis, and G. Papadakis, "A multi-agent decentralized energy management system based on distributed intelligence for the design and control of autonomous polygeneration microgrids," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 103, pp. 166–179, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2015.06.021>.

[10] S.-H. Yoon, S.-Y. Kim, G.-H. Park, Y.-K. Kim, C.-H. Cho, and B.-H. Park, "Multiple power-based building energy management system for efficient management of building energy," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 42, pp. 462–470, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2018.08.008>.

[11] P. Kofinas, A. I. Dounis, and G. A. Vouros, "Fuzzy Q-Learning for multi-agent decentralized energy management in microgrids," *Applied Energy*, vol. 219, pp. 53–67, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.03.017>.

[12] W. Liu *et al.*, "Smart Micro-grid System with Wind/PV/Battery," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 152, pp. 1212–1217, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2018.09.171>.

[13] G. V. B. Kumar, P. Kaliannan, S. Padmanaban, J. B. Holm-Nielsen, and F. Blaabjerg, "Effective Management System for Solar PV Using Real-Time Data with Hybrid Energy Storage System," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 3, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 1108, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10031108>.

[14] O. O. Mengi and I. H. Altas, "A New Energy Management Technique for PV/Wind/Grid Renewable Energy System," *International Journal of Photoenergy*, vol. 2015, Mar. 2015, Art. no. e356930, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/356930>.

[15] A. M. Abdelshafy, J. Jurasz, H. Hassan, and A. M. Mohamed, "Optimized energy management strategy for grid connected double storage (pumped storage-battery) system powered by renewable energy resources," *Energy*, vol. 192, Feb. 2020, Art. no. 116615, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.116615>.

[16] M. Chen, S. Ma, H. Wan, J. Wu, and Y. Jiang, "Distributed Control Strategy for DC Microgrids of Photovoltaic Energy Storage Systems in Off-Grid Operation," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 10, Oct. 2018, Art. no. 2637, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11102637>.

[17] Y. Salgueiro, M. Rivera, and G. Nápoles, "Multi-agent-Based Decision Support Systems in Smart Microgrids," in *Intelligent Decision Technologies 2019*, Singapore, 2020, pp. 123–132, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-8311-3_11.

[18] I. N. Moghaddam, "Optimal Sizing and Operation of Energy Storage Systems to Mitigate Intermittency of Renewable Energy Resources," Ph.D. dissertation, University of North Carolina at Charlotte, Charlotte, NC, USA, 2018.

[19] R. S. S. Singh, M. Abbod, and W. Balachandran, "Renewable energy resource self-intervention control technique using Simulink/Stateflow modeling," in *Proceedings of the 50th Universities Power Engineering Conference (UPEC 2015)*, Trent, UK, 2015, vol. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/UPEC.2015.7339803>.

The Effect of Using Plastic Strips and Sheets on the Properties of Slurry Infiltrated Fiber Concrete

Adraa M. Najeeb

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad

Baghdad, Iraq

a.najib1101@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Nada Mahdi Fawzi

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad

Baghdad, Iraq

nada.aljalawi@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract-Slurry Infiltrated Fiber Concrete (SIFCON) is a high-strength material that is regarded as a unique type of high fiber content concrete. This paper aims to study the influence of the use of plastic strips and plastic sheets in the SIFCON slurry. Three sets (normal SIFCON as control, SIFCON with plastic strips, and SIFCON with plastic sheet), in a 1:1.08 cement-sand ratio by weight has been used with water to cement ratio (w/c) by weight equal to 0.3, and superplasticizer equal to 1% by weight. In addition, 6% by volume crimped steel fibers with an aspect ratio of 60 were applied and 1.34% by volume plastic was used, in strips of 5×1cm for both prism and cube samples and in sheets of 25×5cm and 7×7cm for prism and cube samples respectively. The compressive and flexural strength tests studies were conducted on typical cubes of 10×10×10cm and prisms of 40×7×7cm respectively to find out the way the plastic affects the SIFCON properties. The results indicate that the models with plastic sheets placed in SIFCON slurry give the highest compressive and flexural strength whereas the models with plastic strips gave the lowest. The difference percentages in compressive and flexural strength were -27.3, 8, -3.8 and 66.6% for all sets respectively when compared to the control set (using no plastic).

Keywords-SIFCON; plastic strips; plastic sheet; crimped fibers; aspect ratio

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a need to develop new forms of concrete that utilize fieldwork at reduced cost and in less time, therefore theoretical studies have been conducted utilizing building materials, additives, and sustainable materials of various types to create and discover types of concrete other than the conventional concrete, one of which is the Slurry Infiltrated Fiber Concrete (SIFCON). SIFCON is developed by increasing the percentage of steel fibers in the cement slurry. It has exceptionally high strength as compared to steel fibers reinforced concrete. SIFCON is an extra strong material that incorporates fibers in a high percentage volume [1]. SIFCON's matrix has no coarse particles but a high concentration of cementitious component. It may, however, incorporate fine (or coarse) sand as well as additives such as fly ash, micro silica, and latex emulsions. The ratios of cement and sand used to make SIFCON are typically 1:1, 1:1.5, or 1:2. The water cement ratio ranges from 0.3 to 0.4. The percentage of

superplasticizers in cement ranges from 2 to 5% by weight. The proportion of fibers by volume can vary from 4 to 20%, while the present practical range is between 4 and 12% [2]. SIFCON is being frequently used, particularly in seismic modification design and in constructions subjected to impact forces. It also exhibits novel behavioral phenomena such as the fiber lock [3]. SIFCON is used within applications where large ductility and energy absorbing are required, such as seismic-resistant reinforced concrete members and structures subjected to unusual or exploding forces. Pavement toppings, pre-stressed beams repairs, and structural reinforced concrete element restoration are some of its other successful uses. In addition, it is used in military structures against blasts, industrial sites, runways, and bridge foundations [3, 4].

An investigation about the effectiveness of combining steel and polypropylene fibers in various combinations in the SIFCON had been studied using fibers to cover 1/1, 1/3, and 2/3 of the molds in [5]. The mechanical and physical characteristics of SIFCON were investigated in this study. The usage of fibers in different combinations resulted in raising the fiber volume. The greatest flexural strength rates were obtained using specimens entirely filled with fibers, which were 44.02MPa and 41.23MPa with steel fiber at lengths of 6cm and 3.5cm respectively, and with a composite of 6cm steel and 5cm polypropylene fiber. The usage of polypropylene fibers in conjunction with steel fibers enhanced fracture toughness and flexural strength. As a result, it had been discovered that polypropylene fibers offer great benefits over the use of SIFCON in terms of cost and unit weight due to their reduced cost and density.

The effect of adding steel fibers on the mechanical properties of concrete had been examined in [6] using fraction volumes of 0.5, 0.75, and 1 of concrete and an aspect ratio of 100. The study was conducted on ordinary concrete specimens (cubes and prisms) and on concrete reinforced with steel fibers that had been water cured. All the mixtures had the same volumetric percentage of coarse and fine aggregates, and the same amount of water, resulting in a constant w/c ratio of 0.54. The largest increase percentage in compressive strength for specimens of concrete reinforced with steel fibers cured in water for 90 days was 8, 11.1, and 17.1%. The flexural strength of prisms cured in water increased with curing time. The

Corresponding author: Adraa M. Najeeb

maximum improvements at 90 days of curing for plain concrete and concrete reinforced with fiber for all sets were 30.4, 36.8, and 44.3% respectively.

Regarding the curing temperature of high performance concrete, the influence of curing temperatures of 30, 40, and 50°C on the compressive strength growth of high performance concrete was studied in [7]. The results were compared to concrete cured under standard circumstances at the usual curing temperature of 21°C. The study findings revealed that at early ages, the rate of strength growth is larger at high than at reduced curing temperatures, with the greatest rising percentage in compressive strength at 50°C. Yet, at older ages, the strength produced at elevated curing temperatures was lower than that produced at normal temperatures, and the greatest percentage of loss was 5.7% percent at the curing temperature of 50°C in 91 days curing age.

Self-Compacted Concrete (SCC) is considered to have advantages similar to SIFCON's, such as improved construction quality and faster construction activity. Various fibers were utilized in [8] as fiber reinforcement in SCC. They were proved to have a significant impact on the fresh and hardened characteristics of SCC. In most situations, the inclusion of fibers reduces the fresh characteristics of concrete (e.g. flow ability, passing ability, and segregation resistance), but increases the mechanical properties substantially. The kind and shape of fiber, aspect ratio, and volumetric fraction were found to be important parameters regarding the performance of SCC.

The aim of adding and promoting the usage of plastic waste in concrete was studied in [9]. The flexural strength and the workability of concrete were examined using different percentages of plastic fibers. M15 grade concrete beams were casted and cured for 7 and 28 days. The results showed that the use of plastic fibers reduced workability marginally while they increased flexural strength by 16.5% at 0.6% addition of plastic fibers in concrete [9].

II. MATERIALS USED

The investigation work has been carried out in the Civil Engineering Department's laboratory at the University of Baghdad. The used materials were:

- Ordinary Portland Cement type 42.5R complying to [10].
- Zone 4 sand complying to [11].
- Crimped steel fibers with a circular cross-section, with a length of 6cm, diameter of 0.1cm, and aspect ratio of 60 were utilized. Table I explains the characteristics of steel fibers, and Figure 1 depicts their form.
- Tap water complying with [12] was utilized.
- Sika ViscoCrete – 1316 Hi-Tech high range water reduction superplasticizer was utilized. The superplasticizer meets the Type D and G criteria of [13].
- The plastic strips used were 5cm long and 1cm wide and were cut from plastic water bottles (Figure 2).

- Plastic sheets, 25×5cm for prisms and 7×7cm for cubes having openings of 1×1.5cm, were used (Figure 2).

TABLE I. STEEL FIBER PROPERTIES

Fiber type	Cross-section	Length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Aspect ratio	Density (kg/m ³)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Crimped	Circular	60	1	60	7870	>800

NOTE: The values are according to the importing company

Fig. 1. Crimped steel fibers.

Fig. 2. Plastic strips and sheets.

III. MIXING DESIGN AND PROCEDURE

The cement-to-sand ratio was set at 1:1.08 by weight, the w/c ratio was set at 0.3 by weight, and the superplasticizer percentage was set at 1% by cement weight. Crimped steel fibers were utilized at a rate of 6% by volume. Cement and sand were mixed in their dry form. The superplasticizer was added to the water in a bowl and they were stirred until a homogeneous solution was produced. Then, the water with the superplasticizer were gradually added to the dried materials and blend until a homogeneous slurry mixture was obtained. Before casting, all the molds (10×10×10cm cubes and 40×7×7cm prisms) were cleaned and lubricated. For the first SIFCON set (control set), a thin layer of the slurry was placed in the molds and then the entire fiber quantity was placed at once. Another layer of slurry was placed over the fibers and it was let to be penetrated by them. For the second set of SIFCON with plastic strips, a thin layer of the slurry was put into the molds first, followed by the fibers with plastic strips all at once, and then another layer of the slurry was poured over the fibers. For the last set, a layer of slurry was first placed in the molds, followed by a layer of fibers and slurry, then the plastic sheet was placed in the middle. Afterward, again one layer of fibers and one of slurry were placed and let to be penetrated. To ensure that there are no honeycombs inside the specimens, the molds were lightly knocked on the outer face. The top surface of the specimens does not need to be level because the mixture is slurry and claims a level face on its own. Regarding demolding, all specimens were submerged in a basin with tap water at room temperature in accordance with [14], until testing time.

IV. TEST PROCEDURES

A. Compressive Strength Test

The compressive strength test was performed on the 10×10×10cm cubes in accordance with [15]. This test was carried out using a compressive strength hydraulic machine with 2000KN capacity at fixed load (Figure 3). The outcomes are the average of cubes for each set at ages of 7 and 28 days.

Fig. 3. Compressive strength measuring equipment.

B. Flexural Strength Test

The flexural strength test was carried out in accordance with [16] employing the 40×7×7cm prisms. This test was performed with the use of a flexural strength test machine with capacity up to 400KN (Figure 4). The average of each batch at ages of 7 and 28 days was used as the final result.

Fig. 4. Flexural strength measuring equipment.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Compressive Strength Test Results

The cubes prepared for compressive strength test were inspected at the age of 7 and 28 days for all sets. The outcomes show that adding plastic sheet in the SIFCON mixture gives higher results than the mixture with the plastic strips and the control, while the results of plastic strip SIFCON are lower than the other two sets. The reason for the enhanced results

when the plastic sheets are present is the contribution of the sheets in keeping the steel fibers distributed over the entire model without falling to the bottom due to their higher density. The reason for the presence of holes in the plastic sheets is that they allow the slurry to penetrate the entire form without accumulating on the top of the sheets. The reason for the reduction in the outcomes when the plastic strips are present is the relatively large cross section of the plastic strip, which leads to the heterogeneity of the specimens, which in turn leads to the reduction in the outcome. Table II and Figures 5-7 show the outcomes of the compressive strength tests. The outcomes of this study are higher than the ones in [17, 18].

Fig. 5. Compressive strength change with age.

Fig. 6. Compressive strength change with age when using 6% steel fibers.

Fig. 7. Sample for tested for compressive strength after failure.

B. Flexural Strength Test Results

The specimens showed no deformation during the flexural strength testing. The fibers have been removed from the hardened slurry, in contrast to the plastic that remained conjoined, indicating that the adhesion between the fibers and the hardened slurry has been overcome. Despite this, the adhesion between the hardened slurry and the fibers is excellent, agreeing with the findings in [5].

The prisms were tested for flexural strength at 7 and 28 days. The outcomes demonstrate that, the set using plastic sheets between the SIFCON slurry layers performed better than the set using plastic strips and the control mix, while the set using plastic strips produced the worst results. The enhanced results of the set containing plastic sheets were caused by the homogeneity of the respective samples which kept the fibers distributed over the entire sample. The negative outcomes of the set containing plastic strips must be attributed to the non-homogeneity of the samples due to the relatively large cross section of the plastic strips. The outcomes of this paper are higher than the ones in [9, 19]. Table II and Figures 8-10 show the outcomes of the flexural strength tests.

Fig. 8. Flexural strength change with age.

Fig. 9. Flexural strength change with age when using 6% steel fibers.

As a result summary, incorporating plastic sheets between the SIFCON's slurry layers gives an enhanced result regarding compressive and flexural strength since the specimens are having good distribution of fibers over the entire model. Incorporating plastic strips along with steel fibers inside the SIFCON slurry reduces the outcomes of compressive and flexural strength tests due to the cross section of the plastic strips used which leads to uneven steel fiber distribution in the samples.

Fig. 10. A sample for flexural strength test after failure.

TABLE II. RESULTS OF COMPRESSIVE AND FLEXURAL STRENGTH TESTS

Set	Control set		SIFCON with plastic strips set		SIFCON with plastic sheet set	
	7	28	7	28	7	28
Compressive strength (MPa)	Age (day)					
	34.72	53.74	25.23	39.04	37.50	57.84
	% Change		-27.3		8	
Flexural strength (MPa)	Age (day)					
	7.52	8.89	7.23	8.55	12.53	14.83
	% Change		-3.8		66.6	

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, used plastic was re-used as a sustainable material in SIFCON mixes. The outcomes of this investigation obtained from using 10×10×10cm cubes and 40×7×7cm prisms with 6% steel fibers and plastic strips or sheets. The samples were cured for 7 and 28 days and then their compressive and flexural strength was tested. As a conclusion of this investigation the following points should be noted:

- The results of compressive strength tests demonstrate that the use of plastic sheets within the SIFCON enhanced the results by about 8%. The combination of plastic strips with steel fibers in SIFCON gives a reduction in the results of about 27.3%.
- The flexural strength test outcomes clarify that the plastic sheets used within the SIFCON improve the result by about 66.6%, while using plastic strips with steel fibers in SIFCON reduces the result by about 3.8%.

REFERENCES

[1] K. Dagar, "Slurry Infiltrated Fibrous Concrete (SIFCON)," *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 99–100, 2012.

[2] R. Giridhar and P. R. M. Rao, "Determination of Mechanical Properties of Slurry Infiltrated Concrete (SIFCON)," *International Journal For Technological Research In Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 1366–1368, Mar. 2015.

[3] S. A. Salih, Q. J. Frayyeh, and M. A. Al-wahab Ali, "Flexural Behavior of Slurry Infiltrated Fiber Concrete (SIFCON) Containing Supplementary Cementitious Materials," *Journal of Engineering and Sustainable Development*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 35–48, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.31272/jeasd.2018.2.32>.

- [4] N. Soyly and A. F. Bingöl, "Research on effect of the quantity and aspect ratio of steel fibers on compressive and flexural strength of SIFCON," *Challenge Journal of Structural Mechanics*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 29, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.20528/cjsmec.2019.01.004>.
- [5] M. Ipek and M. Aksu, "The effect of different types of fiber on flexure strength and fracture toughness in SIFCON," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 214, pp. 207–218, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.04.055>.
- [6] S. Alaa and D. Aljalawi, "Effect of Petroleum Products on Steel Fiber Reinforced Concrete," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 16–43, Jan. 2013.
- [7] N. M. Fawzi and A. S. T. Agha, "The Effect Of Curing Types On Compressive Strength Of High Performance Concrete," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 18, no. 7, pp. 768–783, 2012.
- [8] N. A. Memon, M. A. Memon, N. A. Lakho, F. A. Memon, M. A. Keerio, and A. N. Memon, "A Review on Self Compacting Concrete with Cementitious Materials and Fibers," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 2969–2974, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2006>.
- [9] M. T. Lakhari, S. Sohu, I. A. Bhatti, N. Bhatti, S. A. Abbasi, and M. Tarique, "Flexural Performance of Concrete Reinforced by Plastic Fibers," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 3041–3043, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2084>.
- [10] *Iraqi Standard No. 5: Portland Cement*. Baghdad, Iraq: Central Organization for Standardization and Quality Control, 2019.
- [11] *Iraqi Specification No. 45: Iraqi Specification Limits for Aggregates Test from Natural Sources for Concrete and Building Constructions*. Baghdad, Iraq: Central Agency for Standardization And Quality Control, 1984.
- [12] *Iraqi Specification, No .1703: Water Used for Concrete and Mortar*. Baghdad, Iraq: Central Organization for Standardization and Quality Control, 2018.
- [13] *ASTM C494 / C494M-15, Standard Specification for Chemical Admixtures for Concrete*. West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International, 2015.
- [14] "Standard Practice for Making and Curing Concrete Test Specimens in the Laboratory," ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, USA, ASTM C192/C192M-07.
- [15] *BS EN 12390-4:2019: Testing hardened concrete - Compressive strength. Specification for testing machines*. London, UK: British Standards Institution, 2019.
- [16] *BS EN 12390-5:2019: Testing hardened concrete - Flexural strength of test specimens*. London, UK: British Standards Institution, 2019.
- [17] A. A. Thomas and J. Mathews, "Strength and Behaviour of Sifcon with Different Types of Fibers," *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 25–30, Dec. 2014.
- [18] S. A. Khan and G. Selvaraju, "Characteristic of Slurry Infiltrated Fibrous Concrete (SIFCON) Produced by Partially Replacing Cement by Mineral Admixtures and Steel Fibers by Waste Plastic Fibers," *Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering Knowledge*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2019.
- [19] B. H. A. Bakar, A. T. Noaman, and H. M. Akil, "Cumulative Effect of Crumb Rubber and Steel Fiber on the Flexural Toughness of Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1345–1352, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.854>.

Evaluating the Possibility of Replacing Natural Fine Aggregates in Concrete with Recycled Aggregates

Duy Duan Nguyen
Faculty of Construction
Vinh University
Vinh, Vietnam
duan468@gmail.com

Dieu Thuy Nguyen
Faculty of Construction
Vinh University
Vinh, Vietnam
dieuthuy03@gmail.com

Thi Hao Cao
Faculty of Construction
Vinh University
Vinh, Vietnam
haoxd13@gmail.com

Van Tien Phan
Faculty of Construction
Vinh University
Vinh, Vietnam
vantienxd@vinhuni.edu.vn

Abstract-This paper presents an investigation on the possibility of replacing natural fine aggregates with recycled aggregates in concrete. The studied recycled aggregates were acquired from crushed waste concrete from demolishing works. The rate of replacement of natural fine aggregates was 10%, 20%, and 30% by weight. Compressive and flexural tensile strength of concrete incorporating recycled aggregates was investigated at 28 days of curing. The results show that the compressive and flexural strength of concrete is strongly affected by the percentage of recycled aggregates. It has been found that the strength decreases linearly with increasing recycled aggregate content. So, in order to apply recycled waste to concrete as fine aggregates, it is necessary to perform supplement research with appropriate additives to compensate for the loss of compressive and flexural strength.

Keywords-compressive strength; flexural tensile strength; recycled concrete; fine aggregates

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of recycled materials instead of natural sources in concrete has been concerned by various researchers [1-6]. The influence of using recycled waste aggregates instead of natural fine aggregates to the modulus of elasticity, pulse velocity and long-term properties such as drying shrinkage and creep has been investigated in [1]. It has been found that the detrimental effects of using crushed concrete fines in concrete can be mitigated by a partial replacement of crushed concrete fines with pulverized fuel ash [1]. It was found that the rate of replacement of fine aggregates by recycled sources can be up to 10% for producing C30 concrete [2]. By using recycled fine concrete aggregates, the environmental impact and the consumption of natural resources can be significantly reduced. The results in [5] indicate that recycled concrete has a suitable behavior according to the limits indicated by different international codes for structural concrete. The durability of concrete with recycled fine aggregates has also been

investigated in [4], in which the recycled fine aggregates proved to be sustainable materials for construction works. The optimum replacement percentage of river sand by recycled fine aggregates was found to be 30%. Authors in [5] studied the use of recycled fine aggregates in concrete with durability requirements. Different percentages of recycled fine aggregates (0%, 20%, and 30%) were considered and evaluated. It has been found that the compressive strengths of recycled and conventional concrete are similar and the durable behavior of recycled concrete is as good as that of the conventional concrete.

Many studies on the use of recycled coarse aggregates instead of natural coarse aggregates in concrete have been carried out [2, 6-11]. The effect of the amount of recycled coarse aggregates on the properties of recycled aggregate concrete has been investigated in [11], in which 4 different recycled aggregate concrete types were produced with the same design compressive strength in replacement ratios up to 100%. The influence of the type of recycled aggregates, namely unbound stone, crushed concrete, and crushed brick, to the properties of concrete has been studied in [12]. The results showed that the performance of concrete containing each type of recycled aggregates was largely influenced by the aggregate nature and quality, in addition to the attached mortar content.

Studies on the use of recycled aggregates in concrete instead of natural coarse aggregates have been carried out by various authors. However, there are only a few published papers on the use of recycled aggregates instead of fine aggregate in concrete. In this paper, the possibility of replacing natural fine aggregates by recycled aggregates in concrete will be evaluated in terms of compressive and flexural strength of concrete. The results will give documented recommendations for further studies.

Corresponding author: Van Tien Phan

II. COMPOSITION OF RECYCLED CONCRETE

Waste concrete obtained from demolishing works was crushed and then sieved through standard sized sieves to obtain fine recycled aggregates with diameter ranging between 0.14mm and 5mm. The crushed aggregates were soaked in water until saturation, and then they were allowed to dry at room temperature. For evaluating the possibilities of replacing natural fine aggregates with recycled aggregates in concrete, a reference mixture was selected. Natural sand was then replaced by recycled aggregates at various rates, namely 10%, 20%, and 30% by weight. After casting into molds, the samples were stored under normal conditions and the experiments were carried out at 28 days of curing.

In the compressive strength experiment, normal force was applied on both surfaces of cylindrical concrete specimens with the loading speed set to 0.5kN/s. The maximum compression force was then recorded (Figure 1). Cylindrical samples sizes D150×H300 were cast and cured in normal conditions before being compressed to determine their compressive strength. The compressive strength of concrete was determined based on the Vietnamese standard TCVN 10303:2014.

In the flexural bending test, 3 beam specimens with a size of 150×150×600mm were sampled following the standard TCVN 3105:1993, and were left to be cured for 28 days. The flexural strength of concrete beams was determined based on the TCVN 3119:1993 standard. The four-point bending test set-up is shown in Figure 2. The bending load was continuously increasing at a constant rate equal to 0.6±0.4daN/cm² for 1s until failure occurred.

The replacement rates of recycled aggregates were 0%, 10%, 20% and 30%. Mix components for 1m³ of concrete are presented in Table I.

Fig. 1. (a) An in-process experiment (CP20) and (b) the recorded destructive force.

Fig. 2. Flexural experimental set-up.

TABLE I. MIX CONTENTS FOR 1 m³ OF CONCRETE

Cement (kg)	Sand (kg)	Coarse aggregates (kg)	Water (kg)
292.5	648.3	1216.3	195.0

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The peak normal load obtained in the compression experiment is shown in Table II. From the value of the destructive force P (kN) of each sample, the compressive strength (MPa) is calculated as follows:

The bearing area S is calculated by (1) where R is the sample radius, which is half the sample diameter D = 15cm, so:

$$S = \pi \cdot R^2 = \pi \cdot 7.5^2 = 176.71 \text{ cm}^2 \quad (1)$$

The compressive strength is then calculated by (2):

$$R = \alpha \cdot P / S \quad (2)$$

where P is the destructive load of the sample, S is the compressive area, α is the coefficient of converting the experimental results when compressing samples with different size from the standard samples (150×150×150mm). With cylinder sample D150×H300, α = 1.2.

TABLE II. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH EXPERIMENT RESULTS

No.	Replacement rate	Sample destructive force (kN)	Compressive strength (MPa)	Average value (MPa)
1	0 %	295.2	20.04	19.98
2		293.5	19.93	
3		294.1	19.97	
4	10 %	288.1	19.56	19.36
5		286.2	19.43	
6		281.3	19.10	
7	20 %	262.1	17.79	17.82
8		259.4	17.61	
9		265.8	18.04	
10	30 %	251.2	17.05	17.07
11		252.4	17.13	
12		250.8	17.03	

The value of compressive strength of the experimental samples is shown in Table II. It can be observed that the replacement of recycled fine aggregates affects significantly the compressive strength of concrete. The decrease is recorded as 3% at the replacement rate of 10%, 10% at the replacement rate of 20%, and 14% at the replacement rate of 30%. The compressive strength of concrete at various replacement rates of recycled fine aggregate is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Compressive strength of concrete at various replacement rates of natural fine aggregates with recycled fine aggregates.

The maximum force achieved in the bending test is the bending load that breaks the specimen. Table III shows the maximum bending force obtained in the flexural bending test. The flexural strength of beam specimens was calculated according to TCVN 3119:1993 by using (3):

$$R_{fs} = \gamma \cdot P \cdot l / (a \cdot b^2) \text{ (daN/cm}^2\text{)} \quad (3)$$

where P is the recorded maximum force, l is the span length, a and b are the dimensions of the specimen and γ is the coefficient of converting the experimental results when compressing samples of different size from the standard samples. In the present flexural experiment, the beam specimen was cast in standard dimensions, therefore $\gamma = 1$.

It can be seen from Figure 4 that the flexural strength of the specimens decreased linearly with increasing recycled aggregates percentage of replacement.

Fig. 4. Flexural strength of concrete at various replacement rates of natural fine aggregates with recycled fine aggregates.

The diminution of strength of recycled concrete with partially replacement of recycled aggregates has been reported by numerous authors [2, 3, 7, 10, 12]. The present investigation on the influence of recycled fine aggregates on the compressive and flexural strength of concrete indicates that the compressive strength and flexural strength decrease linearly with the increasing content of recycled aggregates. Therefore, in order to apply recycled waste to concrete as fine aggregates, it is necessary to perform supplement research with appropriate additives to compensate for the shown above loss of strength. It is also possible to consider reinforcing concrete with fibers at appropriate concentrations.

IV. CONCLUSION

The current paper presented the results of a research on the compressive and flexural strength of concrete utilizing recycled fine aggregates from demolition works. The rates of replacement of natural aggregate with recycled aggregates were 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30%. The experiments were performed at 28 days of curing. The results show that the compressive strength and flexural strength of concrete are strongly affected by the percentage of recycled aggregates. It has been found that the strength decreases linearly with the increasing percentage of recycled aggregates. Additional studies are needed to evaluate more thoroughly the effectiveness of the use of recycled aggregates in concrete.

REFERENCES

[1] R. Sri Ravindrarajah and C. T. Tam, "Recycling concrete as fine aggregate in concrete," *International Journal of Cement Composites and Lightweight Concrete*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 235–241, Nov. 1987, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0262-5075\(87\)90007-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0262-5075(87)90007-8).

[2] V. T. Phan and T. H. Nguyen, "The Influence of Fly Ash on the Compressive Strength of Recycled Concrete Utilizing Coarse Aggregates from Demolition Works," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7107–7110, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4145>.

[3] H. Yaprak, H. Aruntaş, I. Demir, O. Simsek, and G. Durmuş, "Effects of the fine recycled concrete aggregates on the concrete properties," *International Journal of Physical Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 10, pp. 2455–2461, May 2011.

[4] S. K. Kirthika and S. K. Singh, "Durability studies on recycled fine aggregate concrete," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 250, Jul. 2020, Art. no. 118850, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.118850>.

TABLE III. FLEXURAL BENDING EXPERIMENT RESULTS

No.	Replacement rate	Maximum force (kN)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Average value (MPa)
1	0 %	52.03	8.48	8.56
2		53.12	8.66	
3		52.37	8.53	
4	10 %	52.28	8.52	8.47
5		52.09	8.49	
6		51.50	8.39	
7	20 %	50.26	8.19	8.27
8		50.96	8.30	
9		51.02	8.31	
10	30 %	50.12	8.17	8.05
11		49.05	7.99	
12		48.98	7.98	

- [5] C. J. Zega and Á. A. Di Maio, "Use of recycled fine aggregate in concretes with durable requirements," *Waste Management*, vol. 31, no. 11, pp. 2336–2340, Nov. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2011.06.011>.
- [6] D. V. M. Reddy and M. M. S. Swaroop, "Effect of Recycled Aggregates on Strength and performance of Recycled Aggregate Concrete," *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 184, 2020, Art. no. 01085, <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202018401085>.
- [7] X. H. Vu, T. C. Vo, and V. T. Phan, "Study of the Compressive Strength of Concrete with Partial Replacement of Recycled Coarse Aggregates," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7191–7194, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4162>.
- [8] M. Oad, A. H. Buller, B. A. Memon, and N. A. Memon, "Impact of Long-Term Loading on Reinforced Concrete Beams Made with Partial Replacement of Coarse Aggregates with Recycled Aggregates from Old Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3818–3821, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2498>.
- [9] M. F. Koondhar, B. A. Memon, M. Oad, F. A. Chandio, and S. A. Chandio, "Water Penetration of Concrete made with Coarse Aggregates from Demolishing Waste," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6445–6449, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3891>.
- [10] L. Butler, J. S. West, and S. L. Tighe, "Effect of recycled concrete coarse aggregate from multiple sources on the hardened properties of concrete with equivalent compressive strength," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 47, pp. 1292–1301, Oct. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.05.074>.
- [11] M. Etxeberria, E. Vázquez, A. Mari, and M. Barra, "Influence of amount of recycled coarse aggregates and production process on properties of recycled aggregate concrete," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 735–742, May 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2007.02.002>.
- [12] N. A. Abdulla, "Effect of Recycled Coarse Aggregate Type on Concrete," *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, vol. 27, no. 10, Oct. 2015, Art. no. 04014273, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0001247](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0001247).

Investigation on the Performance of a Portable Power Generation System with a Low-Cost Vertical Axis Wind Turbine

Mohd Farriz Basar

Faculty of Electrical & Electronic Engineering Technology
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Melaka, Malaysia
mfarriz@utem.edu.my

Aina Musfirah Norazizi

Faculty of Electrical & Electronic Engineering Technology
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Melaka, Malaysia
ainamusfirah@utem.edu.my

Izadora Mustaffa

Faculty of Electrical & Electronic Engineering Technology
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Melaka, Malaysia
izadora@utem.edu.my

Carlos Trenado Colin

Leibniz Research Centre for Working Environment and
Human Factors at TU Dortmund University
Dortmund, Germany
trenado@ifado.de

Siti Nor Suhaila Mirin

Faculty of Electrical & Electronic Engineering Technology
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Melaka, Malaysia
suhaila@utem.edu.my

Zanariah Jano

Institute of Technogy Management and Entrepreneurship
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Melaka, Malaysia
zanariahjano@utem.edu.my

Abstract—The purpose of this project was to develop an innovative, small-scale, and portable vertical axis wind turbine for power generation. The wind turbine was simple in design and economical. Wind speeds ranging from 2.0ms^{-1} to 7.0ms^{-1} were tested on the proposed wind turbine. The experiments revealed that the turbine required a minimum wind speed of 3.9ms^{-1} to operate. According to the results, the proposed turbine achieved its maximum power output of 5.6W at a rotational speed of 65rpm when the wind speed was 7.0m/s. Additionally, voltage and current increased proportionately with increasing wind speed. The proposed system showed an average coefficient factor between 0.10 and 0.12. This portable wind turbine potentially revolutionizes industry while raising public awareness about clean and renewable energy.

Keyword—power generation; vertical axis; wind turbine

I. INTRODUCTION

Between 2018 and 2050, global energy consumption is expected to grow by about 50%. Most of this growth comes from non-Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (non-OECD) countries, and it is concentrated in places with rapid economic growth, particularly in Asia [1]. Wind turbine power is one of the solutions to resolve these issues [2-4]. Wind power was the fastest growing energy technology in the 1990s, in terms of installed capacity and

annual growth rates [4-6]. Prior to 1999, approximately 69% of all wind energy was installed in Europe, 19% in North America, and 10% in Asia and the Pacific [7]. The innovative Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT) to harness wind energy is proposed and implemented in this study.

II. CONCEPT OF THE WIND TURBINE

Wind turbines are a type of power generation equipment that uses the kinetic energy of the wind to generate electricity [12]. Wind turbines are typically classified into two types: Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWTs) and VAWTs [8-11]. HAWT's main rotor shaft and generator are mounted on a tower [12-15]. VAWTSs have a fixed structure and are insensitive to wind direction [16-18]. Typically, the VAWT gearbox and electrical generator are located on the system's ground [19-21]. The basic difference between VAWTs and HAWTs is their blade orientation. To construct a wind turbine model, it is necessary to understand the fundamental computation for the wind turbine's generated kinetic energy. The schematic of a VAWT is shown in Figure 1. The arrows in Figure 1 indicate the swept area for wind turbines [22]. The following equation expresses the potential power that can be harnessed from the kinetic energy of the wind [23]:

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 \quad (1)$$

Corresponding author: Mohd Farriz Basar

where P_w = power (W), ρ = density of the air (kgm^{-3}), A = swept area (m^2), and v = velocity of wind (ms^{-1}).

Fig. 1. Schematic vertical axis wind turbine.

The wind density of the air (ρ) at sea level is 1.2256kgm^{-3} [10]. Theoretically, the kinetic energy generated by a wind turbine is proportional to the size of the swept area and the wind speed, as shown in (1). Large wind turbines have a large swept area. The term "swept area" refers to the cross-sectional area through which wind flows [8]. The effective swept area of a VAWT is shown in (2), as indicated by the arrows in Figure 1.

$$A = rh \quad (2)$$

According to Betz's Law, the theoretical maximum efficiency of any wind turbine design is 0.59. A wind turbine can capture no more than 59% of the energy carried by the wind [11]. This is known as the "power coefficient," and is defined as follows:

$$C_p = \frac{P_o}{P_w} \quad (3)$$

where P_o is the power generated by the wind turbine and P_w the available power in the wind.

The power coefficient must account for all other components of a wind turbine system, such as the gearbox, bearings, and generator [11]. Large wind turbines have a power coefficient of 0.45, but small wind turbines have a power coefficient of approximately 0.25 and can be placed in any location regardless of wind conditions [12].

III. DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT

The system proposed in this study was a modification of the Savonius VAWT currently in use. It was chosen because it is capable of harnessing more wind energy than other VAWTs. The wind proposed turbine is portable, user friendly and affordable, allowing its use by the public.

A. Design of a Portable VAWT

The portable wind turbine depicted in Figure 2 was created with the Autodesk Fusion 360 software. Fusion 360 Autodesk enabled the design of various wind turbines in 2D (two-dimensional) or 3D (three-dimensional) and eased material selection for each part of the model. Figure 3 shows the design of this project drawn with the Fusion 360 Autodesk. The proposed wind turbine had a simple geometrical design,

consisting of three major components: the wind turbine, the generator, and a metal frame.

Fig. 2. VAWT design with Autodesk Fusion 360

B. Development of a Low Cost VAWT

This project was developed based on the design created by the Fusion 360 Autodesk. The system was simple to assemble and affordable in cost due to the use of basic materials available at local hardware stores. The materials used to construct the wind turbine were canvas for the blades of the turbine and round iron for the tower, pole, and blade frame. This turbine was supported by a modified stand hawking umbrella. Additionally, a DC96-01218e permanent magnet motor was installed as the generator. This motor is frequently used in washing machines to rotate the tub. The wind turbine is light, easily transportable, and easy to store or assemble. The wind turbine consisted of 3 blades with 0.60m height and 0.46m radius. Using (2), the effective swept area of each blade is $A = 0.276\text{m}^2$. This wind turbine has a total height of 1.60m. Figure 3 depicts a fully functional laboratory prototype.

The cost of VAWT is shown in TABLE I. The entire cost was USD \$129, and the VAWT took approximately 6 hours to complete. The cost of the materials was only US \$39, or 30.2% of the overall cost. US \$90, or 69.7% of the entire cost, was spent on labor. The most expensive component of the turbine was the round iron used for the blade frame, tower, and pole, with the total cost of US \$52 to develop.

Fig. 3. A fully functional laboratory prototype.

TABLE I. VAWT COSTS

Turbine Parts	Costing			
	Material cost (USD)	Labour hours (\$16/h)	Labour cost (USD)	Total (USD)
Canvas (Qty: 3) *Size : 0.46m (w) x 0.6m (h)	4	1	16	20
Permanent magnet generator (Qty: 1)	18	1	16	34
Round iron for blade frame, tower & pole. (Qty 1 set)	10	3	42	52
Turbine stand (Qty: 1)	5	0.5	8	13
Coupling and seal.	2	N/A	N/A	2
Assembly and balancing.	N/A	0.5	8	8
Total	39	6	90	129

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The proposed VAWT's performance was evaluated with the use of an effective experimental setup that was simple to install and closely replicated the real conditions found in low wind areas. The wind turbine was tested by applying a modest wind speed to the blade in the horizontal direction. The artificial wind speed was produced using a 26-inch stand fan with a 160W motor and 3 different wind speed settings. Figure 4 shows the experimental setup in the laboratory. The stand fan was positioned at various distances from the turbine in order to generate a variety of wind speed profiles. In Figure 4, the "X" indicates the distance between the stand fan and the wind turbine. The wind speed profiles at a given distance "X" are shown in Table II.

The results showed that the experimental setup produced artificial wind speeds ranging from 1m/s to 5m/s. A digital anemometer was used to determine the wind speed. Meanwhile, a digital Onosokki HT-4200 tachometer was utilized to determine the rotational speed of the wind turbine blade. The tachometer was able to detect speed without touching the moving item due to the addition of a reflector. The following are some aspects to consider when performing such experiments:

- Ensure there are no additional wind sources inside the laboratory.
- Experimental data are to be measured and recorded after the turbine has been spinning for 30s.
- Ensure the canvas used as a turbine blade is in a good condition before the experiment.

Fig. 4. Experimental setup.

TABLE II. WIND SPEED PROFILES

Fan speed	Distance between the stand fan and the wind turbine (X)	
	1 m	2 m
Low (Knob 1)	2.8ms ⁻¹	2.0ms ⁻¹
Medium (Knob 2)	4.8ms ⁻¹	3.9ms ⁻¹
High (Knob 3)	7.0ms ⁻¹	5.1ms ⁻¹

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Figures 5 and 6 and Tables III-V depict the proposed wind turbine's theoretical and measured performance curves. The results were shown for various wind speeds, with an emphasis on those less than 5m/s.

A. Minimum Wind Speed

The section discusses the minimal wind speed required to rotate a wind turbine's blade. Using the experiment setup discussed above, the speed was increased incrementally while simultaneously determining whether the blade rotated or not. Once the blade rotated, the generator's output voltage was monitored. When the wind speed was 3.9ms⁻¹, the blades of VAWT began rotating at 35rpm and concurrently created a voltage of 9.6V (Figure 5, Table III). If the wind speed was less than 2.8ms⁻¹, the turbine did not run, and no output was generated. In order to move the turbine blade from its stationary position, wind with greater force and kinetic energy were required to push the turbine's mass and overcome the motor's torque. Additionally, the experimental results indicated that the proposed system generated 15.1V at 65rpm with a wind speed of 7.0ms⁻¹. When the wind speed increased, the blade speed and the voltage output increased continually. The results demonstrated that the proposed VAWT was able to produce significant power at low wind speeds.

TABLE III. BLADE SPEED FOR VARIOUS WIND SPEEDS

Wind speed	Blade speed	Voltage (V_{oc})
2.0ms^{-1}	0 rpm	0.0V
2.8ms^{-1}	0 rpm	0.0V
3.9ms^{-1}	35 rpm	9.6V
4.8ms^{-1}	43 rpm	11.1V
5.1ms^{-1}	51 rpm	12.5V
7.0ms^{-1}	65 rpm	15.1V

Fig. 5. Blade speed and generated voltage.

B. Power Output and Efficiency

This section examines the power generated by the wind turbine, the accessible power in the wind, and the system's efficiency. The voltage and current generated by the system should be determined. Tables IV and V and Figure 6 demonstrate the proposed wind turbine's overall performance.

TABLE IV. POWER OUTPUT

Wind speed	Voltage (V_{oc})	Current (I_{sc})	Power output (P_o)
2.8ms^{-1}	0.0V	0.0A	0.0W
3.9ms^{-1}	9.6V	0.1A	1.0W
4.8ms^{-1}	11.1V	0.16A	1.8W
5.1ms^{-1}	12.5V	0.21A	2.6W
7.0ms^{-1}	15.1V	0.37A	5.6W

TABLE V. EFFICIENCY OF THE PROPOSED VAWT

Wind speed	Power output (P_o)	Potential power (P_w)	Coefficient factor (C_p)
2.8ms^{-1}	0.0W	3.9W	0.00
3.9ms^{-1}	1.0W	9.7W	0.11
4.8ms^{-1}	1.8W	18.1W	0.10
5.1ms^{-1}	2.6W	21.7W	0.12
7.0ms^{-1}	5.6W	56.1W	0.10

According to Table IV, when the speed was less than 2.8ms^{-1} , no power was generated from the wind turbine, because it could not function when the blades were idle. Additionally, the power generated increased continually as the wind speed increased. The highest output power was 5.6W when the wind speed was 7.0ms^{-1} . The voltage generated at that moment was 15.1V and the current was 0.37A. When the speed turbine was set to 3.9ms^{-1} , the power output and the generated current were 1.0W and 0.1A respectively. After measuring the proposed wind turbine's power output, the efficiency was determined. Equation (1) was used to determine the wind's potential power. Thus, using an effective swept area (A) of

0.276m^2 and an air density (ρ) of 1.22kgm^{-3} , the proposed wind turbine's efficiency was calculated, and the results are shown in Table V.

According to Table V and Figure 6, the coefficient factor (C_p) ranged between 0.10 and 0.12. This is consistent with the discussion in Section II, where the maximum C_p for a wind turbine was determined as 0.59. The experimental results demonstrated that the proposed system operated at an acceptable coefficient factor. As wind speed increased, the value of the power output and the potential power increased proportionately. However, the C_p value remained between 0.10 and 0.12. The greatest potential power was generated when the wind speed was 8.3ms^{-1} .

Fig. 6. Potential power and power output.

In [10], the authors created a Savonius VAWT. They modified the typical Savonius wind turbine model by adding single and multiple layer blades. Wind rates of 6.46, 6.99, and 7.27m/s were used to test the system. The experimental results indicated that the redesigned wind turbine exhibits C_p values ranging from 0.02 to 0.12. Additionally, the actual power obtained was between 2.2W and 4.2W. The proposed turbine in the current study performs similarly to the one in [10]. Both turbines perform similarly in terms of C_p and output power when wind speeds are identical. This demonstrates that the proposed wind turbine's performance is acceptable and that it can contribute to the field of wind energy generation.

VI. CONCLUSION

Overall, the designed wind turbine works satisfactorily. Despite its simplicity and low cost, the system is capable of producing a significant output power of up to 5.6W with an acceptable coefficient factor of 0.10 to 0.12. Additionally, laboratory testing demonstrates that these wind turbines can generate power even when exposed to low-speed winds, less than 7.0ms^{-1} . This research also demonstrates that the proposed wind turbine will operate when a minimal wind speed 3.9ms^{-1} is available to move the turbine blades. The higher the wind speed, the higher the voltage, current, and the created power output. Further research is needed to determine the impact of blade number and size on system performance. Electric generators can also be diversified to produce more power.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to express their appreciation to the Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) for supplying the laboratory space and technical help. Additionally, the authors would like to express their gratitude to Mr. Mohammad Faisal Zulfaqqar Bin Hasbullah for his technical assistance.

REFERENCES

- [1] "EIA projects nearly 50% increase in world energy usage by 2050, led by growth in Asia," *US Energy Information Administration - Today in Energy*, Sep. 24, 2019. <https://www.eia.gov/todayinenergy/detail.php?id=41433> (accessed Oct. 26, 2021).
- [2] I. Malacl and V. Dragan, "Numerical and Experimental Efficiency Evaluation of a Counter-Rotating Vertical Axis Wind Turbine," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3282–3286, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2231>.
- [3] M. B. Fazzari, A. N. Azmi, N. A. M. Said, A. Ahmad, and K. A. Baharin, "A study on the wind as a potential of renewable energy sources in Malaysia," in *ECTI-CON2010: The 2010 ECTI International Conference on Electrical Engineering/Electronics, Computer, Telecommunications and Information Technology*, Chiang Mai, Thailand, May 2010, pp. 651–655.
- [4] P. A. C. Rocha *et al.*, "The effects of blade pitch angle on the performance of small-scale wind turbine in urban environments," *Energy*, vol. 148, pp. 169–178, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.01.096>.
- [5] W. Tian, Z. Mao, B. Zhang, and Y. Li, "Shape optimization of a Savonius wind rotor with different convex and concave sides," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 117, pp. 287–299, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2017.10.067>.
- [6] R. Gupta, A. Biswas, and K. K. Sharma, "Comparative study of a three-bucket Savonius rotor with a combined three-bucket Savonius–three-bladed Darrieus rotor," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 33, no. 9, pp. 1974–1981, Sep. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2007.12.008>.
- [7] J. B. V. Subrahmanyam, P. Alluvada, Bandana, K. Bhanupriya, and C. Shashidhar, "Renewable Energy Systems: Development and Perspectives of a Hybrid Solar-Wind System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 177–181, Feb. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.104>.
- [8] K. Sahim, D. Santoso, and D. Puspitasari, "Investigations on the Effect of Radius Rotor in Combined Darrieus-Savonius Wind Turbine," *International Journal of Rotating Machinery*, vol. 2018, Mar. 2018, Art. no. e3568542, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/3568542>.
- [9] Y. Kyoizuka, "An Experimental Study on the Darrieus-Savonius Turbine for the Tidal Current Power Generation," *Journal of Fluid Science and Technology*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 439–449, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1299/jfst.3.439>.
- [10] Y. Kurniawan, D. D. D. P. Tjahjana, and B. Santoso, "Experimental Study of Savonius Wind Turbine Performance with Blade Layer Addition," *Journal of Advanced Research in Fluid Mechanics and Thermal Sciences*, vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 23–33, Dec. 2020.
- [11] I. Paraschivoiu, O. Trifu, and F. Saeed, "H-Darrieus Wind Turbine with Blade Pitch Control," *International Journal of Rotating Machinery*, vol. 2009, May 2009, Art. no. e505343, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2009/505343>.
- [12] H. Dumitrescu, A. Dumitrache, F. Frunzulica, A. Pal, and V. Turbatu, "TORNADO concept and realisation of a rotor for small VAWTs," *INCAS BULLETIN*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 69–75, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.13111/2066-8201.2013.5.3.8>.
- [13] M. J. Werle and W. M. Presz, "Ducted Wind/Water Turbines and Propellers Revisited," *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 1146–1150, Sep. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.37134>.
- [14] S. Ivanell, J. N. Sørensen, and D. Henningson, "Numerical Computations of Wind Turbine Wakes," in *Wind Energy*, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2007, pp. 259–263, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-33866-6_48.
- [15] D. Hartwanger and A. Horvat, "3D modelling of a wind turbine using CFD," presented at the NAFEMS UK Conference 2008, Cheltenham, UK, Jun. 2008.
- [16] M. Raciti Castelli, A. Englaro, and E. Benini, "The Darrieus wind turbine: Proposal for a new performance prediction model based on CFD," *Energy*, vol. 36, no. 8, pp. 4919–4934, Aug. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2011.05.036>.
- [17] B. Memon, M. H. Baloch, A. H. Memon, S. H. Qazi, R. Haider, and D. Ishak, "Assessment of Wind Power Potential Based on Raleigh Distribution Model: An Experimental Investigation for Coastal Zone," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3721–3725, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2381>.
- [18] W. A. Timmer and R. P. J. O. M. van Rooij, "Summary of the Delft University Wind Turbine Dedicated Airfoils," *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering*, vol. 125, no. 4, pp. 488–496, Nov. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1626129>.
- [19] I. Mălăeș, V. Drăgan, and G. Vizitiu, "The Vertical Axis Wind Turbine Efficiency Evaluation by Using the CFD Methods," *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, vol. 772, pp. 90–95, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.772.90>.
- [20] H. Dumitrescu, V. Cardoso, and I. Mălăeș, "The Physics of Starting Process for Vertical Axis Wind Turbines," in *CFD for Wind and Tidal Offshore Turbines*, E. Ferrer and A. Montlaur, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2015, pp. 69–81, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16202-7_7.
- [21] G. Naccache and M. Paraschivoiu, "Parametric study of the dual vertical axis wind turbine using CFD," *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, vol. 172, pp. 244–255, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2017.11.007>.
- [22] M. Dranca, M. Chirca, V. Zaharia, A. Zaharia, and S. Breban, "Permanent magnet generator for counter-rotating vertical axis micro-wind turbine," in *2017 52nd International Universities Power Engineering Conference (UPEC)*, Heraklion, Greece, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/UPEC.2017.8231959>.
- [23] R. Howell, N. Qin, J. Edwards, and N. Durrani, "Wind tunnel and numerical study of a small vertical axis wind turbine," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 412–422, Feb. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2009.07.025>.

A Two-Level Desired Load Profile Tracking Algorithm for Electric Two-Wheeler Charging Stations

Duc Nguyen Huu

Faculty of Energy Technology
Electric Power University
Hanoi, Vietnam
ducnh@epu.edu.vn

Van Nguyen Ngoc

Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Electric Power University
Hanoi, Vietnam
vannn@epu.edu.vn

Abstract-In Vietnam and in other developing countries, two-wheeled electric vehicles are potential alternatives to gasoline-powered motorbikes. The growth in the number of Electric Two-Wheelers (E2Ws) requires a large power demand of charging load. In addition, the increasing spread in the appearance and penetration of rooftop photovoltaic (PV) power systems, with their intermittence and uncertain nature, poses technical challenges that need to be addressed. The coordination of PV rooftop operation and EV charging may be an effective solution to meet the emerging load demand from EVs, increasing solar power penetration while minimizing the cost of grid reinforcement or possible upgrades. In this paper, a two-level desired load profile tracking algorithm for PV integrated electric bicycles/electric motorcycle charging stations is proposed with the purposes of load leveling, valley filling, and peak shaving. The simulation results show that the proposed algorithm is an effective solution, significantly improving the load profile, especially when compared with uncontrolled charging and constant charging power scheme.

Keywords-electric two-wheelers; charging stations; load leveling; charging algorithm; solar power

I. INTRODUCTION

The transport sector currently accounts for about 20% of CO₂ emissions and more than 50% of fossil fuel consumption. Recently, transport electrification has been considered as an effective measure to reduce Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions. However, basically, the GHG reduction purpose is only obtainable if the energy used for transport electrification is from renewable sources, instead of fossil fuel power plants [1]. Therefore, EV charging combined with renewable energy offers the potential for eco-friendly and sustainable development in both transportation and energy sectors. In Vietnam, the transition to electric mobility has notable characteristics. Instead of electric cars, electric bikes and motorcycles (hereafter referred to as electric two-wheelers or E2Ws) have been more attractive [2, 3]. A continuous growing in the number of affordable E2Ws in urban traffic initiates necessities like charging points at homes and workplaces.

More charging load leads to a higher demand for electrical energy. With modest battery capacity and charging power compared to electric cars, E2Ws charging at home might utilize portable chargers (which came with EVs) plugging in standard socket outlets. Because of modest power rating, these chargers, often of one direction type, are designed to optimally supply electricity to the EV's battery without caring of the electricity price scheme and the impacts to the grid or to other loads. However, in locations like offices, supermarkets, campuses, apartment buildings, transport terminals, or public parkings, a high number of E2Ws charging simultaneously would introduce a very high charging demand which might impact the grid or the provided power quality. In such cases, dedicated charging facilities are required, which could regulate and coordinate charging loads in the station, decide each EV's charging pattern based on EV owners' settings, technical constraints and/or economic/technical objectives. In other business models, such as battery swapping stations, coordination charging of batteries in the station might be more imperative since it can help both station operators/service providers and EV users to maximize their benefits.

Regarding to the electrical energy sector, Vietnam has a great potential of solar power [4] exploitation. According to the draft national power development plan for the period 2021-2030, with a vision to 2045 (Draft Master Plan VIII or PDP8), the total installed capacity in 2020 was about 69,094MW, with hydropower accounting for 30%, coal-fired power for 30%, gas natural/diesel power for 13%, and renewable energy for 26% [5] of total production. Total solar power generation in 2020 was 10.6×10^9 kWh, of which rooftop solar power was 1.16×10^9 kWh. In comparison with other power sources, renewable energy, especially solar power, is developed very quickly in Vietnam. However, because of its intermittent and uncertain nature, the continuing growth in the share of PV power leads to grid issues such as power, voltage and frequency fluctuations. This requires expensive spinning reserves, directly affecting the economic efficiency. In addition, transmission/distribution system infrastructure investment does not keep up with PV development, which results in cut-downs in the solar output.

By the end of December 31, 2020, there were 101,029 rooftop PV projects (nearly 9,296MWp installed capacity) connected to the national power system [5]. The development in the distributed rooftop solar power sources, along with the increasing popularity of E2Ws, poses technical challenges that need to be addressed. Uncontrolled EV charging may increase the peak load demand and energy losses in residential buildings and distribution power grids [6-8], which result in inefficient operation of the system. Noteworthy, the higher amount of solar PV output usually corresponds to low load time (about from 10 AM to 2 PM), resulting in needs of load shifting or energy storage systems. If the EV charging and discharging processes are properly controlled, EV batteries can also act as both loads and as energy storage devices or power regulating components. The involvement of EVs might contribute to increase renewable energy penetration without impact on grid stability because solar power is locally generated and consumed. The participation of EV batteries and PV systems contributes to smart grids with lots of potential such as load shifting, valley filling, peak clipping (peak shaving), regulation and spinning reserve. Several researches on optimal allocation of EVs are mentioned in [9], combined PV and EV charging in [10] and efficiency improvement of EV's motors in [11].

A. Related Work

It is shown that, the uncoordinated EV charging can trigger power loss and voltage deviation significantly [7]. With regard to load shifting and valley filling, studies focused on shifting the charging load to off-peak hours rather than uncontrolled charging. In [12], the authors proposed a decentralized valley filling strategy to build a day-ahead pricing scheme by solving the overall generation cost optimization problem (including base load and EVs). The pricing scheme is then broadcasted to vehicle owners to indirectly regulate charging behavior. Changing the charging pattern of each EV leads to valley filling at the system level. Authors in [13] proposed a decentralized charging algorithm for a large number of EVs by applying the Nash equilibrium principle. The authors found out that if the EVs are uniformly distributed, charging based on the Nash equilibrium principle would fill the overnight valley optimally. Linear programming was used in [14] to minimize the total electricity cost and reduce the power peak in a Time Of Use (TOU) price market while Quadratic Programming (QP) is utilized to minimize the overall load variance in a regional micro-grid in [15]. A decentralized charging protocol based on QP is also adopted to achieve the valley filling for the grid operators in [16]. In [17], a heuristic charging strategy for commercial buildings containing PV systems and EVs is proposed, where the EV charging rate is adjusted according to the variation of PV generation and the charging priority of each EV. Similarly, in [18], a centralized heuristic charging strategy is proposed to achieve the valley-filling for large scale EVs.

There are a very few studies relating E2Ws charging. Authors in [19] developed a PV-powered electric bicycle charging station providing AC/DC and wireless charging. The charging station had a built-in energy storage device that allows both grid-connected and standalone operations. Authors in [20] introduced a charging station powered by the grid, fuel cells, and PV to unburden the grid from charging. The station

can provide service when power outages occur. However, the aforementioned studies were restricted to only developing a PV integrated charging station for E2Ws. They did not focus on E2Ws optimal charging especially when a large number of vehicles are charging simultaneously. In general, researchers mainly focus on charging algorithms for electric cars with large battery capacity and significant charging/discharging power. There are very few studies aimed at developing control algorithms and operation schemes for electric bicycles/electric motorbikes charging stations, although the potential of this vehicle type is undeniable in urban traffic. Besides, due to the great number of vehicles in the station, the application of multi-target optimal charging algorithms for electric cars may not be computationally feasible for E2Ws. A higher vehicle number in the station means a higher number of variables, which requires a higher computational capability.

B. The Proposed Algorithm

In this study, we propose a two-level desired load profile tracking algorithm to allocate charging power to electric bicycles/electric motorcycles. The algorithm has a small number of iterations and does not require high computational capability. The contributions of the proposed algorithm are summarized as follows:

The study proposes and develops an algorithm (level 1) to find out the total charging power scheme for E2Ws in the charging station. The total charging scheme and the netload compose the desired total load profile. Based on the total charging scheme, a power allocation algorithm (level 2) is proposed and utilized to decide the charging pattern of each E2W or group of E2Ws having similar parameters. These charging patterns satisfy the charging requirements of E2Ws and the aggregated charging powers approximate to the total charging power attained after level the implementation. The proposed algorithm is applied for load leveling, peak clipping, and valley filling. By utilizing the algorithm, rooftop PV penetration rate can be increased with lesser impact on microgrids. The algorithm helps to increase the penetration of E2Ws without requiring grid upgradation or reinforcement.

II. SYSTEM MODELLING

A. EV Charging Infrastructure Model

In this study, the charging station is controlled and managed by a centralized controller that optimizes the coordination of E2W loads with other loads and with the rooftop PV generation in order to improve load profile and perform valley filling and peak clipping. Based on the existing load, the controller estimates the total charging power pattern supplied to all E2Ws in the station. The estimation process is planned considering the total required energy of E2Ws and other technical constraints. The controller then allocates the total charging power to each E2W or a group of E2Ws at each period, which results in a specific charging pattern for each E2W or group. Assuming that the charging station accommodates N electric bikes/electric motorcycles, EV_i is the i^{th} E2W in the N -vehicle parking at the charging station. Let $C_S(t)$ be the total amount of energy stored in the batteries at time t , $D_S(t)$ is the non-EV load demand minus the power generated by solar panels at time t , also known as the netload,

$E_S(t)$ is the total load demand (charging load plus netload); T_h is the discretization in time, and $P_S(t)$ is the total charging power of all E2Ws at time t . We assume that the charging station is connected to the grid, to the load of the building, and to a rooftop PV system, and all chargers have a Vehicle to Grid (V2G) feature. Thus, the charging station can be described by the following discrete-time linear equations:

$$C_S(t+1) = C_S(t) + P_S(t) \cdot T_h \quad (1)$$

$$E_S(t) = D_S(t) + P_S(t) \quad (2)$$

In this study, $T_h = 0.5h = 30min$. Since the chargers at the station include the V2G feature, the power exchange between the grid and E2Ws can be implemented in two directions. The charging behavior of all EVs can be determined by the sign of $E_S(t)$ where $E_S(t) > 0$ ($P_S(t) > 0$) if the aggregated batteries receive energy from the microgrid and $E_S(t) < 0$ ($P_S(t) < 0$) if the aggregated batteries discharge energy to the grid. The power constraints of charging and discharging processes (assuming all the EVs in the station are connected to the chargers) can be described as:

$$\text{Charging: } P_S(t) \leq \min\{\sum_{i=1}^N P_{cmax_i}, \sum_{i=1}^N P_{bmax_i}\} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Discharging: } P_S(t) \geq \max\{\sum_{i=1}^N P_{cmin_i}, \sum_{i=1}^N P_{bmin_i}\} \quad (4)$$

where P_{cmax_i} and P_{cmin_i} are the maximum charging and discharging power of charger i respectively and P_{bmax_i}, P_{bmin_i} are the maximum permitted charging and discharging powers of EV_i .

It is assumed that all E2Ws have the same P_{bmax}, P_{bmin} and P_{cmax}, P_{cmin} of all chargers are uniform. Then, the constraints in equations (3) and (4) become:

$$\text{Charging: } P_S(t) \leq \min\{N \cdot P_{cmax}, N \cdot P_{bmax}\} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Discharging: } P_S(t) \geq \max\{N \cdot P_{cmin}, N \cdot P_{bmin}\} \quad (6)$$

where P_{cmin} (discharge) and P_{cmax} (charge) are respectively the maximum permitted discharging/charging powers of the chargers. P_{bmin} (discharge), P_{bmax} (charge) are the maximum allowable discharging/charging powers of the battery, depending on the battery status. In this study, it is assumed that the charging power of an E2W has a positive sign and has a highest value of 400W. Discharging power is negative and the maximum value is -400W.

In addition, the total charging and discharging power must not exceed the feeder capacity:

$$\text{Charging: } P_S(t) \leq P_{feedermax} - D_S(t) = P_{amax} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Discharging: } P_S(t) \geq -P_{feedermax} + D_S(t) = -P_{amax} \quad (8)$$

where P_{amax} is the maximum power that the grid can exchange with the EV loads, which is equivalent to the maximum grid-microgrid exchange power ($P_{feedermax}$) minus the net load. It is assumed that the non-EV load demand is uncontrolled. The charging station needs to control the total charging demand of the EVs so as to do not violate the constrains (7) and (8). The constraint on energy requirement of E2Ws is:

$$\begin{aligned} R_S &= \sum_{i=1}^N \text{Required Energy of } EV_i \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N A_i (\text{LastSOC}_{EV_i} - \text{InitSOC}_{EV_i}) \quad (9) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\int_{t_0}^{t_m} P_i(t) \right) = 1 - p \end{aligned}$$

where R_S is the total amount of the energy required by all the vehicles in the station, A_i is EV_i 's battery capacity, LastSOC_{EV_i} is the SOC of EV_i at the end of the working day, InitSOC_{EV_i} is the initial SOC of EV_i , t_0 is the beginning time of the charging process, t_m is the departure time, and $P_i(t)$ is the charging/discharging power of EV_i at time t . If a working day from time t_0 to the t_m is divided into M periods with duration T_h , the above constraint becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} R_S &= \sum_{i=1}^N A_i (\text{LastSOC}_{EV_i} - \text{InitSOC}_{EV_i}) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\sum_{j=1}^M P_{ij} \cdot T_h \right) \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

where P_{ij} is the charging power of EV_i at period (4).

Individually, each EV must satisfy the following constraints:

The amount of required energy constraint:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{EV_i} &= A_i (\text{LastSOC}_{EV_i} - \text{InitSOC}_{EV_i}) \\ &= \int_{t_0}^{t_m} P_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^M P_{ij} \cdot T_h \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

The constraint on charging/discharging power:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Charging: } P_i(t) &\leq \min\{P_{cmax}, P_{bmax}\} = \overline{P_{EV_i}} \\ \text{Discharging: } P_i(t) &\geq \max\{P_{cmin}, P_{bmin}\} = \underline{P_{EV_i}} \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

In this study, it is assumed that a charging station is built on the campus of EPU, servicing 160 electric bicycles/electric motorbikes during working hours from 7 AM to 17 PM. The E2W's battery has a capacity of 1200Wh. Maximum charging/discharging powers are 400/400W, respectively. Batteries are not allowed to discharge if the SOC is less than 10%. At the end of the working day, the E2Ws' batteries are full.

B. Rooftop PV Simulation

We conduct this study using data from our previous work on the feasibility of PV-Integrated Charging Station for E2Ws [3]. Accordingly, the rooftop PV system is designed and simulated as follows:

- Capacity: 150kWp.
- Location: Electric Power University (EPU), 21°02'49", 105°47'07"; Hoang Quoc Viet Street, Cau Giay District, Vietnam.
- Scale: Most of electric bicycles / motorbikes currently adopt battery capacity of about 0.57-1.2kWh. The charging station is assumed to serve about 160 E2Ws staying at the station from 7h00 AM to 17h00 PM.
- Sunshine hours, solar irradiation, temperature at the site are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. SOLAR IRRADIATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Daily average value	Yearly average value
Direct normal irradiation (DNI)	1.688 kWh/m ² /day	616 kWh/m ² /year
Global horizontal irradiation (GHI)	3.584 kWh/m ² /day	1308 kWh/m ² /year
Diffuse horizontal irradiation (DIF)	2.320 kWh/m ² /day	847 kWh/m ² /year
Global tilted irradiation at optimum angle	3.652 kWh/m ² /day	1333 kWh/m ² /year
Air temperature	24.1 °C	
Terrain elevation	12 m	

After conducting the simulation, the power output of the PV system in a typical day of each month was obtained and is shown in Table II.

C. Non-EV Load Profile

In order to meet the charging demands of E2Ws, the charging station at the EPU is interconnected with the grid and the rooftop PV system. It is also connected to building's loads, forming a microgrid. The load profile of non-EV loads in a typical day is shown in Figure 1. For the purpose of testing the algorithm effectiveness, we did not investigate non-EV load profiles in a typical working day/weekend and we did not account for load demand variation in different seasons. We assumed that the daily profile of non-EV loads is homogeneous. It is realized that a working day consists of two peaks: The first peak occurs at about 10 AM and the second at around 14 PM. The difference between the highest and the lowest load demand is quite large with the highest load being

more than 3.6 times higher than the lowest. When considering rooftop PV power, the net load profiles in January and July are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

The integration of the 150kWp rooftop PV system significantly reduces electricity consumption, but the unmatched figures of solar power profile and non-EV load profile result in more serious variations in the netload. Off-peak periods of netload usually occur around 12 AM due to high solar power and low non-EV load. In January, the netload reaches the peak of nearly 40kW at 8 AM. This figure is 5.7 times greater than the lowest value of 7kW at 12 AM. In July, the netload is even negative from 10:305 AM to 14 PM, meaning that if there is no charging load participation, the rooftop PV power, after meeting load demand, can be injected into the grid.

III. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

To implement load leveling we propose a two-level desired load profile tracking algorithm.

A. Level 1: Total Charging Pattern Finding

This level includes the following steps:

- At the beginning of the process, collect the data of E2Ws in the charging station.
- Collect the data of non-EV load and solar power output forecast.
- Calculate the total load demand and the total energy demand of E2Ws.

TABLE II. SOLAR POWER OUTPUT (W)

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
0-5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5-5.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	307.7	307.7	333.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5.5-6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1692.3	1692.3	1666.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
6-6.5	0.0	0.0	285.7	3125.0	7407.4	7407.4	6352.9	5446.8	3600.0	2777.8	695.7	307.7
6.5-7	0.0	0.0	1714.3	6875.0	12592.6	12592.6	11647.1	10553.2	8400.0	7222.2	3304.3	1692.3
7-7.5	4235.3	5953.5	8800.0	14450.0	20756.8	20571.4	20756.8	19592.6	18438.1	17465.3	13927.7	7692.3
7.5-8	7764.7	10046.5	13200.0	19550.0	27243.2	27428.6	27243.2	26407.4	25561.9	24534.7	20072.3	12307.7
8-8.5	14222.2	16790.7	19555.6	26488.2	36000.0	36571.4	35788.2	35788.2	36000.0	34795.2	29257.1	19168.3
8.5-9	17777.8	21209.3	24444.4	31511.8	42000.0	43428.6	42211.8	42211.8	42000.0	41204.8	34742.9	24831.7
9-9.5	21942.9	26698.4	30461.5	37426.9	49614.7	52608.7	50841.6	50612.6	49843.3	49843.3	41634.4	32885.9
9.5-10	26057.1	31301.6	35538.5	42573.1	54385.3	57391.3	55158.4	55387.4	54156.7	54156.7	46365.6	37114.1
10-10.5	31565.2	37097.6	42316.9	49308.1	60298.0	63533.8	61015.9	62015.6	59775.1	60259.1	52778.3	42549.5
10.5-11	34434.8	40902.4	45683.1	52691.9	63702.0	66466.2	62984.1	63984.4	62224.9	61740.9	55221.7	45450.5
11-11.5	37788.8	45782.4	50260.9	57016.9	68258.1	70750.9	65503.8	67000.0	65750.9	63751.0	58504.2	49261.1
11.5-12	40211.2	48217.6	51739.1	58983.1	69741.9	71249.1	66496.2	67000.0	66249.1	64249.0	59495.8	50738.9
12-12.5	44251.4	52504.9	55018.9	63275.7	73014.1	73793.6	69014.9	68796.9	68534.4	67063.5	62276.2	54019.2
12.5-13	43748.6	51495.1	52981.1	60724.3	70985.9	70206.4	66985.1	65203.1	65465.6	62936.5	59723.8	51980.8
13-13.5	45097.6	52083.3	52356.0	59342.5	70595.4	67871.5	66601.6	62608.7	64155.2	60729.0	59450.2	51634.4
13.5-14	40902.4	47916.7	47644.0	54657.5	65404.6	62128.5	61398.4	57391.3	57844.8	53271.0	52549.8	46365.6
14-14.5	38281.3	45522.6	45127.5	52067.8	62296.3	57742.6	57742.6	53763.4	53355.6	47410.3	47716.1	43457.1
14.5-15	31718.8	38477.4	36872.5	43932.2	53703.7	50257.4	50257.4	46236.6	44644.4	38589.7	38283.9	34542.9
15-15.5	26784.8	33306.9	29714.3	37551.7	47040.0	44444.4	44137.9	39876.9	37551.7	32044.0	31441.9	27842.1
15.5-16	19215.2	24693.1	22285.7	28448.3	36960.0	35555.6	35862.1	32123.1	28448.3	21956.0	20558.1	18157.9
16-16.5	12903.2	17818.2	16095.2	21018.2	28800.0	28444.4	29411.8	26520.5	21407.4	12945.0	10364.4	9074.1
16.5-17	7096.8	10181.8	9904.8	12981.8	19200.0	19555.6	20588.2	17479.5	12592.6	7055.0	5635.6	4925.9
17-17.5	1333.3	2666.7	4000.0	5333.3	10666.7	11571.4	12903.2	9333.3	4000.0	1200.0	933.3	800.0
17.5-18	666.7	1333.3	2000.0	2666.7	5333.3	6428.6	7096.8	4666.7	2000.0	600.0	466.7	400.0
18-18.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2000.0	2000.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
18.5-24	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Fig. 1. Non-EV load profile.

Fig. 2. Netload in January.

Fig. 3. Netload in June.

- Define the desired total load profile (including charging load and netload) which satisfies the total load demand as well as the charging energy requirement.
- At each period, preliminary total charging power can be obtained by subtracting the netload from the desired total load.
- Browse all periods, implement correction if at a certain period the total charging power of E2Ws violates the constraints. Reallocate the power at the unsatisfactory period for the remaining periods in order to ensure that at

the end of the working day, the total amount of energy supplied to the E2Ws meets the requirements. At the end of this step, we obtain an improved total charging power profile.

- Calculate the battery capacity of the representative. Browse all periods, check the Depth Of Discharge (DOD) and the maximum battery capacity constraints. Reallocate charging power at the unsatisfactory period for the remaining time steps. At the end of this reallocation, we find the final total charging pattern.

B. Level 2

Based on the total charging pattern obtained at Level 1, allocating the total charging power for each EV or groups of similar parameter EVs is conducted. Level 2 includes the following steps:

- Browse the EV groups.
- Repeat the steps of Level 1 in order to identify the preliminary charging power pattern for the considered group.
- Check the charging/discharging power constraints at each period.
- Browse all periods, conduct corrections and reallocate if there is any charging/discharging power constraint violation.
- Calculate battery capacity. Check whether there is any DOD or maximum battery capacity violation. If the constraints are violated, reallocate the charging/discharging power of the unsatisfactory period for the remaining periods.
- After the two corrections above, conduct the third reallocation, so as to the sum of EV groups' charging power at each period reaches the total charging demand (after Level 1) with predefined error.

The pseudocode of the proposed algorithm is shown below.

C. Algorithm: Desired TotalLoad Profile Tracking – Load Leveling

1: INPUT: At the beginning, the controller acquires data of E2Ws in the charging station. The data includes:

- The battery capacity of EV_i : A_i
- The initial SOC and the required SOC at the departure time of the EV_i : $InitSOC_{EV_i}$; $LastSOC_{EV_i}$
- The maximum charging and discharging power of EV_i : $\overline{P_{EV_i}}$ (charging); $\underline{P_{EV_i}}$ (discharging)
- The permitted depth of discharge of EV_i : DOD_{EV_i}
- Besides, non-EV load forecast and PV power output forecast are also collected.

2: OUTPUT: At each time step $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M$, output the total desired charging power.

3: PROCEDURE:

4: Total required energy assignment: $R_S \leftarrow 0$

5: for $i = 1$ to N do

6: Calculate the required energy of EV_i :

$$R_{EV_i} \leftarrow A_i(\text{LastSOC}_{EV_i} - \text{InitSOC}_{EV_i})$$

7: $R_S := R_S + R_{EV_i}$

8: end for

9: Calculate the initial SOC of an EV which can be a representative of E2Ws in the station.

10: Preliminary allocation of R_S for M periods. Calculate the preliminary total charging power at each time step:

$$P_{pre_S} \leftarrow \frac{R_S}{M \cdot T_h}$$

11: for $i = 1$ to M do

12: Calculate netload at each time step:

$$D_i = P_{non-EV_i} - P_{solar_i}$$

13: Calculate the total load: $E_{S_i} = D_{S_i} + P_{pre_S}$

14: end for

15: Average E_{S_i} in M time periods. From the desired load profile, get the total load demand at each time step E_{SD_i}

16: for $i = 1$ to M do

17: Calculate the preliminary total charging power at each time step: $P_{Si} = E_{SD_i} - D_i$

18: Check charging/discharging power constrains at period i (P_{Si})

19: if P_{Si} violates power constraints

20: Reallocate P_{Si} for the remaining periods in order to ensure that at the end of the working day, the total amount of the energy supplied to the E2Ws meets the requirements and the allocation does not make charging powers at the remaining periods violate the power constraints.

21: end if

22: end for

23: for $i = 1$ to M do

24: Calculate battery capacity of the representative at period i .

25: if the battery capacity at period i violates DOD or maximum battery capacity constraints

26: Reallocate the charging power at the period (which violates the constraints) for the remaining periods. The allocation does not make charging powers at the remaining periods violate the power constraints.

27: end if

28: end for

IV. SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS

The current study assumes that the accurate day-ahead forecast of non-EV load and generation capacity forecast of the solar power system are available. For the purpose of verifying the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, we did not consider the variations in the accuracy of the forecasts. With 160 E2Ws in the charging station, we relied on the research data of [21] about the charging behavior. Accordingly, the initial SOC distribution is shown in Table III.

TABLE III. INITIAL SOC DISTRIBUTION

Percentage	Initial SOC	Group
11.6 %	90 – 100% SOC	G1
14.8 %	80 – 90% SOC	G2
14.9 %	70 – 80% SOC	G3
14.9 %	60 – 70% SOC	G4
13.7 %	50 – 60% SOC	G5
10.8 %	40 – 50% SOC	G6
8.4 %	30 – 40% SOC	G7
6.1 %	20 – 30% SOC	G8
3.5 %	10 – 20% SOC	G9
1.3 %	0 – 10% SOC	G10

The average initial state of charge of the EVs is 62%. In more than two thirds of all charges, the initial state of charge was above 50% SOC and 11.6% of all charges were even initiated with a nearly full battery with more than 90% SOC. The required amount of energy (R_S) of the 160 E2Ws is determined by (9). The battery capacity of an E2W is 1200Wh and the maximum allowable charging/discharging power is 400/400W respectively. In this study, we divided the 160 EVs into 10 groups as shown in Table III. In order to investigate the efficiency of the algorithm, simulations were conducted considering three cases:

- Case 1: Max speed charging: E2Ws are charged at maximum charging rate from 7 AM until reaching the required amount of energy.
- Case 2: Constant charging power: E2Ws are charged at a constant rate during working time so that the required amount of energy is attainable at 17 PM.
- Case 3: Smart charging: E2Ws follow the proposed algorithm.

The simulation results of the three cases during January, which is the month having the lowest solar power generation, are shown in Figure 4. It was found that, in case 1, when the E2Ws are charged at the maximum rate, the peak load occurred at 7:30 AM. This is 14.7 times higher than lowest load at 12 AM and 2.5 times higher than the netload peak value. When the vehicles are charged at constant power, the difference between peak and base load does not improve compared to the netload profile. The peak load, which occurs at 8 AM, is 46.25kW and the base load is 14kW at 12 AM. With the proposed algorithm, the charging and discharging powers of the vehicles are controlled to reduce peak load and perform valley filling and load leveling. The load power from 7 AM to 17 PM ranges from 32.27kW to 33.53kW. At the last time steps, although the netload is higher than the average load, the E2Ws' battery does not discharge to ensure that it is full at the

departure time. In case 3, the profile of total charging load and charging profiles of typical E2Ws in 10 groups are shown in Figures 5 and 6.

and perform valley filling. Considering the typical charging patterns of the 10 E2W groups, group 1 which has the biggest initial SOC, performs energy discharge during the first hours, whereas group 10 has the lowest Initial SOC. So, in general, this group is mainly charged from 7 AM to 17 PM. The change in the battery capacity representing the 160 E2Ws in the station is shown in Figure 7. The battery capacity increases rapidly from 10:30 AM and 15 PM, corresponding to the periods of highest solar power and charging rate. Figure 8 illustrates the typical battery capacity variation of the 10 E2W groups.

Fig. 4. Load profile in January.

Fig. 7. Battery capacity profile of the representative in January.

Fig. 5. Total charging load profile in case 3.

Fig. 8. Typical battery capacity variation of 10 E2W groups in January.

Fig. 6. Charging profiles of the 10 E2W groups in case 3.

Generally, it is found that, from 7:30 AM to 10 AM, the total charging power of E2Ws in the station is negative, meaning that the batteries discharge energy, partly powering non-EV loads so as to reduce the peak load. At the hours of large solar power and low netload, the total charging power increases in order to absorb electricity from the solar panels

Fig. 9. Load profile in June.

The load profile for the three different charging schemes during June (the month with the largest solar power generation) is shown in Figure 9. Compared to January, the netload in June is much lower because this is the month with the largest solar power output. If there is no charging load or even there is a charging load following scheme 1 or 2, at high solar power output duration, PV generation does not only meet the load demand but also it can inject the surplus power into the grid. However, in case 1, the simultaneous charging of E2Ws as soon as they are connected to the chargers makes the total load reach a very high peak, up to 78.67kW at 7:30 AM. In case 2, the peak load reaches 26.9kW at 16:30 PM, which is significantly lower than the peak load in case 1. In the case of charging following the proposed algorithm, the peak load decrease does not improve compared to case 2, but the load fluctuation is significantly reduced. The valley filling effect is clearly observable from 10:30 AM to 13:30 PM and peak shaving occurs from 7 AM to 9:30 AM. The total charging power profile during June and the charging profiles of the 10 E2W groups are shown in Figures 10 and 11. Generally, with the high solar power in June, E2Ws' batteries only discharge energy to reduce peak load in the early morning. From 9 AM onwards, when the solar power output is high, the battery will be in the charging process. In comparison to January, the charging ends earlier as the excess solar power allows the vehicles to be charged at a higher power.

Fig. 10. Total charging power in June.

Fig. 11. Charging patterns of the 10 E2W groups.

Fig. 12. Battery capacity profile of the representative during June.

Fig. 13. Typical battery capacity variation of the 10 E2W groups during June.

The battery capacity change of the representative is shown in Figure 12. Figure 13 shows the battery capacity variation of the 10 E2W groups. By about 14 PM, most E2Ws were fully charged. At the end of the working day, the batteries were not discharged to ensure that the vehicles are fully charged at 17 PM.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In case of a given electricity tariff, optimizing EV charging cost may result in a large number of vehicles charging simultaneously during low-cost price periods. This can lead to unwanted peak load and an adversely impact on the grid stability and power quality. If the utilities adjust electricity tariff according to real-time load demand variations (indirectly adjusting to the charging behavior of EV owners), the algorithm that identifies real-time tariff may not converge.

Unlike the case of electric cars, the decentralized approaches through adjusting the electricity tariff do not make much sense in changing the behavior of individual E2W owner because the charging power and battery capacity of E2Ws are much lower. However, when a large number of electric bicycles and electric scooters are present in buildings, offices, campuses, public parking, etc., the uncontrolled charging of that large number of E2Ws at the same time might trigger many unwanted technical problems.

Compared to other studies on load leveling using centralized approach, the proposed algorithm does not focus on forming and solving optimal objective functions. Instead, we derive from the estimated total amount of energy required by EVs and non-EV loads to establish the desired total load profile. Charging power is then allocated to the E2Ws on the basis of that desired profile and relevant constraints. Therefore, when compared to prior studies [15, 16, 22-24] our algorithm does not require high computational capability or computational time of the controller for solving optimization problems. It also ensures the finding each E2W's or group of E2Ws' charging schedule. This is especially meaningful because the number of E2Ws in the charging station can be very higher than the number of electric cars, leading to a higher number of variables in the optimization problems.

In this study, we propose a power distribution algorithm for E2Ws in an integrated PV charging station. The controller implements a two-level algorithm tracking the desired load profile in order to perform load leveling, valley filling, and peak clipping. The study offers a novel approach to control and coordinate E2W charging loads in the integrated PV charging station in which the controller decides the charging pattern for each E2W to improve the overall load profile. Simulation results show that, when compared to uncontrolled charging and constant power charging scheme, the proposed algorithm proves its effectiveness in load leveling, dramatically narrowing the load fluctuations while the peak load is even lower than the highest value of netload. The proposed algorithm can help increasing the penetration rate of both E2Ws and PV power and can indirectly lighten the adverse impacts on the microgrid and reduce the need of grid upgradation or reinforcement. In our future studies, we will further carry out research on the optimal control methods based on the available energy of distributed-mobile storage EVs as in [25-28].

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Messagie, F.-S. Boureima, T. Coosemans, C. Macharis, and J. V. Mierlo, "A Range-Based Vehicle Life Cycle Assessment Incorporating Variability in the Environmental Assessment of Different Vehicle Technologies and Fuels," *Energies*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1467–1482, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en7031467>.
- [2] D. N. Huu and V. N. Ngoc, "Analysis Study of Current Transportation Status in Vietnam's Urban Traffic and the Transition to Electric Two-Wheelers Mobility," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 10, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 5577, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105577>.
- [3] D. N. Huu and V. N. Ngoc, "A Research on the Trend of Transport Electrification in Vietnam and the Feasibility of PV-Integrated Charging Station for Electric Two-wheelers at Electric Power University," in *11th International Conference on Power, Energy and Electrical Engineering*, Shiga, Japan, Feb. 2021, pp. 255–260, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CPEEE51686.2021.9383333>.
- [4] E. Riva Sanseverino, H. Le Thi Thuy, M.-H. Pham, M. L. Di Silvestre, N. Nguyen Quang, and S. Favuzza, "Review of Potential and Actual Penetration of Solar Power in Vietnam," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 10, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 2529, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13102529>.
- [5] M. Oakley, T. Dobson, H. Pham, and D. Tran, "Draft Power Development Planning 8 Of Vietnam," *Energy Central*, Aug. 26, 2021, <https://energycentral.com/news/draft-power-development-planning-8-vietnam> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [6] D. Fischer, A. Harbrecht, A. Surmann, and R. McKenna, "Electric vehicles' impacts on residential electric local profiles – A stochastic modelling approach considering socio-economic, behavioural and spatial factors," *Applied Energy*, vol. 233–234, pp. 644–658, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.10.010>.
- [7] K. Clement-Nyns, E. Haesen, and J. Driesen, "The Impact of Charging Plug-In Hybrid Electric Vehicles on a Residential Distribution Grid," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 371–380, Feb. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2009.2036481>.
- [8] L. Pieltain Fernandez, T. Gomez San Roman, R. Cossent, C. Mateo Domingo, and P. Frias, "Assessment of the Impact of Plug-in Electric Vehicles on Distribution Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 206–213, Feb. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2010.2049133>.
- [9] V. K. B. Ponnampalani and K. Swarnasri, "Multi-Objective Optimal Allocation of Electric Vehicle Charging Stations and Distributed Generators in Radial Distribution Systems using Metaheuristic Optimization Algorithms," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5837–5844, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3517>.
- [10] M. E. Bendib and A. Mekias, "Solar Panel and Wireless Power Transmission System as a Smart Grid for Electric Vehicles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5683–5688, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3473>.
- [11] H. Aygun and M. Aktas, "A Novel DTC Method with Efficiency Improvement of IM for EV Applications," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3456–3462, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2312>.
- [12] K. Zhang *et al.*, "Optimal decentralized valley-filling charging strategy for electric vehicles," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 78, pp. 537–550, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2013.11.011>.
- [13] Z. Ma, D. Callaway, and I. Hiskens, "Decentralized charging control for large populations of plug-in electric vehicles: Application of the Nash certainty equivalence principle," in *IEEE International Conference on Control Applications*, Yokohama, Japan, Sep. 2010, pp. 191–195, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCA.2010.5611184>.
- [14] Z. Xu, Z. Hu, Y. Song, W. Zhao, and Y. Zhang, "Coordination of PEVs charging across multiple aggregators," *Applied Energy*, vol. 136, pp. 582–589, Dec. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.08.116>.
- [15] L. Jian, X. Zhu, Z. Shao, S. Niu, and C. C. Chan, "A scenario of vehicle-to-grid implementation and its double-layer optimal charging strategy for minimizing load variance within regional smart grids," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 78, pp. 508–517, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2013.11.007>.
- [16] L. Zhang, F. Jabbari, T. Brown, and S. Samuelsen, "Coordinating plug-in electric vehicle charging with electric grid: Valley filling and target load following," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 267, pp. 584–597, Dec. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.04.078>.
- [17] N. Liu *et al.*, "A Heuristic Operation Strategy for Commercial Building Microgrids Containing EVs and PV System," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 2560–2570, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2014.2364553>.
- [18] L. Jian, Y. Zheng, and Z. Shao, "High efficient valley-filling strategy for centralized coordinated charging of large-scale electric vehicles," *Applied Energy*, vol. 186, pp. 46–55, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.10.117>.
- [19] G. R. Chandra Mouli, P. Van Duijzen, F. Grazian, A. Jamodkar, P. Bauer, and O. Isabella, "Sustainable E-Bike Charging Station That Enables AC, DC and Wireless Charging from Solar Energy," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 14, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 3549, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13143549>.
- [20] D. K. Dhaked and D. Birla, "Microgrid Designing for Electrical Two-Wheeler Charging Station Supported by Solar PV and Fuel Cell," *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, vol. 14, no. 30, pp. 2517–2525, 2021.
- [21] P. Fieltsch, H. Flamig, and K. Rosenberger, "Analysis of charging behavior when using battery electric vehicles in commercial transport," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 46, pp. 181–188, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.03.179>.

- [22] Y. Zheng, Y. Shang, Z. Shao, and L. Jian, "A novel real-time scheduling strategy with near-linear complexity for integrating large-scale electric vehicles into smart grid," *Applied Energy*, vol. 217, pp. 1–13, May 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.02.084>.
- [23] T. Mao, X. Zhang, and B. Zhou, "Intelligent Energy Management Algorithms for EV-charging Scheduling with Consideration of Multiple EV Charging Modes," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 2, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 265, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12020265>.
- [24] C. Le Floch, F. Belletti, and S. Moura, "Optimal Charging of Electric Vehicles for Load Shaping: A Dual-Splitting Framework With Explicit Convergence Bounds," *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 190–199, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TTE.2016.2531025>.
- [25] D. Nguyen Huu, "An Innovative Adaptive Droop Control Based on Available Energy for DC Micro Distribution Grids," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 11, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 2983, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13112983>.
- [26] D. N. Huu, "An adaptive control of hybrid battery-supercapacitor storage for integration of wind and solar," in *IEEE International Conference on Sustainable Energy Technologies*, Hanoi, Vietnam, Nov. 2016, pp. 157–162, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSET.2016.7811774>.
- [27] D. Nguyen Huu and H. T. Nam, "Adaptive coordinated droop control for multi-battery storage," in *International Conference on Computer as a Tool*, Salamanca, Spain, Sep. 2015, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EUROCON.2015.7313703>.
- [28] K. Strunz, E. Abbasi, and D. N. Huu, "DC Microgrid for Wind and Solar Power Integration," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 115–126, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JESTPE.2013.2294738>.

A Survey of the Application of Artificial Intelligence on COVID-19 Diagnosis and Prediction

Hana Alalawi

Computer Science Department
College of Computer and Information Systems
Umm Al-Qura University
Makkah, Saudi Arabia
s44280166@st.uqu.edu.sa

Manal Alsuwat

Computer Science Department
College of Computer and Information Systems
Umm Al-Qura University
Makkah, Saudi Arabia
s44280158@st.uqu.edu.sa

Hosam Alhakami

Computer Science Department
College of Computer and Information Systems
Umm Al-Qura University
Makkah, Saudi Arabia
hhhakam@uqu.edu.sa

Abstract—The importance of classification algorithms has increased during the recent years. Classification is a branch of supervised learning with the goal of predicting class labels categorical of new cases. Additionally, with Coronavirus (COVID-19) propagation since 2019, the world still faces a great challenge in defeating COVID-19 even with modern methods and technologies. This paper gives an overview of classification algorithms to provide the readers with an understanding of the concept of the state-of-the-art classification algorithms and their applications used in the COVID-19 diagnosis and detection. It also describes some of the research published on classification algorithms, the existing gaps in the research, and future research directions. This article encourages both academics and machine learning learners to further strengthen the basis of classification methods.

Keywords—artificial intelligence; machine learning; deep learning; classification algorithms; COVID-19; medical image introduction

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is one of the fastest growing fields in Artificial Intelligence (AI). Classification algorithms refer to the problem of predictive modeling, in which the class classification is predicted for a given example of input data. Many machine learning algorithms are used. This paper will consider k-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Neural Networks (NNs), Decision Tree (DT), Logistic Regression (LR), and Random Forest (RF). Machine learning is divided into 3 main fields based on the learning style: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, or reinforcement learning. This research will present an overview of the classification algorithms and their application in predicting COVID-19 cases, focusing on the strengths and weaknesses of each algorithm. This research surveys the machine learning

classification algorithms used to predict and diagnose COVID-19.

II. COVID-19 CASES AND SYMPTOMS

Coronaviruses are a wide class of virus infections that produce illnesses that range from colds to more serious diseases, like the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS). In 2019, in Wuhan, China, a new coronavirus was discovered which since then has evolved to a global pandemic status. To diagnose COVID-19, quickly and efficiently, screening tools are needed. Machine learning algorithms with computer vision systems help diagnose COVID-19. This section highlights the research focused on machine learning and classification algorithms for COVID-19 diagnosis.

A. Symptoms of COVID-19

According to the World Health Organization [1], COVID-19 influences people in various ways. Most people who contract it have mild to moderate symptoms and improve without hospitalization. The common characteristic symptoms include high temperature, dry cough, and exhaustion. The less common symptoms are aches, sore throat, diarrhea, conjunctivitis, headaches, loss of sense of taste or smell, rashes, and discoloration of the fingers or toes. The most dangerous symptoms are breathing difficulties or shortness of breath, the losing the ability to speak or move and, chest pain or pressure.

B. The Way COVID-19 Spreads

Individuals can catch COVID-19 from other people who have the virus. The disease spreads principally by droplets, which are spread by a person with COVID-19 through coughing, sneezing, or talking. If people breathe in these droplets from an infected person, they, too, can become

Corresponding author: Hana Alalawi

infected with COVID-19. Thus, people should keep at least 1m distance from one another.

C. The Precautions to Stop the Spread of COVID-19

Since December 2019, COVID-19 has influenced all countries in the world. As of May 2020, the number of confirmed cases and deaths worldwide has sharply increased [2]. The pandemic has negatively impacted different industries, such as transportation, health services, and tourism. Many countries took quick action to stop the spread of the virus, which included awareness campaigns, social distancing, lockdowns, and quarantines, and transferring all work and schooling online. Virus researchers and doctors began searching for a cure for the virus. COVID-19 is now the most significant cause of mortality in many countries, specifically the United States, Spain, Italy, China, and Iran. Figure 1 presents the most recent number of individuals diagnosed with COVID-19 around the world, while Figure 2 illustrates daily COVID-19 deaths per million people. It can be clearly seen that the number of confirmed cases and the number of deaths fluctuate from time to time.

Fig. 1. Confirmed COVID-19 cases per million. Published online at OurWorldInData.org. Retrieved from: <https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus-testing> [3].

During the COVID-19 pandemic, in May 2020, authors in [4] provided a pre-tuned boosted RF classification algorithm to help the medical industry overcome the gaps of the traditional healthcare system through applying machine learning

algorithms in terms of real-time processing and prediction. Authors in [2] used a novel dataset with different algorithms. After comparing the results, the boosted RF classifier was identified as a good model for the problem. It achieved an accuracy of 94% and an F1 score of 0.86. Authors in [5] provided a comprehensive survey of various classifications by introducing basic classification algorithms and discussing some of the main classification methods, including Bayesian networks, KNN classification, RF extrapolation, and SVM. They also discussed the problems and potential solutions associated with each. Authors in [6] focused on implementing AI and machine learning in healthcare by providing better solutions with a high rate of accuracy to overcome the challenges presented by COVID-19. They presented a review of the previous studies that applied AI algorithms and techniques to tackle COVID-19, such as support vector regression algorithms, supervised multi-layered classifiers (XGBoost), deep learning LSTM networks, and regression trees. They presented the results associated with the pros and cons for each suggested model.

Fig. 2. Confirmed COVID-19 deaths per million. Published online at OurWorldInData.org. Retrieved from: <https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus-testing> [3].

Early detection of COVID-19 is essential. Previous studies have shown that in initial COVID-19 screenings and in all patient-care environments, blood tests are relatively rapid, cheap, and simple to conduct. Authors in [7] analyzed the state-of-the-art COVID-19 detection techniques, and clinical data were provided in order to encourage researchers to develop better disease prediction modeling. Authors in [8] provided a

comprehensive overview of the methods used for COVID-19 detection as well as a compendium of available open-source datasets related to COVID-19. Sixty newspaper articles, reports, factsheets, and websites dealing with COVID-19 were studied and reviewed. Most mathematical models were based on Susceptible-Infected-Recovered (SIR) models and Susceptible-Exposed-Infected-Removed (SEIR) models, while Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) was the main AI implementations used with X-ray and CT images. Mathematical modeling and AI have proved to be reliable tools to mitigate this pandemic.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For searching and selecting previous studies, the Saudi Digital Library (SDL), IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar databases were consulted. These databases are considered appropriate for COVID-19 prediction and cover the newest literature. The research studies retrieved from these databases are relevant and guaranteed to comprehend the purpose of AI systems in COVID-19. The databases were searched in a 2-year period between 2019 and 2021. The following keywords were utilized to direct the process of searching: classification algorithms, classification applications, classification review, machine learning, coronavirus, and COVID-19. Only modern studies and articles containing relevant information about the application of classification techniques concerning COVID-19 were selected and extracted. All publication types that were published in conferences, journals, and review papers were selected. The primary result of the search process identified 47 articles that met the review's eligibility rules, which are the novelty of the paper and the use of AI. After examining the full texts, 40 were selected and 4 articles were excluded because other methods were used in diagnosing COVID-19 instead of AI. It is difficult to present a comprehensive review of all machine learning classification methods in one article; consequently, this survey only focused on commonly used classification techniques.

IV. CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS

Classification algorithms are the most widely used techniques in the machine learning field. In general, the models in machine learning are divided into 3 general approaches based on their learning style: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning. The classification is a way of learning as the machine learns how to assign the labels to each class of the data. There are several models of classification algorithms, such as LR, DT classifier, SVM, NNs, KNN, and RF. Table I shows a quick comparison of all the mentioned classification algorithms in terms of their advantages and disadvantages.

A. Support Vector Machine

SVM classification has become popular due to its impressive performance, which is comparable to the performance of advanced NNs trained in complex tasks, using high computing cost algorithms. SVMs were originally designed as an effective approach for pattern recognition and classification [9]. Immediately after their introduction, these algorithms were used for some classification problems and applications, such as speech recognition [10], computer vision,

and image processing [11]. The SVM algorithm is primarily used for classification techniques. SVM generates a hyperplane that separates data into various classes. SVM can resolve either linear or non-linear issues. The main objective of the SVM is to discover a hyperplane in N-dimensional space (N matches the number of features), which clearly classifies the datasets or points of data. The accuracy of the outcome is directly related to the selected hyperplane. It discovers a plane with the maximum distance among the data points of two classes. The hyperplane is illustrated graphically as a line that divides one class from another. The data points are on different sides of the hyperplane and are assigned to different classes. The hyperplane dimension is dependent on the feature quantity. If the input is two features, then the hyperplane is a line and a 2D plane if the true of input is three. The SVM is also utilized in medical diagnosis to detect anomalies and in air quality management systems and financial analyses.

B. K-Nearest Neighbor

The KNN algorithm supposes that similar objects are close to one another. This algorithm is one of the most powerful supervised classification algorithms. KNN classification models are often used for searching the nearest neighbor class to predict the target name or label. The KNN is a simple algorithm used to save all available cases and classify new cases according to a measure of similarity, which is measured by a distance function (Manhattan, Euclidean, Minkowski, or Hamming). Nearest neighbor techniques are categorized as structureless KNN techniques and structure-based KNN techniques. Structure-based KNN techniques are based on structures of data, such as the Orthogonal Structure Tree (OST), axis tree, k-d tree, and ball tree. Additionally, data and site patterns suggesting suspicious behavior are analyzed by KNN algorithms.

C. Neural Networks

More accurately Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). An ANN is a series of neurons associated with synapses that mimic the human brain structure and has several components of processing. The human brain, however, is much more complicated. There are neurons or nodes in a neural network. Each of these neurons accepts data, processes them, and transfers them to a different neuron. The various units are communicating by transmitting signals to each other. An ANN is constructed as a directed graph with nodes and edges that link the nodes. The edges of each node are the interconnections. NNs can essentially be used for any task, from spam filtering to computer vision. They are typically utilized for machine translation, identification of anomalies and risk management, as well as language and face recognition.

D. Logistic Regression

LR is a machine-learning algorithm that predicts the likelihood of the response variables by given a set of explanatory independent variables. It is a supervised binary classification algorithm [12]. The response variables are coded as binary values, 0 and 1, and based on the values of the binary target variables, the data will be classified. The LR types are binary or binomial, multinomial, and ordinal. The values of the target variable in the binary LR have two possible types, 0 and

1, to represent gender (male and female), success or failure etc. Multinomial LR is used when the response variable has an unordered 3 or more possible values to represent the data, such as class types A, B, C, and D. The ordinal LR is the classification in which the response variable has 3 or more ordered values, such as student's scores (high, middle, and low). The LR algorithm has a solid statistical and mathematical background, but it is sensitive to outliers and prone to multicollinearity.

E. Decision Tree

The DT classifier is a supervised machine learning algorithm that builds a tree structure to classify the labeled data

based on a condition. The root node is the topmost node in the tree, and the leaf nodes represent the outcomes, where the edges connect the nodes to the leaf nodes.

F. Random Forest

RF is a classification and regression model, however, it is usually used in classification problems. It is a combination of random DTs selected to find the average of the best predictions [13]. To measure the best separates of the data, the RF uses the most voted class approach to select the best solutions [14]. This algorithm is used in different fields in real life applications, such as gene selection, finance analysis, stock market, e-commerce, and medical diagnoses.

TABLE I. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF DIFFERENT CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS

Models	Advantages	Disadvantages
SVM	- Efficient, better accuracy. - Not biased by outliers. - Non-overfitting sensitive.	- Problems in selecting the right kernel function. - Datasets have different results based on the kernel function. - Not optimal for non-linear situations or problems, not the best option for a huge number of features.
KNN	- Simple to understand. - Fast and efficient.	Sensitive to noise; the k number of neighbors should be picked manually.
NN	- Identifies complex associations between independent and reliable variables efficiently. - Capable of managing noisy data.	- Prone to local minima and overfitting. - ANN processing is complicated to interpret and demands a long processing time.
LR	- Reasonable accuracy for datasets and works perfectly if the data set is separated linearly.	- Cannot solve non-linear problems, since it has a linear decision surface. - In real-world situations, linearly separable data are rarely found. - Sensitive to outliers.
DT	- Easily processing large dimension data Interpretability works for both linear and nonlinear tasks, with no need for scaling or normalizing features.	Poor performance, and overfitting can easily occur with very small datasets.
RF	- Powerful and accurate. - Good performance on a variety of problems.	- No interpretability, overfitting can easily occur. - Need to choose the number of trees manually.

V. APPLICATIONS OF CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS IN COVID-19 DETECTION AND DIAGNOSIS

In coronavirus research, diagnosis is an essential preventive phase because it has a similar appearance to other forms of pneumonia. Consequently, the discovery of COVID-19 is critically important and vital in its initial stages. Different diagnostic methods for COVID-19, including a range of techniques of medical imagery, blood tests (CBCs), and PCR, have been suggested. The World Health Organization states diagnoses of COVID-19 disease have to be checked with reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) tests [15]. According to the U.S. Food and Drug Administration [39], there are 2 main types of tests that have been used to diagnose the virus, RT-PCR and imaging methods such as X-ray and CT-scanning [16, 17]. RT-PCR testing, however, takes time and this can be dangerous. For this reason, the initial detection of COVID-19 is often first conducted with medical imaging and the RT-PCR test is then carried out. The latest results from radiological imagery indicate that these images provide valuable details on the COVID-19 virus. The use of advanced AI technology combined with radiological imaging can be useful to accurately diagnose this disease. X-ray imaging has the benefits of being cheap and of low risk for human health [25, 26]. In an X-ray, it is a relatively complex process to detect COVID-19. In these photos, the radiologist should carefully note the very long and problematic spots carrying water and pus. Therefore, illnesses such as pulmonary tuberculosis may be erroneously identified by a radiologist or a

doctor as COVID-19. So, the X-ray method has a big error rate. Compute Tomography (CT) images are often utilized to detect the virus more precisely. However, CT images are much more costly for patients than X-rays. Detecting the effect of different respiratory system diseases such as ARDS, streptococcus pneumonia, chlamydia pneumonia, cavitating pneumonia, pneumococcal pneumonia, aspiration pneumonia, and COVID-19 on human lungs by using X-ray imaging techniques can be challenging as these diseases have the same impact on human lungs.

In raw Chest X-Ray (CXR) samples using deep NNs, authors in [18] implemented a personalized network (DarkCovidNet) for the automatic detection of COVID-19. The proposed model provides accurate classifications concerning Binary (COVID vs. No-Findings) and Multi-class (COVID vs. No-Findings vs. Pneumonia) classification with outstanding performance precision, 98.08% for binary- and 87.02% for multi- classification. Multi-classification demonstrated that the expert system can be applied to assist the radiologists in validating the examination process quickly and accurately.

Coronavirus causes different symptoms such as cough, fever, dyspnea, musculoskeletal, and anosmia/dysgeusia compared to the common cold, flu, and influenzas [19]. Authors in [20] proposed a method for binary classification and multi-classification problems by using deep learning CNN networks for COVID-19 detection. The model attains 99.6% accuracy on X-ray images and 71.81% on CT-scan images.

CNNs have been used to classify the images of the patients (COVID, normal, and pneumonia classes). The accuracy of the CNN multiclass model with Adam, sProp, and Sgdm optimizers was 96.4%, 95.4%, and 95.5% respectively. On the other hand, the individual classification accuracy with Adam, RmsProp, and Sgdm optimizers was 97.7%, 94.8%, and 97.8.

Authors in [21] proposed a method that used the Decompose, Transfer, and Compose (DeTraC) technique to predict and classify the chest images of COVID-19 patients. DeTraC deals with image recognition and classification successfully. The authors applied the CNN DeTraC in an X-ray images dataset gathered from many hospitals around the world. The model was trained in 3 steps: first was the extraction of the deep features of the images. Second, the optimization step is done by using Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD). Finally, the images were classified by using the last layer of the DeTraC network. The model achieved a good performance with 95.12% accuracy, 97.91% sensitivity, and 91.87% specificity. On the other hand, authors in [22] proposed a new deep CNN framework to detect and classify the patient's X-Ray images as positive or negative cases. The proposed framework, COVIDX-Net, includes 7 different CNN layers built by 7 models such as VGG16, InceptionV3, V3, DenseNet, and Google MobileNet to analyze and detect viruses. The COVIDX-Net achieved a good performance in VGG19 and DenseNet with F1-scores of 0.89 and 0.9, respectively. Furthermore, authors in [23] introduced another CNN model to detect the confirmed cases of the coronavirus. Authors in [17] used machine-learning for the classification of COVID-19 and non-COVID lung scan slices with 89.8% classification accuracy. Authors in [24] used chest X-ray images for COVID-19 diagnosis, and their classification accuracy was 99.56% for the disease class. Authors in [27] presented an early COVID-19 detection using SVM. The algorithm has applied to CT of abdominal images. From 150 CT images, 4 various dimensional datasets were generated and 4 different methods were employed for extracting chest CT picture features. Then, SVM was utilized to distinguish COVID-19 patients. During the classification process, 10 times cross-validation was used. The achieved classification accuracy was 99.68%.

In coronavirus detection and prediction, deep learning with a CNN is one of the most accurate solutions. Diagnosing the infected patients currently is done by either CT-scan or X-ray chest imaging. Authors in [28] used a dataset provided by the Kaggle to develop a COVID-19 detector, the dataset contained Chest X-Ray (CXR) images of COVID-19 infected patients and of uninfected people. The proposed CNN-based COVID-19 detector was trained on augmented data and achieved high accuracy in the prediction of the patients' needs in the next 7 days. In addition, the prediction of the number of deaths, new confirmed cases and recovered cases was 94.18%, 99.94%, and 90.29% respectively. Implementing the VGG16 CNN in the detector enhanced the model's accuracy. Authors in [29] introduced a new open-source network called COVID-Net. COVID-Net is a deep CNN to detect the COVID-19 positive cases by analyzing CXR images. COVIDx is the largest open-source dataset of COVID-19 patient's CSR images that have been applied to train and assess the suggested COVID-Net. The model achieved good test accuracy equal to

93.3%. Authors in [30] introduced a technique of learning pipeline and multi-view representation of COVID-19 classification utilizing different types of features extracted from CT images. 2522 CT images were used (1495 for COVID-19 patients, and 1027 for Community-Acquired Pneumonia (CAP)). The classification was carried out with different machine learning models, i.e. LR, SVM, KNN, Gaussian-Naive-Bayes classifier, and NNs. The proposed method outperformed the examined machine learning models with accuracy of 95.5%, sensitivity of 96.6%, and specificity of 93.2%.

For the selection of features and classification of COVID-19, authors in [31] suggested two optimization algorithms. There are 3 cascade phases in the proposed structure. Initially, features are being extracted using a CNN called AlexNet from the CT scans. Then, the proposed feature selection algorithm is implemented, a guided Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) based on Stochastic Fractal Search (SFS). The selected features were then balanced. Finally, using voting classification and guided WOA based on Particle Swarm Optimization, different classifiers' predictions were collected to determine the most voted class. For evaluating their proposed model, two data sets were used with positive and negative COVID-19 clinical CT-images. The proposed voting classification (PSO-guided-WOA) was 99.5%, higher than the other voting classifiers. Authors in [32] proposed a new architecture for COVID-19 prediction consisting of 3 principal manners: random selection of the region of interest, training of the CNN network to obtain features, and model training on a fully connected network and prediction of various classifiers. This method achieved a classification accuracy of 82.9% utilizing the modified Inception (M-Inception) deep model developed using CT images. Authors in [33] created a large dataset of CT scan and X-ray images from multiple sources and presented two CNN approaches to classify them as having COVID-19 or not, which are transfer learning AlexNet and a simple CNN architecture. They achieved 98% accuracy via the pre-trained model and 94.1% by using the modified CNN. Authors in [34] reviewed the possibility of ML models for diagnosis corona virus using X-Ray images. They used LR and CNN and Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) for data augmentation in order to overcome the overfitting problem. The model gives 95.2–97.6% accuracy without PCA and 97.6–100% with PCA.

During the coronavirus period, the collected data were often heterogeneous. Their features were categorical and numerical, or specific categorical such as the occurrence of cough, while the numerical features are quantitative, for example the temperature of the body. It is difficult to process these two forms. Moreover, this information may be incomplete as certain features have missing values. Incompleteness and heterogeneity are major challenges in identifying COVID-19 cases for data collected from many people. Heterogeneity and missing values are not directly handled by the common classification algorithms. To deal with these two issues, authors in [34] proposed the KNN Variant (KNNV) classification algorithm for incomplete and heterogeneous datasets as tools for detecting COVID19 cases accurately and efficiently. The two key concepts of the proposed algorithm are that the parameter K is chosen adaptively and that it calculates the

distances from other instances in a new way for each case being classified. The datasets were manually generated from a dataset of 68 COVID-19 and 62 non-COVID-19 cases from the SIRM database. Flu cases from the Influenza Research Database (IRD) were used. Then, the 2 datasets were merged and shuffled randomly to obtain an IHC dataset with two subsets: COVID-19 and flu. The results indicate that the suggested algorithm outperforms other known algorithms in terms of accuracy, recall, and F score. Authors in [35] published the initial research of applying an RF algorithm to determine the COVID-19 in clinically available blood test data. The researchers obtained 253 blood samples, including 105 confirmed COVID-19 cases, from different hospitals in Lanzhou, China. The method uses 11 key features out of the 49 clinical blood indexes that have been derived from the RF algorithm. The trained model, with 11 main features, exhibited 95.12% sensitivity, 96.97% specificity, and an overall 96.95% accuracy. In external blood samples, the algorithm's efficiency was slightly lower, with 95.12% sensitivity, 96.97% specificity, and 95.95% accuracy. The used dataset has a very high positive ratio of 41.5% which can affect performance. Moreover, the model in [2] revealed a high positive correlation between the patient's age and gender with the possibility of getting infected by COVID-19. Authors in [36] introduced a study of analyzing X-ray images of patient's and healthy person's lungs to compare and detect the level of infection on the lungs, and then classify it into level-based effect. Because of the complexity and the limited access to X-ray images, complexity-based theory was used to analyze the images.

During the COVID-19 epidemic, classifying the patients into infected or healthy is critical to prevent the spread of the virus. Authors in [37] suggested a technique based on deep learning by utilizing an SVM classifier to detect and classify the X-ray images of the patients' lungs as infected or healthy. Due to the limitation of diagnostic kits, the diagnosis of the disease has been used by X-ray imaging machines, as they are widely available in clinics and hospitals. The proposed system, based on deep CNNs, was used to analyze the X-ray image datasets. The system was trained on two datasets, namely one dataset of positive and one of negative cases. The datasets have been used to extract the images' features based on deep architectures such as GoogleNet, ResNet50, and Inception V3. The combination of the SVM classifier, the open-source dataset, and deep feature extraction techniques achieved accuracy of 95.38%. Authors in [38] proposed a COVID-19 classification by using CT chest images to classify the patients into two groups, +Ve (infected) and -Ve (not-infected). The model, called Multi-Objective Differential Evolution (MODE), with CNN has been implemented in a CT-chest images dataset, but the deep CNN showed some hyperparameter-tuning issues. However, the image features have been extracted by implementing many convolutions and the max-pooling layer was used to minimize the spatial size. The suggested model showed a good rate of accuracy, F-measure, and Kappa with values of 97.89%, 2.0928%, 1.9276% respectively.

Authors in [40] introduced a deep learning-based transfer model to diagnose COVID-19 cases by using CT-scan and CXR images. The algorithm was trained on 3 datasets. The model showed the detection results faster than the RT-PCR

method. In addition, they discovered a pattern between the infected patients with COVID-19 and pneumonia. Performing an X-ray or CT-scan in an infected lung a shadowy area called Ground Glass Opacity (GGO) will appear. Applying deep learning led to fast and efficient detection results. The aim of the model is the binary classification of the chest images in a fast and accurate way. Image classification was conducted and 3 experiments were proposed and applied on the dataset. The model achieved accuracy of 95.61%. Authors in [7] established a community learning model known as ERLX in routine blood tests diagnostics for COVID-19. The proposed model used structural diversity by 2 classificatory levels. To improve predictive capabilities, the prediction from the first classification (extra trees, RF, LR) was supplied to the second classifier (XGBoost). A series of steps in data preparation were performed using the KNN algorithm to control the null values of the data collection. Isolation Forest (iForest) was used to eliminate outlier data, and SMOTE to equalize data distribution. By comparing the findings with the state-of-the-art studies available for a publicly available dataset from the Albert Einstein Hospital in Brazil, the efficacy and reliability of the model for diagnosing COVID-19 was demonstrated. Ensemble models are more efficient, robust, and flexible since diversity is the fundamental guiding principle for capture underlying training data structure. The ensemble model achieved outstanding performance with an overall accuracy of 99.88%, sensitivity of 98.72%, and specificity of 99.99%.

Due to the small number of X-rays and CT images with COVID-19, training the machine learning and deep network models is extremely difficult. Therefore, transfer-learning could be an applicable solution that has been extensively adopted in several latterly submitted COVID-19 detection methods. A deep transfer learning-based approach has been suggested in [41] using COVID-19, normal, and viral pneumonia CXR images to detect COVID-19 pneumonia automatically, using deep CNNs. The results show that transfer learning has proven to be successful, robust, and easily deployable for detecting COVID-19 with 98% accuracy. However, the conventional transfer-learning system which uses a developed, pre-trained deep network in the images database to transmit the original information might not be an excellent option, since the features of X-rays and CT-image of COVID-19 are completely different from pictures for other apps. But after this research, researchers gave hope that COVID-19 can be recognized from other infections and normal lung conditions by utilizing CXR imaging. Authors in [42] report a COVID-19 prediction analysis in CXR imagery by applying transfer learning. They compared 4 common deep CNN predictors (ResNet18, ResNet50, SqueezeNet, and DenseNet-161). After training, the models presented an average specificity rate of ~90% and 97.5% sensitivity. Authors in [43] suggested a weakly supervised deep-learning technique to detect and identify CT image infection with COVID-19 using 3D CT volumes for classification of COVID-19 and lesion location. The proposed method can reduce the manual labeling requirements of CT images, but it can still reliably detect infections and draw a distinction between COVID-19 and non-COVID-19 images. The model achieved 96.2% accuracy,

94.5% sensitivity, 95.3% specificity, and an AUC value of 0.970.

Authors in [44, 45] stated that for computerized COVID-19 pneumonia detection, CT scans are utilized in deep learning systems. Although CT scans contribute more comprehensive information, X-rays are faster, easier to take, less unhealthy, and cheaper. Nevertheless, it is extremely hard to effectively train a very deep network because of the scarcity of COVID-19 X-rays at that time. The accuracy of their research in COVID-19 classification exhibited 96% AUC, 90% sensitivity, and 96% specificity and 99.6% AUC, 98.2% sensitivity, and 92.2% specificity respectively. In terms of analyzing and detecting the radiological images automatically, CNN deep learning techniques are widely used [46]. Usually in deep learning techniques, model training is conducted with large datasets, but due to the limitation of the infected X-ray or CT scan images, the network weights have been fine-tuned from pre-trained networks. Authors in [47] proposed a classification model to classify the chest CT scan of COVID-19 patients as positive (infected) or negative (uninfected). The model was based on Deep Transfer Learning (DTL) with DenseNet201 and CNN. It had 99.82% training accuracy and the achieved testing and validation accuracies were 96.25% and 97.4% respectively.

Authors in [48] proposed a deep DT classifier consisting of 3 stages. Each DT was trained using a deep learning model with a NN based on a PyTorch frame for the detection of COVID-19 in chest X-ray images. The average acquired accuracy was 95%. Authors in [49] utilized a pretrained DenseNet121 model for the classification of segmented 3D lung regions. The dataset consisted of 2724 CT scans from 2617 sufferers. Lung regions were separated via utilizing the 3D Anisotropic Hybrid Network (AH-Net) architecture, achieving 90.8% accuracy, 93% specificity, and 94.9% AUC score. The significance of using AI in the medical domain to diagnose and predict diseases is in making several decisions based on big data analysis. Authors in [50] suggested a deep learning-based model to predict the coronavirus severity level by using CT scan images of infected patients. The model was trained in 303 chest images and was tested in 105 images, achieving 97.4% training and 81.9% testing accuracy.

Based on coronavirus confirmed cases, countries have been classified into categories based on the risk rate. Authors in [51] proposed an AI-guided method to predict the long-term country-specific risk of COVID-19 by the Bayesian optimization guided shallow LSTM. On average the model showed an accuracy of 77.4%. Applying the model during the pandemic posed many challenges such as the limitation of the dataset, data uncertainty, and data confusion. Authors in [52] provided a system based on deep learning to COVID-19 detection using CNN and convolutional (ConvLSTM) with 100% accuracy and F1 score, while authors in [53] obtained 89.5% accuracy, 88% specificity and 87% sensitivity in CT images. Authors in [54] got AUC of 99% and recall of 93% in COVID-19 diagnosis. Authors in [55] used the ResNet-50 deep learning model to classify COVID-19 in CT scans with 96% AUC. Authors in [56] identified coronavirus cases rapidly using the ResNet-100 CNN along with LR achieving accuracy of 99.15%. Authors in [57] proposed COVID-19 pneumonia

detection using a small number of COVID-19 CXR images. They optimized the features using the CNN model CONVNet with 98.1% accuracy. Authors in [58] investigated the performance of KNN, DT, NB, SVM, and LR to discover COVID-19 cases. The results were 93% accuracy for NB and DT, 93.60% for SVM, 93.50% for KNN, and 92.80% for LR and they concluded that ML methods have an important use in identifying COVID-19. Authors in [59] proposed a detection-classification approach to diagnose COVID-19 by examining the patients' lungs using CT-scan and X-ray images. Their approach was compared with the SVM classifier. The comparison was made on the classification accuracy as a performance indicator. The classification-detection model achieved 84% and 75% with CXRs and CT-scans, respectively.

Table II provides a summary of all the reviewed studies.

VI. COVID-19 IMAGE DATASETS

CT scanning and X-ray imaging are the most common used techniques in respiratory disease diagnosis. For decades, radiologists and other healthcare professionals have used them. Discovering COVID-19 early is crucial to prevent its spread by using diagnostic imagery methods. To show the damage of COVID-19 on the patient's lungs, many health and technology centers publish data about COVID-19, pneumonia, and acute respiratory distress syndrome. Authors in [61] produced the first public dataset of the frontal view of X-ray images. The dataset was collected from different open sources by the University of Montreal. It consists of more than 400 CT and X-ray images of COVID-19, SARS, MERS-CoV, varicella, influenza, and herpes patients. The dataset is continuously updated by the newest COVID-19 cases through the GitHub link [62]. The dataset in [63] is a public dataset of 5,863 X-Ray images categorized into normal/healthy lungs and pneumonia-infected lungs. Another dataset of chest X-ray images of COVID-19 cases was published in 2020 [64]. The dataset contains X-ray images of COVID-19-infected lungs along with normal lungs in addition to viral pneumonia images. It consists of 3,487 images of normal, COVID-19, and viral patients. There is also a public dataset available on the Kaggle website [65], which contains a mixture of X-ray and CT scan images of patients diagnosed with COVID-19. Patients' images were extracted from public articles in RSNA, Radiopaedia, and SIRM [66]. ChestX-ray8 is a large public database provided in [32]. It consists of frontal-view X-ray images collected from 1992 to 2015. The dataset contains 108,948 images of more than 32,717 patients. Images are labeled and divided among 8 common thoracic pathology diseases. Authors in [67] produced a publicly available dataset of CT scan images of COVID-19 cases. The COVID-CT dataset contains 349 CT scans of confirmed cases, which were collected from relative sources, such as medRxiv, NEJM, JAMA, Lancet, and bioRxiv. The COVID-19 CT lung and infection segmentation dataset [68] contains 100 CT images collected from more than 40 patients with COVID-19. The COVID-19 imaging database is another open-source dataset used by the British Society of Thoracic Imaging [69]. This dataset is used for learning and education purposes and it consists of 59 images of SARS-CoV2 patients.

VII. DISCUSSION

This study focused on the latest studies that used AI applications to confront COVID-19. In imaging-based COVID-19 classification, AI has been successfully applied. However, much work remains to be done. A growing number of different classification and prediction models use AI along with more publicly available datasets. In this paper, many recent research studies were reviewed. These studies involved deep learning and machine learning for COVID-19 classification. Deep learning approaches, such as CNNs, automatically perform the function extraction process. Little research, however, has been done on traditional machine learning models, like KNN, SVM, RF, and DT (see Table II). Most of this research used medical images to diagnose COVID-19 because they provide more details and depict the diseased areas of the body. The AI-based classification of CXRs has the untapped potential to meet this need.

Latest research has shown that compared with CT and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), CXR-related diagnosis is the most widely used because of its low cost, short therapy time, and low radiation exposure. However, the reviewed studies that used these images have some weaknesses. Some did not involve all age groups or adequately considered the patient's gender. Improving upon this can help facilitate the classification process of machine learning models. Given the small number of CXR and CT pictures available for COVID-19 at that time, the AI models were trained on fewer pictures, which may lead to overfitting in classification models and low accuracy. Deep learning models must be based on large datasets to work efficiently. For this reason, some techniques, such as augmentation, have been used to generalize models and to increase the size of the datasets. Researchers constantly work to update classification models and to increase their reliability and usefulness in real-life circumstances using the available datasets. In addition, the availability of more and more diversified training images would make the creation of strong and scalable classification models easier. AI-based disease classification can be merged with confirmed lab tests. It would be an excellent suggestion to help diagnose and evaluate recovering/infected patients utilizing fast AI-based tools.

Deep learning has become the dominant approach for detecting and diagnosing COVID-19. The image data in COVID-19 applications, however, could be inconsistent and inaccurate, posing a challenge for the creation of an exact segmentation and diagnostic network. For this situation, weakly supervised deep learning approaches may help. Some researchers diagnose COVID-19 cases employing machine learning methods by utilizing deep learning strategies via selecting the features of the images and obtaining high quality results. Finally, all the medical images used in the previous studies were not standardized and from different sources, in addition to the different medical devices that took these pictures. All these factors make a comprehensive comparison difficult.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The negative impact of COVID-19 has increased since December 2019. AI methods and applications in the medical

fields showed success in fighting the virus. In this paper, an extensive review of the latest studies in COVID-19 classification and prediction was presented with a description of the frequently used methods and techniques in disease diagnosis, detection, and prediction. The number of contributions in this field is growing exponentially due to their success in preventing the spread of COVID-19. This paper summarized the research papers in classification algorithms and their applications in COVID-19 prediction models with a review of the method's aim in addition to the models' performance. Among the published studies, the use of deep learning in radiology imaging machines improved the models' performance.

IX. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND CHALLENGES

The researchers in machine learning –related COVID-19 detection may face several challenges, especially when dealing with data provided from different sources and different formats.

- Large-scale training data are scarce and difficult to get.

Many deep learning techniques rely on a large dataset to train models, such as medical images to build an automatic system for prediction [70]. Due to the rapid explosion of COVID-19, the interpretation and labeling of training samples are time-consuming and require expert physicians, which results in insufficient data [71].

- Inappropriate data

Diverse online publications have published incorrect reports concerning COVID-19. Because of this problem, the use and reliability of AI-based methods have been reduced.

- Data protection and privacy.

To prevent the spread of COVID-19 and conduct proper contact tracing, patient's personal information is often collected, such as their identity number, contact information, and medical data. Therefore, protecting and maintaining the patient's privacy during treatment is incredibly important.

- Incorrect structured and unstructured data.

Incorrect information in text descriptions and medical images poses a challenge to researchers and machine learning models. A huge amount of data from various sources may be impossible to be used. AI also faces problems, such as dealing with unbalanced datasets, difficulty in screening, triaging patients due to restrictions [72], and social distancing, as well as dealing with poor quality data. Regarding future research directions, AI can be used in remote video investigation and consultations, biological research and knowledge of important protein structures and virus sequences, impact assessment of COVID-19, drug development, patient contact tracking, as well as diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF THE RESEARCH ON COVID-19 DIAGNOSIS

Ref.	Aim	Methods	Datasets	Performance
[2]	Proposed a fine-tuned RF model supported with AdaBoost algorithm for covid-19 prediction.	Boosted RF algorithm	Novel Coronavirus 2019 dataset.	Revealed a high positive correlation between the patient's age and sex with the possibility of getting infected by Covid-19.
[3]	ERLX model developed for the detection and classification of COVID-19.	Extra trees, RF, LR, XGBoost	Routine blood examinations of COVID-19 cases at Albert Einstein Hospital.	99.88% accuracy, 98.72% sensitivity, 99.99% specificity.
[4]	Classifying COVID-19 and non-COVID classes based on lung CT scans	NB, KNN, DT, RF, SVM	CT scans from available datasets, including 500 photos (250 normal and 250 COVID-19).	Accuracy of NB, KNN, DT at 80%, of RF at 79%, and of SVM at 81%
[5]	Implemented a personalized network (DarkCovidNet) for automatic COVID-19 detection	DarkNet classifier	127 infected patients, 500 normal cases, and 500 pneumonia frontal X-ray images.	98.08% for binary and 87.02% for multi-class classification accuracy.
[6]	Proposed a method for binary classification and multi-classification problems by using a deep learning CNN network for the identification of COVID-19.	Deep CNN	910 X-rays and CT scans of COVID-19.	99% accuracy on X-ray images, and 71% on CT-scan images.
[7]	Used DeTraC to predict and classify the chest images of COVID-19 sufferers	DeTraC with CNN	CXR photos from many hospitals worldwide.	95.12% accuracy, 97.91% sensitivity, 91.87% specificity.
[8]	Prediction of patient's images as positive or negative cases.	COVIDX-Net deep CNN framework	50 X-ray photos with 25 positive COVID-19 confirmed cases.	The COVIDX-Net achieved a good performance in VGG19 and DenseNet including f1-scores of 0.89 and 0.9, respectively.
[9]	Detect the confirmed cases of coronavirus	Deep CNN with ResNet50, ResNet101, ResNet 152, Inception V3, and Inception-ResNet V2	Dr. Joseph Cohen open-source dataset and CXR images (pneumonia).	Accuracy of 96.1%, 99.5, and 99.7 for dataset-1, dataset-2, and dataset-3 respectively.
[10]	Utilizing CNN to diagnose cases of COVID-19 with chest X-rays	Xception and ResNet50V2-based CNN	X-rays datasets of 180 images of COVID-19.	99.56% accuracy and 80.53% recall.
[11]	Early COVID-19 detection	SVM	150 CT images for COVID-19.	99.68% accuracy.
[12]	A detector trained on augmented data with high accuracy in the prediction of the patients' needs in the next 7 days.	Deep learning CNN	COVID-19 X-ray images	High accuracy of 94.18%, 99.94%, and 90.29% respectively in predicting the number of deaths, newly confirmed cases, and recovered cases.
[13]	A new open-source network called COVID-Net to distinguish the Covid-19 positive cases by analyzing CXR images.	Deep CNN	COVIDx is the largest open-source dataset of Covid-19 patient's CXR images.	93.3% accuracy.
[14]	COVID-19 classification based on pipeline and multiview representation learning method.	Pipeline and multiview representation learning	CT images of 1495 COVID-19 1027 CAP.	95.5% accuracy, 96.6% sensitivity, 93.2% specificity.
[15]	Two optimization algorithms were introduced in order to select and classify features of the COVID-19.	CNN, Guided WOA	334 CT images for COVID-19 and 794 CT images for non-COVID-19.	99.5% accuracy.
[16]	COVID-19 prediction consisting of 3 main processes.	CNN	CT images of 453 COVID-19 cases	82.9% accuracy.
[17]	KNNV classification algorithms for incomplete and heterogeneous datasets as tools for detecting COVID19 cases	KNNV	IHC dataset with 68 COVID patients and 62 flu patients.	All metrics indicate that KNNV is much stronger than the relevant algorithms.
[18]	Discover COVID-19 from clinically available blood test data	RF	Hospitals, Lanzhou, China.	95.12% sensitivity, 96.97% specificity, 96.95% accuracy.
[19]	Suggested a system based on deep CNNs to analyze X-ray image datasets.	Deep CNN	One dataset with 25 cases of COVID-19+ and 25 of COVID-19- X-ray images and another with 133 CRX images as COVID-19- and 133 as COVID-19+.	Achieved accuracy in terms of testing, F1 score, MCC, and Kappa, 95.38%, 95.52%, 91.41%, 90.76 % respectively.
[20]	Classify the patients into +Ve (infected) and -Ve (not-infected) groups.	MODE with CNN	X-ray and CT scan images	Accuracy, F-measure, and Kappa statistics were 97.89%, 2.0928%, 1.9276% respectively
[21]	A deep learning-based transfer model to diagnose COVID-19 cases. Binary classification in a fast and accurate way.	Deep learning-based transfer model	Three datasets SARS-COV2 CT-scan, CRX, and COVID-CRX	95.61% accuracy.
[22]	Automatic detection of COVID-19 pneumonia utilizing DCNNs.	DCNN	864 COVID-19, 1345 pneumonia, and 1341 CXR images.	98% accuracy.
[58]	Building automatic CT picture analysis tools based on AI for Coronavirus identification, quantification, and tracking.	Deep Learning	CT image datasets, the testing set had 157 international patients	99.6% AUC, 98.2% sensitivity, 92.2% specificity.

[54]	A weakly-supervised DL for identifying and classifying COVID-19 from CT scans and reduce the requirements of labeling the CT images.	Weakly-supervised deep learning system using CNN	150 3D chest CT scans of COVID-19, CAP, and NP patients respectively	96.2% accuracy, 94.5% sensitivity, 95.3% specificity, 97.0% AUC.
[23]	COVID-19 prediction in CXR imaging using transfer learning.	Deep Transfer Learning (CNN)	5,000 CXRs from publicly available datasets	Specificity rate of ~90% with a sensitivity range of 97.5%
[54]	A weakly-supervised DL for identifying and classifying COVID-19 from CT scans and reduce the requirements of labeling the CT images.	Weakly-supervised deep learning system using CNN	150 3D chest CT scans of COVID-19, CAP, and NP patients respectively	96.2% accuracy, 94.5% sensitivity, 95.3% specificity, 97.0% AUC.
[16]	A fully automated chest CT framing for detecting COVID-19	Deep Learning	3D chest CT exams acquired from 6 medical centers, consisting of 1296 images of COVID-19 patients	96% AUC, 90% sensitivity, 96% specificity.
[59]	A deep learning-based transfer model to diagnose COVID-19 cases by utilizing CT-scan and X-ray images of the human's chest. The aim is the binary classification of the chest images in a fast and accurate way.	Deep learning-based transfer model	Three datasets SARS-COV2 CT-scan, Chest X-Ray images, and COVID-CXRs	95.61% accuracy.
[60]	A COVID-19 assessment DT classifier from CXR images.	Deep learning-based DT classifier	CXR	95.0% accuracy.
[28]	Utilized pre-trained model DenseNet121 to classify the segmented 3D lung regions.	AH-Net DenseNet121	CT images of 1029 COVID-19 1695 non-COVID-19 patients.	0.90% accuracy, 93% specificity, and 94% AUC.
[62]	Predict the severity level of Coronavirus by using CT scan images of infected patients.	Deep learning	The dataset contains 303 CT-images as a training set and 105 images as testing set.	97.4% training and 81.9% testing accuracy.
[43]	Classify the countries based on the risk rate.	AI-guided method with Bayesian optimizer	COVID-19 open-source dataset and weather dataset, the number of cases confirmed, number of cases recovered, and the total number of deaths are included.	77.4% accuracy.
[44]	Create a large dataset and classify COVID-19	CNN model and pre-trained AlexNet	170 X-ray images and 361 CT images of COVID-19	AlexNet =98%, CNN =94.1%.
[62]	Diagnose corona virus with PCA.	LR, CNN	X-ray images.	95.2–97.6% accuracy without PCA and 97.6–100% with PCA.
[63]	COVID-19 detection	LSTM and CNN	CT and X-ray images	100% for accuracy and F1 score.
[64]	COVID-19 detection	Deep learning	CT images of 259 patients.	89.5% accuracy, 88% specificity, 87% sensitivity.
[65]	COVID-19 diagnosis	Deep learning-based CT diagnosis	CT scans of 88 patients of COVID-19, 101 of bacterial pneumonia, 86 healthy persons.	AUC of 0.99 and recall of 0.93.
[66]	Classify COVID-19	ResNet-50 deep learning	CT scan	96% AUC
[67]	Identify corona virus rapidly	ResNet-100	CT scan	99.15% accuracy.
[37]	Feature optimization using CNN	CNN model (COVXNet)	X-rays	98.1% accuracy.
[38]	Investigate the performance of ML to discover the COVID-19.	KNN, DT, NB, SVM, LR	Digital data of 1,048,576 patients.	93% accuracy for NB and DT, 93.60% for SVM, 93.50% for KNN, 92.80% for LR.
[39]	Classify COVID-19 using CT-scan and X-ray imaging techniques.	ResNet50, InceptionResNetV2, Xception, VGGNet16, SVM	CXR images and CT scans.	Accuracy of 84% and 75% for X-Ray and CT-scans, respectively.

REFERENCES

- [1] World Health Organization, "Q&As on COVID-19 and related health topics." <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/question-and-answers-hub> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [2] S. Parasa, N. Reddy, D. O. Faigel, A. Repici, F. Emura, and P. Sharma, "Global Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Endoscopy: An International Survey of 252 Centers From 55 Countries," *Gastroenterology*, vol. 159, no. 4, pp. 1579-1581.e5, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2020.06.009>.
- [3] "Coronavirus (COVID-19) Testing," *Our World in Data*, Mar. 05, 2020. <https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus-testing> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [4] C. Iwendi *et al.*, "COVID-19 Patient Health Prediction Using Boosted Random Forest Algorithm," *Frontiers in Public Health*, vol. 8, 2020, Art. no. 357, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00357>.
- [5] A. A. Soofi and A. Awan, "Classification Techniques in Machine Learning: Applications and Issues," *Journal of Basic & Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, pp. 459-465, 2017.
- [6] S. Lalmuanawma, J. Hussain, and L. Chhakchhuak, "Applications of machine learning and artificial intelligence for Covid-19 (SARS-CoV-2) pandemic: A review," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, vol. 139, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 110059, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2020.110059>.
- [7] M. AlJame, I. Ahmad, A. Intiaz, and A. Mohammed, "Ensemble learning model for diagnosing COVID-19 from routine blood tests," *Informatics in Medicine Unlocked*, vol. 21, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 100449, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2020.100449>.
- [8] Y. Mohamadou, A. Halidou, and P. T. Kapen, "A review of mathematical modeling, artificial intelligence and datasets used in the study, prediction and management of COVID-19," *Applied Intelligence*, vol. 50, no. 11, pp. 3913-3925, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10489-020-01770-9>.

- [9] C. Cortes and V. Vapnik, "Support-vector networks," *Machine Learning*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 273–297, Sep. 1995, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00994018>.
- [10] K. Aida-zade, A. Xocayev, and S. Rustamov, "Speech recognition using Support Vector Machines," in *10th International Conference on Application of Information and Communication Technologies*, Baku, Azerbaijan, Oct. 2016, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAICT.2016.7991664>.
- [11] Y. Tian, E. Li, L. Yang, and Z. Liang, "An image processing method for green apple lesion detection in natural environment based on GA-BPNN and SVM," in *International Conference on Mechatronics and Automation*, Changchun, China, Aug. 2018, pp. 1210–1215, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMA.2018.8484624>.
- [12] S. Dreiseitl and L. Ohno-Machado, "Logistic regression and artificial neural network classification models: a methodology review," *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 352–359, Oct. 2002, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1532-0464\(03\)00034-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1532-0464(03)00034-0).
- [13] G. Biau and E. Scornet, "A random forest guided tour," *TEST*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 197–227, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11749-016-0481-7>.
- [14] M. Zakariah, "Classification of large datasets using Random Forest Algorithm in various applications: Survey," *International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 189–198, 2014.
- [15] C. Sohrabi *et al.*, "World Health Organization declares global emergency: A review of the 2019 novel coronavirus (COVID-19)," *International Journal of Surgery*, vol. 76, pp. 71–76, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijisu.2020.02.034>.
- [16] I. D. Apostolopoulos and T. A. Mpesiana, "Covid-19: automatic detection from X-ray images utilizing transfer learning with convolutional neural networks," *Physical and Engineering Sciences in Medicine*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 635–640, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13246-020-00865-4>.
- [17] S. Kadry, V. Rajinikanth, S. Rho, N. S. M. Raja, V. S. Rao, and K. P. Thanaraj, "Development of a Machine-Learning System to Classify Lung CT Scan Images into Normal/COVID-19 Class," *arXiv:2004.13122 [cs, eess, stat]*, Apr. 2020, Accessed: Oct. 28, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2004.13122>.
- [18] T. Ozturk, M. Talo, E. A. Yildirim, U. B. Baloglu, O. Yildirim, and U. Rajendra Acharya, "Automated detection of COVID-19 cases using deep neural networks with X-ray images," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 121, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 103792, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2020.103792>.
- [19] A. Carfi, R. Bernabei, and F. Landi, "Persistent Symptoms in Patients After Acute COVID-19," *JAMA*, vol. 324, no. 6, pp. 603–605, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.12603>.
- [20] M. K. Nath, A. Kanhe, and M. Mishra, "A Novel Deep Learning Approach for Classification of COVID-19 Images," in *5th International Conference on Computing Communication and Automation*, Greater Noida, India, Oct. 2020, pp. 752–757, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCA49541.2020.9250907>.
- [21] A. Abbas, M. M. Abdelsamea, and M. M. Gaber, "Classification of COVID-19 in chest X-ray images using DeTraC deep convolutional neural network," *Applied Intelligence*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 854–864, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10489-020-01829-7>.
- [22] E. E.-D. Hemdan, M. A. Shouman, and M. E. Karar, "COVIDX-Net: A Framework of Deep Learning Classifiers to Diagnose COVID-19 in X-Ray Images," *arXiv:2003.11055 [cs, eess]*, Mar. 2020, Accessed: Oct. 28, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.11055>.
- [23] A. Narin, C. Kaya, and Z. Pamuk, "Automatic detection of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) using X-ray images and deep convolutional neural networks," *Pattern Analysis and Applications*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 1207–1220, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10044-021-00984-y>.
- [24] M. Rahimzadeh and A. Attar, "A modified deep convolutional neural network for detecting COVID-19 and pneumonia from chest X-ray images," *Informatics in Medicine Unlocked*, vol. 19, 2020, Art. no. 100360, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2020.100360>.
- [25] W. H. Self, D. M. Courtney, C. D. McNaughton, R. G. Wunderink, and J. A. Kline, "High Discordance of Chest X-ray and CT for Detection of Pulmonary Opacities in ED Patients: Implications for Diagnosing Pneumonia," *The American journal of emergency medicine*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 401–405, Feb. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajem.2012.08.041>.
- [26] G. D. Rubin *et al.*, "The Role of Chest Imaging in Patient Management during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Multinational Consensus Statement from the Fleischner Society," *Radiology*, vol. 296, no. 1, pp. 172–180, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2020201365>.
- [27] M. Barstugan, U. Ozkaya, and S. Ozturk, "Coronavirus (COVID-19) Classification using CT Images by Machine Learning Methods," *arXiv:2003.09424 [cs, eess, stat]*, Mar. 2020, Accessed: Oct. 28, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.09424>.
- [28] M. Alazab, A. Awajan, A. Mesleh, A. Abraham, V. Jatana, and S. Alhyari, "COVID-19 Prediction and Detection Using Deep Learning," *International Journal of Computer Information Systems and Industrial Management Applications*, vol. 12, pp. 168–181, 2020.
- [29] L. Wang, Z. Q. Lin, and A. Wong, "COVID-Net: a tailored deep convolutional neural network design for detection of COVID-19 cases from chest X-ray images," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 10, no. 1, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 19549, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-76550-z>.
- [30] H. Kang *et al.*, "Diagnosis of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) With Structured Latent Multi-View Representation Learning," *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol. 39, no. 8, pp. 2606–2614, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2020.2992546>.
- [31] E.-S. M. El-Kenawy, A. Ibrahim, S. Mirjalili, M. M. Eid, and S. E. Hussein, "Novel Feature Selection and Voting Classifier Algorithms for COVID-19 Classification in CT Images," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 179317–179335, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3028012>.
- [32] X. Wang, Y. Peng, L. Lu, Z. Lu, M. Bagheri, and R. M. Summers, "ChestX-Ray8: Hospital-Scale Chest X-Ray Database and Benchmarks on Weakly-Supervised Classification and Localization of Common Thorax Diseases," in *Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Honolulu, HI, USA, Jul. 2017, pp. 3462–3471, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2017.369>.
- [33] H. S. Maghddid, A. T. Asaad, K. Z. Ghafoor, A. S. Sadiq, and M. K. Khan, "Diagnosing COVID-19 Pneumonia from X-Ray and CT Images using Deep Learning and Transfer Learning Algorithms," Mar. 2020, Accessed: Oct. 28, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://128.84.4.34/abs/2004.00038>.
- [34] J. Rasheed, A. A. Hameed, C. Djeddi, A. Jamil, and F. Al-Turjman, "A machine learning-based framework for diagnosis of COVID-19 from chest X-ray images," *Interdisciplinary Sciences: Computational Life Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 103–117, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12539-020-00403-6>.
- [35] J. Wu *et al.*, "Rapid and accurate identification of COVID-19 infection through machine learning based on clinical available blood test results," Apr. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.02.20051136>.
- [36] H. Namazi and V. V. Kulish, "Complexity-based classification of the coronavirus disease (covid-19)," *Fractals*, vol. 28, no. 05, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 2050114, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218348X20501145>.
- [37] P. K. Sethy, S. K. Behera, P. K. Ratha, and P. Biswas, "Detection of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) based on Deep Features and Support Vector Machine," *International Journal of Mathematical Engineering and Management Sciences*, pp. 643–651, 2020.
- [38] D. Singh, V. Kumar, Vaishali, and M. Kaur, "Classification of COVID-19 patients from chest CT images using multi-objective differential evolution-based convolutional neural networks," *European Journal of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 1379–1389, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10096-020-03901-z>.
- [39] U.S. Food and Drug Administration, "FDA Approves First COVID-19 Vaccine," *FDA*, Aug. 23, 2021. <https://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/fda-approves-first-covid-19-vaccine> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [40] H. Panwar, P. K. Gupta, M. K. Siddiqui, R. Morales-Menendez, P. Bhardwaj, and V. Singh, "A deep learning and grad-CAM based color visualization approach for fast detection of COVID-19 cases using chest X-ray and CT-Scan images," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, vol. 140, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 110190, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2020.110190>.

- [41] S. Asif, Y. Wenhui, H. Jin, and S. Jinhai, "Classification of COVID-19 from Chest X-ray images using Deep Convolutional Neural Network," in *6th International Conference on Computer and Communications*, Chengdu, China, Dec. 2020, pp. 426–433, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCC51575.2020.9344870>.
- [42] S. Minaee, R. Kafieh, M. Sonka, S. Yazdani, and G. Jamalipour Soufi, "Deep-COVID: Predicting COVID-19 from chest X-ray images using deep transfer learning," *Medical Image Analysis*, vol. 65, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 101794, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2020.101794>.
- [43] S. Hu *et al.*, "Weakly Supervised Deep Learning for COVID-19 Infection Detection and Classification From CT Images," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 118869–118883, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3005510>.
- [44] L. Li *et al.*, "Artificial Intelligence Distinguishes COVID-19 from Community Acquired Pneumonia on Chest CT," *Radiology*, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 200905, <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2020200905>.
- [45] O. Gozes *et al.*, "Rapid AI Development Cycle for the Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic: Initial Results for Automated Detection & Patient Monitoring using Deep Learning CT Image Analysis," *arXiv:2003.05037 [cs, eess]*, Mar. 2020, Accessed: Oct. 28, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.05037>.
- [46] M. Kaur, H. K. Gianey, D. Singh, and M. Sabharwal, "Multi-objective differential evolution based random forest for e-health applications," *Modern Physics Letters B*, vol. 33, no. 05, Feb. 2019, Art. no. 1950022, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0217984919500222>.
- [47] A. Jaiswal, N. Gianchandani, D. Singh, V. Kumar, and M. Kaur, "Classification of the COVID-19 infected patients using DenseNet201 based deep transfer learning," *Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics*, vol. 39, no. 15, pp. 5682–5689, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07391102.2020.1788642>.
- [48] S. H. Yoo *et al.*, "Deep Learning-Based Decision-Tree Classifier for COVID-19 Diagnosis From Chest X-ray Imaging," *Frontiers in Medicine*, vol. 7, 2020, Art. no. 427, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.00427>.
- [49] S. A. Harmon *et al.*, "Artificial intelligence for the detection of COVID-19 pneumonia on chest CT using multinational datasets," *Nature Communications*, vol. 11, no. 1, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 4080, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-17971-2>.
- [50] L. Xiao *et al.*, "Development and Validation of a Deep Learning-Based Model Using Computed Tomography Imaging for Predicting Disease Severity of Coronavirus Disease 2019," *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, vol. 8, 2020, Art. no. 898, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2020.00898>.
- [51] R. Pal, A. A. Sekh, S. Kar, and D. K. Prasad, "Neural Network Based Country Wise Risk Prediction of COVID-19," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 18, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 6448, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10186448>.
- [52] A. Sedik, M. Hammad, F. E. Abd El-Samie, B. B. Gupta, and A. A. Abd El-Latif, "Efficient deep learning approach for augmented detection of Coronavirus disease," *Neural computing & applications*, pp. 1–18, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-020-05410-8>.
- [53] S. Wang *et al.*, "A deep learning algorithm using CT images to screen for Corona virus disease (COVID-19)," *European Radiology*, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 6096–6104, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-021-07715-1>.
- [54] Y. Song *et al.*, "Deep learning Enables Accurate Diagnosis of Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) with CT images," *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics*, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCBB.2021.3065361>.
- [55] S. Serte and H. Demirel, "Deep learning for diagnosis of COVID-19 using 3D CT scans," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 132, p. 104306, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbiomed.2021.104306>.
- [56] M. Kavitha, T. Jayasankar, P. M. Venkatesh, G. Mani, C. Bharatiraja, and B. Twala, "COVID-19 Disease Diagnosis using Smart Deep Learning Techniques," *Journal of Applied Science and Engineering*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 271–277, 2021, [https://doi.org/10.6180/jase.202106_24\(3\).0001](https://doi.org/10.6180/jase.202106_24(3).0001).
- [57] T. Mahmud, M. A. Rahman, and S. A. Fattah, "CovXNet: A multi-dilation convolutional neural network for automatic COVID-19 and other pneumonia detection from chest X-ray images with transferable multi-receptive feature optimization," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 122, Jul. 2020, Art. no. 103869, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbiomed.2020.103869>.
- [58] M. Malik *et al.*, "Determination of COVID-19 Patients Using Machine Learning Algorithms," *Intelligent Automation and Soft Computing*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 207–222, 2022.
- [59] X. Deng, H. Shao, L. Shi, X. Wang, and T. Xie, "A Classification–Detection Approach of COVID-19 Based on Chest X-ray and CT by Using Keras Pre-Trained Deep Learning Models," *Computer Modeling in Engineering & Sciences*, vol. 125, no. 2, pp. 579–596, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.32604/cmescs.2020.011920>.
- [60] A. Hamed, A. Sobhy, and H. Nassar, "Accurate Classification of COVID-19 Based on Incomplete Heterogeneous Data using a KNN Variant Algorithm," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 46, no. 9, pp. 8261–8272, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-020-05212-z>.
- [61] J. P. Cohen, P. Morrison, L. Dao, K. Roth, T. Q. Duong, and M. Ghassemi, "COVID-19 Image Data Collection: Prospective Predictions Are the Future," *arXiv:2006.11988 [cs, eess, q-bio]*, Dec. 2020, Accessed: Oct. 28, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2006.11988>.
- [62] J. P. Cohen, *ieee8023/covid-chestxray-dataset*. 2021. Accessed: Oct. 28, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ieee8023/covid-chestxray-dataset>.
- [63] "Chest X-Ray Images (Pneumonia)." <https://kaggle.com/paultimothymooney/chest-xray-pneumonia> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [64] M. E. H. Chowdhury *et al.*, "Can AI Help in Screening Viral and COVID-19 Pneumonia?," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 132665–132676, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3010287>.
- [65] "COVID-19 Radiography Database." <https://kaggle.com/tawfifurrahman/covid19-radiography-database> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [66] "COVID-19 X rays." <https://kaggle.com/andrewmvd/convid19-x-rays> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [67] X. Yang, X. He, J. Zhao, Y. Zhang, S. Zhang, and P. Xie, "COVID-CT-Dataset: A CT Scan Dataset about COVID-19," *arXiv:2003.13865 [cs, eess, stat]*, Jun. 2020, Accessed: Oct. 28, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.13865>.
- [68] "COVID-19," *Medical segmentation*. <http://medicalsegmentation.com/covid19/> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [69] "COVID-19 British Society of Thoracic Imaging Database | The British Society of Thoracic Imaging." <https://www.bsti.org.uk/training-and-education/covid-19-bsti-imaging-database/> (accessed Oct. 28, 2021).
- [70] P. Chakraborty and C. Tharini, "Pneumonia and Eye Disease Detection using Convolutional Neural Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5769–5774, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3503>.
- [71] H. H. A. Owida, A. Al-Ghraibah, and M. Altayeb, "Classification of Chest X-Ray Images using Wavelet and MFCC Features and Support Vector Machine Classifier," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7296–7301, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4123>.
- [72] N. K. Al-Shammari, H. B. Almansour, and M. B. Syed, "Development of an Automatic Contactless Thermometer Alert System Based on GPS and Population Density," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 7006–7010, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4103>.

Evaluation of Rutting in Conventional and Rubberized Asphalt Mixes Using Numerical Modeling Under Repeated Loads

Dhuha Ameer Saad

Department of Civil Engineering

College of Engineering

University of Baghdad

Baghdad, Iraq

d.saad1901m@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Hayder A. Al-Baghdadi

Department of Civil Engineering

College of Engineering

University of Baghdad

Baghdad, Iraq

baghdadi.hayder@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract-This research aimed to predict the permanent deformation (rutting) in conventional and rubberized asphalt mixes under repeated load conditions using the Finite Element Method (FEM). A three-dimensional (3D) model was developed to simulate the Wheel Track Testing (WTT) loading. The study was conducted using the Abaqus/Standard finite element software. The pavement slab was simulated using a nonlinear creep (time-hardening) model at 40°C. The responses of the viscoplastic model under the influence of the trapezoidal amplitude of moving wheel loadings were determined for different speeds and numbers of cycles. The results indicated that a wheel speed increase from 0.5Km/h to 1.0Km/h decreased the rut depth by about 22% and 24% in conventional and rubberized asphalt mixes, respectively. Moreover, increasing the number of cycles from 7,500 (15,000 passes) to 15,000 (30,000 passes) under constant speed increased the rut depth by about 25% and 30% in conventional and rubberized asphalt mixes, respectively. Furthermore, the addition of Crumb Rubber (CR) to the asphalt reduced its rut depth by 55% compared to conventional asphalt.

Keywords-rutting; finite element method; rubberized asphalt; repeated load; creep

I. INTRODUCTION

Rutting distress is one of the most common types of failure in flexible pavements. It is generated by accumulated permanent deformations in the wheel path as a result of repeated axle loads [1]. The rutting depth is an important factor to assess a pavement's condition [2]. Pavements are complex systems that include several variables that affect their performance [3]. The behavior of non-linear asphalt mixtures is divided into two types: viscoelastic and viscoplastic, which are associated with recoverable and non-recoverable deformations, respectively [4, 5]. Temperature is one of the most critical factors affecting the resistance of asphalt pavement to rutting. Temperature variations allow the asphalt pavement to expand and contract, altering the asphalt mixture's characteristics and resulting in pavement deformation [6]. Moreover, the increasing number of loading cycles affects the asphalt paving, as the rutting develops gradually and usually appears in the wheel tracks as a longitudinal drop with small side upheavals

[7]. Lower vehicle speed results in a longer load period and lower frequency, having a greater effect on permanent deformation compared to higher speeds for the same number of passes [8]. Hot asphalt mixture at low temperatures and high loading speed are considered as a liquid plastic thermoplastic, while high temperatures and slow loading appear as a viscous liquid and elastic solid. This classic duality necessitates the improvement of the asphalt binder's performance to reduce cracking stresses at low temperatures and plastic deformations at high temperatures.

One method to achieve the specified pavement performance standards is to use a polymer-modified asphalt binder [9]. It is therefore imperative to enhance the properties of the conventional asphalt content, as well as the advancement of successful asphalt mix design technology [10, 11]. Overall, Crumb Rubber Modifier (CRM) additions appear to improve the maximal initial strength of conventional asphalt [12]. CRM is a powder produced by crushing and grinding vehicle waste tires [13]. To anticipate permanent deformation, a variety of analytical methods are available such as multilayer elastic theory, Finite Difference Method (FDM), and Finite Element Method (FEM) [14]. There are several advantages of using finite element analysis. These advantages include the modeling capabilities on the model geometry designs that are irregularly shaped or complex, various loading options, representation of an unlimited number of materials, unlimited boundary conditions, and finally a study of large deformations with nonlinear behavior of viscoplastic response [15]. FEM depends on inputs obtained from the experimental data of bituminous materials. This study used the parameters adopted in [16]. The main objective of the current research was to study the effect of repeated wheel loading under the influence of different speeds and the number of loading cycles. To investigate the impact of the assumptions on rutting predictions, a Wheel Tracking Test (WTT) was simulated in a 3D finite element model generated from rubberized and conventional asphalt mixtures. The Abaqus software was utilized, as it includes a creep power-law model that simulates the viscoplastic behavior of the asphalt layer.

Corresponding author: Dhuha Ameer Saad

II. METHOD

The WTT was simulated as an illustration of how rutting forecasts are affected by repeated wheel loading assumptions at different speeds and numbers of passes. A three-dimensional FEM model was constructed using flexible pavements made from conventional and rubberized asphalt mixtures. The asphalt layer was modeled as a viscoplastic substance using the creep power-law model (time-hardening) of the Abaqus software.

III. CREEP POWER-LAW

A constitutive model of viscoplastic deformation for flexible pavements developed in the Abaqus software [18] was adopted, which, despite its simplicity, is used to solve complex problems [17]. The model is given by:

$$\epsilon_v = A\sigma^n t^m \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_v is the creep strain rate, σ is the equivalent stress, t is the time of loading, and A , n , and m are the model's parameters. The parameters were obtained from laboratory tests by using the dynamic creep test [16] listed in Table I. An important assumption in this analysis is the use of the creep power-law model to depict the nonlinear behavior of the asphalt concrete mixture. The hardening time assumption available in the Abaqus library was used. Creep is the time-dependent behavior of a solid material to deform under constant stress less than the yield stress of the material. All non-recoverable components must be included during asphalt mix permanent deformation analysis, particularly viscous deformation. There are three stages to typical nonlinear creep behavior: primary, secondary, and tertiary, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Te three stages of plastic strain in repeated load creep testing.

TABLE I. LAW PARAMETERS OF THE CREEP MODEL

Mix type	Temperature (°C)	A(e-5)	n	m
Rubberized asphalt	40	4.2	1.5	-0.609
Conventional asphalt	40	7.3	1.5	-0.570

IV. FEM SIMULATION

This section describes the 3D finite element simulation of asphalt slab in a WTT, the employed wheel loading

assumptions, and a synopsis of an analysis technique to determine the material properties associated with the presented constitutive model. FEM has been proven to be suitable for analyzing the complex nonlinear behavior of composite pavement materials and has been effectively applied to flexible pavement performance analysis [19]. Numerical simulation in pavement engineering is an efficient and effective way to verify the pavement's response and performance under moving vehicle loads. It is an easy, inexpensive, and time-reducing method, in addition to the versatility and flexibility required for WTT simulation [18]. Abaqus was adopted to simulate the paving structure, as it is a powerful FEM software that can easily solve complicated problems by using nonlinear analysis for the realization of the basic concept. The software includes a library with many finite elements and different behavior models of materials. Abaqus can automatically select reasonable increments and logical defaults.

A. Geometry, Boundary Conditions, and Meshing

Defining the physical model is the first step of FEM. Figure 1 presents the geometry of the studied WTT. Its dimensions were 300×300×50mm in length, width, and depth respectively as shown in Figure 2. These dimensions were chosen to correspond with the WTT specimens [16].

Fig. 2. Three-dimensional slab modeling.

The model's boundary conditions were modeled by specimen circumstances in WTT. Boundary conditions have a major influence on expected responses since they have a strong influence on the reaction of the form. The bottom surface of the bituminous wheel tracking test slab was assumed to be fixed and restrained in all directions to have a completely fixed end. The nodes at the bottom were unable to move horizontally or vertically, simulating the experimental conditions, while the upper surface of the sample was free to move. The side edges were constrained in the horizontal but not in the vertical direction, as shown in Figure 3.

The body was divided into 960 small, discrete Finite Elements (FEs), which were all resolved at the same time for all simulations. These FEs were connected to 1581 common shared nodes. The mesh was formed by combining nodes and elements, as shown in Figure 4. The size of the element mesh has a significant impact on numerical accuracy, while the fine mesh size requires a longer time for model analysis.

Fig. 3. Boundary conditions, temperature distribution, and loading along the wheel path.

Fig. 4. Mesh of 3D finite element model.

B. Employed Material Parameters

The viscoplastic permanent deformation properties of the flexible pavement materials are usually determined using the Dynamic Creep Test. Abaqus is efficient in analyzing complex time rate-dependent and viscoplastic problems. The time-hardening version of the power-law creep model is most suitable when the stress state remains essentially constant. Temperature is an important factor affecting the corrosion resistance of all mixtures. All materials' model parameters used in the simulation, the elastic modulus, and Poisson's ratio were collected from laboratory results [16]. An elastic modulus of 3,800MPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.35 were also obtained from laboratory results.

C. Characterization of Moving Wheel Load Amplitude

A 150kPa uniform vertical tire pressure was adopted in the simulation of a moving load. The moving load was applied along the test path with a length of 230±10mm. Under the influence of a 40°C temperature applied to the entire model, the contact pressure will be equal to the tire pressure when the stiffness effect of the tire wall is neglected, according to the National Cooperative Highway Research Program (NCHRP), where the load was simplified and assumed as a rectangular area and distributed evenly on the loading footprint of 50mm and 30mm in length and width respectively [20]. To simulate the gradual loading of the test wheel back and forth, the loading path was divided into 8 regions, depending on the length of the wheel path and the tire footprint, and then each region was having one-third of the wheel loads. This load was applied repeatedly overlapping to the wheel path. The repeated load was applied with trapezoidal amplitude and the loading time for one pass at 0.5Km/h was 1.728s, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Repeated loading amplitude of one pass.

V. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Sensitivity analysis was carried out to study how the wheel speed and the number of loading cycles affect the reaction of flexible pavements, depending on the mixture type.

A. Wheel Speed

Hot Mix Asphalt (HMA) is a time-dependent material. As a result, wheel speed, which is proportional to loading duration, is likely to affect the reactivity of HMA mixes. When it increases, loading time and rut depth decreases, and vice versa. This explains the rutting in the pavement in crossroads and other places where vehicles move slowly. Rut depths predicted for 10,000 loading cycles (20,000 passes) at 0.5 and 1.0Km/h wheel speeds are shown in Figures 6 and 7 for rubberized and conventional asphalt pavements, respectively. The decrease in crack depth when increasing speed from 0.5Km/h to 1.0Km/h is about 22% and 24% in the conventional and rubberized mixture, respectively, as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 6. Predicting rutting under repeated loading for rubberized asphalt pavement at 20,000 passes at different speeds, (a) 0.5Km/h, (b) 1.0Km/h.

Fig. 7. Predicting rutting under repeated loading for conventional asphalt pavement at 20,000 passes at different speeds, (a) 0.5Km/h, (b) 1.0Km/h.

Fig. 8. Comparison of rutting under repeated load for conventional and rubberized asphalt pavements at 20,000 passes with different speeds.

B. Number of Cycles

The major cause of rutting in wheel paths can be correlated to wheel load repetitions. The accumulation of permanent deformation, which rises with the number of loading cycles, is the basic mechanism of rutting. Larger loading stress causes more rutting at steady temperatures and speeds. Figure 9 indicates that increasing the number of passes increases the rutting values of asphalt samples. On the other hand, rubber asphalt reduces rutting values compared to ordinary samples.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a study on the permanent deformation of conventional and rubberized asphalt mixes based on repeated loads. A three-dimensional viscoplastic model was developed to simulate the WTT. The creep behavior of such mixtures was investigated based on creep power-law parameters. The following conclusions were obtained:

Fig. 9. Rutting with different numbers of passes in the model of WTT, (a) rubberized asphalt, (b) conventional asphalt.

- Rubber crumbs improve the rutting performance of asphalt specimens, as they reduce the rut depth of the rubberized asphalt by 55%.
- The results showed that the proposed numerical models portrait satisfactorily the rut behavior at various operating speeds and cycle numbers.
- Speed has a significant effect on rutting depth. When increasing the wheel speed from 0.5 to 1.0Km/h (100%), the rut depth decreases about 22% in the rubberized and 24% in the conventional asphalt mixtures.
- The number of cycles has a significant effect on the rutting depth. When the number of cycles increases from 7500 to 15000, the rut depth increases by about 25% in rubberized and 30% in conventional asphalt mixtures.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Sincere thanks to the staff at the University of Baghdad, Department of Civil Engineering, College of Engineering, for their assistance in completing this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Saleh and M. Ghorban Ebrahimi, "Finite Element Modeling of Permanent Deformation in the Loaded Wheel Tracker Test," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 2641, no. 1, pp. 94–102, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.3141/2641-12>.
- [2] F. Alzaidy and A. H. K. Albayati, "A Comparison between Static and Repeated Load Test to Predict Asphalt Concrete Rut Depth," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7363–7369, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4236>.
- [3] J. Wu, J. Liang, and S. Adhikari, "Dynamic response of concrete pavement structure with asphalt isolating layer under moving loads," *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering (English Edition)*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 439–447, Dec. 2014, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-7564\(15\)30294-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-7564(15)30294-4).

- [4] Harold L. Von Quintus, "Performance Prediction Models In the Superpace Mix Design System," Strategic Highway Research Program, Washington, D.C., USA, SHRP-A-699, Aug. 1994. Accessed: Oct. 30, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://trid.trb.org/view/406369>.
- [5] A. C. Collop, A. (Tom) Scarpas, C. Kasbergen, and A. de Bondt, "Development and Finite Element Implementation of Stress-Dependent Elastoviscoplastic Constitutive Model with Damage for Asphalt," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 1832, no. 1, pp. 96–104, Jan. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.3141/1832-12>.
- [6] J. Ji, L. Chen, Z. Suo, Y. Xu, and Y.-L. Han, "Effect of high temperature and heavy load on deformation resistance of DCLR modified asphalt mixture," *Jiaotong Yunshu Gongcheng Xuebao/Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering*, vol. 19, pp. 1–8, Feb. 2019.
- [7] M. M. Pradhan, "Permanent deformation characteristics of asphalt-aggregate mixtures using varied materials and molding procedures with Marshall method," Ph.D. dissertation, Montana State University, Bozeman, MT, USA, 1995.
- [8] E. G. Epifanio and L. Gan, "Validation of a Pavement Performance Model for Flexible Pavements Based on," M.S. thesis, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden, 2009.
- [9] I. A. Mahmoud, "Performance Modification of Saudi Asphalt Binders Using SABIC Polymers," M.S. thesis, King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals, Dhahran, Saudi Arabia, 2002.
- [10] H. Ziari, A. Goli, and A. Amini, "Effect of Crumb Rubber Modifier on the Performance Properties of Rubberized Binders," *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, vol. 28, no. 12, Dec. 2016, Art. no. 04016156, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0001661](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0001661).
- [11] A. Amini, H. Ziari, and A. Goli, "Investigating the performance of rubberised binders used in Iran based on multiple stress creep recovery and performance grading systems," *Road Materials and Pavement Design*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 803–818, May 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680629.2016.1274676>.
- [12] K. Jadidi, M. Khalili, M. Karakouzian, and S. Amirhanian, "Toughness, Tenacity and Maximum Initial Strength of Rubber Modified Asphalt Binders," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3765–3769, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2526>.
- [13] M. Bekhiiti, H. Trouzine, and A. Asroun, "Properties of Waste Tire Rubber Powder," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 669–672, Aug. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.439>.
- [14] M. Arabani, R. Jamshidi, and M. Sadeghnejad, "Using of 2D finite element modeling to predict the glasphalt mixture rutting behavior," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 68, pp. 183–191, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2014.06.057>.
- [15] J. Hua, "Finite element modeling and analysis of accelerated pavement testing devices and rutting phenomenon," Ph.D. dissertation, Purdue University, West Lafayette, IN, U.S., 2000.
- [16] B. Bakhshi and M. Arabani, "Numerical Evaluation of Rutting in Rubberized Asphalt Mixture Using Finite Element Modeling Based on Experimental Viscoelastic Properties," *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 6, Jun. 2018, Art. no. 04018088, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0002116](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0002116).
- [17] T. D. White, J. E. Haddock, A. J. T. Hand, and H. Fang, "Contributions of Pavement Structural Layers to Rutting of Hot Mix Asphalt Pavements," Transportation Research Board - National Research Council, Washington, D.C., USA, 468, 2002. Accessed: Oct. 31, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://trid.trb.org/view/710690>.
- [18] "Abaqus 6.11 - Scripting User's Manual," Dassault Systèmes Simulia, 2011.
- [19] F. Bai, X. Yang, and G. Zeng, "A stochastic viscoelastic-viscoplastic constitutive model and its application to crumb rubber modified asphalt mixtures," *Materials & Design*, vol. 89, pp. 802–809, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2015.10.040>.
- [20] Y. H. Huang, *Pavement analysis and design*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J., U.S.: Prentice-Hall, 1993.

Numerical Investigation of Oil Gas Separation with the Use of VOF CFD

Sorin Tomescu

Screw Compressors Department
NRDI for Gas Turbines COMOTI
Bucharest, Romania
sorin.tomescu@comoti.ro

Ioana Octavia Bucur

Computational Fluid Dynamics Department
NRDI for Gas Turbines COMOTI
Bucharest, Romania
ioana.bucur@comoti.ro

Abstract-In this research paper, a numerical study regarding gas-oil separation is presented. Employing the geometry of a classic separator used by the NRDI for Gas Turbines COMOTI and a Computer-Aided Design (CAD) software, the computational domain was defined. To perform the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) investigation, the mesh was created with the ANSYS Meshing tool, and the ANSYS CFX was employed as a solver. The computational domain was split into 5 subdomains, 3 were fluid and 2 were defined as porous media. The volume porosity, loss model, and permeability were set up. In terms of turbulence flow, the standard $k-\epsilon$ model was adopted. The results of the numerical calculations in terms of oil volume fraction and streamline profiles were used to analyze the separator configuration. The results show that the numerical investigation with the VOF (Volume of Fluid Method) - CFD model is capable of analyzing the performance of a two-phase separator equipped with two demisters-porous media.

Keywords-two-phase separator; computational fluid dynamics; volume of fluid; porous media; demister

I. INTRODUCTION

Technological evolution is currently mainly based on fossil fuels and their impact will continue to persist, although the trend is to redirect to the use of renewable energy with low environment impact and reduced pollution emissions [1]. In the petroleum extraction industry, air at high pressure is often employed in the oil extraction and recovery processes, which are complex procedures that require advanced installations [2]. Systems that can provide the needed amount of pressurized air for the extraction process, can be screw compressors with oil injection, which can raise the air pressure up to 40 bars [3]. In general, an oil-injected screw compressor developed for the petroleum and petrochemical industries is provided with a complex lubrication oil system that incorporates separator vessels. The separator vessels mainly consist of an inlet, a demister pad, and an outlet and they should ensure an efficient oil-gas separation. The process along with various configurations for the separator, are discussed broadly in [4]. Figure 1 illustrates a complex screw compressor with oil injection equipment, developed by the NRDI for Gas Turbines COMOTI. The use of such a system implies oil-air separation, which can be done using a separator vessel [5] that is provided with filters capable to retain the oil particle and separate them

from the pressurized air [6]. A schematic presentation of a classic two-phase separator can be observed in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Screw compressor installation.

Fig. 2. Two-phase separator principle.

The efficiency evaluation of a two-phase separator can be done by employing the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method. This method is broadly applied in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) for various flow applications such as the dam-break problem or the surge propagation in a dry channel, as well as the one identified above, i.e. the efficiency evaluation of a two-phase separator. The method is best suited for the mentioned applications as it manages to track vapor-liquid interference while giving various alternatives for the reconstruction of the interface with precision whilst preserving the fractional volume

of the fluid [7]. CFD tools have been proven to be reliable flow investigation instruments and have an important role in the design and optimization processes of complex systems, having large applications in the turbomachinery industry [8].

The use of CFD methods for the investigation of oil particles behavior in a separator vessel is studied in [9, 10]. In [9], the conducted research confirms that CFD tools and methods are accurate by comparing the numerical results with the experimental data. On the other hand, the authors in [10] largely present various CFD studies of separators using the VOF method, concluding that the numerical approach has numerous benefits, being cost effective and flexible with regard to design alterations. Furthermore, using the numerical results, the optimization of oil-air separation process leads to enhanced separator vessel designs capable to capture up to 10 micrometer oil particles [11]. In [12], the authors use the Rosin Rammmler distribution [13] to conduct a numerical investigation employing the ANSYS Fluent, for the oil droplet distribution at the inlet of a separator vessel using a multiphase model. In [14], the authors apply CFD tools for the investigation of the flow through a separator vessel with different inlet designs, concluding that CFD methods represent a valuable tool for the performance evaluation and optimization processes of separator vessels. Besides numerical alternatives, the flow in such systems can also be investigated using advanced measurement techniques as the Capacitance Wire Mesh Sensor (WMS) and the Electrical Capacitance Tomography (ECT) [15].

This paper aims to numerically investigate the oil/air separation process in a separator vessel by using ANSYS CFX, employing the VOF method.

II. METHODOLOGY

This section addresses the computational domain creation, mesh generation, and case set up for the numerical investigation of the oil/air separation process.

A. Computational Domain Creation

The computational domain was generated using the 3D CAD model of the separator vessel by utilizing the Boolean function. Figure 3 depicts the computational domain that is divided into 5 subdomains: 3 defined as fluid and 2 with porous media properties.

B. Mesh Generation and Boundary Conditions

The grid was generated based on a hybrid scheme by combining tetrahedral and hexahedral elements. Due to the complex geometry of the inlet and outlet domains, the mesh for these zones was automatically generated with ANSYS Meshing. The maximum element size was set at 50mm. For the demister domains, with porous media characteristics, the blocking method was employed in ICEM in order to generate the grid. Mesh statistics are detailed in the Figure 4 and the resulting mesh is illustrated in Figure 5. The quality of the grid is visualized in Figure 6, for both types of elements - tetrahedral and hexahedral. It can be observed that only a negligible fraction of cells had poor quality.

Fig. 3. Computational domain. (a) 3D CAD model for the separator vessel, (b) computational domain prepped for CFD, (c) computational domain cross plane: 1, 3, 5 fluid subdomains; 2, 4 porous media properties subdomains.

Selected Regions:	
Assembly 2	
Assembly 3	
Assembly 4	
Assembly 5	
Number of Nodes:	1709254
Number of Elements:	6227229
Tetrahedra:	5599333
Pyramids:	70894
Wedges:	6340
Hexahedra:	550662
Extents:	
min x, max x:	-0.425 [m], 0.532044 [m]
min y, max y:	0.008 [m], 2.217 [m]
min z, max z:	-0.293 [m], 0.293 [m]
Max Edge Length Ratio:	83.4312
Volume:	0.575509 [m ³]

Fig. 4. Mesh statistics.

Fig. 5. Mesh for the numerical investigation. (a) Separator mesh, (b) cross plane view, (c) close-up on demister mesh.

The boundary conditions for the case set-up are described in Table I. A static pressure inlet boundary type and the volume fraction for each phase were defined for the fluid inlet. Regarding the porous media zones, the volume porosity was set at 0.7 with isotropic loss model and $3.8e-05m^2$. Figure 7 illustrates the boundary conditions that were previously described.

Fig. 6. Element quality.

TABLE I. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Location	BC Description
INLET	Boundary type: static pressure Relative pressure [bar]: 22.5 Static Temperature [°C]: 80
OUTLET	Boundary type: Bulk Mass Flow Rate Mass flow rate [kg/s]: 0.2
OIL OUTLET	Boundary type: Bulk Mass Flow Rate Mass flow rate [kg/s]: 2.25
WALLS	Boundary type: Wall No-slip condition

Fig. 7. (a) Computational domain, (b) boundary conditions.

The flow through the gas-oil separator equipped with two demisters was numerically modeled by solving the Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes (URANS) equations with the standard $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model. The transport equations for this turbulence model are presented below.

The transport equation for the turbulent kinetic energy (k) is:

$$\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} + \bar{u} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial k}{\partial y} + \bar{w} \frac{\partial k}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial z} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{\rho} \sum_{i,j} \tau_{ij} \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} - \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where ρ represents the density, μ the dynamic viscosity, μ_t the turbulent viscosity, and σ_k the turbulent Prandtl number for kinetic energy.

The transport equation for the turbulent kinetic energy dissipation (ϵ) is:

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial t} + \bar{u} \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial y} + \bar{w} \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\epsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\epsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\epsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial z} \right) \right] + C_{\epsilon 1} \frac{\epsilon}{\rho k} \sum_{i,j} \tau_{ij} \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} - C_{\epsilon 2} \frac{\epsilon^2}{k} \quad (2)$$

where σ_ϵ is the turbulent Prandtl number for dissipation and $C_{\epsilon 1}$ and $C_{\epsilon 2}$ are constants.

C. Results

The 3D CFD investigation was a transient one with a total flow time duration of 50s and a time step size that was set at 0.01s. For this study, a multiphase homogeneous model with no heat transfer from the working fluid to the vessel walls was adopted. The evolution of the volumetric mass fraction of oil was investigated, as well as the development of the streamlines.

Figure 8 describes the oil volume fraction for different moments of time in the simulation. The regions where only oil is present are depicted with red, whereas the dark blue zones represent the areas without oil. It can be observed that the separation process is efficient. After the initialization stage (Figure 8(a), Time = 0s), where the oil level is defined according to the real operational conditions, the mixture of oil and gas is noticeable in the feeding pipe, but oil particles detectable above the region 2 (demister) are within reasonable boundaries at any moment of time. After region 4 (second demister), only a ratio of 0.1% of the inlet oil eludes the separation process and slips through the gas outlet.

In [16], the authors investigated numerically the performances of a two-phase separator and improved its internal configuration, reaching an efficiency of 99.49%. The high efficiency of 99.9% of the system evaluated in this paper can save up to 33.2kg/h of oil in comparison with the enhanced geometry from the mentioned paper. Thus, the oil gas separation procedure is fulfilled properly and the methodology adopted for numerical evaluation is accurate.

Fig. 8. Oil volume fraction for different moments in the simulation: (a) 0s, (b) 10s, (c) 20s, and (d) 30s.

The 2D streamlines are illustrated in Figure 9. Cross planes multiple recirculation zones can be identified, but this phenomenon does not have a negative influence on the overall performance of the separator as the vortices are developed for low values of velocity. According to the presented streamlines, the velocity of the mixture slightly accelerates as it exits the feeding pipe and enters the separator. An increase in velocity is also noticeable at the liquid outlet, which is explained by the abrupt area reduction. Regarding the velocity of the gas, it is conspicuous from Figure 9 that its velocity increases slightly in time after the first demister (Figure 8(a), region 2) and more obvious after the second one (Figure 8(a), region 4) at the gas outlet duct (Figure 8(a), region 5).

Fig. 9. Streamlines for different moments in the simulation. (a) 0s, (b) 10s, (c) 20s, and (d) 30s.

The flow behavior of the investigated phenomenon and the obtained results are in agreement with the results from similar works in the field [17]. In [18], a similar CFD investigation is conducted but in terms of particle size it can only capture oil particles that are bigger than $100\mu\text{m}$, whereas the method adopted for the current CFD analysis is more precise, as it allows the visualization of oil particles bigger than $10\mu\text{m}$.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the efficiency of a gas-oil separator was numerically investigated with the use of the ANSYS CFX software. A two-phase homogeneous model was defined for a computational domain with 5 subdomains, 3 defined as fluid and 2 as porous media, capable to capture the oil particles that are bigger than $10\mu\text{m}$. For the study of the oil flow in the separator vessel, a volume fraction evolution is presented

throughout the simulation. After a flow time of 50s only 0.1% of the inlet oil is escaping through the gas outlet. The present research contribution for the addressed field consists in a well-defined methodology for the numerical investigation of oil gas separation, with the addition of successfully employing the VOF method for this application. The paper's contents broadly describe the stages leading to the numerical evaluation, concentrating on mesh generation and characteristics, as well as on case set-up and turbulence model selection.

Future work will consist of a grid influence study and the results will be compared with the experimental data from testing campaigns. The testing facility is depicted in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Testing facility.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the "NUCLEU" Program TURBO 2020+, grant number 2N/2019, supported by the Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Zou, Q. Zhao, G. Zhang, and B. Xiong, "Energy revolution: From a fossil energy era to a new energy era," *Natural Gas Industry B*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ngib.2016.02.001>.
- [2] T. Paulauskiene, "Petroleum Extraction Engineering," in *Recent Insights in Petroleum Science and Engineering*, M. Zoveidavianpoor, Ed. IntechOpen, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.70360>.
- [3] M. Nitulescu, C. Slujitoru, and V. Petrescu, "Case Study regarding the test of the new screw compressor with high delivery pressure - 45 bara - on the test bench (with air)," *INCAS BULLETIN*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 151–159, Dec. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.13111/2066-8201.2012.4.4.14>.
- [4] W. J. Milligan, D. I. Muir, and D. K. Harrison, "Oil level measurement in oil-injected screw compressor packages used in the petroleum, petrochemical, refrigeration and fuel gas markets," in *8th International Conference on Compressors and their Systems*, London, UK, Jan. 2013, pp. 77–85, <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781782421702.2.77>.
- [5] S. F. A. Bukhari, I. Ismail, and W. Q. Yang, "Visualising oil separator vessel and decision-making for control," in *4th World Congress in Industrial Process Tomography*, 2005, pp. 855–860.
- [6] S. Kaiser, A. Gugelfuß, A. Gyurkovich, M. Rupp, C. Mehring, and M. Piesche, "Characterization of oil injected screw compressors and air/oil separators at realistic operating pressures," *Aerosol Science and Technology*, vol. 53, no. 11, pp. 1311–1321, Nov. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02786826.2019.1659937>.
- [7] N. D. Katopodes, *Free-Surface Flow: Computational Methods*, Oxford, UK: Butterworth-Heinemann, 2019.
- [8] V. Dragan, I. Malael, and B. Gherman, "A Comparative Analysis Between Optimized and Baseline High Pressure Compressor Stages Using Tridimensional Computational Fluid Dynamics," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1103–1108, Aug. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.696>.
- [9] S. C. K. De Schepper, G. J. Heynderickx, and G. B. Marin, "CFD modeling of all gas–liquid and vapor–liquid flow regimes predicted by the Baker chart," *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 138, no. 1, pp. 349–357, May 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2007.06.007>.
- [10] A. P. Laleh, W. Y. Svrcek, and W. D. Monnery, "Design and CFD studies of multiphase separators—a review," *The Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 90, no. 6, pp. 1547–1561, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjce.20665>.
- [11] G. Cheng, L. Y. Yan, and H. Zhou, "The Oil Vessel Structure Optimization by the use of CFD in the Oil Injection Twin-Screw Compressor," presented at the International Compressor Engineering Conference, West Lafayette, IN, USA, 2004, Art. no. 1714.
- [12] N. Kharoua, L. Khezzar, and H. Saadawi, "CFD Simulation of Three-Phase Separator: Effects of Size Distribution," presented at the ASME 2013 Fluids Engineering Division Summer Meeting, Incline Village, NV, USA, Jul. 2013, Art. no. FEDSM2013-16322, <https://doi.org/10.1115/FEDSM2013-16322>.
- [13] P. A. Vesilind, "The Rosin-Rammler particle size distribution," *Resource Recovery and Conservation*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 275–277, Sep. 1980, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3967\(80\)90007-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3967(80)90007-4).
- [14] F. P. Lucas and R. Huebner, "Numerical Simulation of Single-Phase and Two-Phase Flows in Separator Vessels with Inclined Half-Pipe Inlet Device Applied in Reciprocating Compressors," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 2897–2900, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1993>.
- [15] L. A. Abdulkareem, "Identification of Oil-Gas Two Phase Flow in a Vertical Pipe using Advanced Measurement Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6165–6171, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3679>.
- [16] A. Efendioglu, J. Mendez, and H. Turkoglu, "The numerical analysis of the flow and separation efficiency of a two-phase horizontal oil-gas separator with an inlet diverter and perforated plates," presented at the AFM2014, La Coruña, Spain, Jul. 2014, pp. 133–142, <https://doi.org/10.2495/AFM140121>.
- [17] L. Z. Wang, X. Gao, J. M. Feng, and X. Y. Peng, "Research on the two-phase flow and separation mechanism in the oil-gas cyclone separator," in *9th International Conference on Compressors and their Systems*, London, UK, Sep. 2015, Art. no. 012075, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/90/1/012075>.
- [18] V. Vijayan, M. Vivekanandan, R. Venkatesh, K. Rajaguru, and A. Godwin Antony, "CFD modeling and analysis of a two-phase vapor separator," *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, vol. 145, no. 5, pp. 2719–2726, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-020-09825-2>.

Design and Analysis of a Dual Rotor Multiphase Brushless DC Motor for its Application in Electric Vehicles

Mujtaba Hussain

Department of Electrical Power Engineering
U.S.-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Energy
National University of Sciences and Technology
Islamabad, Pakistan
mujtaba.hussein@gmail.com

Abasin Ulasyar

Department of Electrical Power Engineering
U.S.-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Energy
National University of Sciences and Technology
Islamabad, Pakistan
abasin@uspcae.nust.edu.pk

Haris Sheh Zad

Department of Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering
Pak-Austria Fachhochschule Institute of Applied Sciences and
Technology
Haripur, Pakistan
haris.shehzad@fcm3.paf-iast.edu.pk

Abraiz Khattak

Department of Electrical Power Engineering
U.S.-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Energy
National University of Sciences and Technology
Islamabad, Pakistan
abraiz@uspcae.nust.edu.pk

Shibli Nisar

Military College of Signals
National University of Sciences and Technology
Islamabad, Pakistan
shiblinisar@mcs.edu.pk

Kashif Imran

Department of Electrical Power Engineering
U.S.-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Energy
National University of Sciences and Technology
Islamabad, Pakistan
kashifimran@uspcae.nust.edu.pk

Abstract—The main objective of this paper is to study the effect of phase numbers in the dual rotor Brushless DC (BLDC) motor for its application in Electric Vehicles (EVs). The performance of two novel 5-, and 7-phase dual rotor BLDC motors is compared against the standard 3-phase dual rotor BLDC motor. The proposed motors combine the positive characteristics of multiphase BLDC motor and the dual rotor BLDC motor thus achieving better fault tolerance capability, high power density, and less per phase stator current. Finite Element Method (FEM) was used to design the 3-, 5-, and 7-phase dual-rotor BLDC motors. The design parameters and operating conditions are kept the same for a fair comparison. The stator current and torque performance of the proposed motors were obtained with FEM simulation and were compared with the standard 3-phase dual rotor BLDC motor. It is possible to use low power rating power electronics switches for the proposed motor. The simulation results also validate low torque ripples and high-power density in the proposed motors. Finally, the fault analysis of the designed motors shows that the fault tolerance capability increases as the phase number increases.

Keywords—dual rotor; Brushless DC (BLDC); Electric Vehicle (EV); multiphase; Finite Element Method (FEM)

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric Vehicles (EVs) are the future of road transportation. Extensive research has been conducted on the drive system of EVs to provide low-cost and energy-efficient solutions. The electric motor is an integral part of its propulsion system along with the transmission system, the power electronics, and the battery [1]. The basic requirements of the electric motor for EV applications include high torque and power density, varied speed range (high speed cruising and low speed crawling), high efficiency over wide torque and speed ranges, wide constant power operation region, high intermittent overload capability, and high reliability and robustness [2-6]. The main advantages of the Brushless DC (BLDC) motor are its small size, the absence of rotor copper losses due to the absence of rotor windings, and its low maintenance cost [7]. The BLDC motor offers high efficiency, high power, and torque density, but the conventional BLDC motor topologies do not provide all the requirements for EV application [8-10].

The dual-rotor BLDC machine promises high torque density and high efficiency. This motor consists of an outer rotor, an inner rotor, and a stator between them. In other words, two separate motors share the same stator nested between them

[11-12]. Since both sides of the stator are used as compared to single rotor Permanent Magnet (PM) BLDC, this structure improves the torque density. The topology reduces the copper quantity, which in turn reduces the winding resistance. Thus, the copper losses are reduced, and efficiency is improved. The reduced copper usage also cuts down the cost [13-15].

The next important requirement for PM BLDC machines used in EV applications is fault tolerance which is the ability of a system to continue working even if a fault occurs. The fault-tolerant capability of the PM BLDC motors can be enhanced by increasing the number of stator phases (more than three-phase). In a multiphase PM BLDC drive system, increasing the phase number also increases the number of power electronic switches while it reduces the converter rating required per phase [16-17]. The multiphase PM BLDC motors have low torque ripple and high torque density as compared to the three-phase electric motors [18-20]. It is now evident that dual-rotor PM BLDC and multiphase PM BLDC topologies offer unique advantages for EV application. These two topologies can be combined to get the positive characteristics of multiphase PM BLDC machines and dual-rotor PM BLDC machines.

In our research work, two dual rotor BLDC motors with 5, and 7 phases are designed for EV application. These motors are fed with square wave currents and have trapezoidal back EMF waveform unlike the sinusoidal PMSM motors. The characteristics of these two motors are compared against the standard 3-phase dual rotor BLDC motor. They combine the positive characteristics of the dual rotor and multiphase BLDC motors, thus achieving less per phase stator current, high power and torque density, and better fault tolerance capability. The main contributions of the current paper are:

- Two new dual rotor multiphase BLDC motors as 5-, and 7-phase are designed to drive an EV. The characteristics of these motors are compared with the standard 3-phase dual rotor BLDC motor. Finite Element Method (FEM) based two-dimensional models of the motors were developed with the JMAG Designer.
- Load and no-load analysis of the three designed motors were performed.
- Fault analysis of the three motors is provided to compare their fault tolerance. Open circuit faults, high-impedance faults, and demagnetization of the permanent magnets are studied.

II. ANALYTICAL STUDY

The main design parameters of the BLDC motor are the diameter of the armature, the stack length, and the air-gap length, through which the energy conversion process is completed. The calculation of these three design parameters is a fundamental step in any electric motor design. BLDC motor's electromagnetic loading comprises of the specific electrical loading and the specific magnetic loading. These loads define torque, efficiency, and other mechanical characteristics of the motor. Even though the motors in this study have two rotors, the design of any BLDC motor starts with the general sizing equation. The sizing equation gives the relationship between the main design parameters and the electromagnetic load of the

dual-rotor BLDC motor. The main design specifications of the dual-rotor BLDC motor are derived as follows.

$$P_{em} = 11. \alpha_p \cdot B_a \cdot A_a \cdot \left(\frac{D}{1000}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{L}{1000} \cdot n_N \quad (1)$$

where P_{em} is the apparent power, L is the stator's stack length, D is the armature's diameter, B_a is the specific magnetic loading, and A_a is the specific electrical load. The rated speed of the motor represented by n_N and α_p is a constant which depends on the pole arc of the motor.

The BLDC motor having trapezoidal back EMF is modeled using the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 1. The voltage of the single phase can be derived as:

$$V_a = i_a R_a + L_a \frac{di_a(t)}{dt} + e_a \quad (2)$$

where V_a is the phase voltage, R_a is the phase resistance, L_a is the phase inductance, e_a is the generated back EMF, and i_a is the phase current.

The generated back EMF and torque constant are functions of the relative rotor position. The voltage equation for multiple phases based on the back EMF is expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ \vdots \\ V_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_a & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & R_b & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & R_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ \vdots \\ i_n \end{bmatrix} + \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ \vdots \\ i_n \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e_a \\ e_b \\ \vdots \\ e_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1. Equivalent circuit of the n-phase BLDC motor.

For single phase, the expression for the current is derived as a function of supplied voltage, phase inductance, and back EMF as:

$$\frac{d}{dt} i_a = \frac{1}{3L_a} [2V_{bb} + V_{bc} - 3R_a i_a + \phi p \omega_m (-2e'_a + e'_b + e'_c)] \quad (4)$$

where ω_m is the rotational speed, p is the pole pair number, and ϕ is the induced flux. The phase inductance is considered constant as the relative rotor position does not affect it. The following equation shows phase inductances BLDC motor:

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_a &= L_{aa} - M \\
 L_b &= L_{bb} - M \\
 &\vdots \\
 &\vdots \\
 L_n &= L_{nn} - M \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

where M is the mutual inductance, L_n is the phase inductance for the n -phase and L_{nn} is the self-inductance. From (3) and (5), the equation for phase voltages can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ \vdots \\ V_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_a & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & R_b & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & R_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ \vdots \\ i_n \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} L_a & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & L_b & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & L_n \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ \vdots \\ i_n \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e_a \\ e_b \\ \vdots \\ e_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The back EMF of the motor depends on rotor speed, rotor relative position, magnetic field intensity, and the number of turns. For a n -phase BLDC motor, the phase angle difference is $(360/n)$ for each phase of the back EMF. So, the back EMF of each phase is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} e_a \\ e_b \\ \vdots \\ e_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{E_n}(\theta) \\ K_{E_n}\left(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{n}\right) \\ \vdots \\ K_{E_n}\left(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{n}(n-1)\right) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \omega \quad (7)$$

In (7), the back electromotive force constant of one phase of n -phase BLDC motor is represented by K_{E_n} . The per phase output torques are derived as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} T_a \\ T_b \\ \vdots \\ T_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{T_n}(\theta) \\ K_{T_n}\left(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{n}\right) \\ \vdots \\ K_{T_n}\left(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{n}(n-1)\right) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} I_a \\ I_b \\ \vdots \\ I_n \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where K_{T_n} is the torque constant of one phase of the n -phase BLDC motor. The total electromagnetic torque is given as:

$$T_e = T_a + T_b + \dots + T_n \quad (9)$$

III. DUAL ROTOR MULTIPHASE BLDC MOTOR DESIGN

A. Structure of the Dual Rotor BLDC Motor

Figure 2 represents the cross-section of the 2D CAD model of a dual rotor BLDC motor. The motor consists of a stator sandwiched between two (outer and inner) rotors. The magnets of both rotors are polarized in the same direction. The flux generated by the outer magnets goes through the outer teeth of the stator and the flux driven by the inner magnets goes through the inner teeth of the stator. This structure enables the motor to have low overall volume and improved torque density. With this structure, high torque to volume ratio is obtained, which is critical for EV applications. In the designed dual-rotor multiphase BLDC motor, full-pitched concentrated

windings are used. This winding configuration reduces the requirement of greater stator slot numbers and reduces the use of copper.

Fig. 2. Structure of the proposed dual rotor BLDC motor.

B. Determination of Motor Power

The first step in any motor design is to determine the motor torque and the nominal speed. Two parameters define the motor dimensions, motor radius and stack length. The required power to drive the vehicle can be deduced as [21]:

$$p_{em} \geq \max[p_e, p_a, p_c] \quad (10)$$

where p_e is the maximum power of the motor when the vehicle achieves maximum speed, p_a is the maximum power of the motor when the vehicle is at highest gradient, and p_c is the maximum power of the motor when the vehicle achieves maximum acceleration. p_e , p_a and p_c are defined by (11), (12) and (13) respectively:

$$p_e = \frac{u_{max}}{360\eta_T} \left(mgf + \frac{C_D A u_{max}^2}{21.15} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$p_a = \frac{u_i}{360\eta_T} \left(mgf \cos\alpha_{max} + mg \sin\alpha_{max} + \frac{C_D A u_i^2}{21.15} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$p_c = \frac{1}{360t_a\eta_T} \left(\delta m \frac{u_a^2}{2\sqrt{t_a}} + mgf \frac{u_a}{1.5} t_a + \frac{C_D A u_a^3}{21.15 \cdot 2.5} t_a \right) \quad (13)$$

where u_i is the initial velocity, u_{max} is the maximum velocity, u_a is the final velocity, and δ is the mass conversion coefficient of the vehicle.

The maximum speed n_{max} of the motor is calculated as:

$$n_{max} = \frac{u_{max} \cdot 10^3}{120\pi r} \quad (14)$$

The nominal speed n_N is related to maximum speed as:

$$n_{max} = \beta n_N \quad (15)$$

where β is the coefficient of constant power meter. Increasing the value of β will increase the generated torque. Its value ranges between 2 and 4. A large size power converter is needed to achieve a greater value of β .

C. Machine Design and Comparison

To study the effect of different phase numbers on the performance of motors, three different BLDC (3-phase, 5-phase, and 7-phase) motors were designed. To allow a fair comparison of the three motors, similar materials were used and most of the geometric parameters were kept the same. The three motors were analyzed with FEM. Table I shows the design parameters of the three dual rotor BLDC motors. The cross sections of the simulation models for the three motors are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Cross section of the simulation models. (a) 3-phase dual rotor motor, (b) 5-phase dual rotor motor, (c) 7-phase dual rotor motor.

TABLE I. DESIGN PARAMETERS

Designed Motors	3- Ph	5- Ph	7- Ph
Number of poles (p)	20	20	20
Number of turns	35	35	35
Number of slots	27	40	63
Outer diameter(mm)	110	110	110
Stack length (mm)	50	50	50
Current density (A/mm ²)	5	5	5
Rated speed	900rpm	900rpm	900rpm
Magnetic loading (T)	0.8	0.8	0.8
Magnets	NdFeB	NdFeB	NdFeB

IV. NO LOAD OPERATION

In dual rotor BLDC motor, two independent flux loops are formed in the outer and inner air gaps as displayed in Figure 1. The flux flows from one magnet in the outer rotor through the outer air gap to the teeth of the outer stator. Following the core of the outer stator, the flux flows back to the opposite polarity

of the magnet and thus completes a loop. In a similar fashion, a flux loop is created in the lower air gap between the inner rotor and the stator. A different amount of flux is generated in each air gap and two independent back EMFs are generated in each stator. At no-load conditions, no current flows in the armature winding, and a magnetic field is generated by the permanent magnet. The no-load characteristics of the motor are obtained by running the motor without input current. Cogging torque is generated due to the interaction of magnets and coils at no load. The cogging torques of the three designed motors were compared. The conventional three-phase BLDC motor demonstrated a greater cogging torque as compared to the two proposed motors. Furthermore, the 7-phase dual rotor BLDC motor indicated a reduction in cogging torque than the 5-phase dual rotor BLDC motor.

Fig. 4. Cogging torque of the 3-phase BLDC motor.

Fig. 5. Cogging torque of the 5-phase BLDC motor.

Fig. 6. Cogging torque of the 7-phase BLDC motor.

V. LOAD OPERATION

To analyze the dual rotor multi-phase motors under load conditions, they were driven by a trapezoidal current source. A logic commutation was developed for each motor [22]. The interaction of permanent magnets and the magnetic field of the stator coils produce torque. For an n-phase dual rotor BLDC motor, one phase is positively energized, another phase is negatively energized, and the remaining phases are not energized.

Fig. 7. Stator winding configuration: (a) 5-phase motor (b) 7-phase motor.

As shown in Figure 8, each phase of the n-phase BLDC motor is star-connected using 2n switches, where n is the number of phases. Since all three dual rotor BLDC motors are designed with the same electric and magnetic loading, the per phase rms current of the three-phase motor is the largest. As shown in Figure 9, the peak value of the 3-phase motor is 86A, of the 5-phase motor is 45A, and of the 7-phase motor is 32A.

Fig. 8. Winding diagram of the n-phase BLDC motor.

Fig. 9. Stator phase current waveforms.

Figures 10-12 show the wave forms of the steady state output electromagnetic torques of the three motors. The torque ripples of the 3-phase motor are the highest, whereas the torque ripples are reduced with increasing number of phases. However, the torque ripples of the 5-phase motor can be considered satisfactory. Hence, a phase number greater than 5 is only necessary to reduce the stator current.

Fig. 10. Torque waveform of the 3-phase motor.

Fig. 11. Torque waveform of the 5-phase motor.

Fig. 12. Torque waveform of the 7-phase motor.

VI. FAULT ANALYSIS

This section analyzes the transient process of the three designed dual rotor BLDC motors under various fault conditions. The performance of the three motors under various short and open circuit faults was analyzed. Figure 13 shows the comparison of the average output torque of each motor under different faults. The Figure shows either an open circuit fault or short circuit faults by phase number. To simulate these faults, a fault was introduced at certain time using switches. At the time of the fault, there was a sudden dip in the average torque and the torque ripples were increased.

Fig. 13. Average torque under various open or short circuit fault conditions.

High impedance faults occur due to broken strands of the motor winding. The most common type is the high resistance fault. This fault was simulated using extra resistance in series with the phase winding. The value of this resistance is obtained from:

$$R_{extra} = \frac{1}{1-\sigma} (R_{inductor} + R_{end}) \quad (16)$$

where σ defines the percentage of the broken wires. Tables II-IV compare the effect of this fault on the three motors. Increasing the phase number makes the motor more prone to broken strand faults.

TABLE II. HIGH IMPEDANCE FAULT CONDITION IN 3-PHASE MOTOR

Condition	Average torque	Percentage of normal torque
Normal condition	30	100%
20% Broken strands	21.708	72.36%
35% Broken strands	20.319	67.3%
65% Broken strands	14.469	48.23%

TABLE III. HIGH IMPEDANCE FAULT CONDITION IN 5-PHASE MOTOR

Condition	Average torque	Percentage of normal torque
Normal condition	30	100%
20% Broken strands	26.41	88.04%
35% Broken strands	23.54818966	76.8%
65% Broken strands	20.15	67.17%

TABLE IV. HIGH IMPEDANCE FAULT CONDITION IN 7-PHASE MOTOR

Condition	Average torque	Percentage of normal torque
Normal condition	30	100%
20% Broken strands	28.43	84.76%
35% Broken strands	26.02	86.73%
65% Broken strands	23.72	79.06%

Extreme temperature and high electrical loading can cause demagnetization of the BLDC motors, decreasing the average output torque. The designed motors were studied under different demagnetization conditions. When all magnets were demagnetized by 4%, the average torque decreased by 12.7%, 8.3%, and 6.6% for the 3-phase, 5-phase, and 7-phase BLDC motors respectively.

VII. COMPARISON WITH THE AVAILABLE LITERATURE

The combination of the characteristics of the dual rotor and multiphase permanent motors is available in literature for Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSM) [23-24]. In [23], a dual-rotor PMSM was designed, a motor with sinusoidal back EMF, to get high torque density and good fault tolerance capability. The performance and fault tolerance of the same dual-rotor five phase PMSM is investigated in [24].

To the best of our knowledge, no literature is available with regard to the dual-rotor multiphase BLDC motors. In the current research work, two dual rotor BLDC motors with 5 and 7 phases were designed for EV application. These motors were fed with square wave currents having trapezoidal back EMF waveforms unlike the sinusoidal back EMF in PMSM motors. The characteristics of the two proposed motors were compared against the standard 3-phase dual rotor BLDC motor. The designed motors have the advantages of the dual rotor and multiphase motors, thus achieving less per phase stator current, high power and torque density, and better fault tolerance capability.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Considering the requirements of a high torque EV, two new dual rotor BLDC motors were designed and studied in this paper. The dual-rotor PM BLDC motor promises high torque density and high efficiency. This machine consists of an inner rotor, an outer rotor, and a stator between the two rotors. Three motors: 3-phase, 5-phase, and 7-phase have been designed and FEM was utilized to analyze their performance. The main design parameters and materials are preliminarily decided by standard methods. Analytical modeling of the multiphase BLDC motor has been presented. The performance of the 5- and 7-phase dual rotor BLDC motors has been evaluated under load and no-load conditions and the results were compared with the standard 3-phase dual rotor BLDC motor.

To allow a fair comparison, most of the design parameters and operating conditions of the motors were kept the same with the ones of the base motor. The number of stator slots for each motor has been determined by the phase number. The cogging torque and back EMF waveforms were obtained at no load. Average torque and stator current waveforms were obtained at loaded conditions. The results show that increasing the phase number decreases phase current. This enables the use of low rating power electronic switches. The output torque can also be increased per RMS current for the same volume of the motor. Torque ripples also decreased as the number of phases increased. Finally, fault analysis of the three motors has been performed to analyze their performance under fault conditions. It was found that the increased phase number makes the motor more fault tolerant and increases reliability.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Zheng, Y. Liu, Y. Wang, and S. Cheng, "Magnetization analysis of the brushless DC motor used for hybrid electric vehicle," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 522–524, Jan. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMAG.2004.838746>.
- [2] J. A. Sanguesa, V. Torres-Sanz, P. Garrido, F. J. Martinez, and J. M. Marquez-Barja, "A Review on Electric Vehicles: Technologies and Challenges," *Smart Cities*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 372–404, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/smartcities4010022>.
- [3] K. T. Chau, C. C. Chan, and C. Liu, "Overview of Permanent-Magnet Brushless Drives for Electric and Hybrid Electric Vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 2246–2257, Jun. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2008.918403>.
- [4] W. Cai, X. Wu, M. Zhou, Y. Liang, and Y. Wang, "Review and Development of Electric Motor Systems and Electric Powertrains for New Energy Vehicles," *Automotive Innovation*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 3–22, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42154-021-00139-z>.
- [5] A. Eldho Aliasand and F. T. Josh, "Selection of Motor for an Electric Vehicle: A Review," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 24, pp. 1804–1815, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.03.605>.
- [6] T. A. Zarma, A. A. Galadima, and M. A. Aminu, "Review of Motors for Electric Vehicles," *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports*, pp. 1–6, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.9734/jsrr/2019/v24i630170>.
- [7] M. Yildirim, H. Kurum, D. Miljavec, and S. Corovic, "Influence of Material and Geometrical Properties of Permanent Magnets on Cogging Torque of BLDC," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2656–2662, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1725>.
- [8] Z. Q. Zhu and D. Howe, "Electrical Machines and Drives for Electric, Hybrid, and Fuel Cell Vehicles," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 95, no. 4, pp. 746–765, Apr. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2006.892482>.
- [9] T.-Y. Lee, M.-K. Seo, Y.-J. Kim, and S.-Y. Jung, "Motor Design and Characteristics Comparison of Outer-Rotor-Type BLDC Motor and BLAC Motor Based on Numerical Analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 1–6, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASC.2016.2548079>.
- [10] M. Dabbi, S. Doubabi, A. Rachid, and D. Oulad-Abbou, "Performance evaluation of electric vehicle brushless direct current motor with a novel high-performance control strategy with experimental implementation," *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part I: Journal of Systems and Control Engineering*, vol. 234, no. 3, pp. 358–369, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959651819854562>.
- [11] Y. Li, D. Bobba, and B. Sarlioglu, "Design and Optimization of a Novel Dual-Rotor Hybrid PM Machine for Traction Application," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 1762–1771, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2017.2739686>.
- [12] B. V. R. Kumar and K. S. Kumar, "Design of a new Dual Rotor Radial Flux BLDC motor with Halbach array magnets for an electric vehicle," in *International Conference on Power Electronics, Drives and Energy Systems*, Trivandrum, India, Dec. 2016, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PEDES.2016.7914552>.
- [13] Y.-H. Yeh, M.-F. Hsieh, and D. G. Dorrell, "Different Arrangements for Dual-Rotor Dual-Output Radial-Flux Motors," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 612–622, Mar. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.2011.2180495>.
- [14] A. Dalal and P. Kumar, "Design, Prototyping, and Testing of a Dual-Rotor Motor for Electric Vehicle Application," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 7185–7192, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2018.2795586>.
- [15] P. Pisek, B. Stumberger, T. Marcic, and P. Virtic, "Design Analysis and Experimental Validation of a Double Rotor Synchronous PM Machine Used for HEV," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 152–155, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMAG.2012.2220338>.
- [16] G. Boztas, M. Yildirim, and O. Aydogmus, "Design and Analysis of Multi-Phase BLDC Motors for Electric Vehicles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2646–2650, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1781>.
- [17] M. Salehifar, R. S. Arashloo, J. M. Moreno-Equilaz, V. Sala, and L. Romeral, "Fault Detection and Fault Tolerant Operation of a Five Phase PM Motor Drive Using Adaptive Model Identification Approach," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 212–223, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JESTPE.2013.2293518>.
- [18] L. Parsa and H. A. Toliyat, "Five-phase permanent-magnet motor drives," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 30–37, Jan. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.2004.841021>.
- [19] H. Lu, J. Li, R. Qu, D. Ye, and Y. Lu, "Fault-Tolerant Predictive Control of Six-Phase PMSM Drives Based on Pulsewidth Modulation," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 66, no. 7, pp. 4992–5003, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2018.2868264>.
- [20] E. Levi, "Multiphase Electric Machines for Variable-Speed Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 55, no. 5, pp. 1893–1909, May 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2008.918488>.
- [21] Y. Yuan, W. Meng, X. Sun, and L. Zhang, "Design Optimization and Analysis of an Outer-Rotor Direct-Drive Permanent-Magnet Motor for Medium-Speed Electric Vehicle," *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, vol. 10, no. 2, Jun. 2019, Art. no. 16, <https://doi.org/10.3390/wevj10020016>.
- [22] C. Oprea, C. Martis, and B. Karoly, "Six-phase brushless DC motor for fault tolerant electric power steering systems," in *International Aegean Conference on Electrical Machines and Power Electronics*, Bodrum, Turkey, Sep. 2007, pp. 457–462, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACEMP.2007.4510543>.
- [23] Y. Li, J. Zhao, Z. Chen, and X. Liu, "Investigation of a Five-Phase Dual-Rotor Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Used for Electric Vehicles," *Energies*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 3955–3984, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en7063955>.
- [24] J. Zhao, X. Gao, B. Li, X. Liu, and X. Guan, "Open-Phase Fault Tolerance Techniques of Five-Phase Dual-Rotor Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor," *Energies*, vol. 8, no. 11, pp. 12810–12838, Nov. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en81112342>.

Experimental and Numerical Analysis of the Punching Shear Resistance Strengthening of Concrete Flat Plates by Steel Collars

Ahmed Aziz Abdulhussein
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad

Baghdad, Iraq
a.abdhussain1101@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Mohannad H. Al-Sherrawi
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq

Dr.Mohannad.Al-Sherrawi@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract-In this study, six square reinforced concrete flat plates with dimensions of (1500×1500×100) mm were tested under a concentrated load applied on a column located at the center of the slabs. One of these slabs was the control specimen, whereas, in the others, steel angles (steel collars) were used, fixed at the connection region between the slab and the column to investigate the effect of the presence of these collars on punching shear strength. Five thicknesses were used (4, 5, 6, 8, 10mm) with constant legs of angles (75×75) mm of the steel collars to investigate the effects on the punching shear resistance with respect to the control slab. The results of the experimental study show that the punching shear resistance increased by 41 to 77% when steel collars were used. The experimental results were in good agreement with the numerical analysis acquired with the ABAQUS software.

Keywords-flat plates; punching shear strength; steel collar; strengthening

I. INTRODUCTION

Through the past decades, many experimental tests have been performed to enhance the punching shear strength of Reinforced Concrete (RC) flat plates by using different mechanisms and materials such as Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP), shear bolts, shear reinforcements, and steel plates, placed in the slab around the column. Authors in [1] studied the strengthening of slab-column connection by drilling prestressed shear bolts in the slab regions around the columns. These bolts have high tensile strength with steel plates at each end. The experimental results showed that the ultimate load increased by about 67% with respect to the unbolted slab and the ultimate moment increased by 23% in comparison with the unbolted slab. Authors in [2] studied a strengthening method by utilizing steel plates on two-way square slabs subjected to punching loading. These steel plates were bonded in both sides (tension and compression) with epoxy and bolts in different patterns, numbers, and distributions. The results showed that the ultimate load increased by 56%-64%. The author in [3] tested RC flat plates strengthened with strips of CFRP, which passed through holes in the slab around the column and were wrapped around to form closed stirrups. Different patterns were used depending on the number and position of the holes. The

test results showed that the proposed method was successful in strengthening the slab-column connection and when the slabs were subjected to concentric and eccentric loads.

In the field of retrofitting damaged RC flat plates due to punching shear, authors in [4, 5] investigated experimentally the use of prestressed and non-prestressed shear bolts, which were inserted in the slabs around the column and were anchored in steel plates on the slab faces. They observed that the use of shear bolts led to an increment on the punching shear strength and can be considered efficient and applicable. Authors in [6] tested seven interior slab-column connections to evaluate the effectiveness of various rehabilitation techniques (CFRP stirrups, well anchored CFRP sheets, and square tube steel collars) on repairing seismic-damaged slab-column connections and improving their punching shear strength. The installation of the steel collars prevented punching shear failure under the application of simulated seismic displacements.

Authors in [7] conducted an experimental research on the strengthening of slab-column connection by bonded CFRP strips. The CFRP strips were fixed on the tension face of the slab in perpendicular or inclined orientation around the slab-column connection and were bonded by an epoxy adhesive at adjusted or offset at the column face. The test result showed increment in punching strength up to 29% for strengthened specimens in comparison with the reference slab. Also, the strengthened slab was much stiffer when the CFRP strips were near the column while the punching shear strength increased when the strips were offset from the column. Authors in [8] studied the load-deflection behavior and the load-carrying capacity of RC flat plates built on corner columns using the non-linear three-dimensional finite element software ANSYS. The obtained failure mechanism showed that the slabs failed near the columns due to the flexural punching mechanism resulting from local flexural yielding of the slab reinforcement around the column.

The effect of column rectangularity (aspect ratio) on the punching shear behavior is not dependent on the column cross-section dimensions only, and becomes more serious as the ratio of the minimum column dimension to the effective slab depth

Corresponding author: Ahmed Aziz Abdulhussein

increases [9]. Authors in [10] outlined a simple theoretical method based on the yield line theory to predict the flexural capacity of a strengthened RC flat slab with unequal-leg steel angle plates. Adding fibers to the concrete made the flat plate fail in a more ductile mode, while the failure was sudden with brittle mode in slabs that contained no fibers [11-13].

In this research, punching shear strengthening of RC flat plates is investigated by using steel angle sections (steel collars) fixed in the column-slab connection region by epoxy and stud bolts in the column. One control specimen without strengthening and 5 strengthened specimens with steel collars of different thickness were experimentally tested. The analytical predictions of the punching shear capacity obtained with the use of the ABAQUS software were compared with the experimental results.

II. TEST SPECIMENS

The studied specimens in this paper were 6 RC flat plates with dimensions of $1500 \times 1500 \times 100$ mm with effective depth $d=70$ mm, column with cross-section 150×150 mm, and height 200 mm located at the center of the slab. All specimens were tested under punching loading and were simply supported in the four sides over a span of 1400 mm. Two meshes of flexural reinforcement were used in the specimens, $\phi 10$ at 75 mm c/c in the tension zone and $\phi 8$ at 150 mm c/c in the compression zone, whereas the yield strength of the reinforcements was 616 and 624 MPa respectively. The compressive strength of the concrete cylinders was 30 MPa and the column was reinforced with 4 $\phi 16$ mm and $\phi 8$ mm stirrups. One of these specimens was used as a control slab (S_0 /Reference), without any strengthening. The rest 5 flat plates, were strengthened with steel collars connected to the region of slab-column connection by epoxy and stud anchors. The yield strength of steel angles is 400, 400, 440, 420, and 375 MPa for thicknesses of 4, 5, 6, 8, and 10 mm respectively and the stud anchors had yield strength of 520 MPa. The details of the tested specimens are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Details of the tested specimens.

Variable thicknesses of steel collars were used in the 5 flat plates:

- $75 \times 75 \times 4$ mm steel angle (S1/collar/75/4)
- $75 \times 75 \times 5$ mm steel angle (S2/collar/75/5)
- $75 \times 75 \times 6$ mm steel angle (S3/collar/75/6)

- $75 \times 75 \times 8$ mm steel angle (S4/collar/75/8)
- $75 \times 75 \times 10$ mm steel angle (S5/collar/75/10)

III. TEST SETUP AND MEASUREMENTS

The tests were carried out in the structural laboratory of the Department of Civil Engineering of the University of Baghdad. The specimens were setup on a simply supported steel frame in 4 edges and the load was applied concentric to the column stub (Figure 2). To record the vertical deflection, three Linear Variable Differential Transducers (LVDT) were used, the first one beneath the centre of the slab and the other two were located at the 1/3 and 2/3 of the distance between the centre of the slab and the support. To measure the strain in the reinforcements and steel collar, steel strain gages were placed in the tension reinforcements under the center of the column and near the inner edge of the steel angle. The strain in concrete was measured using concrete strain gauges attached to the top surface of the slab (compression face) and the bottom surface (tension face) at distance equal to $4d$ from the face of the column (this paper was drawn from a PhD dissertation that had many specimens strengthened with large sizes of steel angles (e.g. $150 \times 150 \times 10$ mm) and the strain gauges were put in the same position to all specimens in order to make comparisons between the samples. For this reason the distance $4d$ was used to avoid the location of strain gauge located on the leg of the steel angle). All instrumentations were connected to a computer by a data logger and the measurements were recorded with the Lab View 2018.

Fig. 2. (a) Test setup and (b) LVDTs distribution.

IV. STRENGTHENING PROCEDURE

The steps of strengthening the column-slab connection of RC flat plates using steel angle sections are:

- Form the steel angle as shown in Figure 3 by cutting one leg of steel angle with the right angle and the other leg cut with an angle of 45°.
- Roughen the region of concrete where the steel angle will be attached (the area of slab-column connection).
- Drill a hole on the column face in four sides using a hammer drill.
- Clean the steel angle pieces with sand paper.
- After cleaning the specific area from dust, insert Hilti stud anchor $\phi 10$ mm (Figure 4) in the hole of the column and apply a two-part epoxy resin Sikadur 31 (Figure 5) on the concrete surface. Then attach the steel angles in the four sides of the column and tighten the studs which passed through the holes of the steel angles.
- Weld the pieces of steel angles together to be like a collar around the column.

The procedure of the strengthening mechanism is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 3. A piece of steel angle.

Fig. 4. Hilti stud anchor.

Fig. 5. Sikadur 31.

Fig. 6. The strengthening steps of column-slab connection.

V. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Load-Deflection Response

Three LVDTs were used to measure the vertical deflections in (C), (a) and (2a). C represents the center of the slab and the a represents one third of the distance from the center to the support. Figure 7 showed that the load-deflection curves began as elastic and stiffer until first cracking. After that, the deflection increased rapidly and the stiffness decreased until the failure load was reached. In the reference specimen, the punching failure occurred suddenly but in strengthened specimens, before the collapse the crack number and the width of cracks increased giving alarm for failure. The ultimate load of the strengthened specimens increased with respect to the reference slab between 41% and 77% as the thickness of steel collars increased.

Table I shows the cracking and ultimate loads and the enhancement ratio of punching shear resistance due to the strengthening of the specimens by steel collars with variable steel angle thickness. The P_{cr} of strengthening specimens were larger than unstrengthening slab.

TABLE I. RESULTS

ID	Collar thickness (mm)	P_{cr} (kN)	Δ_{cr} (mm)	P_u (kN)	Δ_u (mm)	Enhancement ratio P_u (%)
S ₀	R	30	1.94	161	23.8	R
S ₁	4	38	2.7	227	26.33	41
S ₂	5	37	2.1	240	26.4	49
S ₃	6	38	2.9	251	29.8	56
S ₄	8	40	5.1	262	35.8	62.7
S ₅	10	40	4.8	285	40.5	77

Fig. 7. Load-deflection relationship of the tested specimens.

B. Strain in Flexural Reinforcements

The strain was measured at the maximum moment under the center of the column to observe when the reinforcement reached yielding. The yield strain of tensile steel bars was equal to 0.0031. Figure 8 shows the load-strain curves in flexural reinforcements for the reference slab and the strengthened specimens.

Fig. 8. Load-reinforcement strain of the tested specimens.

It was noticed that the specimens S_0 , S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 failed in pure punching shear because the failure occurred before the

reinforcement bars reached yield, but the mode of failure of S₄ and S₅ specimens combined flexural and punching shear, where the strains in the reinforcement exceeded the yielding limit before failure. The strengthened specimens showed enhancement in the values of strain, which decreased corresponding to the reference slab (S₀), due to the presence of the steel collars, which increased the stiffness of the specimens. Increasing the thickness of steel collars led to decrease in the strain values.

C. Compressive and Tensile Strains in Concrete

To measure the compressive and tensile strains of concrete, two strain gauges were fixed on the top and bottom concrete surfaces of the flat plate specimens at a distance equal to (4d) from the face of the column. Figure 9 shows the results of load-strain relationship for the reference specimen and the five specimens with different thicknesses of steel collars. The relationships show that the values of tensile strains were higher than compressive strains in all tested slabs, because concrete is weak against tension, which makes the neutral axis move toward the compression zone of concrete. The compressive strains in the strengthened slabs were greater than that in the reference slab at the same level of loading due to the use of steel collars. When the thickness of steel collar increased, the compressive strain increased. On the other hand, the tensile strains in strengthened specimens decreased with respect to the reference specimen at the same level of loading. This gave an indication of enhancement in tensile strain because the strengthened specimens became stiffer than the reference slab.

Fig. 9. Load-compressive and tensile strain in the tested specimens.

D. Strain in the Steel Collars

When failure occurred during the experimental tests of strengthened specimens, no deformation in the steel collars was observed and the strain recorded small values due to the high

stiffness of steel angles due to the thickness of the steel section ($\leq 4\text{mm}$). Also, no separation of the steel collars from the concrete was observed. The steel collar and the column penetrate the slab as one piece, due to the use of proper epoxy.

VI. FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

Finite element analysis with the ABAQUS software was conducted to simulate the 6 flat plate specimens. Only one quarter was modeled due to the double symmetry of the flat plate specimens. Concrete slab was modeled as solid 3D-8 node brick elements (C3D8R) with reduced integration (Figure 10(a)). Truss elements with two noded linear elements (T3D2) were used to model the steel reinforcements (Figure 10(b)) and the embedded method was used to model the interaction between reinforcements and concrete, assuming perfect bond between them.

Fig. 10. Simulation of strengthening flat-plate specimens by ABAQUS. (a) Geometry of concrete flat plate, (b) modeling of reinforcements, (c) steel collar and stud anchor, (d) epoxy, (e) boundary conditions and supports.

The steel collar and stud anchor were modeled as C3D8R solid elements (Figure 10(c)) and the epoxy was simulated as COH3D8 8-node three dimensional cohesive elements (Figure 10(d)) and a tie constraint modeled the contact between the steel collar and the concrete. The stud anchors were installed in columns by drilled holes and contact between them by the tie constraint. The boundary conditions and supports are shown in Figure 10(e) which simulates the supports as restrained at the bottom of slab in the y -direction and lets the corners of slab free to lift.

A. Load-Deflection Relationship

Figure 11 shows the comparison between the experimental results and the numerical analysis of load-deflection curves for the reference and the strengthened specimens. A good agreement is observed. The difference between the experimental and the ABAQUS results for ultimate load ranges between 10.8% and 2.6%.

B. Crack Pattern

The first crack starts near the edge of the column in the tension side of concrete with longitudinal form. The first cracking is followed by many longitudinal cracks forming parallel to the flexural bars. After increasing the load, transverse cracks began to appear and connect to the longitudinal cracks. Also, radial cracks formed from the center of the slab reached the corners and the edges. At the collapse load, shear cracks of irregular round shape were formed around the bottom of the column in the tension side.

Fig. 11. Experimental and ABAQUS load-deflection curves.

Fig. 12. Comparison between the experimental and the analytical crack pattern.

In the strengthened specimens, the numbers of cracks was more than the reference slab because the load reached higher values. The perimeter of the failure area was increased at S₄ and S₅ which have maximum values of punching shear strength. Figure 12 illustrates the comparisons between the crack pattern of the experiments and the numerical analysis in ABAQUS.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

- The punching shear resistance of strengthened specimens was enhanced with respect to the unstrengthened slab.
- The punching shear resistance of strengthened specimens increased with respect to the reference slab. The increment ranged between 41% and 77%, and was bigger when the thickness of steel collars increased.
- The steel collars increase the perimeter of failure zone therefore the shear strength increases.
- The value of cracking load increased in strengthened slabs due to the presence of the steel collar, which increased the stiffness of the region around the column in which the first crack began to appear.
- The values of reinforcement strain decreased in the strengthened specimens due to the presence of the steel collars which increased the stiffness of the specimens.
- The strengthened specimens showed enhancement in tensile concrete strain.
- The strengthened specimens S₄ and S₅ failed in a combined punching-flexural mode. The steel collar strengthening technique has effectively turned the final mode of failure from punching shear to flexural and punching shear mechanism outside the strengthened zone.
- The technique of strengthening by steel collars was easy, effective, and fast to implement with respect to previous studies that used steel sections.
- The collapse in strengthened specimens did not occur suddenly which gave alarm by the increased number and width of cracks.
- The results of the comparison between the experimental and the numerical load-deflection curves and crack patterns for the reference and the strengthened specimens were in a good agreement.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Department of Civil Engineering at the University of Baghdad for their support.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Ghali, M. A. Sargious, and A. Huizer, "Vertical Prestressing of Flat Plates Around Columns," *Shear in Reinforced Concrete*, vol. 42, pp. 905–920, Jan. 1974, <https://doi.org/10.14359/17314>.
- [2] U. Ebead and H. Marzouk, "Strengthening of two-way slabs using steel plates," *ACI Structural Journal*, vol. 99, no. 1, Jan. 2002.
- [3] B. Binici and O. Bayrak, "Punching Shear Strengthening of Reinforced Concrete Flat Plates Using Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 129, no. 9, pp. 1173–1182, Sep. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2003\)129:9\(1173\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2003)129:9(1173)).
- [4] M. M. G. Inácio, A. Pinho Ramos, and D. M. V. Faria, "Strengthening of flat slabs with transverse reinforcement by introduction of steel bolts using different anchorage approaches," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 44, pp. 63–77, Nov. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2012.05.043>.
- [5] H. S. Askar, "Repair of R/C flat plates failing in punching by vertical studs," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 541–550, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2015.03.033>.
- [6] Widiyanto, O. Bayrak, J. O. Jirsa, and Y. Tian, "Seismic Rehabilitation of Slab-Column Connections," *ACI Structural Journal*, vol. 107, no. 2, pp. 237–247, Mar. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.14359/51663540>.
- [7] K. Soudki, A. K. El-Sayed, and T. Vanzwol, "Strengthening of concrete slab-column connections using CFRP strips," *Journal of King Saud University - Engineering Sciences*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 25–33, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksues.2011.07.001>.
- [8] A. Hameed, H. Husain, and M. Al-Sherrawi, "Analysis of Corner Column-Slab Connections in Concrete Flat Plates," *East African Scholars Journal of Engineering and Computer Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 37–46, Jan. 2019.
- [9] G. J. Milligan, M. A. Polak, and C. Zurell, "Finite element analysis of punching shear behaviour of concrete slabs supported on rectangular columns," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 224, p. 111189, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.111189>.
- [10] H. R. Taresh, M. Y. M. Yatim, and M. R. Azmi, "Punching shear behaviour of interior slab-column connections strengthened by steel angle plates," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 238, p. 112246, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2021.112246>.
- [11] A. N. Dalaf and S. D. Mohammed, "The Impact of Hybrid Fibers on Punching Shear Strength of Concrete Flat Plates Exposed to Fire," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7452–7457, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4314>.
- [12] A. S. Mahdi and S. D. Mohammed, "Experimental and Numerical Analysis of Bubbles Distribution Influence in BubbleDeck Slab under Harmonic Load Effect," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6645–6649, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3963>.
- [13] B. Gebretsadik, K. Jadidi, V. Farhangi, and M. Karakouzian, "Application of Ultrasonic Measurements for the Evaluation of Steel Fiber Reinforced Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6662–6667, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3915>.

Robust Speed Control of a Three Phase Induction Motor Using Support Vector Regression

Noor Hussain Mugheri

Department of Electrical Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering Science and
Technology
Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan
noorhussain@quest.edu.pk

Muhammad Usman Keerio

Department of Electrical Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering Science and
Technology
Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan
usmankeerio@quest.edu

Saadullah Chandio

Department of Electrical Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering Science and
Technology
Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan
sadchandio@quest.edu.pk

Riaz Hussain Memon

Department of Electrical Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering Science and
Technology
Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan
r.hmemon@quest.edu.pk

Abstract-The Three Phase Induction Motor (TIM) is one of the most widely used motors due to its low price, robustness, low maintenance cost, and high efficiency. In this paper, a Support Vector Regression (SVR) based controller for TIM speed control using Indirect Vector Control (IVC) is presented. The IVC method is more frequently used because it enables better speed control of the TIM with higher dynamic performance. Artificial Neural Network (ANN) controllers have been widely used for TIM speed control for several reasons such as their ability to successfully train without prior knowledge of the mathematical model, their learning ability, and their fast implementation speed. The SVR-based controller overcomes the drawbacks of the ANN-based controller, i.e. its low accuracy, overfitting, and poor generalization ability. The speed response under the proposed controller is faster in terms of rising and settling time. The dynamic speed response of the proposed controller is also superior to that of the ANN-PI controller. The performance of the proposed controller was compared for TIM speed control with an ANN-PI controller via simulations in SIMULINK.

Keywords- three-phase induction motor; indirect vector control; ANN controller; SVR controller

I. INTRODUCTION

Its simple structure, inexpensive, and good robustness have made the Three-phase Induction Motor (TIM) a most attractive choice [1, 2] for industrial applications. In high performance speed control of the TIM, the Indirect Vector Control (IVC) method is extensively used. The IVC method of speed control has been preferred due to its good dynamic performance [3, 4]. ANN research has been increasing fast since the '80s [5]. ANN-based controllers are widely used for the speed control of the TIM. The ANNs have the capability to map non-linear dependencies in the data without using any preconceptions. Their ability to successfully train without prior knowledge of

the mathematical model and load variations are their main advantages [6, 7]. However, ANN controllers have some drawbacks such as: low accuracy, poor generalization ability, and overfitting [8]. A Support Vector Regression (SVR) -based controller can overcome the drawbacks of the ANN controller with superior generalization ability. It has high accuracy and good performance despite the small training samples [9, 10].

Recently, the SVR technique has been applied in the field of electrical engineering. M. Pellegrini proposed a technique based on SVR for short-term load forecasting in smart grids and concluded that the SVR can predict load demand more accurately than the ANN [11]. Authors in [12] proposed an SVR model for predicting the electricity consumption and concluded that the proposed model predicts the electricity consumption with higher accuracy than the ANN model. Authors in [13] proposed an SVR based dynamic behavioral model for RF power amplifiers. The obtained results show that the SVR model gives an improved performance and predicts the behavior of power amplifier more accurately than the ANN model. Authors in [14] presented solar power forecasting using SVR and ANN and concluded that the best solar power forecast is obtained with the SVR model. Authors in [15] developed an SVR model for the prediction of light energy consumption. The obtained results showed that the proposed model outperformed the ANN model [15]. Authors in [16] presented an SVR-based behavioral model for RF power transistors. The obtained results suggested that the SVR based approach is more efficient and overcomes the overfitting issue of the ANN-based approach. The reason for choosing SVR over ANNs is that it is based on the structural risk minimization principle that minimizes the generalization errors, rather than minimizing the errors on the training data as is the case of the ANNs [17].

Corresponding author: Noor Hussain Mugheri

II. THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Different controllers have been developed to control the speed of TIM as PI [18, 19], Fuzzy-PI [20-22], ANNs [23-25], ANN-PI [26], Fuzzy-Neuro [27, 28] and Support Vector Machine (SVM) [29]. This paper presents a new PI-SVR controller technique for speed tracking of TIM based on IVC. For the first time, the SVR-PI controller is successfully developed and implemented for TIM speed control using the IVC. Here, the Radial Basis Function (RBF) is used as the kernel function. The proposed controller approach has the advantages of having very fast response, superior dynamic performance, and higher stability. Figure 1 depicts the block diagram of the suggested framework. An Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT) inverter converts the DC voltage to AC voltage and variable frequency. The TIM is fed by the PWM inverter. The TIM provides feedback signals to the SVR-PI controller. The speed control approach employed here is IVC, which is a dynamic and reliable control method.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed framework.

III. THE ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK CONTROLLER

An ANN-PI controller was developed for TIM speed control. Figure 2 depicts the SIMULINK model of the ANN-PI controller.

Fig. 2. The ANN-PI TIM controller.

Figure 3 depicts the construction of the developed ANN controller. The hidden layer uses a logarithmic sigmoid activation function and the output uses a linear activation function.

Fig. 3. The ANN controller developed in SIMULINK. (a) Internal layers, (b) weight and bias of the first layer, (c) weight and bias of the second layer.

IV. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE FOR REGRESSION

SVM is a machine learning technique that can be used for classification and regression analysis. When SVM is used for regression analysis, it is termed as SVR [30-32]. SVR is considered as a non-parametric technique because it depends on kernel functions. In linear epsilon-intensive SVR (ϵ -SVR), the training data set comprises of the observed response values and the predictor variables. The aim is to determine a function $f(x)$ that deviates from y_n by no more than ϵ for each training point x and simultaneously is as even as possible [33]. Here, the RBF used as the kernel function. This paper for the first time presents a modern performing SVR-PI controller. The trained SVR calculates the output according to the reference constant speed. Then the output of the trained SVR is added to the PI output. It makes the TIM speed response faster and stable. Table I shows the epsilon, sigma and C parameters for SVR. Epsilon denotes the epsilon-insensitive loss function, sigma is the RBF kernel, and C is the upper limit of double problem variable alpha. Figure 4 depicts the simulation in SIMULINK of the SVR-PI controller.

TABLE I. SVR PARAMETERS

Parameters	ϵ	σ	C
Values	10^{-6}	0.6	10^4

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The TIM was built using the asynchronous machine block in SIMULINK. The complete simulation in SIMULINK of the TIM speed control using IVC is shown in Figure 5. The three-phase induction motor is fed by the three-phase inverter that is built using a universal bridge block. The TIM drives a mechanical load characterized by inertia, friction coefficient,

and load torque. The speed control loop produces the quadrature-axis current reference that controls the TIM speed using the SVR based controller. Originally, the three phase induction motor is at standstill without load. Then the load is increased from 0 to 200Nm. Simulations were carried out on

both controllers. The simulated results of the SVR controller were compared with the results of the ANN controller. Table II summarizes the simulation results of the ANN-PI and SVR-PI controllers.

Fig. 4. The three-phase induction motor controller using SVR-PI.

Fig. 5. The complete simulation in SIMULINK of the IVC based TIM speed controller.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Load (Nm)	Controller	Settling time (s)	Overshoot (%)	Rise time (s)
0	ANN-PI	0.567	0	0.508
	SVR-PI	0.408	0	0.367
50	ANN-PI	0.684	0	0.613
	SVR-PI	0.475	0	0.417
100	ANN-PI	0.861	0	0.772
	SVR-PI	0.541	0	0.487
150	ANN-PI	1.161	0	1.041
	SVR-PI	0.647	0	0.581
200	ANN-PI	1.782	0	1.596
	SVR-PI	0.810	0	0.718

Figure 6 shows that the SVR-PI controller has better performance than the ANN-PI controller. The settling time and rise time of SVR-PI controller are smaller than the ANN-PI controller's.

Fig. 6. No load response of the TIM.

Fig. 7. Speed response of the TIM at 50Nm load.

Figure 7 shows that the SVR controller gives better settling time and faster response than the ANN-PI controller. As shown in Figure 8, the motor reaches the reference speed faster when using the SVR-PI controller. When we use the ANN controller for a load of 150Nm, it will increase rise time and settling time. On the other hand, as illustrated in Figure 9, the proposed controller performs better with less settling and rise time.

Fig. 8. Speed response of the TIM at 100Nm load.

Fig. 9. Speed response of the TIM at 150Nm load.

Fig. 10. Speed response of the TIM at 200Nm load.

We used the ANN controller for a large load of 200Nm as shown in Figure 10. We see that the system suffers from high settling time of 1.782s and high rise time of 1.596s, while the SVR controller takes only 0.810s to stabilize and has a rise time of 0.718s. To study the TIM dynamic performance, a step change in load torque and a step change in reference speed are employed. Figures 11 and 12 show the dynamic response of the TIM. Due to the huge increase in load, the ANN controller

does not settle down at a required initial and final speed steps. The SVR controller settles down at the initial and final reference speed step of 100rad/s and 160rad/s without undershoot and with small settling and rise times. These results indicate that the SVR controller gives a robust and superior dynamic performance.

Fig. 11. Dynamic speed response of the TIM with the final speed reference at 160rad/s at $t=0.4s$ and a 300Nm load at $t=1.6s$ with SVR and ANN controllers.

Fig. 12. Dynamic speed response of the TIM with the initial speed reference at 100rad/s at $t=0.4s$ and a 300Nm load at $t=1.6s$ with SVR and ANN controllers.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents for the first time the use of SVR with PI controller for TIM speed control using IVC. This method combines the advantages of the SVR technique and the conventional PI controller to further improve the TIM speed response. The IVC is widely used for speed control due to its simple configuration. The controller was successfully developed and simulated in MATLAB/SIMULINK. The ANN controller offer no % OS due to its self-learning ability. The proposed controller was tested at different load torque values and had less rise time and faster settling time than the ANN controller. The simulation results suggested that the SVR controller is generally more effective and performs faster. The proposed controller improves greatly the dynamic performance.

On the other hand, the dynamic performance of the ANN controller is poor.

APPENDIX

TIM Electrical Parameters

3 Phases, Poles = 4, P = 50hp, $N_s=1800\text{rpm}$
Voltage = 460V, F = 60Hz
$R_s = 0.087\Omega$, $R_r = 0.227\Omega$
$L_s = 0.8\text{mH}$, $L_r = 0.8\text{mH}$
$L_m = 34.7\text{Mh}$
$J = 1.662\text{Kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Abdel Menaem, M. Elgamal, A.-H. Abdel-Aty, E. E. Mahmoud, Z. Chen, and M. A. Hassan, "A Proposed ANN-Based Acceleration Control Scheme for Soft Starting Induction Motor," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 4253–4265, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3046848>.
- [2] N. H. Mugheri and M. U. Keerio, "An Optimal Fuzzy Logic-based PI Controller for the Speed Control of an Induction Motor using the V/F Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7399–7404, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4255>.
- [3] M. A. Hannan, J. A. Ali, P. J. Ker, A. Mohamed, M. S. H. Lipu, and A. Hussain, "Switching Techniques and Intelligent Controllers for Induction Motor Drive: Issues and Recommendations," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 47489–47510, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2867214>.
- [4] A. Bounab, A. Chaiba, and S. Belkacem, "Evaluation of the High Performance Indirect Field Oriented Controlled Dual Induction Motor Drive Fed by a Single Inverter using Type-2 Fuzzy Logic Control," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6301–6308, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3799>.
- [5] S. K. Rani and S. Prabhakaran, "ANN Based DC Link Control of STATCOM in Wind Integrated Distribution System for Power Quality Conditioning," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 5896–5902, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3630>.
- [6] Md. A. Rafiq, Md. Habibullah, and B. C. Ghosh, "Artificial Neural Network based speed tracking of a field oriented induction motor drive," in *2012 7th International Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Dec. 2012, pp. 315–318, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICECE.2012.6471549>.
- [7] J. Bača, D. Kouřil, P. Palacký, and J. Strossa, "Induction motor drive with field-oriented control and speed estimation using feedforward neural network," in *2020 21st International Scientific Conference on Electric Power Engineering (EPE)*, Prague, Czech Republic, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EPE51172.2020.9269215>.
- [8] D. Xinhui, W. Liang, S. Jiancheng, and Z. Yan, "Application of Neural Network and Support Vector Machines to Power System Short-term Load Forecasting," in *2010 International Conference on Computational Aspects of Social Networks*, Taiyuan, China, Sep. 2010, pp. 729–732, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CASoN.2010.167>.
- [9] G. Mitchell, S. Bahadoorsingh, N. Ramsamooj, and C. Sharma, "A comparison of artificial neural networks and support vector machines for short-term load forecasting using various load types," in *2017 IEEE Manchester PowerTech*, Manchester, UK, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PTC.2017.7980814>.
- [10] G. I. S. Ruas, T. A. C. Bragatto, M. V. Lamar, A. R. Aoki, and S. M. de Rocco, "Electrical energy demand prediction using Artificial Neural Networks and Support Vector Regression," in *2008 3rd International Symposium on Communications, Control and Signal Processing*, Saint Julian's, Malta, Mar. 2008, pp. 1431–1435, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCCSP.2008.4537451>.
- [11] M. Pellegrini, "Short-term load demand forecasting in Smart Grids using support vector regression," in *2015 IEEE 1st International Forum on Research and Technologies for Society and Industry Leveraging a better*

- tomorrow (RTSI), Turin, Italy, Sep. 2015, pp. 264–268, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RTSI.2015.7325108>.
- [12] G. Oğcu, O. F. Demirel, and S. Zaim, "Forecasting Electricity Consumption with Neural Networks and Support Vector Regression," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 58, pp. 1576–1585, Oct. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.1144>.
- [13] J. Cai, C. Yu, L. Sun, S. Chen and J. B. King, "Dynamic Behavioral Modeling of RF Power Amplifier Based on Time-Delay Support Vector Regression," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 533–543, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2018.2884414>.
- [14] A. Fentis, L. Bahatti, M. Mestari, and B. Chouri, "Short-term solar power forecasting using Support Vector Regression and feed-forward NN," in *2017 15th IEEE International New Circuits and Systems Conference (NEWCAS)*, Jun. 2017, pp. 405–408, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NEWCAS.2017.8010191>.
- [15] D. Liu and Q. Chen, "Prediction of building lighting energy consumption based on support vector regression," in *2013 9th Asian Control Conference (ASCC)*, Istanbul, Turkey, Jun. 2013, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ASCC.2013.6606376>.
- [16] J. Cai, J. King, C. Yu, J. Liu and L. Sun, "Support Vector Regression-Based Behavioral Modeling Technique for RF Power Transistors," *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 428–430, May 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LMWC.2018.2819427>.
- [17] M. K. Azad, S. Uddin, and M. Takruri, "Support vector regression based electricity peak load forecasting," in *2018 11th International Symposium on Mechatronics and its Applications (ISMA)*, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates, Mar. 2018, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISMA.2018.8330143>.
- [18] G. A. Olarinoye, C. Akinropo, G. J. Atuman, and Z. M. Abdullahi, "Speed Control of a Three Phase Induction Motor using a PI Controller," in *2019 2nd International Conference of the IEEE Nigeria Computer Chapter (NigeriaComputConf)*, Zaria, Nigeria, Oct. 2019, pp. 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NigeriaComputConf45974.2019.8949624>.
- [19] A. E. Mansuri, "Adjustable Speed Drive of Asynchronous Machine Using Volt/Hz amp; PI Technique," in *2018 IEEE International Students' Conference on Electrical, Electronics and Computer Science (SCEECS)*, Bhopal, India, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SCEECS.2018.8546917>.
- [20] D. Asija, "Speed control of induction motor using fuzzy-PI controller," in *2010 2nd International Conference on Mechanical and Electronics Engineering*, Kyoto, Japan, Aug. 2010, vol. 2, pp. 460–463, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMEE.2010.5558463>.
- [21] B. Sahu, K. B. Mohanty, and S. Pati, "A comparative study on fuzzy and PI speed controllers for field-Oriented induction motor drive," in *2010 Modern Electric Power Systems*, Wroclaw, Poland, Sep. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IECR.2010.5720134>.
- [22] B. N. Kar, K. B. Mohanty, and M. Singh, "Indirect vector control of induction motor using fuzzy logic controller," in *2011 10th International Conference on Environment and Electrical Engineering*, Rome, Italy, May 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEEIC.2011.5874782>.
- [23] F. Lftisi, G. H. George, A. Aktaibi, C. B. Butt and M. A. Rahman, "Artificial neural network based speed controller for induction motors," *IECON 2016 - 42nd Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, 2016, pp. 2708–2713, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2016.7793117.
- [24] S. A. R. Kashif, M. A. Saqib, S. Zia, and A. Kaleem, "Implementation of neural network based Space Vector Pulse Width Modulation inverter-induction motor drive system," in *2009 Third International Conference on Electrical Engineering*, Lahore, Pakistan, Apr. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEE.2009.5173177>.
- [25] W. Wasusatein, S. Nittayawan, and W. Kongprawechnon, "Speed Control Under Load Uncertainty of Induction Motor Using Neural Network Auto-Tuning PID Controller," in *2018 International Conference on Embedded Systems and Intelligent Technology International Conference on Information and Communication Technology for Embedded Systems (ICESIT-ICICTES)*, Khon Kaen, Thailand, May 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICESIT-ICICTES.2018.8442062>.
- [26] N. M. A. E. Mahmoud, M. M. Abdu, M. S. Moustafa and S. F. Saraya, "Speed control of three phase induction motor using neural network," *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)*, vol. 16, no. 5, May 2018.
- [27] J. Ko, J. Choi, and D. Chung, "Hybrid Artificial Intelligent Control for Speed Control of Induction motor," in *2006 SICE-ICASE International Joint Conference*, Busan, South Korea, Oct. 2006, pp. 678–683, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SICE.2006.315623>.
- [28] L. Yi and P. Yonghong, "Application of fuzzy neural network in the speed control system of induction motor," in *2011 IEEE International Conference on Computer Science and Automation Engineering*, Shanghai, China, Jun. 2011, vol. 3, pp. 673–677, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSAE.2011.5952765>.
- [29] Z. Shao, "Support vector machine-based fuzzy self-learning control for induction machines," in *2010 International Conference on Computer and Communication Technologies in Agriculture Engineering*, Chengdu, China, Jun. 2010, vol. 3, pp. 12–16, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCTAE.2010.5543140>.
- [30] K. Leauprasert, T. Suwanasri, C. Suwanasri, and N. Poonnoy, "Intelligent Machine Learning Techniques for Condition Assessment of Power Transformers," in *2020 International Conference on Power, Energy and Innovations (ICPEI)*, Chiangmai, Thailand, Oct. 2020, pp. 65–68, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPEI49860.2020.9431460>.
- [31] P. Qun, W. Lin, and Z. Yan-bin, "Wireless communication reliability prediction based on Support Vector Regression," in *2010 3rd International Conference on Advanced Computer Theory and Engineering (ICACTE)*, Chengdu, China, Aug. 2010, vol. 4, pp. 603–606, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICACTE.2010.5579094>.
- [32] V. Vapnik, *The Nature of Statistical Learning Theory*, New York, NY, USA: Springer-Verlag, 1995.
- [33] S. Kavitha, S. Varuna, and R. Ramya, "A comparative analysis on linear regression and support vector regression," in *2016 Online International Conference on Green Engineering and Technologies (IC-GET)*, Coimbatore, India, Nov. 2016, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/GET.2016.7916627>.

Evaluating the Performance Parameters of Cryptographic Algorithms for IOT-based Devices

Umar Iftikhar

Computer and Information Systems Engineering Dept.
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan

Maria Waqas

Computer and Information Systems Engineering Dept.
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan

Kashif Asrar

Computer and Information Systems Engineering Dept.
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan

Syed Abbas Ali

Computer and Information Systems Engineering Dept.
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan

Abstract-Nowadays, terabytes of digital data are generated and sent online every second. However, securing this extent of information has always been a challenging task. Cryptography is a fundamental method for securing data, as it makes data unintelligible for attackers, offering privacy to authorized clients. Different cryptographic algorithms have different speeds and costs that make them suitable for different applications. For instance, banking applications need outrageous security amenities, as they utilize superior algorithms having greater requirements, while gaming applications focus more on speed and cost reduction. Consequently, cryptographic algorithms are chosen based on a client's prerequisites. This study compared DES, AES, Blowfish, and RSA, examining their speed, cost, and performance, and discussed their adequacy for use in wireless sensor networks and peer-to-peer communication.

Keywords-DES; AES; Blowfish; RSA

I. INTRODUCTION

Cryptography is the study of utilizing math to conceal messages and has been around since the inception of human civilizations. From the hand-ciphers used thousands of years ago, to electronic ciphers used in modern commercial applications and war, mankind utilized cryptography to ensure the secrecy of information. The advance of programmable computers necessitated more complex cryptographic algorithms and expanded their application domain to secure data confidentiality and integrity, user authentication, and prevention of cyber-attacks [1]. Today, there is a wide variety of powerful encryption algorithms, offering different combinations of speed, security, and computational resources. All efforts in this area converge to the single goal of making the encryption secure at the best cost to performance ratio [2-6]. Cryptographic algorithms are characterized as symmetric or asymmetric, depending on the keys they utilize.

Data Encryption Standard (DES) was developed in the '70s and is considered to be the pioneer symmetric algorithm, using fixed key lengths. Its most prominent successors are Triple-

DES (3DES) and Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), with the latter being the most preferred today. Blowfish is another popular symmetric scheme that uses variable key length, while River Ciphers also belong in this group. In the asymmetric category, Rivest-Shamir and Adleman (RSA) and Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) are the undisputed kings [7]. Many researchers investigated these strategies to track down the best in terms of execution cost [2-21]. Authors in [10] compared the strengths and weaknesses of each algorithm. They compared experimentally the most significant encryption algorithms on metrics like memory usage, time consumption, and the avalanche effect, concluding that each one has a separate set of domain-wise strengths. Blowfish was the most economical in terms of time and memory usage, AES had the most cryptographic strength, and DES was the most bandwidth-efficient.

This study extends the analysis with exclusive emphasis on decryption efficiency, as it can be a useful factor for selecting an encryption algorithm in certain domains. Additionally, these algorithms were examined for their adequacy on wireless sensor networks and peer-to-peer communication.

II. THE INVESTIGATED AND IMPLEMENTED CRYPTOGRAPHY ALGORITHMS

During this study the DES, AES, RSA, and Blowfish algorithms were implemented in Java. The source code used for the evaluation of each algorithm including its description, methodology, and execution pattern is exhibited along with the block diagrams of the main functions of each algorithm.

A. DES

DES is based on symmetric key square code and uses a 56-bit key in 64-bit blocks [7]. DES has 16 phases, also named as rounds [2], and uses the following functions:

- A zor function that takes a stream and generates an integer result

- The En_box function that generates an array
- The S_box that takes a 48-bit input and returns a 32 bit output
- The f_permute that uses a loop to return permuted data
- The fn_function that uses xor to return a xorstream
- A user_input function to get key bits and data bits

Fig. 1. DES sub-key generation.

The function definitions are:

```
def zor(left,xorstream):
xorresult = np.logical_xor(left,xorstream)
xorresult = xorresult.astype(int)
return zorresult
```

```
def En_box(right_data):
expanded_data = np.empty_data(48)
j = 0
for i in EBox:
expanded_data[j] = right[i-1]
j+=1
expanded_data = list(map(int,expanded_data))
expanded_data = np.array(expanded_data)
return expanded_data
```

```
def f_permute(topermute):
permuted_data= np.empty_data(32)
e = 0
```

for f in F_PBox:

```
permuted_data[j] = topermute[f-1]
e+=1
```

return permuted_data

```
def fn_function(right_data,rkey):
expanded_data = E_box(right_data)
xored = xor(expanded_data,rkey)
sboxed = sbox(xored)
xorstream = f_permute(sboxed)
return xorstream
```


Fig. 2. DES block diagram.

Fig. 3. DES round block diagram.

Fig. 4. DES function block diagram.

B. AES

AES is a symmetric key square code algorithm that was developed as a replacement for DES. AES utilizes three key sizes of 128, 192, and 256 bits, and uses 128-bit blocks that can be encrypted in one go, as it is much faster than DES. Encryption and decryption in AES are performed in multiple rounds. The number of rounds used for the encryption or decryption varies with the key size between 10, 12, and 14 for 128, 192, and 256 keys respectively. AES consists of 3 steps that contain different combinations of specified operations [4]. The step by step procedure for AES algorithm is:

- Initialize the constructor function
- Change_of_key uses a text to matrix function along with a control structure to generate a list of round keys
- The encryption gets a plain state from text to matrix and returns the matrix to text
- The decryption gets the cipher state object and uses multiple returns matrix to text
- round_key_addition, _rounding_ encrypt, and a few more functions are used to generate the final output

The function definitions are:

```
def text_to_matrix(text_data):
    matrix_data = []
    for e in range(16):
        byte = (text >> (8 * (15 - e))) & 0xFF
        if e % 4 == 0:
```

```
matrix_data.append([byte_data])
    else:
        matrix_data[e / 4].append(byte_data)
    return matrix_data
def matrix_to_text(matrix_data):
    text_data = 0
    for e in range(4):
        for f in range(4):
            text |= (matrix_data [e][f] << (120 - 8 * (4 * e + f)))
    return text
def round_key_addition(self, r, k):
    for e in range(4):
        for f in range(4):
            s[e][f] ^= k[e][f]
```


Fig. 5. AES block diagram.

```
def rounding_encrypt(self, state_matrix_data,
key_matrix_data):
    self.__sub_bytes_data(state_matrix_data)
    self.__shift_rows_data(state_matrix_data)
    self.__mix_columns_data(state_matrix_data)
    self.__add_round_key_data(state_matrix_data,
key_matrix_data)
```

The encryption steps are:

- ADD ROUND KEY: Data are straightforwardly XORed with the round key or the code key of 128 pieces.
- SUB BYTES: Breaks the input into bytes and then passes it via a substitution box. Unlike DES, AES has the same s-box for all bytes. Returns a 4×4 matrix.
- SHIFT ROWS: The rows of the obtained matrix from the sub bytes are shifted left. Since it's a 4×4 network, the fourth column is moved threefold, the third is moved twice, the second is shifted once, and the first remains unshifted. Hence, each n-th row will be shifted (n-1) times.
- MIX COLUMNS: Interchanges the columns via a mathematical function to get the output.

The above steps may be applied in reverse to get the deciphered text.

C. RSA

RSA was named after its 3 donors, Rivest–Shamir–Adelman. The key length must be greater than 1024 bits and the plain text to encrypt must be at least 512 bits. Since it utilizes mathematic prime number calculations, it has very high encryption and decryption times and consumes a lot of computational power [20]. The private key is generated in the PKCS#8 format, whereas the public key uses the X.509 format.

Fig. 6. RSA encryption.

The step by step procedure of RSA is:

- Two large prime numbers are selected
- A pair of public and private keys is generated.
- The user enters a message to be encrypted

- The encrypt_data_message function takes two arguments (public key and message) to generate the encrypted text.
- The private key can be used to decrypt the data message.

Fig. 7. RSA decryption.

Fig. 8. RSA key generation.

The function definitions are:

```
def encrypt_data_message(pk, plaintext):
    key, n = p_k
    cipher_text = [pow(ord(char), key, n) for char in plaintext]
    return cipher_text

def decrypt_data_message(pk, cipher_text):
    key, n = p_k
    aux = [str(pow(char, key, n)) for char in cipher_text]
    plain = [chr(int(char2)) for char2 in aux]
    return join(plain)
```

D. Blowfish

Blowfish is a symmetric key square code with a variable key length from 32 to 448 bits and a block size of 64 bits. Blowfish is faster than DES and is considered a promising encryption algorithm. Blowfish's advantages are its speed, the fewer memory requirements, whereas it is straightforward and more secure as it uses variable key length [5]. Blowfish is a block cipher having a variable order_of_byte which finds out the number of bytes and uses the big-endian byte order. The functions Per_array and Sub_boxes are used to define array and substitute boxes. Two static methods are used, namely data_encrypt and data_decrypt, to get the encrypted and decrypted data.

The function definitions are:

```
def data_encrypt(L, R, P, S1, S2, S3, S4, u4_1_pack,
u1_4_unpack):
    for p1, p2 in P[:-1]:
        L ^= p1
        a, b, c, d = u1_4_unpack(u4_1_pack(L))
        R ^= (S1[a] + S2[b] ^ S3[c]) + S4[d] & 0xffffffff
        R ^= p2
        a, b, c, d = u1_4_unpack(u4_1_pack(R))
        L ^= (S1[a] + S2[b] ^ S3[c]) + S4[d] & 0xffffffff
        p_penultimate, p_last = P[-1]
    return R ^ p_last, L ^ p_penultimate

def data_decrypt(L, R, P, S1, S2, S3, S4, u4_1_pack,
u1_4_unpack):
    for p2, p1 in P[:0:-1]:
        L ^= p1
        a, b, c, d = u1_4_unpack(u4_1_pack(L))
        R ^= (S1[a] + S2[b] ^ S3[c]) + S4[d] & 0xffffffff
        R ^= p2
        a, b, c, d = u1_4_unpack(u4_1_pack(R))
        L ^= (S1[a] + S2[b] ^ S3[c]) + S4[d] & 0xffffffff
```

```
p_first, p_second = P[0]
```

```
return R ^ p_first, L ^ p_second
```

```
def __init__(self, key, byte_order = "large", P_array =
PI_P_ARRAY, S_boxes = PI_S_BOXES):
```

1) Sub-Key Generation

Keys should be ready before data encryption or decryption. The variable-length key is produced using $K_1, K_2, K_3 \dots K_n$, where $[1 \leq n \leq 14]$ and every K has 32-bits. Key length can be anything from 32 to 448 bits. The P-array has eighteen 32-cycle sub-keys: P1, P2... P18. Four S-boxes or replacement boxes are used, each having 256 entries, and all 256 elements are of 32bits.

```
S1 → S0, S1, ... S255
```

```
S2 → S0, S1, ... S255
```

```
S3 → S0, S1, ... S255
```

```
S4 → S0, S1, ... S255
```

The sub-keys are produced as:

- Instate the P-exhibit and four S-boxes with a static string. This string contains the hexadecimal digits of π .
- The main component in the P-exhibit (P1) is XORed with the initial 32 pieces of the key K_1 , the second component in the P-cluster (P2) is XORed with the second 32 pieces of the key K_2 . Rehash until every P-cluster component is XORed with the key pieces.
- Encode every string by blowfish encryption calculation utilizing the sub keys from P1 to P18.
- Change P1 and P2 with the yield of the third step.
- Utilize the adjusted sub keys to encode the yield of the third step.
- Change P3 and P4 with the yield of the fifth step. This interaction proceeds until the whole of the P-cluster is changed.

2) Data Encryption

The following steps are used for data encryption in the Blowfish algorithm:

- The 64-bit plain content is isolated into two sections, left 32-bit and right 32-bit.
- The left 32-bit is XORed with P1 and the yield is shipped off. Blowfish Function F is additionally utilized as right 32-digit for the next round
- The yield of capacity F is XORed with the right 32-digit and the result is utilized as the left 32-bit of the next round.
- This cycle is continued for 18 rounds, and the left and right output of round 18 are joined to give a 64-bit figure text.

3) Blowfish Function

Blowfish Function (F) uses the following process:

- The 32-bit input is divided into four 8-bit data, one for each S-box.
- The S-boxes substitute 8-bit data into 32-bits.
- The output of the first two S-boxes is added.
- The result of the third step is XORed with the output of S-box 3.
- The result of the fourth step is added to the yield of S-box 4.
- The result of the fifth step is the final output.

Fig. 9. Blowfish block diagram.

Fig. 10. Blowfish function F block diagram.

III. EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Each encryption strategy has advantages and disadvantages. Specific details, such as speed and cost requirements, should be examined before choosing an appropriate cryptographic algorithm for an application. This section describes the parameters used to evaluate those algorithms.

A. Encryption Time

Encryption time is the time needed to transform a plaintext to ciphertext and depends on three parameters: key size, plaintext block size, and mode. In this study, encryption time was estimated in milliseconds (ms). Encryption time impacts a framework's implementation, as shorter encryption time makes the framework more quick and responsive.

B. Decryption Time

Decryption time is the time needed to convert ciphertext into plaintext. Like encryption time, shorter decryption time increases a framework's responsiveness and speed. Decryption time is also measured in ms.

C. Memory Used

Each algorithm requires a different amount of memory space to execute. The memory size needed depends upon the number and kind of calculations, key size, and presentation vectors and affects system's cost.

D. Avalanche Effect

A desirable property of cryptographic algorithms is when a slight change in input changes the output significantly. This property is called dissemination or torrential slide impact. This is assessed using hamming distance, via the following equation:

$$\text{Avalanche effect} = \text{hamming distance} \div \text{file size} \quad (1)$$

E. Entropy

Irregularity or vulnerability is a significant property in cryptography since data should not be speculated by an attacker. Entropy is a measure of irregularity in data. Higher entropy is essential for a more intricate connection between key and ciphertext. This property is called disarray and is determined by Shannon's formula.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The encryption and decryption algorithms of AES, DES, RSA, and Blowfish algorithms were implemented in Java. Java has packages that provide extensive support for AES and DES. Three parameters were identified for each algorithm: memory used in KBs, encryption and decryption times in ms. Four different plain texts were used for each algorithm.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Encryption Time

The result comparison is exhibited in Figure 11. It can be noticed that Blowfish has the shortest encryption time.

B. Decryption Time

As it can be noted from Figure 12, decryption time is generally lesser than encryption time, while the RSA

decryption requires longer and the Blowfish requires lesser time.

Fig. 11. Encryption time in ms for each algorithm.

Fig. 12. Encryption time in ms for each algorithm.

C. Memory Used

Memory utilization specifies the memory usage in both the encryption and decryption processes. Figure 13 shows that RSA consumed more memory, due to its longer key length and two-step process nature, as it generated a pair of public and private keys before encryption.

Fig. 13. Memory used by each algorithm.

Fig. 14. Memory used in encryption by each algorithm.

The decryption memory usage comes to be negligible (almost 0) when compared to encryption. The snapshots in

Figures 15-19 show the outputs observed after encrypting and decrypting a text.

```
encrypted text is /aJkmv+ssalaI3Um/1UUp92VTtkrduRc5u2hoXzUWrpxHCd+URiL7zkKvWzMyMnwDY0f
decrypted text is Cryptography is an integral part of modern world
```

Fig. 15. AES algorithm output.

```
Message
Encrypted Data
Ss*a.0µp8g,i+IAPqefYv<4@jag□□A2□□...J-iB*4A@□□□cA%{90'A%4yl+.%□□)0□□É□-0-t□-):0
Message
Decrypted Data
Cryptography is an integral part of modern world information security making the virtual wor
```

Fig. 16. DES algorithm output.

```
Public key is MIGfMA0GCSqGSIb3DQEBAQUAA4GNADCBiQKBgQCU7aSW2f8ORwGj5H5pnuA25pbTCqWFLDQyqOpGYH:
Private key is MIICdgIBADANBgkqhkiG9w0BAQEFAASCAMAwggJcAgEAAoGBAJTtpJbZ/w6HaaFkfmnC4BnmltMRp:
```

Fig. 17. RSA key generation step.

```
Encrypted text is LadTmuQ9rYCC0bMjtILE3QG4ldFmyl10XkBZ+6wTirOu3mN/Eq4ZDDI
decrypted text is Cryptography is an integral part
```

Fig. 18. RSA output.

```
your encrypted data is k+Hmpr0tC/gylrwRU+YSzUHJMRxQONLtaxDy5eHO595
your decrypted text is Cryptography is an integral pa
```

Fig. 19. Blowfish output.

VI. CONCLUSION

Every cryptographic algorithm has its strengths and weaknesses. RSA is comparatively costly in terms of time and power consumption. Blowfish is effective for applications that require fast and secure communication, as it has lesser encryption and decryption times. AES is a very secure algorithm with a tradeoff of more memory usage and encryption time, whereas DES has a lesser memory footprint. Moreover, since decryption time is considerably lesser than encryption time, it requires less computational power making it highly effective in electronic devices having power consumption and battery life as crucial parameters [21]. For example, the control signals sent to sensors in wireless sensor networks that must be encrypted to avoid attacking or eavesdropping [6]. Since those sensors' operation depends heavily on battery life, decryption algorithms can be used without significantly increasing power consumption or memory usage.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Patil, P. Narayankar, D. G. Narayan, and S. M. Meena, "A Comprehensive Evaluation of Cryptographic Algorithms: DES, 3DES, AES, RSA and Blowfish," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 78, pp. 617–624, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.02.108>.
- [2] A. Jeeva, D. V. Palanisamy, and K. Kanagaram, "Comparative Analysis of Performance Efficiency and Security Measures of some Encryption Algorithms," *International Journal of Engineering Research and*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 3033–3037, May 2012.
- [3] H. O. Alanazi, B. B. Zaidan, A. A. Zaidan, H. A. Jalab, M. Shabbir, and Y. Al-Nabhani, "New Comparative Study Between DES, 3DES and AES within Nine Factors," vol. 2, no. 3, p. 6, Mar. 2010.

- [4] R. Tripathi and S. Agrawal, "Comparative Study of Symmetric and Asymmetric Cryptography Techniques," *International Journal of Advanced Foundation and Research in Computer*, vol. 1, no. 6, Jun. 2014.
- [5] M. S. Mahindrakar, "Evaluation of Blowfish Algorithm based on Avalanche Effect," *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 99–103, Jun. 2014.
- [6] R. Pahal, "Efficient Implementation of AES," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, pp. 290–295, Jul. 2013.
- [7] Y. Kumar, R. Munjal, and H. Sharma, "Comparison of Symmetric and Asymmetric Cryptography with Existing Vulnerabilities and Countermeasures," *International Journal of Computer Science and Management Studies*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 60–63, Oct. 2011.
- [8] C. P. Mandal, "Superiority of Blowfish Algorithm," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 9, pp. 196–201, Sep. 2012.
- [9] S. Karthik and A. Muruganandam, "Data Encryption and Decryption by Using Triple DES and Performance Analysis of Crypto System," *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research*, vol. 2, no. 11, pp. 24–31, Nov. 2014.
- [10] G. Prashanti, S. Deepthi, and K. Sandhya Rani, "A Novel Approach for Data Encryption Standard Algorithm," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 264–267, Jun. 2013.
- [11] D. P. Mahajan and A. Sachdeva, "A Study of Encryption Algorithms AES, DES and RSA for Security," *Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, vol. 13, no. 15, Jul. 2013.
- [12] N. Kaur and S. Sodhi, "Data Encryption Standard Algorithm (DES) for Secure Data Transmission," *IJCA Proceedings on International Conference on Advances in Emerging Technology*, vol. ICAET 2016, no. 2, pp. 31–37, Oct. 2016.
- [13] M. R. Asassfeh, M. Qatawneh, and F. M. ALAzzeh, "Performance Evaluation of Blowfish Algorithm on Supercomputer IMAN1," *International journal of Computer Networks & Communications*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 43–53, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.5121/ijcnc.2018.10205>.
- [14] P. Rawat, K. D. Singh, H. Chaouchi, and J. M. Bonnin, "Wireless sensor networks: a survey on recent developments and potential synergies," *The Journal of Supercomputing*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 1–48, Apr. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-013-1021-9>.
- [15] M. A. Al-Shabi, "A Survey on Symmetric and Asymmetric Cryptography Algorithms in information Security," *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 576–589, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.9.03.2019.p8779>.
- [16] D. P. Joseph and M. Krishna, "Cognitive Analytics and Comparison of Symmetric and Asymmetric Cryptography Algorithms," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 51–56, May 2015.
- [17] A. Gupta and N. K. Walia, "Cryptography Algorithms: A Review," *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 1667–1672, 2014.
- [18] S. Kumari, "A research Paper on Cryptography Encryption and Compression Techniques," *International Journal of Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 20915–20919, Apr. 2017.
- [19] J. Thakur and N. Kumar, "DES, AES and Blowfish: Symmetric Key Cryptography Algorithms Simulation Based Performance Analysis," *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 5–12, Dec. 2011.
- [20] E. S. I. Harba, "Secure Data Encryption Through a Combination of AES, RSA and HMAC," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1781–1785, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1272>.
- [21] A. S. Alshammari, "Comparison of a Chaotic Cryptosystem with Other Cryptography Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6187–6190, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3745>.

A Battery Voltage Level Monitoring System for Telecommunication Towers

Rahab Uwamahoro

School of Computational and Communication Sciences and Engineering
The Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology
Arusha, Tanzania

Neema Mduma

School of Computational and Communication Sciences and Engineering
The Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology
Arusha, Tanzania

Dina Machuve

School of Computational and Communication Sciences and Engineering
The Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology
Arusha, Tanzania

Abstract-Voltage fluctuations in batteries form a major challenge the telecommunication towers face. These fluctuations mostly occur due to poor management and the lack of a battery voltage level monitoring system. The current paper presents a battery voltage-level monitoring system to be used in telecommunication towers. The proposed solution is incorporated with a centralized mobile application dashboard for accessing the live data of the installed battery, integrated with voltage-level, current, temperature, fire, and gas sensors. An Arduino Uno microcontroller board is used to process and analyze the collected data from the sensors. The Global Service Message (GSM) module is used to monitor and store data to the cloud. Users are alerted in the case of low voltage, fire, and increase in harmful gases in the tower through Short Message Service (SMS). The experiment was conducted at Ngorongoro and Manyara telecommunication towers. The developed system can be used in accessing battery information remotely while allowing real-time continuous monitoring of battery usage. The proposed battery voltage-level monitoring system contributes to the elimination of battery hazards in towers. Therefore, the proposed battery voltage level monitoring system can be adopted by telecommunication tower engineers for the reduction of voltage fluctuation risks.

Keywords-battery voltage level monitoring; telecommunication towers; renewable energy; GSM sim 8001 module; dashboard

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapidly growing population, technological advancements, and climate change, raise the demand for more energy [1], which is expected to increase the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions in the atmosphere. Global population, for instance, is expected to increase from 7.7 to 9 billion by 2050 [2], whereas, in Sub-Saharan Africa, where Tanzania is located, the population is predicted to double by 2050 [3]. Also, 80% of the 1.4 billion of the global population living in rural areas have inadequate access to electricity [4, 5]. These people not only

have a low life quality but also lack access to technology, which means that they fall under the energy poverty deception category. The instability of the national grid and the low proportion of the population accessing it, makes renewable energy a priority for electrification, especially in Africa, since it is low-cost, user-friendly, and can reduce carbon footprint [6]. Telecom tower companies in Tanzania have found significant reliable use of renewable energy by using solar panels to power their services during power outages and hence enabling a cost-efficient evolution to a low-carbon power system [7]. The advancements in solar energy are increasing in Tanzania [8]. However, solar energy offers efficient production only during the day. This necessitates energy storage in batteries to ensure the continuation of services [9-12].

Telecom towers connect people with their business remotely by accessing the internet and other services. Powering the towers requires a stable energy source for versatile operations. To guarantee their uninterrupted operation, the towers need to depend on renewable energy sources, like solar panels, to eliminate the inconveniences caused by unpredictable power cuts on the national grid [13, 14]. The most serious challenge encountered by telecom towers is the unexpected voltage drops followed by cutoffs that occur without alerting users to act accordingly. This makes the tower services unavailable, thus lowering productivity while putting sensitive electrical equipment at risk. Additionally, the hydrogen gas from batteries affects human health and the environment [15-17]. So, there is a need to monitor and eliminate battery voltage-level changes and other parameters that may pose a threat to public health and safety. Among the factors that have been identified as the primary contributors to voltage fluctuations are the lack of battery data visualization and the big number of devices allocated to be powered by a battery [18]. They, therefore, lack information with regard to when the voltage battery is expected to be low for timely actions. With the technological advancements through the

Corresponding author: Rahab Uwamahoro (uwamahoro@nm-aist.ac.tz)

Internet of Things (IoT), accessing data remotely has been a routine for many companies and individuals. IoT is proved to be fundamental in receiving, controlling, and accessing data remotely and acting accordingly. The technology is also user-friendly and grants real-time data access [19, 20]. Taking advantage of this technological advancement, some studies have been carried out to review, analyze, monitor, and compute data for real-time sensing in different areas [21, 22]. However, most of these studies have only concentrated on monitoring geographical areas and excluded monitoring batteries installed in towers.

Several measuring components have been used to monitor voltage fluctuations in batteries. Voltage changes in batteries have been reviewed to identify battery parameters that can be at risk due to voltage changes in order to improve the economic and sustainable use of their energy [23]. One recent approach included the integration of an Arduino microcontroller board with thermometer, voltmeter, and ammeter sensors through a correlation and regression algorithm to measure the battery's state of charge and estimate its useful remaining life [24]. The study showed that battery estimation on the state of charge, state of health, and discharge rate with its remaining useful life can be derived in real-time. However, this system failed to estimate the remaining voltage of the battery and presented a low real-time data acquisition due to the usage of an SD-card which lacks efficiency in data security. So, there is a need to develop a low-cost, efficient battery voltage-level monitoring system to increase the sustainable utilization of the voltage stored in the battery remotely. Authors in [25] conducted a simulation work on discharging and charging of battery banks for telecom sites in India. Similar work was conducted in [26], again in India, aimed to control the voltage drop of the battery bank. However, these works were limited only on the simulation approach without being tested to real life applications. Authors in [27] presented a review on the methods of monitoring the charging and discharging of batteries connected to renewable energy sources through a centralized controller. However, they took into consideration only the energy supplied to the load without alerting the user on battery discharge and charge. Changes in current, temperature, and the state of health of the battery are considered as the factors affecting the most voltage fluctuation in batteries installed in electric vehicles, which is only beneficial to only a section of battery users [28]. Besides, some studies use high technological methods which turn away most users from adopting them due to their high costs and requirements of high technical skills to operate [29].

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number 7 is to ensure access to modern, affordable, clean, and reliable energy for all by 2030 [30]. However, the previous works have failed to contribute to the accomplishment of this goal. To eliminate these challenges, the present study proposes a low battery voltage level monitoring system that can be beneficial to all battery users in accessing battery information remotely by allowing them to continuously monitor the battery usage in real-time and contribute to the elimination of battery hazards. With this, attention needs to be drawn to a cost-effective and user-friendly battery voltage-level monitoring system. This will contribute to real-time access of information about faults in

batteries and consumption, through a dashboard for the sustainability of usage.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out at 2 towers of Habari Node Public Limited Company which is an Internet Service Provider (ISP) in Arusha, Tanzania. Firstly, coordinates of the towers were measured with GPRS devices, as shown in Table I. The two towers were selected due to their ability to store energy in batteries. Also, they are most affected by voltage fluctuations due to the huge number of users residing far from company offices. The coordinate measurements helped in sending data to the towers accurately without any data loss. Furthermore, the measured coordinates assisted system installation and the testing process in the field.

TABLE I. TOWER LOCATIONS

Location	Coordinates	
	Latitude (LAT)	Longitude (LONG)
Ngorongoro	-3.27544	35.438886
Manyara	-3.37764	35.81857

The voltage levels of the installed batteries and solar panels in the tower were measured. The currents through the batteries and the solar panels were measured manually with a digital AC/DC UNI-T UT890D multimeter. The measurements were conducted on two batteries located in Ngorongoro tower and Manyara tower as shown in Table II. The results present a mix of used and full batteries with different values. Furthermore, their cutoff times were observed based on the voltage stored in the batteries. The measurements helped in the development and real application of the proposed system.

TABLE II. MANUAL MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Battery location	Voltage				Results
	Battery	Solar	Load	Low voltage	Time (hrs)
Ngorongoro	14.8V	20V	0.05	11.88V	6
Manyara	14.5V	20V	0.07	11.8V	4

A. Hardware Integration

After data collection, verification of the hardware part was done using the Proteus simulation software. Figure 1 shows the system overview design in the circuit, which consists of voltage sensor, current sensor, gas sensor, frame sensor, an Arduino Uno microcontroller board, the SIM808 GSM/GPRS/GPS module, a 14.8V to 14.5 V battery for power supply, and a 20V solar panel. Simulations were conducted before the real application of the integrated circuit components to ensure they behaved efficiently. The components were integrated into the Proteus software. Arduino Uno, was selected due to its efficiency to help the development of the proposed low-cost system. It consists of 14 digital input and output pins and 6 analog pins. The voltage sensor which acts as a voltage divider was connected to measure the voltage level of the batteries and solar panels. The GSM module transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) pins were connected to pins 0 and 1 respectively. The fire sensor was connected to pin 2 of the Arduino and the gas sensor was connected to pin 10. Furthermore, two relays were connected, one to allow the voltage from the solar panel to go

to the battery and the other to allow the load to function. The load used was a bubble light, tested at 5V at Ngorongoro and 3V at Manyara. Four Light-Emitting Diode (LED) indicators were used to alert the user if any hazard was happening near the batteries. The red LEDs represent hazard, the blue network connection, the yellow represent the relay, and the green was for power. A long leg pin was connected to pin 10 of the Arduino and set to the output of the GSM module. In real life

system application, a short message notification was used as an alert to the user with the help of the GSM module. The GSM was powered by 12V and the other components were supplied with 5V voltage from the Arduino. After system simulation, the hardware components were integrated for real-life application and their interactions proved the system functionality and its compliance with the requirements. Figure 2 shows the prototype integration of the GSM and the sensors.

Fig. 1. Circuit diagram of the developed system.

Fig. 2. Prototype integration.

B. Calculations

The calculations shown below helped in producing reliable and accurate voltages to the batteries and the solar panels. The values read by the analog pin of the Arduino were converted and the voltage stored in the battery was considered to be the

battery voltage. Let the value to be read by the analog pin be the ADC-Value as shown in (1):

$$ADC\ Voltage\ Value \times \frac{5}{1024} \quad (1)$$

where ADC represents the Analog to Digital Converter, 5 is the reference voltage of the Arduino, and 1024 is the ADC resolution. The formula for calculating the voltage divider is:

$$\frac{R3}{R3+R4} = Ratio \quad (2)$$

The resistances R3 and R4 are presented in Figure 3. R4 in this work was 30KΩ and R3 was 7.5KΩ. Therefore, the voltage divider is 37.5KΩ. The ADC voltage is calculated as shown in (3), (4), and Figure 3.

$$ADC\ voltage = \frac{R3}{R3+R4} \times Battery\ Voltage \quad (3)$$

Therefore:

$$ADC\ voltage = \frac{7.5\ Kilohms}{37.5\ Kilohms} \times Battery\ Voltage \quad (4)$$

From (1), the *ADC-Voltage* is calculated as:

$$ADC \text{ Voltage} = ADC \text{ value} \times 0.00489 \quad (5)$$

Substitution of *ADC-Voltage* in (3) gives (6):

$$ADC \text{ Value} \times 0.0049 = \frac{7.5 \text{ K}\Omega}{37.5 \text{ K}\Omega} \times \text{Battery Voltage} \quad (6)$$

For 0.02444 *ADC-Value*, the *solar-volt* is shown in (7).

$$\text{Solar} - \text{volt} = 0.2445 \times ADC \text{ Value} \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the voltage constant used in the code battery was 0.02499999 and for the solar constant, it was 0.02499989.

Fig. 3. Voltage divider.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section contains the results of the system's tests and analysis. The voltage sensor experiment was recorded to ensure that the circuit was in good working order followed by recording experiments and results used to verify battery voltage fluctuations as shown in Table III. Analysis was conducted for the proposed system and the two batteries located in the respective towers as shown in Figure 4. Their voltage levels and the current from solar panels and the load were successfully measured by the developed system as shown in Table III. Furthermore, the system could measure the humidity of the battery and detect gas and fire near the battery. A 14.8V fully-charged battery which reached 11.86V after usage was used for the Ngorongoro tower and an 11.85V used rechargeable solar battery for the Manyara tower. A voltmeter was used to compare the voltage measured manually with the voltage measured by the system as shown in Table III. The two voltages were found to be the same. This helped to know the voltage level of the batteries before they reached low voltage. The GSM could send SMS notifications to the intended users to act accordingly. The other parameters were monitored similarly. The measurements taken manually with a multimeter showed that the voltage level was different due to the usage of different batteries. Figure 4(a) shows the solar battery used in the experiment, Figure 4(b) shows the prototype testing with a voltmeter, and Figure 4(c) shows the complete prototype with 5V solar lamp as the load and solar panel.

TABLE III. RESULTS FROM THE DEVELOPED SYSTEM

Battery	Voltage results		Current		Humidity	Gas		Fire	
	Multimeter (V)	Voltage sensor	Solar	Load		Detected	Not detected	Detected	Not detected
1	11.86V	11.87V	20V	0.00	Good	No	Yes	No	Yes
2	11.85V	11.86V	20V	0.03	Good	No	Yes	No	Yes

Fig. 4. System testing.

From the multimeter measurements, the value was accurately similar to the one measured using the system as shown in Table III. It can, therefore, be concluded that the voltage sensor provides valid measurement values of the batteries. The other battery parameters were measured to determine whether they could be risky to humans and the environment. Using current as an example, the current sensor load and the DC for which a solar panel was used to charge the batteries were respectively measured. The solar panel was able to charge the battery, the lamp was used as a load, and its current was measured and monitored respectively as shown in Figure 4. Battery voltage data were sent to one centralized mobile application dashboard.

A. The Dashboard Data

Figure 5 shows the final prototype of both systems tested for Ngorongoro and Manyara towers. Data from the sensors were collected and sent to a mobile app dashboard as shown in Figure 6. The battery parameters were updated every 5s, they were stored in the cloud using the ThingsWeb server, and were displayed on the Arduino IDE serial monitor. The actual voltage and current comparison were used to control the voltage level of the battery installed in each tower. The comparison was done based on measuring the actual battery voltage to the remainder, and the current coming from the solar panel to the battery to the actual current. Furthermore, temperature, humidity, fire, and gas were continuously monitored to assess whether they were detected or not. As shown in Figure 6, the screenshot of the app developed for monitoring the batteries shows that the approach was effectively evaluated and met the requirements in instances of live data every 5s. Figure 7 shows the screenshot of a message received as an alert to the user about the low voltage of the battery installed at Ngorongoro tower which enabled the user to turn on the relay. Data were uploaded onto the dashboard and stored on a server. When the load was connected and the solar panel begun to power the battery, the current was efficiently measured by the system as shown in Figure 7. The load charging current was 0.32 since the 5V solar lamp was

connected as the load and the solar panel current was 0.32 as it was charging the low battery. Fire and gas were not detected at the Ngorongoro tower. Furthermore, the system was able to alert the user of the low battery voltage 11.8V at the Ngorongoro tower using a message sent by the GSM project (Figure 7).

Fig. 5. Final prototypes for Manyara and Ngorongoro towers.

Fig. 6. The developed mobile application dashboard.

Fig. 7. Short message alert received from the system installed at Ngorongoro.

B. Discussion

The conducted experiments proved the validity of the status information from batteries located in the telecommunication towers: their voltage and current levels, temperatures, and presence of fire or gas were monitored while the risks of voltage fluctuation were reduced. Figures 6 and 7 show the monitoring and access through the mobile dashboard of the

voltage level and other battery status parameters from the battery located at the Ngorongoro tower. Data processed from the sensor were sent in real-time to the cloud and battery voltage level, current, temperature, fire warning, and gas status were visualized through the mobile app dashboard as shown in Figures 5 and 6.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The current work lays the foundation for the development of a battery voltage level monitoring system for communication towers to ensure suitable battery performance and real-time monitoring. The development of the system consisted of the integration of sensors for battery monitoring devices and a dashboard as a user interface which ensures central monitoring. The system can send information to the administrator dashboard via a cloud server from the related towers using its coordinate locations via the GPRS internet module. An SMS notification is sent to the user as an alert when the battery voltage becomes low. The dashboard allows real-time access and monitoring of the battery status. Future research can add more functionality to the current work, e.g. by adding Ethernet that can be used to improve internet connectivity over GPRS.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank the Center of Excellence for ICT in East African (CENIT@EA), the Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST), Dr. Elizabeth Mkoba from NM-AIST, the industry supervisor Mr. Lomayani Solomon from HABARI NODE PLC in Arusha, and Mr. Judah A. Robert, chief technical officer of Automatenics Technologies Company in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. N. Bhanutej and R. C. Naidu, "A 7-level inverter with less number of switches for grid-tied PV applications," *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering Exploration*, vol. 8, no. 78, pp. 631-642, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.19101/IJATEE.2021.874090>.
- [2] "Growing at a slower pace, world population is expected to reach 9.7 billion in 2050 and could peak at nearly 11 billion around 2100 | UN DESA," *United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs*. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/en/news/population/world-population-prospects-2019.html> (accessed Nov. 06, 2021).
- [3] "Africa's population will double by 2050," *The Economist*, Mar. 26, 2020.
- [4] K. Kaygusuz, "Energy for sustainable development: A case of developing countries," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 1116-1126, Feb. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2011.11.013>.
- [5] "Report: Universal Access to Sustainable Energy Will Remain Elusive Without Addressing Inequalities," Jun. 2021, Accessed: Nov. 06, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://119.78.100.173/C666/handle/2XK7JSWQ/329629>.
- [6] L. Odarno, E. Sawe, M. Swai, M. J. J. Katyega, and A. Lee, *Accelerating Mini-grid Deployment in Sub-Saharan Africa: Lessons from Tanzania*. Washington, DC, USA: World Resources Institutes, 2017.
- [7] R. Kaur, V. Krishnasamy, N. K. Kandasamy, and S. Kumar, "Discrete Multiobjective Grey Wolf Algorithm Based Optimal Sizing and Sensitivity Analysis of PV-Wind-Battery System for Rural Telecom Towers," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 729-737, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSYST.2019.2912899>.

- [8] "TANZANIA: Greenlight energises 1.5 million people with solar kits," *Afrik 21*, Mar. 27, 2020. <https://www.afrik21.africa/en/tanzania-greenlight-energises-1-5-million-people-with-solar-kits/> (accessed Nov. 06, 2021).
- [9] B. Y. Lucien, J. B. Byiringiro, B. W. Abraham, G. B. Aristide, and K. Célestin, "Evaluation of the Criteria in the Choice of Energy Storage or Non-Storage in Photovoltaic Systems in the Sahelian Zone," *Energy and Power Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 236–242, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.4236/epe.2021.136016>.
- [10] M. H. Chakrabarti, S. A. Hajimolana, F. S. Mjalli, M. Saleem, and I. Mustafa, "Redox Flow Battery for Energy Storage," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 723–739, Apr. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-012-0356-5>.
- [11] Z. Yi, W. Dong, and A. H. Etemudi, "A Unified Control and Power Management Scheme for PV-Battery-Based Hybrid Microgrids for Both Grid-Connected and Islanded Modes," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5975–5985, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2017.2700332>.
- [12] Q. Li, Y. Liu, S. Guo, and H. Zhou, "Solar energy storage in the rechargeable batteries," *Nano Today*, vol. 16, pp. 46–60, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nantod.2017.08.007>.
- [13] P. K. Dalela, S. Basu, A. Singh, S. Majumdar, N. Nagpal, and V. Tyagi, "Geo-intelligence based carbon footprint monitoring and prediction of suitable renewable energy technology system for mobile towers," in *IEEE International Conference on Advanced Networks and Telecommunications Systems*, New Delhi, India, Dec. 2014, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ANTS.2014.7057244>.
- [14] Y. Kassem, H. Gokcekus, and H. S. A. Lagili, "A Techno-Economic Viability Analysis of the Two-Axis Tracking Grid-Connected Photovoltaic Power System for 25 Selected Coastal Mediterranean Cities," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7508–7514, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4251>.
- [15] R. K. Lattanzio and C. E. Clark, "Environmental Effects of Battery Electric and Internal Combustion Engine Vehicles," Jun. 2020, Accessed: Nov. 06, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://trid.trb.org/view/1718426>.
- [16] T. Gao, Z. Wang, S. Chen, and L. Guo, "Hazardous characteristics of charge and discharge of lithium-ion batteries under adiabatic environment and hot environment," *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 141, pp. 419–431, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2019.06.075>.
- [17] A. Nedjalkov *et al.*, "Toxic Gas Emissions from Damaged Lithium Ion Batteries—Analysis and Safety Enhancement Solution," *Batteries*, vol. 2, no. 1, Mar. 2016, Art. no. 5, <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries2010005>.
- [18] H. Sugihara, K. Yokoyama, O. Saeki, K. Tsuji, and T. Funaki, "Economic and Efficient Voltage Management Using Customer-Owned Energy Storage Systems in a Distribution Network With High Penetration of Photovoltaic Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 102–111, Feb. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2012.2196529>.
- [19] N. L. M. Azemi and N. Wahid, "Uncertainty in internet of things: a review," *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering Exploration*, vol. 8, no. 75, pp. 422–431, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.19101/IJATEE.2020.762115>.
- [20] S. Rawat and T. Arjariya, "An efficient Association based Optimization technique for Web pages," *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering Exploration*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 54–59, 2015.
- [21] F. Wortmann and K. Fluchter, "Internet of Things," *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 221–224, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-015-0383-3>.
- [22] B. F. Alshammari and M. T. Chughtai, "IoT Gas Leakage Detector and Warning Generator," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6142–6146, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3712>.
- [23] M. A. Hannan, Md. M. Hoque, A. Hussain, Y. Yusof, and P. J. Ker, "State-of-the-Art and Energy Management System of Lithium-Ion Batteries in Electric Vehicle Applications: Issues and Recommendations," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 19362–19378, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2817655>.
- [24] M. Maltezo *et al.*, "Arduino-based battery monitoring system with state of charge and remaining useful time estimation," *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering Exploration*, vol. 8, no. 76, pp. 432–444, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.19101/IJATEE.2021.874023>.
- [25] D. K. Dhaked, Y. Gopal, and D. Birla, "Battery Charging Optimization of Solar Energy based Telecom Sites in India," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5041–5046, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3121>.
- [26] T. V. Krishna, M. K. Maharana, and C. K. Panigrahi, "Integrated Design and Control of Renewable Energy Sources for Energy Management," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5857–5863, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3613>.
- [27] N. A. Zainurin, S. a. B. Anas, and R. S. S. Singh, "A Review of Battery Charging - Discharging Management Controller: A Proposed Conceptual Battery Storage Charging - Discharging Centralized Controller," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7515–7521, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4217>.
- [28] M. Faisal, M. A. Hannan, P. J. Ker, and M. N. Uddin, "Backtracking Search Algorithm Based Fuzzy Charging-Discharging Controller for Battery Storage System in Microgrid Applications," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 159357–159368, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2951132>.
- [29] D. Liu, X. Yin, Y. Song, W. Liu, and Y. Peng, "An On-Line State of Health Estimation of Lithium-Ion Battery Using Unscented Particle Filter," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 40990–41001, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2854224>.
- [30] "1.1 billion people still lack electricity. This could be the solution," *World Economic Forum*. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/06/1-billion-people-lack-electricity-solution-mini-grid-ica/> (accessed Nov. 06, 2021).

AUTHORS PROFILE

automation, and smart agriculture.

Rahab Uwamahoro received her Bachelor in Computer Science from the Kigali Independent University (ULK), Rwanda. Currently, she is taking her Masters in Embedded and Mobile system (EMOS) program, specialty in embedded systems at the Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST) in Tanzania. Her research interest lies in digital solutions, renewable energy, smart home

L'Oréal UNESCO in 2020. Her research interests are artificial intelligence, machine learning, and data science.

Neema Mduma is a lecturer at the Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST) in Tanzania. She got her PhD and MSc degrees in Information, Communication Sciences and Engineering from NM-AIST in 2020 and 2016 respectively. During her PhD, she developed a machine learning model called BakiShule which aimed at preventing students from dropping out of school. Neema's efforts towards women in science have been recognized through an award from

schools.

Dina Machuve is a Senior Lecturer and Researcher at the Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST) in Tanzania. She holds a PhD in Information, Communication Science and Engineering from NM-AIST (2016), an MSc in Electrical Engineering from Tennessee Technological University, (2008), and a BSc in Electrical Engineering from the University of Dar Es Salaam (2001). Her research interests are data science and agriculture informatics in

Design and Development of a Group Decision Support System for the Evaluation and Selection of Research Projects

Irakli Bacheleishvili

Department of Computer Technology
Akaki Tsereteli State University
Kutaisi, Georgia
irakli.bacheleishvili@atsu.edu.ge

Avtandil Bardavelidze

Department of Computer Technology
Akaki Tsereteli State University
Kutaisi, Georgia
avtandil.bardavelidze@atsu.edu.ge

Abstract—The current paper deals with the design and development of a web-based group decision support system for the evaluation and selection of research projects. The paper involves the analysis of the system's requirements, the definition of its functional structure, the development of an algorithm for the evaluation and ranking of research projects, the development of a related database and of a user interface along with the writing of the business logic of the system.

Keywords—research projects; group decision; evaluation; selection; multi-criteria analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Decision-making is one of the most difficult problems of human activity, whose solution depends on the effective implementation of relevant activities. Decision-making problems are analytical problems that allow, relying on the primary information base, gaining new knowledge concerning the new situation, deeply understanding the current processes and, consequently, making the right decision [1]. In order to solve such problems, it is important to use the information systems called decision support systems [1-4] which are the model-based or knowledge-based systems designed to assist in decision-making [2].

The current paper deals with the design and development of a group decision support system for the evaluation and ranking of research projects. In decision-making theory and practice, great importance is attached to the so-called group decisions made by several individuals. There is particular interest in group decisions due to the fact that there is a high level of professionalism in society, and at the same time, the physical and informational capacities of an individual are quite limited. The use of this type of system is mainly needed by organizations that announce research grant competitions. The grant competition process can generally be described as follows: the granting organizations announce a scientific grant competition in various fields of science and define the requirements for the research projects. After the announcement of the grant competition, the applicants submit their project proposals according to the area of research, after which the

granting organization appoints a group of experts for the relevant projects, and the experts review and evaluate the submitted project proposals. The granting organization makes the decision to select the best research projects based on the experts' evaluation.

Today there are numerous management information systems used by the organizations providing research grants [8]. The functionality of these systems is largely limited to allowing the grant applicants meet the requirements of a grant project in accordance with the requirements of the organization providing these grants, that is, they are mostly engaged in data collection and submission. These systems do not support decision-making on grant selection. The proposed system, in addition to all these, has the novelty of decision-making support which increases its practical value, making the activities of the grant-proving organizations more effective.

The aim of the current paper is the design and development of a web-based group decision support system that provides support for the research grant competition processes with a view to conduct the research grant competition in an efficient and fair manner. A web-based group decision support system will allow the involvement in this competition of applicants from various and distant geographical locations.

II. IDENTIFYING THE SYSTEM'S REQUIREMENTS

A use case diagram (Figure 1) was developed to specify and analyze the requirements of the group decision support system for the evaluation and selection of research projects. The diagram illustrates the requirements and the functionality that will be imposed on the design system. As shown in this use case diagram, there are four types of roles in the system:

- Administrator: manages the users of the other levels of the system and ensures the efficient operation of the system.
- Manager: represents the organization that announces the research grant competition. The user having this role:
 - Defines the areas of the research grant competition.

Fig. 1. Use case diagram.

- Identifies the requirements and necessary documents for the submission of the research project.
- Defines the evaluation criteria and their weights in accordance with the areas of the research grant competition.
- Nominates the experts in accordance with the scientific areas of the submitted research projects.
- Ranks the research projects based on the experts' evaluation.
- Makes the decision of selecting the research projects.
- Submitter of the research project: this user is registered in the system and submits the information and documentation required for the submission of the grant research project. The submitter of the research project in the system can get information about the evaluation of his research project and the decision on selecting the project, after the evaluation of the project by experts.
- Experts: are registered users in the system and their main function is to evaluate research projects in accordance with the previously defined evaluation criteria, for the projects of the scientific fields that they were nominated for by the manager.

The users of the system can use the above mentioned functions if they are authorized by the system. To do this, it is

necessary for them to register and get a confirmation from the administrator.

III. DEVELOPMENT OF THE REQUIRED ALGORITHM FOR THE OPERATION OF THE SYSTEM

The main issue when designing decision support systems is the development of the mathematical models and the algorithms necessary for its operation. The decision-making problems, in which the possible alternatives are evaluated according to several criteria, are of particular interest. In this case we are dealing with multi-criteria decision-making problems [10]. The problem of evaluating and ranking research projects is a multi-criteria problem, in which the research projects are considered to be the alternatives, while the research project evaluation criteria are considered to be the alternative evaluation criteria. Therefore, multi-criteria decision analysis methods are used to develop an algorithm for evaluating and ranking research projects [3]. Many theoretical studies have been dedicated to this problem, but the analysis reveals that their application in practice is not always possible and is time consuming. Therefore, it is relevant to develop user-friendly, multi-criteria decision-making algorithms and the appropriate software system for practical use, which will allow the decision-makers to promptly evaluate the multi-criteria alternatives and make optimal decisions.

A. The Ranking Algorithm

The ranking of the research projects is carried out once the group of experts evaluates the research projects according to the relevant criteria, based on which it will be possible to form a decision matrix:

$$\begin{matrix}
 & C_1 & C_2 & C_3 & \dots & C_m \\
 A_1 & x_{11} & x_{12} & x_{13} & \dots & x_{1m} \\
 A_2 & x_{21} & x_{22} & x_{23} & \dots & x_{2m} \\
 A_3 & x_{31} & x_{32} & x_{33} & \dots & x_{3m} \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
 A_n & x_{n1} & x_{n2} & x_{n3} & \dots & x_{nm} \\
 w_1 & w_2 & w_3 & \dots & w_m
 \end{matrix} \quad (1)$$

where x_{ij} , $i=1, \dots, n, j=1, \dots, m$ represent the assessment of the i alternative in accordance with the j criterion, defined by the experts. The value of x_{ij} is calculated as:

$$x_{ij} = \frac{1}{t} (x_{ij}^1 + x_{ij}^2 + x_{ij}^3 + \dots + x_{ij}^t)$$

where x_{ij}^k , $k=1, t$ is the k^{th} - expert's assessment of the j criterion of the i alternative.

The multi-criteria decision analysis method AHP is used to calculate the weights of the alternative evaluation criteria [2, 5-8]. The Vikor method [9] was used to identify the research projects. It includes the following steps:

Step 1: Determine the best x_j^+ and the worst x_j^- values of all criteria:

$$x_j^+ = \max(x_{ij}), j = 1, \dots, m \quad (2)$$

$$x_j^- = \min(x_{ij}), j = 1, \dots, m \quad (3)$$

Step 2: Calculate S_i and R_i using (4) and (5):

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^m (w_j * \frac{x_j^+ - x_{ij}}{x_j^+ - x_j^-}) \quad (4)$$

$$R_i = \max_j \left(w_j * \frac{x_j^+ - x_{ij}}{x_j^+ - x_j^-} \right) \quad (5)$$

Step 3: Compute the values Q_i using (6):

$$Q_i = v * \frac{S_i - S^+}{S^- - S^+} + (1-v) * \frac{R_i - R^+}{R^- - R^+} \quad (6)$$

where $S^+ = \min_i S_i$, $S^- = \max_i S_i$, $R^+ = \min_i R_i$, $R^- = \max_i R_i$, and $v=0.5$

Step 4: Ranking of the alternatives for the Q_i values: The rank of alternatives is determined by sorting the obtained values from small to large.

B. Numerical Experiment

To demonstrate the work of the presented algorithm, let's consider a practical case, let's assume we want to evaluate five projects (A_1, \dots, A_5) that are evaluated according to four criteria (c_1, \dots, c_4). Let's assume that the decision matrix based on the experts' evaluations has the form exhibited in Table I.

TABLE I. DECISION MATRIX

	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4
A_1	90	70	85	79
A_2	87	75	96	89
A_3	80	79	74	75
A_4	75	80	92	78
A_5	82	75	69	96

The pairwise comparison matrix of the criteria of assessment is shown in Table II and the normalized pair-wise comparison matrix in Table III. The vector of the weights is determined as:

$$c_1 = 0.48 \quad c_2 = 0.29 \quad c_3 = 0.13 \quad c_4 = 0.09$$

The calculated weighted normalized decision matrix is shown in Table IV. The calculated sum of the weighted values is:

$$c_1 = 1.97 \quad c_2 = 1.21 \quad c_3 = 0.54 \quad c_4 = 0.38$$

The calculated λ_{max} is 4.077618. The calculated Consistency Index (CI) is 0.025873 and the Consistency Ratio (CR) is 0.028748. Because the CR value is less than 0.1 it is acceptable. The determined best x_j^+ and the worst x_j^- values of all criteria are shown in Table V. Then, S_i , R_i , and Q_i are calculated. The final result is shown in Table VI.

TABLE II. PAIRWISE COMPARISON MATRIX

	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4
c_1	1.00	2.00	4.00	4.00
c_2	0.50	1.00	3.00	3.00
c_3	0.25	0.33	1.00	2.00
c_4	0.25	0.33	0.50	1.00

TABLE III. NORMALIZED PAIRWISE COMPARISON MATRIX

	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4
c_1	0.50	0.55	0.47	0.40
c_2	0.25	0.27	0.35	0.30
c_3	0.13	0.09	0.12	0.20
c_4	0.13	0.09	0.06	0.10

TABLE IV. WEIGHTED NORMALIZED MATRIX

	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4
c_1	0.48	0.59	0.53	0.37
c_2	0.24	0.29	0.40	0.28
c_3	0.12	0.10	0.13	0.19
c_4	0.12	0.10	0.07	0.09

TABLE V. BEST AND WORST VALUES OF ALL CRITERIA

	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4
x_j^+	90	80	96	96
x_j^-	75	70	69	75

TABLE VI. RESULT

	S_i	R_i	Q_i	Rank
A_1	0.423997	0.294041	0.467016	2
A_2	0.274038	0.147021	0	1
A_3	0.550943	0.319506	0.713381	4
A_4	0.579133	0.479259	1	5
A_5	0.535828	0.255605	0.592444	3

IV. SYSTEM SOFTWARE

The system’s software package presented in this paper was developed using the Asp.Net Core technology. One of the most important components of a decision-making system is the database, which contains the data on the basis of which the entire system works. The Entity Relationship (EER) model of the database is presented in Figure 2, and is designed with the visual studio 2017 ado.net entity data model.

The database was implemented on an SQL server. The system’s database and business logic have been designed in such a way that it is easy to add new modules to it and improve the system. The system’s software, according to the system

roles, consists of 4 modules: Administrator Module, Expert Module, Manager Module, and Research Project Submission Module. Some fragments of the system software are given in Figures 3-8. Figure 3 presents the form of the determination of the evaluation criteria according to the scientific directions. Figure 4 presents the form of the determination of the weights of the evaluation criteria. Figure 5 presents the form of the assignment of experts according to the scientific directions. Figure 6 shows the upload page of a scientific project. Figure 7 presents the evaluation form of the scientific projects by the experts, and Figure 8 presents the ranking form of the scientific projects.

Fig. 2. The EER model of the database.

Scientific direction	Name of Criteria	description	Edit	Delete
direction 1	Name of Criteria 1	description 1	Edit	Delete
direction 1	Name of Criteria 2	description 2	Edit	Delete
direction 1	Name of Criteria 3	description 3	Edit	Delete

Fig. 3. The evaluation criteria.

	Name of criteria 1	Name of criteria 2	Name of criteria 3	Name of criteria 4
Name of Criteria 1	Equal i	2	4	4
Name of criteria 2	1/2	1/3	Moderat	Moderat
Name of criteria 3	1/4	1/3	Equal in	2
Name of criteria 4	1/4	1/3	1/2	Equal in

Fig. 4. The weights of the evaluation criteria.

Fig. 5. The assignment of experts.

Fig. 8. Ranking of the scientific projects.

Fig. 6. Project submission.

Fig. 7. Evaluation of the scientific projects by the experts.

V. CONCLUSION

The current paper presents a group decision support system for the selection of research projects, which can be effectively used by organizations to conduct research grant competitions fairly and effectively. The resulting system is designed in such a way that it is easy to add new functionalities in order to make it more convenient for a particular organization.

REFERENCES

- [1] C.-L. Hwang and M.-J. Lin, Eds., *Group Decision Making under Multiple Criteria*. Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 1987.
- [2] I. Basheleishvili, "Developing the Expert Decision-Making Algorithm Using the Methods of Multi-Criteria Analysis," *Cybernetics and Information Technologies*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 22–29, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.2478/cait-2020-0013>.
- [3] C. Zopounidis and P. M. Pardalos, Eds., *Handbook of Multicriteria Analysis*. Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2010.
- [4] T. L. Saaty and K. Peniwati, *Group Decision Making: Drawing Out and Reconciling Differences*, 1st ed. Pittsburgh, PA, USA: RWS Publications, 2007.
- [5] D. Sabaei, J. Erkoyuncu, and R. Roy, "A Review of Multi-criteria Decision Making Methods for Enhanced Maintenance Delivery," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 37, pp. 30–35, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2015.08.086>.
- [6] T. L. Saaty, "Group Decision Making and the AHP," in *The Analytic Hierarchy Process: Applications and Studies*, B. L. Golden, E. A. Wasil, and P. T. Harker, Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 1989, pp. 59–67.
- [7] V. Podvezko, "Application of AHP technique," *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 181–189, Jun. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.3846/1611-1699.2009.10.181-189>.
- [8] R. Hruška, P. Průša, and D. Babić, "The use of AHP method for selection of supplier," *Transport*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 195–203, Apr. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.3846/16484142.2014.930928>.
- [9] A. Jahan, F. Mustapha, M. Y. Ismail, S. M. Sapuan, and M. Bahraminasab, "A comprehensive VIKOR method for material selection," *Materials & Design*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 1215–1221, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2010.10.015>.
- [10] İ. Basheleishvili, A. Bardavelidze, and S. Tsirama, "The Development of a Model for Decision Support System of Assessment and Selection of University Academic Staff," *Journal of Intelligent Systems: Theory and Applications*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 18–23, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.38016/jista.538991>.

-
- [11] I. Bacheleishvili, "Development of Method of Multifunctional Personnel Assessment Using a Topsis Method," *Journal of Technical Science and Technologies*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 31–36, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.31578/v7i1.137>.
- [12] I. Bacheleishvili and A. Bardavelidze, "Designing the Decision-Making Support System for the Assessment and Selection of the University's Academic Staff," *International Journal on Information Technologies & Security*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 51–58, 2019.
- [13] I. Bacheleishvili, "The Algorithm of Selection and Functions Distribution of Multifunctional Personnel - Case when the Number of Functions is Greater than the Number of Personnel," *Journal of Technical Science & Technologies*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 23–26, 2017.
- [14] N. Benmoussa, A. Elyamami, K. Mansouri, M. Qbadou, and E. Illoussamen, "A Multi-Criteria Decision Making Approach for Enhancing University Accreditation Process," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3726–3733, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2352>.
- [15] Ateekh-Ur-Rehman and M. Alkahtani, "Automobile Tire Assessment: A Multi-Criteria Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1363–1368, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.797>.
- [16] S. Alshehri, "Multicriteria Decision Making (MCDM) Methods for Ranking Estimation Techniques in Extreme Programming," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 3073–3078, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2104>.

Functionally Graded Materials (FGM) for Spacers in Gas Insulated Systems: A Concise Review and Some Comments

K. L. Wong

RMIT University
School of Engineering, High Voltage Laboratory
Melbourne, Australia
alan.wong@rmit.edu.au

M. G. Danikas

Democritus University of Thrace
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
Xanthi, Greece
mdanikas@ee.duth.gr

Abstract-Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs) present a solution to control electrical stresses in high voltage applications. In this paper, a concise review is presented on the FGMs for spacers in gas-insulated systems. FGMs offer the possibility of a more even electric field distribution and thus a viable solution for industrial applications. FGMs are investigated here primarily as materials for permittivity control. Some aspects of FGMs are discussed as well as some thoughts on future challenges.

Keywords-functionally graded materials; gas insulated systems; dielectric constant; permittivity; triple junction point; dielectric strength; fillers; microfillers; nanofillers

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric stress control is a major challenge in high voltage engineering applications. Excessive electric stress may lead to the breakdown of insulation and definite deterioration of high voltage equipment [1]. Electric field stress control has been dealt with in some detail before, such as field distortions by conducting particles, field distortions by electrode asperities as well as field distortions due to multi-dielectric insulating arrangements [2]. Sandwiched multi-layer insulating systems can cause problems if the layers are of different dielectric constant. However, such insulating systems – if made up from very thin layers – can be of advantage since they usually present fewer defects than thicker insulation slabs [2, 3]. As has been pointed out, sharp edges, small radius elements and needle points must be avoided in insulation design [4, 5].

Elaborating further the question of multiple layer insulation, it was reported that the effect of multiple layers is particularly marked for materials where there is a wide spread in values of dielectric strength measured at different points on the surface. The main factor in this phenomenon is the loss of energy from the discharge at the interfaces. As has been mentioned some decades ago, a partial discharge having penetrated one layer cannot enter the next layer of the insulating material until the spot on the interface, which is centered on the discharge channel, has been charged to a potential which could produce a field comparable with that of the discharge channel at the level in question [6].

Interfaces play a most important role in high voltage engineering applications. In traditional insulating materials, interfaces must be avoided or they must be treated in a way that they do not cause additional problems to the insulating system. As has been pointed out before, irrespectively of the theory put forward to explain pre-breakdown and breakdown phenomena, either electrode imperfections or mismatch of dielectric materials in a composite insulating system result in electric field intensifications that may lead to ultimate failure. It goes without saying that interfaces are the root of a variety of problems regarding the insulating systems [7]. A way out of such problems is the better matching between dielectric materials (in case of an insulating system), or an alleviation of the applied electric field in the case of an insulating material in direct contact with an electrode [8, 9]. Another way is the use of Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs), which are materials characterized by gradual variation in composition and structure over volume, which may result in a more even distribution of the electric field. According to [10], FGMs are novel materials, the properties of which change gradually with respect to their dimensions. It is the advanced development of hitherto used composite materials, consisting of two or more materials, in order to achieve the desired properties according to the application where an FGM can be used. Expressed in a slightly different way, FGMs are very advanced engineering materials designed for a specific property or function, in which spatial gradations in the structure (and possibly in the composition) provide them with the desired characteristics [11]. The present paper aims to offer a concise review of the aforementioned materials with an emphasis on spacers in gas insulated systems.

II. FUNCTIONALLY GRADED MATERIALS

In various high voltage applications, many electric field distortions may be observed. Such distortions are caused by the shape of electrodes and/or spacers and to the mismatch of the insulating materials. Distortions (or intensifications) of this kind may lower the electrical performance of insulating systems and of high voltage equipment. In other words, field intensifications may lead to Partial Discharges (PDs) and electrical treeing. If not detected, these phenomena may lead to complete failure of the insulating systems [12-15]. Thorough

Corresponding author: M. G. Danikas

analyses of field distortions are described in [1, 2, 4, 16]. A possible remedy to field intensifications would be a smoothing out of problematic electrodes and the – as far as possible – better matching of the insulating materials in case of a composite insulating system.

An alternative to the above approaches is the application of FGMs, which with the well-controlled spatial distribution of dielectric constants inside would offer a more even electric field distribution [17, 18]. Although such materials were studied regarding their homogenization, heat transfer, stress, stability, and dynamic analysis and fracture [19], what is of interest for us is the application of such materials in high voltage engineering [20]. FGMs – as far as high voltage applications are concerned – consist of insulating materials with a certain filler concentration in order to vary one basic physical property, so that they can alleviate electric field intensifications [21]. In other words, FGMs replace the sharp transition of properties with smooth and gradually changing properties of the materials such as physical, chemical, mechanical or electrical [11].

FGMs do not encompass all possible high voltage applications. Among them, FGMs are applicable to spacers for gas-insulated power apparatus, cable joints, insulators and bushings, stator coils, and electrical insulation for power electronic modules [21, 22]. In the context of the present paper, a concise review will be given w.r.t. FGMs regarding the spacers in gas insulated systems. In other words, the review will be confined in the aforementioned application.

III. FGMS FOR SPACERS AND GAS-INSULATED EQUIPMENT

Spacers are an indispensable part of gas-insulated switchgear [1, 23]. As was noted in [1], spacer flashover is the most probable breakdown mechanism in a compressed gas insulated system as any contamination of the space surface may produce flashover at a voltage (sometimes well) below the gas breakdown strength. Epoxy resin is primarily the insulating material used for spacers [8]. As is noted in [24], triple junctions present an important problem for spacers since at those points high electric field intensifications may be observed. By building FGMs with higher permittivities at both cathode and anode surfaces compared with other intermediate parts of the spacer, i.e. by having a U-distribution of permittivity, a relaxation of the electric field is obtained. According to [24], the maximum electric field was reduced by about 10% at the triple junction – in case of a foreign particle adhered to spacer - with the application of a U-shape FGM (in this case epoxy resin). Also in [24], it was reported that the electric field was relaxed by about 30% at both high voltage/spacer and ground/spacer interfaces by applying a U-shape FGM. Regarding the presence of foreign particles adhered to the spacer, an earlier study also indicated that their shape and location may influence the performance of FGM [25].

In [26], further discussions ensued w.r.t. the spacers with Graded Low FGM (GL-FGM), Graded High FGM (GH-FGM), and Graded U FGM (GU-FGM). This work was mainly a computer analysis of the various aforementioned FGMs in reference to a three-phase insulated gas bus duct. One of the

conclusions was that the GL-FGM results in rather high electric field stresses. Such conclusions are not at variance with earlier research which showed that GL-FGM gives a field relaxation in a rather narrow range of permittivities whereas GH-FGM offers a field relaxation in a much wider range of permittivities [27]. Authors in [28, 29] did not deviate from the main conclusions of [26], pointing out that the main problem in such structures is the triple point. In [26, 30], similar conclusions were reached regarding the GH-FGM, GU-FGM, and GL-FGM. The authors of [30] indicated that the highest percentage reduction of electric field stress is observed for GH-FGM and GU-FGM gradings. In the same paper, it was remarked that it is preferable to prepare FGMs by applying centrifugal forces, incorporating thus fillers of different diameters in order to obtain permittivity distribution for uniform field distribution rather than three dimensional (3D) printing, since it is the first method that is more efficient. Such views on the preparation method of FGMs are also shared by other researchers [31, 32]. The authors of [11] take a more cautious approach w.r.t. the aforementioned preparation techniques by pointing out that the controllability of the centrifugation method is not always the desired one and that one of the obstacles of the 3D printing technology, among others, is the limitation of printing materials (another preparation method, namely the flexible mixture casting method, has as main drawback the forming of many interfaces of the composing resins). The centrifugation method seems to be also preferred in [33], although the authors remarked that a more flexible fabrication method is urgently required. However, a different view regarding the 3D printing technology was offered in [34], where satisfactory flashover characteristics were obtained for insulators at both SF₆ and vacuum under DC voltages with the Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) manufacturing process.

Further criticism of the above preparation methods was also put forward in [35], where another method was proposed, besides the aforementioned approaches with FGMs, namely to apply FGM to the spacer surface in order to form thickness (d) gradient surface layers of high permittivity (d-SFGM). This was done by the magnetron sputtering technique. The optimum layer thickness was found to be between 8 and 10 μm. The authors of [35], experimenting with d-SFGM, observed that electric field distribution is further homogenized, the maximum electric field strength at the HV triple junction is further reduced, and the AC flashover voltage was very satisfactory. Relevant to [35] is the work by the same research group with FGMs having spatial distribution of conductivity σ (σ -FGM) [36]. Such materials were fabricated with the surface fluorination of the insulating material. Such materials are more orientated to DC applications, where significant improvements were observed w.r.t. the flashover voltage as well as to the homogenization of electric field distribution. The authors of [37] approached the whole question of FGMs from another point of view, namely that of the behavior of FGM spacers in the presence of spherical conducting particles in gas-insulated systems. They also noticed the beneficial effect of the FGMs in this case, pointing out that the influence of the FGM spacer material may vary depending on the positioning and the size of the spherical particle w.r.t. the high voltage electrode and/or the ground electrode. FGM spacers seem to have a better overall

performance with adhering spherical particle than conventional materials.

Experimenting with ϵ -grading to the lower permittivity by fabricating FGMs (GLP-FGM), it was found that the maximum electric field strength of a fabricated coaxial disc-type GLP-FGM spacer at the HV-electrode/spacer interface can be reduced by 12% in comparison with the one of a conventional spacer with uniform permittivity [38]. In contradistinction to the centrifugation method, the Flexible Mixture Casting (FMC) method [39], produced ϵ -FGMs of a wide range of permittivities giving a relaxation of electric stress on the spacer surface by 64% in SF₆ gas and an improvement of discharge inception voltage by 70% in SF₆ gas at 0.4 MPa. A more unified approach to the question of spacers was dealt with in [40], where there was a simultaneous change of both electrode shape and insulating material for optimum electric field distribution. Thus, the cathode shape was modified by rounding the cathode radius near the triple junction. The maximum electric field was efficiently reduced through the application of the FGM spacer. When compared to the uniform permittivity spacer model, a 26.5% decrease in the maximum electric field was obtained with the optimal FGM spacer configuration. FGMs as solution for a more balanced distribution of electrical fields was also presented in [41], mentioning the research on post-type and truncated-cone-type solid insulators for gas-insulated switchgear, which were developed using the centrifugation technique to distribute the fillers and, therefore, permittivity. The authors of [41] present an example of a U-shape permittivity grading, which reduces the electric field stress between 10 to 20 times. Moreover, in the same paper, they propose the use of FGMs as a viable solution of great importance (along, among others, with polymer nanocomposites, high temperature materials, charging control dielectrics and nonlinear dielectrics).

Emphasis on the centrifugal method was given in [42]. This method was successful in obtaining the fabrication of ϵ -FGM materials, for which both the packing fraction and size of the dispersed fillers were graded. According to the authors of [42], the fillers depending on their sizes play different roles in order to determine the profiles of the packing fraction and the resultant permittivity profiles in ϵ -FGM materials. Among the small (with a diameter between 0.1 – 10 μm), medium (with a diameter between 10-100 μm), and larger fillers (with a diameter between 100 μm - 1000 μm), the small and medium size fillers determine the gradient of permittivity in the dispersion layers whereas the larger fillers predominantly determine the permittivity in the fully packed area. The same group of researchers in an earlier paper rightly wrote that – w.r.t. the centrifugal method - the proper choice of the process parameters such that of operational time, of the angular velocity and the statistical distribution of the filler size may lead to the desired profile of permittivities [43]. The authors in [44] proposed a multi-layer FGM approach, according to which different kinds of grading processes are applied and, by so doing, the non-homogeneous dispersion of nanoparticles is achieved between each layer, which in turn creates a smooth grading action and improves the electrical properties of the samples. An improvement in dielectric strength was noted. A comprehensive theoretical analysis of multi-layered FGMs was

offered in [45], where computational estimates of permittivity and conductivity gave results much closer to the experimental data than well-known models (Maxwell-Garnett's model, Bruggeman's model, the coherent potential model, and Lichtenecker's model [46]). As was noted in [44], the theoretical estimates of permittivity and conductivity based on the models of [46] tend to deviate from the respective experimental values when filler loadings exceed the 10% of the volume, whereas this is not observed with the proposed computational model which is based on the Representative Volume Element (RVE) approach.

IV. PROPOSALS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

FGMs contribute to the better distribution of electric fields in certain applications. A possibility for further research can be the exploration of these materials regarding their behavior in voltages at or just below the inception level. Previous work with conventional insulating materials has shown that deteriorating phenomena can be observed at voltage levels below the inception level. Past work compared the by-products emanating from deterioration above inception with the by-products produced below inception. The by-products on both occasions were very similar [47-49]. Moreover, charge injection and extraction may relate to a tree initiation mechanism that does not involve partial discharges [50, 51]. Work done with polymer nanocomposites [52], also tends to confirm the conclusions of [47-49, 53, 54]. It would be interesting to see whether with the FGMs one can get some experimental data at and below inception level, since charging phenomena below inception voltage seem to be important although not much attention has been paid to them. Furthermore, with the advent of recent research, another possibility would be the use of FGMs in high voltage applications having together micro-fillers as well as nano-fillers [55].

Another interesting possibility can be the application of such materials to high voltage applications requiring very thin layers. It is well known that considerable effort has been taken in order to improve the electrical performance of traditional high voltage insulators (glass/porcelain) with RTV coatings [56, 57]. It would be challenging from the fabrication point of view to find whether FGMs can be applied to small thicknesses, such as the thicknesses of the RTV coatings.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this short review, an attempt was made to present some aspects of FGMs. These materials seem to be very promising in alleviating the electric field stress in spacers for gas insulated systems. FGMs – in the context of this short review – were approached primarily as materials for permittivity control. The experimental data show that there is an important diminution of electric stress in the triple junction point, which tends to be most crucial for spacers.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. J. Gallagher and A. J. Pearmain, *High voltage : measurement, testing, and design*. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 1983.
- [2] E. Kuffel, W. S. Zaengl, and J. Kuffel, *High Voltage Engineering Fundamentals*, 2nd Edition. Oxford, UK: Elsevier, 2000.

- [3] J. Staight, "Properties and applications of solid/liquid composites," in *Electrical Insulation*, A. Bradwell, Ed. London, UK: Peter Peregrinus Ltd, 1983, pp. 147–163.
- [4] C. L. Wadhwa, *High Voltage Engineering*, 3rd ed. New Delhi, India: New Age Science, 2010.
- [5] A. Al-Gheilani, W. Rowe, Y. Li, and K. L. Wong, "Stress Control Methods on a High Voltage Insulator: A Review," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 110, pp. 95–100, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.112>.
- [6] N. Parkman, "Breakdown in composites," in *Electrical Insulation*, London, UK: Peter Peregrinus Ltd, 1983.
- [7] M. G. Danikas and R. Sarathi, "Interfaces in High Voltage Engineering: A Most Important Question for Conventional Solid Insulating Materials as well as for Nanocomposite Polymers," *Funktechnikplus # Journal*, vol. 1, pp. 7–31, Mar. 2014.
- [8] D. Kind and H. Karner, *High-Voltage Insulation Technology*. Braunschweig, Germany: Springer, 1985.
- [9] K. Moeller and D. Meurer, "Auswirkungen von Teilentladungen auf elektrischen Isolierstoffe," in *Teilentladungen in Betriebsmitteln der Energietechnik*, D. Koenig and Y. N. Rao, Eds. Berlin, Germany: VDE-Verlag GmbH, 1993, pp. 85–104.
- [10] N. Zhang, T. Khan, H. Guo, S. Shi, W. Zhong, and W. Zhang, "Functionally Graded Materials: An Overview of Stability, Buckling, and Free Vibration Analysis," *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 2019, Feb. 2019, Art. no. e1354150, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/1354150>.
- [11] J. Li, H. Liang, Y. Chen, and B. Du, "Promising functional graded materials for compact gaseous insulated switchgears/pipelines," *High Voltage*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 231–240, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1049/hve.2019.0327>.
- [12] J. H. Mason, "Discharges," *IEEE Transactions on Electrical Insulation*, vol. EI-13, no. 4, pp. 211–238, Aug. 1978, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEI.1978.298074>.
- [13] K. C. Kao and D. M. Tu, "Formation of electrical treeing in polyethylene," in *Conference on Electrical Insulation & Dielectric Phenomena - Annual Report*, Amherst, MA, USA, Oct. 1982, pp. 598–603, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CEIDP.1982.7726585>.
- [14] T. Tanaka and A. Greenwood, *Advanced power cable technology. Volume I. Basic concepts and testing*. Florida, USA: CRC Press, 1983.
- [15] M. G. Danikas, "Small partial discharges and their role in insulation deterioration," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 863–867, Dec. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1109/94.654733>.
- [16] M. S. Naidu and V. Kamaraju, *High-Voltage Engineering*. New Delhi, India: McGraw-Hill, 2000.
- [17] M. Kurimoto, K. Kato, M. Hanai, Y. Hoshina, M. Takei, and H. Okubo, "Application of functionally graded material for reducing electric field on electrode and spacer interface," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 256–263, Feb. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2010.5412025>.
- [18] Y.-F. Zhang *et al.*, "Simulation of Functionally Graded Material (FGM) for Cable Joint in AC and DC Field Optimization," in *IEEE International Conference on High Voltage Engineering and Application*, Beijing, China, Sep. 2020, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICHVE49031.2020.9280030>.
- [19] V. Birman and L. W. Byrd, "Modeling and Analysis of Functionally Graded Materials and Structures," *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, vol. 60, no. 5, pp. 195–216, Sep. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2777164>.
- [20] H. Okubo, K. Kato, N. Hayakawa, M. Hanai, and M. Takei, "Functionally Graded Materials and their Application to High Electric Field Power Equipment," in *Performance of conventional and new materials for high voltage apparatus CIGRE SC D1 – COLLOQUIUM IN HUNGARY BUDAPEST 2009*, Hungary, Budapest, 2009.
- [21] X. Yang, X. Zhao, J. Hu, and J. He, "Grading electric field in high voltage insulation using composite materials," *IEEE Electrical Insulation Magazine*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 15–25, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MEI.2018.8246118>.
- [22] S. Diahm, Z. V. Nava, L. Leveque, T. T. Le, L. Laudebat, and T. Lebey, "An original in-situ way to build field grading materials (FGM) with permittivity gradient using electrophoresis," in *2nd International Conference on Dielectrics*, Budapest, Hungary, Jul. 2018, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICD.2018.8514572>.
- [23] A. P. Purnomoadi, A. Rodrigo Mor, and J. J. Smit, "Spacer flashover in Gas Insulated Switchgear (GIS) with humid SF6 under different electrical stresses," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 116, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 105559, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2019.105559>.
- [24] S. A. Ward, M. A. A. Allah, and A. A. Youssef, "Effect of Functionally Graded Material of Spacer with Contaminating Particle on Breakdown Voltage inside Gas Insulated Bus Duct," *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 756–762, 2014.
- [25] S. Ganga, K. Dwarakanath, A. A. Natarajan, M. G. VijayaRaghavan, L. Ohri, and R. Vaikundh, "A study on suitability of functionally graded material for spacer application," in *IEEE International Conference on Solid Dielectrics*, Toulouse, France, Jul. 2004, vol. 2, pp. 521–524, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSD.2004.1350483>.
- [26] P. Janaki, N. Karthick, and G. V. N. Kumar, "Design and analysis of FGM post type spacer in a three phase common enclosure gas insulated busduct under delamination," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 190, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 106834, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epr.2020.106834>.
- [27] H. Shumiya, K. Kato, and H. Okubo, "Application feasibility of permittivity graded FGM (functionally graded materials) for gas-insulated equipment," *Electrical Engineering in Japan*, vol. 162, no. 2, pp. 39–45, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ej.20363>.
- [28] A. Rukmananda, G. V. N. Kumar, M. A. Bharathi, and S. K. Bali, "Insulation integrity of grading high insulating spacer with functionally graded material in a Gas Insulated Busduct," *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 2269, no. 1, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 030039, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0019505>.
- [29] N. C. Dathu, G. V. N. Kumar, M. A. Bharathi, and S. K. Bali, "Field stress control of a post type grading low insulating spacer with functionally graded material in a gas insulated bus duct," *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 2269, no. 1, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 030045, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0019504>.
- [30] J. Pakalapati, V. N. K. Gundavarapu, D. C. Duvvada, and S. K. Bali, "Study of electric field stress on the surface contour and at the triple junction in three phase GIS with FGM spacer under the depression defect," *International Journal of Emerging Electric Power Systems*, vol. 21, no. 5, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijeees-2020-0080>.
- [31] M. Yoshitaka, K. Hiroki, K. Katsumi, and H. Naoki, "Fabrication of GIS Spacer Model with ϵ -FGM (Functionally Graded Materials) and Theoretical Estimation of its Breakdown Voltage in SF₆ Gas," *IEEE Transactions on Fundamentals and Materials*, vol. 138, no. 4, pp. 155–162, 2018.
- [32] H. Okubo, J. Shimomura, Y. Fujii, N. Hayakawa, M. Hanai, and K. Kato, "Fabrication and simulation techniques of permittivity graded materials for gas insulated power equipment," in *XVII International Symposium on High Voltage Engineering*, Hannover, Germany, Aug. 2011, p. 5.
- [33] K. A. Naidu, G. V. N. Kumar, K. J. Ram, and D. D. Chowdary, "Electric Field Stress mitigation in a Gas Insulated Substation under delamination defect," *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 114, no. 8, pp. 131–141, 2017.
- [34] X.-R. Li *et al.*, "3D printing fabrication of conductivity non-uniform insulator for surface flashover mitigation," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 1172–1180, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2019.007938>.
- [35] H. Yao, B. Du, J. Li, and Z. Wang, "Surface Functionally Graded Insulator for High Voltage Gas Insulated Apparatus," in *Polymer Insulation Applied for HVDC Transmission*, B. Du, Ed. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2020, pp. 549–568.
- [36] B. X. Du, Z. Y. Ran, J. Li, and H. C. Liang, "Novel insulator with interfacial σ -FGM for DC compact gaseous insulated pipeline," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 818–825, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2019.007778>.

- [37] M. Talaat, A. El-Zein, and M. Amin, "Electric field simulation for uniform and FGM cone type spacer with adhering spherical conducting particle in GIS," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 339–351, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2018.006980>.
- [38] J. Ishiguro, M. Kurimoto, H. Kojima, K. Kato, H. Okubo, and N. Hayakawa, "Electric field control in coaxial disk-type solid insulator by functionally graded materials (FGM)," in *IEEE Conference on Electrical Insulation and Dielectric Phenomena*, Des Moines, IA, USA, Oct. 2014, pp. 663–666, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CEIDP.2014.6995799>.
- [39] N. Hayakawa, Y. Miyaji, H. Kojima, and K. Kato, "Simulation on discharge inception voltage improvement of GIS spacer with permittivity graded materials (ϵ -FGM) using flexible mixture casting method," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 1318–1323, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2018.007236>.
- [40] H.-J. Ju, B. Kim, and K.-C. Ko, "Optimal design of an elliptically graded permittivity spacer configuration in gas insulated switchgear," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 1268–1273, Aug. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2011.5976126>.
- [41] H. Okubo and A. Beroual, "Recent trend and future perspectives in electrical insulation techniques in relation to sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) substitutes for high voltage electric power equipment," *IEEE Electrical Insulation Magazine*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 34–42, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MEI.2011.5739421>.
- [42] N. Hayashi, S. Tsuru, T. Onoda, Y. Sakamoto, and M. Hara, "Fabrication of Functionally Graded Epoxy Resin with Alumina Fillers and its Simulation by Using a Centrifugal Method," *IEEE Transactions on Fundamentals and Materials*, vol. 124, no. 7, pp. 598–606, 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1541/ieejfms.124.598>.
- [43] N. Hayashi, T. Onoda, Y. Sakamoto, S. Tsuru, T. Kawabe, and M. Hara, "Fabrication of Permittivity Graded Epoxy Resin with Non-Uniform Dispersion of Alumina Fillers by a Centrifugal Procedure," *Materials Science Forum*, vol. 492–493, pp. 501–506, 2005, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/MSF.492-493.501>.
- [44] A. Al-Gheilani, Y. Li, K. L. Wong, and W. S. T. Rowe, "Electric Field Reduction by Multi-layer Functionally Graded Material with Controlled Permittivity and Conductivity Distribution," in *IEEE Conference on Electrical Insulation and Dielectric Phenomena*, Richland, WA, USA, Oct. 2019, pp. 86–89, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CEIDP47102.2019.9009929>.
- [45] S. A. Qasim and N. Gupta, "Computation of Effective Properties of Graded and Layered Dielectrics," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 460–467, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2020.009206>.
- [46] Y. V. Serdyuk, A. D. Podoltsev, and S. M. Gubanski, "Numerical simulations and experimental study of frequency-dependent dielectric properties of composite material with stochastic structure," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 379–392, Jun. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2004.1306717>.
- [47] A. M. Bruning, D. G. Kasture, F. J. Campbell, and N. H. Turner, "Effect of cavity sub-corona current on polymer insulation life," *IEEE Transactions on Electrical Insulation*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 826–836, Aug. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.1109/14.83709>.
- [48] N. H. Turner, F. J. Campbell, A. M. Bruning, and D. G. Kasture, "Surface chemical changes of polymer cavities with currents above and below corona inception voltage," in *Annual Report: Conference on Electrical Insulation and Dielectric Phenomena*, Victoria, BC, Canada, Oct. 1992, pp. 687–693, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CEIDP.1992.283139>.
- [49] A. M. Bruning and M. G. Danikas, "Experiments on polymer cavity currents above and below CIV," in *Annual Report: Conference on Electrical Insulation and Dielectric Phenomena*, Victoria, BC, Canada, Oct. 1992, pp. 735–740, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CEIDP.1992.283132>.
- [50] B. Bernstein, Personal communication with one of authors (MGD), 14th December 2009
- [51] G. E. Vardakis, M. Danikas, and A. Nterekas, "Partial Discharges in Cavities and their Connection with Dipoles, Space Charges, and Some Phenomena Below Inception Voltage," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 5869–5874, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3593>.
- [52] G. Melissinos and M. Danikas, "On Polymers Nanocomposites: Electrical Treeing, Breakdown models and Related Simulations," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2627–2632, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1726>.
- [53] Y. Zhang, M. G. Danikas, X. Zhao, and Y. Cheng, "Preliminary experimental work on nanocomposite polymers: Small partial discharges at inception voltage, the existence of possible charging mechanisms below inception voltage and the problem of definitions," *Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 63, no. 2, pp. 109–114, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10187-012-0016-8>.
- [54] Y. Zang *et al.*, "Charging phenomena below the inception voltage: Effects of nanofillers on epoxy," *Malaysian Polymer Journal*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 68–73, 2012.
- [55] S. Li, S. Yu, and Y. Feng, "Progress in and prospects for electrical insulating materials," *High Voltage*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 122–129, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1049/hve.2016.0034>.
- [56] K. K. Siderakis, D. Pylarinos, E. Thalassinakis, I. Vitellas, and E. Pyrgioti, "Pollution Maintenance Techniques in Coastal High Voltage Installations," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–7, Feb. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.6>.
- [57] M. Dimitropoulou, D. Pylarinos, K. Siderakis, E. Thalassinakis, and M. Danikas, "Comparative Investigation of Pollution Accumulation and Natural Cleaning for Different HV Insulators," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 764–774, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.545>.

Parametric Analysis of the Defected Ground Structure-Based Hairpin Band Pass Filter for VSAT System on Chip Applications

Navya Ambati

Department of ECE

Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation
Vaddeswaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

M. Venkata Narayana

Department of ECE

Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation
Vaddeswaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

M. Sri Prapura

Department of ECE

Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation
Vaddeswaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

Govardhani Immadi

Department of ECE

Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation
Vaddeswaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

Kalyan Reddy Baredy

Department of ECE

Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation
Vaddeswaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

Jayadeep Yanapu

Department of ECE

Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation
Vaddeswaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

Abstract—In this study, a three-pole hairpin structure was fabricated on the top of the substrate material and an open loop microstrip structure at the ground to give a modified triple-band BPF with a unique design. A Rogers (RT5880) material with $\epsilon_r = 2.2$ and thickness of 1.27mm was used to fabricate the proposed structure. The space between two consecutive hairpin resonators has different distances d_1 and d_2 with values of 0.2mm and 0.4mm respectively. The proposed filter offers a compact size with low return loss. The equivalent LC circuit of the DGS and hairpin structure is obtained with the Ansys electronic desktop and by using simple circuit analysis. The desired microstrip triple-band BPF operates at the Ku band, resonates at 10.28GHz, 12GHz, and 14.62GHz, while the simulated and experimental results are almost identical. The proposed wideband BPF satisfies the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) region 3 spectrum requirements. Direct Broadcast Service (DBS) and Fixed Satellite Service (FSS) in transmit mode respectively employ the frequency band 11.41-12.92GHz and 14-14.5GHz.

Keywords—hairpin line BPF; DGS; microstrip transmission line; group delay; return loss; insertion loss

I. INTRODUCTION

International Telecommunication Union (ITU) has divided the world into three zones for satellite applications in order to efficiently organize the spectrum. The frequency bands for FSS in receive and transmit mode in region-3 are 12.2-12.7GHz and 14-14.5GHz respectively. The reception and transmit frequencies for DBS are 11.7-12.2GHz and 17.3-17.8GHz. In modern wireless communication systems, RF/microwave filter is one of its indispensable components. The development of

transmission standards brought a fast-increasing growth of front-end RF devices and circuits [1, 2]. Their multi-band operation ability, system requirements, small sized filter, low cost, simple fabrication, and higher performance have attracted abundant interest. To satisfy these demands, attention has been centered on the microstrip printed filters because of their advantages in cost, size, and weight. DGS with periodic or aperiodic arrays allows a rejection range in some frequency bands to increase the effective inductance of a microstrip transmission line. These rejection properties of the DGS are available to many circuits such as coplanar antennas, power dividers, filter, etc. [5-7]. Bandpass Filters (BPFs) play a very important role in wireless communication applications due to their superior performance, minute size, and low attenuation within the prescribed pass band and high attenuation within the stop band. Ku-band is a part of the electromagnetic spectrum in the microwave frequency range. It ranges from 12 to 18GHz. The Ku-band is mostly used for TV and VSAT frameworks on boats. The band is split by the ITU into segments, modified by nations.

In this article, a new DGS is developed for the implementation of coupled line filter. An etched structure disrupts the shield current distribution in the ground plane. The properties of the transmission line, such as capacitance and inductance, can be affected by this disruption. As a result, the DGS is represented as an LC tank circuit [3, 4]. The circuit's S-parameters are calculated with a 3D finite element method simulator.

Corresponding author: Navya Ambati (ambatinavya88@gmail.com)

II. FILTER GEOMETRY

The proposed filter's design was simulated in the Electromagnetic Field Simulator and is fabricated on a Rogers (RT5880) substrate with permittivity $\epsilon_r = 2.2$, loss tangent 0.0009, and thickness of 1.27mm. The suggested microstrip hairpin line BPF has a size limit of $14 \times 16 \text{mm}^2$. The distances $d1$ and $d2$ for two consecutive hairpin resonators are distinct, with values 0.2mm and 0.4mm respectively. The ground-based microstrip open loop resonators act as a band rejection resonator. Here, we used 5 hairpin resonators to get an accurate range of frequency. The middle frequency corresponding to wavelength (λ) is affected by the length of the hairpin structure. We can observe that there is a change in f_0 while increasing the length of the microstrip resonators (L). A hairpin filter is designed at the Ku band by keeping the length resonators fixed. To obtain wide band width, the hairpin line BPF is manufactured with 5 resonators in the top plane, a dual armed microstrip resonator in the ground plane, while the ends of these resonators are connected to a 50Ω microstrip feed line.

Fig. 1. Equivalent circuit diagram of the filter. (a) Hairpin BPF, (b) DGS.

Fig. 2. Geometry of the proposed filter.

A. Constructional Details of the Filter

A hairpin line BPF with microstrip open loop resonators in the bottom of the substrate with dimensions is shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows the iteration-wise constructive design of a hairpin BPF with a defected ground structure.

Fig. 3. Hairpin BPF with defected ground structure. (a) Basic shape, (b) iteration 1, (c) iteration 2, (d) iteration 3, (e) iteration 4, (f) iteration 5.

Iteration 0 is the basic microstrip transmission line with a length and width of 15.45mm and 0.75mm. It is designed by using Ansoft HFSS. The length and width of the hairpin resonator are defined as L and W and are denoted by:

$$L = \frac{\lambda_g}{4} \quad (1)$$

where the guided wavelength is given as

$$\lambda_g = \frac{\lambda_0}{4F_r \sqrt{\epsilon_{r_{eff}}}} \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_{r_{eff}} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left[1 + \left[\frac{12h}{w} \right] \right]^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

where h , ϵ_r are the thickness and relative permittivity of the substrate:

$$\frac{w}{h} = \frac{2}{\pi} \left\{ (B-1) - \ln(2B-1) \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2\epsilon_r} \left[\ln(B-1) + 0.39 - \left(\frac{0.61}{2\epsilon_r} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$B = \frac{60\pi^2}{Z_c \sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (5)$$

In iteration 1, a single hairpin structure is designed on the top of the substrate and is fed by a microstrip transmission line. In iteration 2, two hairpin structures are placed on the top of the substrate. In a similar manner, the hairpin structures are added one by one up to iteration 4, and in the final step a defected ground structure is added to the existing hairpin structure to design a tri band BPF. The proposed design is designed to operate at 12GHz. The three transmission zeros at the pass band frequency spectrum are obtained by the hairpin resonators and dual armed microstrip open loop transmission resonators present in the filter.

B. Evolution

The step by step procedure of the proposed hairpin line BPF is represented in Figure 3. A 50Ω microstrip transmission line with a certain length and width will transfer the entire frequencies from one port to another. The hairpin resonators in the structure will reject the respective frequencies from hitting the load. In the second example, the energy flow from the source to the load can be altered by a single resonator. The power is coupled via the resonators from the source to the load, which results in a narrow pass band. It is simple to understand this with the help of Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Parametric analysis of the return loss of the proposed filter by successively adding the hairpin resonators.

C. Filter Analysis

Modeling and analysis of Hairpin line BPF with DGS was performed using HFSS. Their equivalent circuits were drawn with the Ansys electronic desktop. Examination of each filter parameter provided an insight into optimizing the design. The ground plane's microstrip transmission lines contain two transmission zeros at the two ends of the pass band frequency spectrum. In Tables I and II, the measurements used to design the microstrip open loop resonator and hairpin filter are shown.

TABLE I. RESONATOR MEASUREMENTS IN THE HAIRPIN LINE MICROSTRIP BPF

Parameters	Values
Substrate length (L)	9mm
Substrate width (W)	15.45mm
Resonator length (L0-L4)	4.6mm
Resonator height (H0, H2)	2.12mm
Resonator height (H1, H3)	1.73mm
Resonator feed line length (F-F10)	0.75mm
Resonator feed line width (W1-W4)	2.25mm
Resonator width (W, W0)	1.5mm

TABLE I. MEASUREMENTS OF THE MICROSTRIP OPEN LOOP RESONATORS IN THE BOTTOM PLANE

Parameters	Values
Resonator length (L0, L7)	0.75mm
Resonator length (L1)	5.37mm
Resonator length (L2)	2.88mm
Resonator length (L3, L6)	3.2mm
Resonator length (L4, L5)	1.7mm
Resonator width (W0)	8.903mm
Resonator width (W1, W2)	3.95mm
Resonator width (W3, W4)	3.2mm
Resonator width (W5, W6)	1.7mm
Resonator width (W7, W8)	3.275mm
Resonator width (W9)	4.403mm
Resonator width (W10, W11)	0.75mm
Resonator width (W12)	1.003mm

Fig. 5. (a) Top view and (b) bottom view of the proposed BPF. (c) The fabricated BPF. (d) Measuring the proposed BPF with a combinational analyzer.

The design goals of the proposed filter are the acquisition of a well specified reflection coefficient with wide bandwidth and of a transmission coefficient that allows satellite communication applications. The top and bottom views of the proposed microstrip hairpin line BPF are shown in Figure 5 and the dimensions used to design this filter are listed in Tables I and II.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For real time validation, the built prototype was fabricated and tested. The plots show that the simulated and measured

results are very close. The filter's return loss and insertion loss characteristics are detailed in Figure 7 and the reflection coefficient is below 10dB. The maximum possible filter's bandwidth is found to be 0.6GHz, 1.6GHz, and 0.7GHz. The insertion loss is far below 3dB in all states and the insertion loss obtained is 0.8dB. Table III provides a summary of the performance parameters based on the literature, from which it is noted that the proposed filter offers better return loss, transmission coefficient, and a wider bandwidth. Figure 5(d) represents the measurement of a transmission coefficient by using the Anritsu combinational analyzer. The parameters that are measured with this combinational analyzer are the S-parameter, group delay, and phase delay.

Fig. 6. Return loss of the hairpin BPF without DGS.

Figure 4 indicates the parametric analysis of the return loss obtained by successively adding the hairpin structures. The proposed filter is the iteration 5 which is of the basic shape, where the return loss and insertion loss characteristics are better than in other iterations. Figure 6 represents the return loss of the hairpin BPF without a DGS structure. Only two resonant bands are achieved at 12GHz and 13.5GHz with a return loss of -16dB and -17.2dB.

Fig. 7. Simulated vs measured results of return loss and insertion loss of the hairpin BPF with DGS.

Using the Vector Network Analyzer, the reflection coefficient of the manufactured filter was calculated. The proposed filter resonates at 10.28GHz, 12GHz, and 14.62GHz.

The relation between the measured and the computed group delay is shown in Figure 9. For the designed frequency band, the variance of reflection coefficient across frequencies is less than 10dB. The time domain characteristics of the microstrip hairpin line BPF are calculated by using group delay, as shown in Figure 9. With a deviation of 0.2ns, the group delay of the suggested filter is maximally flat. The delay induced by the filter is therefore consistent across the operating range, resulting in minimal signal distortion.

Fig. 8. Surface current distributions of the proposed BPF.

Fig. 9. Simulated vs measured results of group delay of the proposed filter.

The most important features for frequency and bandwidth of the proposed microstrip hairpin line BPF are:

- The proposed filter is designed to operate at the frequency of 12GHz. We can easily control bandwidth and frequency.
- The method is much simpler than the complicated standard methods such as coupling reducers and switched delay lines.
- The filter's frequency and bandwidth tuning features are independent.
- This filter is fabricated on a less valuable dielectric material, making many operations inexpensive and simple to replicate. Without encroaching additional space, the two microstrip resonators are enclosed within the stepped loop structure.
- By varying the size of the hairpin resonators and microstrip open loop structure accordingly, this prototype can be modelled to work at any desired frequency.

Table III compares the proposed wideband BPF with various known wide band BPFs at the Ku band. It is evident that the proposed wideband BPF has better bandwidth and insertion loss. Filters at the Ku band for satellite applications have been proposed in [8-11], but they all have narrower bandwidth and higher insertion loss. The proposed wideband BPF is compared with the bandpass filter proposed in [11] having high return loss, however the BPF has a bigger size and narrower bandwidth. Also, chemical etching microstrip devices without DGSs or vias also reduce process costs and improve manufacturing efficiency.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED WITH KNOWN BPFs

Ref.	Substrate	Reflection coefficient	Group delay	Area (mm ²)	Center frequency
[8]	Rogers RT/duroid	-14dB	-	5×13	13.3GHz
[9]	GaAs	-15dB	-	1.09×0.97	13.5GHz
[10]	FR4	-16dB	0.5ns	11.12×8	14GHz
[11]	FR4	-11dB	-	25×25	10GHz
Proposed	Rogers RT5880	-13.25dB -12.8dB -14.721dB	0.2ns	14×16	10.28GHz 12GHz 14.62GHz

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a hairpin BPF with microstrip feed line having defected ground structure has been designed for Ku band satellite applications. The proposed three-pole hairpin BPF is designed for low transmission coefficient, steep pass band edges, high out band rejection, and wide bandwidth, with a frequency band covering the transmit mode of FSS and DBS services (ITU region-3) with an insertion loss of 0.2dB and group delay of 0.2ns. In addition, the proposed filter is the first in this field to offer short group delay and large bandwidth, meeting the ITU Region 3 standards.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Richtarsic and J. Thornton, "Characterization and optimization of LTCC for high density large area MCM's," in *Proceedings. 1998 International Conference on Multichip Modules and High Density Packaging (Cat. No.98EX154)*, Denver, CO, USA, Apr. 1998, pp. 92–97, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMCM.1998.670761>.
- [2] H. Miyake, S. Kitazawa, T. Ishizaki, T. Yamada, and Y. Nagatomi, "A miniaturized monolithic dual band filter using ceramic lamination technique for dual mode portable telephones," in *1997 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest*, Denver, CO, USA, Jun. 1997, vol. 2, pp. 789–792 vol.2, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWSYM.1997.602908>.
- [3] J.-T. Kuo and H.-S. Cheng, "Design of quasi-elliptic function filters with a dual-passband response," *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 14, no. 10, pp. 472–474, Oct. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LMWC.2004.834560>.
- [4] M. Makimoto and S. Yamashita, "Bandpass Filters Using Parallel Coupled Stripline Stepped Impedance Resonators," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 28, no. 12, pp. 1413–1417, Dec. 1980, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.1980.1130258>.
- [5] A. A. Sulaiman et al., "Design of hairpin band pass filters for K-Band application," in *2008 IEEE International RF and Microwave Conference*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Dec. 2008, pp. 23–26, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RFM.2008.4897401>.
- [6] Y. Di, P. Gardner, P. S. Hall, H. Ghafouri-Shiraz, and J. Zhou, "Multiple-coupled microstrip hairpin-resonator filter," *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 13, no. 12, pp. 532–534, Dec. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LMWC.2003.819377>.
- [7] C.-K. Hsu, H.-H. Tung, and C.-H. Hsu, "Microstrip cross-coupled interdigital hairpin bandpass filter," in *2008 Asia-Pacific Microwave Conference*, Dec. 2008, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/APMC.2008.4958177>.
- [8] Q. Yang, X. Xiong, Y. Wu, L. Wang, and H. Xiao, "Design of microstrip tapped-hairpin dual-band pass filter for Ku-band application," in *2010 International Conference on Microwave and Millimeter Wave Technology*, Chengdu, China, May 2010, pp. 772–774, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMMT.2010.5525064>.
- [9] J. Sheen, Y.-H. Cheng, and W. Liu, "Ku-band Bandpass Filter Design with Compact Size and Broad Stopband by pHEMT Process," in *2019 Photonics Electromagnetics Research Symposium - Spring (PIERS-Spring)*, Rome, Italy, Jun. 2019, pp. 1022–1026, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PIERS-Spring46901.2019.9017867>.
- [10] C. S. Panda, R. Nayak, and S. K. Behera, "Design and analysis of a compact Substrate Integrated Waveguide bandpass filter for Ku band applications," in *2016 Online International Conference on Green Engineering and Technologies (IC-GET)*, Coimbatore, India, Nov. 2016, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/GET.2016.7916694>.
- [11] P. Sridharan and S. B.S., "Design and analysis of 1–10GHz band selected bandpass filter with broad tunable range," in *2014 International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing*, Melmaruvathur, India, Apr. 2014, pp. 303–306, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSP.2014.6949850>.
- [12] G. Zhiqiang, "A downsized and integrated C-band transceiver for VSAT," in *Proceedings of 1995 SBMO/IEEE MTT-S International Microwave and Optoelectronics Conference*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, Jul. 1995, vol. 1, pp. 33–36, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SBMOMO.1995.509594>.
- [13] J. S. Hong and M. J. Lancaster, *Microstrip Filters for RF/Microwave Applications*. New York, NY, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2001.
- [14] M. Hayati, L. Noori, and A. Adinehvand, "Compact dual-band bandpass filter using open loop resonator for multimode WLANs," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 48, no. 10, pp. 573–574, May 2012.
- [15] D. V. Doan, K. Nguyen, and Q. V. Thai, "A Novel Fuzzy Logic Based Load Frequency Control for Multi-Area Interconnected Power Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7522–7529, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4320>.
- [16] N. A. Zainurin, S. a. B. Anas, and R. S. S. Singh, "A Review of Battery Charging - Discharging Management Controller: A Proposed Conceptual Battery Storage Charging – Discharging Centralized Controller," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7515–7521, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4217>.
- [17] Z. A. Shamsan, "Statistical Analysis of 5G Channel Propagation using MIMO and Massive MIMO Technologies," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7417–7423, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4264>.
- [18] G. Immadi, N. K. Majji, M. V. Narayana, and A. Navya, "Comparative Analysis of Pass Band Characteristics of a Rectangular Waveguide with and Without a Dielectric Slab," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 1209–1211, Apr. 2019.
- [19] G. Immadi, M. V. Narayana, A. Navya, Y. D. S. Sairam, and K. Shrimanth, "Design and Analysis of Micro strip Circular Ring Band Stop Filter," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 788–790.
- [20] G. Immadi, M. V. Narayana, A. Navya, M. S. V. S. L. Sreejasree, D. S. Krishna, and V. S. Sindhu, "Analysis of Z-Shaped Microstrip Bandpass Filter at Ku Band," *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 8341–8344, May 2020.
- [21] G. Immadi, M. V. Narayana, A. Navya, M. S. V. S. L. Sreejasree, D. S. Krishna, and V. S. Sindhu, "Design of Circular Ring Resonator Microstrip Band Pass Filter at Ku Band," *Journal of Critical Reviews*, vol. 7, no. 13, pp. 465–467, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.13.81>.
- [22] G. Imamdi, M. V. Narayan, A. Navya, and A. Roja, "Reflector array antenna design at millimetric (mm) band for on the move applications," *ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 352–359, 2018.

Design of a 1×2 CPW Fractal Antenna Array on Plexiglas Substrate with Defected Ground Plane for Telecommunication Applications

Chiraz Ben Nsir

Department of Physics
University of Tunis El Manar
Tunis, Tunisia
chiraz.bennsir@fst.utm.tn

Chokri Boussetta

Department of Physics
University of Tunis El Manar
Tunis, Tunisia
chboussetta2020@gmail.com

Jean-Marc Ribero

Department of Electronics
University of Nice Sophia Antipolis
Nice, France
jean-marc.ribero@unice.fr

Ali Gharsallah

Department of Physics
University of Tunis El Manar
Tunis, Tunisia
ali.gharsallah@fst.utm.tn

Abstract—In this paper, a fractal antenna array for telecommunication applications is presented. The proposed antenna array is realized on a Plexiglas substrate, has 1×2 radiating elements, and dimensions of $170\text{mm} \times 105\text{mm}$. The antenna array is composed of two Koch Snowflake patches and is fed by a Coplanar Waveguide (CPW) transmission line. Radiating elements and the ground plane are printed on the top side of the substrate. Defected Ground Structure (DGS) technique is employed to enhance the bandwidth and improve the impedance matching. The proposed antenna array operates at two frequency bands, 1.08-1.32GHz covering the GPS band and 1.7-3.7GHz covering the GSM 1800/1900, UTMS, Bluetooth, LTE, and WiMAX bands. In addition, the antenna has a good performance with efficiency and peak gain of 82% and 6.3dB respectively. These characteristics allow the antenna to be an attractive candidate for telecommunication systems. Design and analysis of different structures were carried out with Ansys HFSS.

Keywords—fractal antenna array; DGS; CPW; wideband

I. INTRODUCTION

The advance in the telecommunication systems has increased significantly during the last years. Many research efforts have been focused to the integration of antennas into telecommunication systems because of their ease of implementation and their low cost. Moreover, the use of glass in the construction of buildings has increased. Therefore, the exploitation of these surfaces for the implementation of antennas is imposed. Antennas with small size and broadband behavior, operating in telecommunication frequency bands are highly recommended. Several techniques are used to achieve bandwidth enhancement. For instance, adding stubs [1] to the radiating element can improve bandwidth. Incorporation of slots on different parts of the antenna is another technique to

obtain broadband features [2-4]. The Coplanar Waveguide (CPW) is the most popular feeding structure utilized for multiband and wideband applications. Several studies prioritize the use of CPW over other excitation techniques, such as the microstrip line, due to features such as the ease of manufacturing, low cost, and wide bandwidth. Many antenna structures that include CPW feed-line have been studied and reported [5-12]. Consequently, the rapid demand of this kind of excitation keeps increasing. Among the techniques used to enhance bandwidth using CPW feed, is the optimization of either the distance between the ground plane and the radiator [13] or the distance between the feed line and the ground plane [14]. Thus, due to the features mentioned above, the CPW is chosen as the feed for the proposed antenna.

Antenna miniaturization is as an interesting topic as the broad-band antenna is. Reducing the size of the antennas can decrease their performance in terms of bandwidth, pattern stability, and efficiency. Thus, many studies have been focused to found an acceptable compromise between antenna size and its features. Antenna miniaturization techniques can affect either the geometry of the antennas by modifying their shapes or their electrical and magnetic characteristics. In [15], an overview has been presented to describe the most important techniques used for antenna miniaturization and the exploitation of these techniques for achieving wideband applications. Fractal geometry [16-17] is one of the most attractive techniques used for antenna design. The main properties of fractal antennas are their self-similarity and space-filling. Self-similarity shows multi-band and wide-band capabilities, while, with space-filling, the perimeter of the antenna can increase without changing the overall size. This property has been used for size reduction. Therefore, the use of fractal structures is a good technique for achieving miniaturized

Corresponding author: Chokri Boussetta

antennas [18]. Recently, numerous fractal geometries have been used to design antennas with compact size and wide bandwidth [19-22]. For instance, a microstrip patch antenna composed with Minkowski island and crossbar fractal layers operating from 4.1 to 19.4GHz for broadband applications has been proposed in [19]. The antenna presented in [20] has been designed using mushroom fractal geometry to achieve wide bandwidth. A novel broadband circular antenna with fractal elements was presented in [21]. Compactness and bandwidth enhancement were obtained in [22] using Koch geometry with the incorporation of modified ground plane and meandering slits, to design a wearable fractal antenna for the ISM band.

From the literature review, it was proved that using fractal geometry with the combination of various techniques can improve the antenna's performance. The proposed antenna array can be printed on a Plexiglas window. Thus, if the ground plane is placed on the bottom side of the Plexiglas substrate (i.e. the outside of the window), there will be a risk of degradation of the antenna performance by external factors such as rain, wind, and pollution. Therefore, the most beneficial is to put the total structure on the top side of the Plexiglas substrate (i.e. the inside of the window). As a result, the most appropriate technique is the use of CPW as feed. In this manner, the radiating elements, feed line, and ground planes will be printed on the same side of the substrate. In addition, the CPW feed insures wider impedance bandwidth, simple structure, low cost, and less radiation loss. The Koch structure [18] has shown the best results compared to the traditional simple patches in terms of efficiency, gain, miniaturization, and multiband and broadband behavior. Also, DGS technique is applied to further improve the bandwidth.

In this paper, a 1x2 fractal antenna array is proposed for telecommunication applications. The proposed antenna is composed by two Koch snowflake fractal patches and CPW is used for feeding. Modified ground plane is employed to enhance bandwidth and improve the impedance matching. Details of the antenna array, simulation results, and measurement are analyzed in the following sections.

II. THE SINGLE FRACTAL ANTENNA DESIGN

A. Koch Snowflake Geometry

The procedure shown in Figure 1 is adopted to generate the Koch snowflake fractal geometry. The Koch structure starts with an equilateral triangle with S being the side of the triangle. In order to obtain the first iteration, an equilateral triangle, which has a side S/3, is placed in the middle of each side of the basic triangle. Therefore, six equilateral triangles appear which have S/3 as side. In the same way, iteration 2 is constituted. In this case, an equilateral triangle, which has a side of S/9, is placed in the middle of each side of generated triangles. After n iterations, the side length of the produced triangles is S/3^n. As the number of iterations increases, the surface of the Koch snowflake tends towards a finite value while its perimeter tends to infinity. The perimeter of the Koch Snowflake after n iterations is given by:

$$P_n = 3 \left(\frac{4}{3}\right)^n S \quad (1)$$

The area of the Koch snowflake converges to:

$$A = \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{5} s^2 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. The Koch snowflake Iterations.

B. Koch Snowflake Geometry

The configuration of the single Koch snowflake antenna for dual-band operation is shown in Figure 2. This antenna is implemented on Plexiglas substrate with dielectric constant ε_r=2.6, thickness h=4mm and dimensions LxW=70x60mm². The radiating element is fed by a CPW transmission line which has a width of W_f=5mm, length L_f=25.6mm, and is separated from the ground plane with a gap distance of G=0.238mm. The width of the feed and the distance of the gap have been optimized to provide 50Ω characteristic impedance.

Fig. 2. Single Koch snowflake antenna configuration.

Initially, this antenna is composed by an equilateral triangular patch having S as side length and two limited ground planes which are placed symmetrically with respect to the CPW line. Then, the Koch snowflake geometry is obtained by adding two Koch iterations as shown in Figure 2. The optimized dimensions for this fractal antenna element are listed in Table I. The resonance frequency [23] of such an antenna is given by:

$$f_r = \frac{2c}{3s_e \sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (3)$$

$$S_e = S \left[1 + 2.199 \frac{h}{s} - 12.853 \frac{h}{s\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} + 16.436 \frac{h}{s\epsilon_r} + 6.182 \left(\frac{h}{s} \right)^2 - 9.802 \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \left(\frac{h}{s} \right)^2 \right] \quad (4)$$

where f_r is the resonant frequency, c the speed of light, ϵ_r the relative permittivity of the substrate, h the height of the substrate, S the patch side length, and S_e the effective patch side length.

TABLE I. OPTIMIZED SINGLE ANTENNA PARAMETERS

Parameters	Value (mm)	Parameters	Value (mm)
L	70	L_f	25.6
W	60	W_g	27.262
S	49.3	L_g	17.5
W_f	5	G	0.238

C. Results and Discussion

After fixing the CPW parameters and the side length S to 49.3mm, the proposed single Koch snowflake antenna is simulated. Figure 3 shows the reflection coefficient S_{11} of the simulated antenna. It can be observed that the proposed antenna covers two bands, 0.90-2.55GHz and 3.41-3.54GHz. The use of fractal geometry increases the perimeter length of the radiating element by increasing its electrical path without changing the total volume of the antenna. This method improves the antenna bandwidth and leads to reduced size.

Fig. 3. Simulated return loss of the single antenna.

Figure 4 shows the radiation pattern of the proposed single antenna at three frequencies, 1.8, 2.1, and 2.4GHz selected from the operating band, 0.90-2.55GHz. From the Figure, it is clear that the simulated radiation patterns are bidirectional in the E-plane and H-plane at all frequencies.

In this section, the basic element Koch snowflake fractal antenna was designed and optimized. This antenna attains good results in terms of bandwidth, return loss, and gain. In the following section, the previously developed single antenna is duplicated to form a fractal antenna array which is subsequently optimized to enhance the gain and improve the bandwidth in order to be suitable for integration in telecommunication systems.

Fig. 4. Simulated radiation patterns of the single antenna at 1.8, 2.1, 2.4GHz: (a) E-plane, (b) H-plane.

III. THE PROPOSED ANTENNA ARRAY DESIGN

The proposed 1×2 fractal antenna array is shown in Figure 5. The two Koch snowflake elements are identical to the basic single antenna previously reported. This antenna array is printed on the same substrate. The dimensions of the substrate are $170 \times 105 \text{mm}^2$. $D = 91 \text{mm}$ is the distance between the two fractal elements. The optimized parameters of the 1×2 antenna array are summarized in Table II. The modification in the ground-plane is used for the antenna array to achieve wider bandwidth with good impedance matching. The proposed antenna array is excited by the T-junction power divider [24] which has an input impedance of 50Ω .

Fig. 5. Configuration of the proposed antenna array.

Figure 6 shows the proposed power divider. $Z_a = 50 \Omega$ and $Z_b = 70.7 \Omega$ are the CPW line impedances used for feeding the antenna array. The width of the power divider as well as the gap between the ground plane and the divider play a crucial role for the determination of the characteristic impedances.

The gaps ($g_a = 0.238\text{mm}$ and $g_b = 0.612\text{ mm}$) and the widths ($W_f = 5\text{mm}$ and $W_{f1} = 3\text{mm}$) are used to obtain Z_a and Z_b . Equation (5) [25] is applied to determine these two impedances:

$$Z = \frac{30\pi}{\sqrt{\epsilon_e}} \frac{K(k'_0)}{K(k_0)} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_e = 1 + \frac{(\epsilon_r - 1)}{2} \left(\frac{K(k'_0)}{K(k_0)} \right) \left(\frac{K(k_1)}{K(k'_1)} \right) \quad (6)$$

where ϵ_e is the effective dielectric constant, K is the complete elliptic integral of the first kind, $k' = \sqrt{1 - k^2}$, and (k_0, k_1) are given as:

$$k_0 = \frac{W_f}{W_f + 2g} \quad (7)$$

$$k_1 = \frac{\sinh(\pi W_f / 4h)}{\sinh(\pi [W_f + 2g] / 4h)} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 6. The proposed power divider.

TABLE II. OPTIMIZED ANTENNA ARRAY PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value (mm)	Parameter	Value (mm)	Parameter	Value (mm)
W	170	W_g	82.262	L_f	25.6
W_1	16.449	W_{g1}	11	L_{f1}	25
W_2	29.051	W_{g2}	14	L_g	13.48
W_3	23.575	W_{g3}	25	L_{g1}	5.01
W_4	65	L	105	L_{g2}	5.01
W_5	10.262	L_1	17.738	s	49.3
W_6	38.374	L_2	24.388	D	91
W_f	5	L_3	12.262	g_a	0.238
W_{f1}	3	L_4	1.4	g_b	0.612

D. Design Procedure

The developed antenna array is carried out in four steps:

- Step-1: A fractal antenna array including a rectangular ground plane with a CPW power divider to feed the two radiating elements is designed.
- Step-2 and step-3: To enhance the impedance bandwidth and to obtain good impedance matching, the ground plane is modified to form a staircase on its upper edges. Two pairs of steps are used to form the staircase shape. The first pair is cut out from the ground plane, which has a size $L_{g1} \times W_{g3}$ of $5.01 \times 25\text{mm}^2$. Then, the second pair is cut out from the ground plane, which has a size $L_{g2} \times W_{g2}$ of $5.01 \times 14\text{mm}^2$. The relation between W_{g1} , W_{g2} , and W_{g3} is: $W_{g3} = W_{g1} + W_{g2}$.

- Step-4: Finally, the proposed antenna array is obtained by etching a rectangular slot, with a size $L_4 \times W_4$ of $1.4 \times 65\text{mm}^2$, in the rectangular ground plane placed between the two radiating elements in order to achieve the desired band.

E. Simulation Results and Parametric Study

Figure 7 shows the simulated S_{11} of the proposed fractal antenna array with and without stepped ground plane. According to the results, Koch snowflake fractal geometry contributes to the appearance of multi-band behavior by increasing the electrical length of the radiating elements. Moreover, stepped ground plane is used to improve the impedance matching. Indeed, the steps in the ground plane create close resonances. The combination of these resonances generates a wide bandwidth. In addition, by adding a rectangular slot in the ground plane, a new path is added for the current thus helping to further increase the bandwidth. Hence, the use of fractal geometry and DGS allows the designed antenna to achieve two operating bands, 1.13-1.39GHz covering the GPS band and 1.79-3.66GHz covering GSM 1800/1900, UTMS, Bluetooth, LTE, and WiMAX bands.

Fig. 7. Simulated return loss of the antenna array with and without stepped ground plane.

Three parameters are studied in order to evaluate their effects on the antenna and subsequently to choose the optimum values which improve the antenna performance.

1) Effect of length L_{g1}

L_{g1} is the length of the first step introduced in the ground plane. This parameter varies from 3.01mm to 6.01mm. The effect of varying L_{g1} on the return loss is shown in Figure 8. It is noticed that for different values of L_{g1} there are practically three frequency bands. By varying the parameter L_{g1} the impedance matching of the second band improves. Indeed, for $L_{g1} = 3.01\text{mm}$, the second band has an operating band from 1.73 to 2.94GHz and the return loss does not exceed -25dB. Thus, by increasing L_{g1} , the impedance matching enhances significantly in this band and for the optimum value $L_{g1} = 5.01\text{mm}$, the appearance of two resonant frequencies of 2.32 and 2.63GHz with an important value of return loss is observed. This result proves that L_{g1} has an effect on impedance matching enhancement.

Fig. 8. Simulated return loss for different values of L_{g1} .

Fig. 10. Simulated return loss for different values of L_4 .

2) Effect of width W_{g2}

The second parameter W_{g2} is the width of the second step of the staircase shaped modified ground plane and is varied from 9mm to 12mm as shown in Figure 9. It is observed from the result that by increasing the width W_{g2} , the upper cut-off frequency of the second band shifts toward the upper frequencies and starts to merge with the adjacent third band. A better result is obtained for $W_{g2} = 11$ mm. It is observed from the Figure that the impedance bandwidth ranges from 1.8 to 3.05GHz for the second band, while it ranges from 3.18 to 3.69GHz for the third band with a good return loss at both frequency bands. The obtained result proves that the parameter W_{g2} affects the impedance bandwidth of the proposed antenna and leads to better performance.

Fig. 9. Simulated return loss S_{11} for different values of W_{g2} .

3) Effect of Length L_4

By increasing L_4 from 1mm to 1.4mm as shown in Figure 10, the second and third frequency bands are combined, for $L_4 = 1.4$ mm, to form wideband ranges from 1.79 to 3.66GHz with a great impedance matching. However, the first frequency band remains almost in the same frequency range of 1.13 to 1.38GHz with a resonant frequency of 1.25GHz and with a return loss of -17dB. This result shows the effect of varying L_4 which leads to bandwidth improvement of the fractal antenna array and consequently covering the desired dual band.

IV. FABRICATION AND MEASURED RESULTS

To validate the simulated results carried out by Ansys HFSS, the proposed antenna was fabricated and tested. Figure 11 shows the prototype of the fabricated antenna array.

Fig. 11. The fabricated antenna array.

Figure 12 shows the simulated and measured return loss. A good agreement between the two curves is observed. The measured S_{11} is below -10dB from 1.7 to 3.7GHz. A small difference between simulation and measurement can be explained by manufacturing defects.

Fig. 12. Simulated and measured return loss of the proposed antenna array.

The radiation patterns of the proposed antenna array were measured in an anechoic chamber. Figure 13 shows the measured radiation patterns at the frequencies 1.8, 2.1, 2.4, and 2.6GHz in the E-plane and the H-plane. From these results, it is clear that the radiation pattern is bi-directional at all frequencies. The measured peak gain and total efficiency are shown in Figure 14. The peak gain is between 5.3dB and 6.3dB from 1.7 to 2.1GHz and between 6dB and 6.25dB from 2.3 to 2.7GHz. The minimum value of peak gain is 3.43dB at 2.16GHz. In addition, total efficiency is between 44% and 82% over the band 1.7-2.7GHz.

Fig. 13. Measured (solid line) and simulated (dashed line) radiation patterns of the proposed antenna in the E-plane and H-plane at: (a) 1.8GHz, (b) 2.1GHz, (c) 2.4GHz, and (d) 2.6GHz.

Fig. 14. Measured antenna peak gain and efficiency.

V. COMPARATIVE STUDY

Table III lists a comparison of the performance of the proposed Koch snowflake fractal antenna array with other, reported antenna arrays. The proposed antenna has a higher gain than those in [26-30]. In addition, the incorporation of Koch geometry, DGS, and CPW feed in the same structure has allowed the proposed antenna to obtain the widest impedance bandwidth compared to those in [27-30]. Therefore, these features make this antenna more advantageous for telecommunication systems than the previously reported antennas.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED WITH OTHER ANTENNA ARRAYS

Ref.	Array type	Feed method	Operating bands/ frequency bands (GHz)	BW (%)	Max gain
[26]	Octagonal fractal antenna array with DGS	Microstrip line feeding	2.3-14	140.64	<3.5 at lower frequencies
[27]	Hexagonal fractal antenna array	Coaxial feeding	1.3, 1.6, 2.4	2.76, 5.625, 4.33	Not given
[28]	Rectangular antenna array with DGS	Microstrip line feeding	2.2	5.45	4.14
[29]	Hexagonal fractal antenna array with DGS	Microstrip line feeding	2.6, 3.5, 5.7	15.38, 8.57, 4.38	4.2, 3.8, 3.6
[30]	E-shaped antenna array	Microstrip line feeding	2.45	3.67	2.48
Proposed	Koch fractal antenna array with DGS	CPW feeding	1.08-1.32, 1.7-3.7	19.83, 79.68	6.3

VI. CONCLUSION

A Koch snowflake fractal antenna array with CPW-fed printed on transparent substrate has been studied. The antenna achieved wideband characteristics and provided good performance in terms of return loss, radiation pattern, gain, and efficiency. The parametric study on the ground plane, which was modified using the DGS technique, contributed to the bandwidth enhancement of the proposed antenna. A good

accordance was acquired between the simulated and the experimental results. The designed antenna operates in two bands, 1.08-1.32GHz for GPS applications and 1.7-3.7GHz for GSM, UTMS, Bluetooth, LTE, and WIMAX applications. The obtained results make the antenna array suitable for telecommunication applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Li, T. Dong, and Z. Xia, "Wideband Printed Wide-Slot Antenna with Fork-Shaped Stub," *Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 3, Mar. 2019, Art. no. 347, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics8030347>.
- [2] M. M. Nahas and M. Nahas, "Bandwidth and Efficiency Enhancement of Rectangular Patch Antenna for SHF Applications," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4962–4967, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3014>.
- [3] M. S. Karoui, N. Ghariani, M. Lahiani, and H. Ghariani, "Bandwidth Enhancement of a Bell-shaped UWB Antenna for Indoor Localization Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6691–6695, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3975>.
- [4] A. Birwal, S. Singh, B. K. Kanaujia, and S. Kumar, "Broadband CPW-fed circularly polarized antenna for IoT-based navigation system," *International Journal of Microwave and Wireless Technologies*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp. 835–843, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1759078719000461>.
- [5] F. Faisal, Y. Amin, Y. Cho, and H. Yoo, "Compact and Flexible Novel Wideband Flower-Shaped CPW-Fed Antennas for High Data Wireless Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 67, no. 6, pp. 4184–4188, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2019.2911195>.
- [6] M. A. Riheen, T. Nguyen, T. K. Saha, T. Karacolak, and P. K. Sekhar, "CPW Fed Wideband Bowtie Slot Antenna on PET Substrate," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research C*, vol. 101, pp. 147–158, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.2528/PIERC20031402>.
- [7] P. Sharma and P. P. Bhattacharya, "Design and Development of a New Wideband CPW Fed Patch Antenna for Wireless Communication," *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Internet of Things*, vol. 5, no. 17, Jan. 2019, Art. no. e4, <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.31-10-2018.162734>.
- [8] M. Karthikeyan, R. Sitharthan, T. Ali, and B. Roy, "Compact multiband CPW fed monopole antenna with square ring and T-shaped strips," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 62, no. 2, pp. 926–932, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mop.32106>.
- [9] F. B. Ghenaya, R. Ghayoula, and A. Gharsallah, "A Novel Linear Array Antenna Based on UWB Slot Antenna," *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 290–298, 2016.
- [10] S. Patil, A. K. Pandey, and V. K. Pandey, "A Compact, Wideband, Dual Polarized CPW-Fed Asymmetric Slot Antenna for Wireless Systems," *Journal of Microwaves, Optoelectronics and Electromagnetic Applications*, vol. 19, pp. 343–355, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1590/2179-10742020v19i3827>.
- [11] B. Jmai, S. Gahgouh, and A. Gharsallah, "A Novel Reconfigurable MMIC Antenna with RFMEMS Resonator for Radar Application at K and Ka Bands," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 468–473, 2017.
- [12] Y. I. Abdulkarim *et al.*, "Design of a Broadband Coplanar Waveguide-Fed Antenna Incorporating Organic Solar Cells with 100% Insolation for Ku Band Satellite Communication," *Materials*, vol. 13, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 142, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13010142>.
- [13] S. Hu, Y. Wu, Y. Zhang, and H. Zhou, "Design of a CPW-Fed Ultra Wide Band Antenna," *Open Journal of Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 18–22, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojapr.2013.12005>.
- [14] R. Kumar and S. Gaikwad, "On the design of nano-arm fractal antenna for UWB wireless applications," *Journal of Microwaves, Optoelectronics and Electromagnetic Applications*, vol. 12, pp. 158–171, Jun. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1590/S2179-10742013000100013>.
- [15] M. Fallahpour and R. Zoughi, "Antenna Miniaturization Techniques: A Review of Topology- and Material-Based Methods," *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, vol. 60, no. 1, pp. 38–50, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MAP.2017.2774138>.
- [16] A. Bunde and S. Havlin, "Fractal Geometry, A Brief Introduction to," in *Mathematics of Complexity and Dynamical Systems*, New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2009, pp. 409–428.
- [17] M. Nurujjaman, A. Hossain, and D. P. Ahmed, "A Review of Fractals Properties: Mathematical Approach," *Science Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 98–105, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.sjams.20170503.11>.
- [18] A. Reha, A. El Amri, O. Benhammouch, and A. Oulad Said, "Fractal Antennas : A Novel Miniaturization Technique for wireless Networks," *Transactions on Networks and Communications*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 165–193, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.14738/tnc.25.566>.
- [19] R. Kubacki, M. Czyżewski, and D. Laskowski, "Minkowski Island and Crossbar Fractal Microstrip Antennas for Broadband Applications," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 3, Mar. 2018, Art. no. 334, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app8030334>.
- [20] S. Nelaturi and N. V. S. N. Sarma, "Compact Wideband Microstrip Patch Antenna based on High Impedance Surface," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3149–3152, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1971>.
- [21] A. Dastranj, F. Ranjbar, and M. Bornapour, "A New Compact Circular Shape Fractal Antenna for Broadband Wireless Communication Applications," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research C*, vol. 93, pp. 19–28, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.2528/PIERC19031001>.
- [22] A. Arif, M. Zubair, M. Ali, M. U. Khan, and M. Q. Mehmood, "A Compact, Low-Profile Fractal Antenna for Wearable On-Body WBAN Applications," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 981–985, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LAWP.2019.2906829>.
- [23] M. Dadel, K. P. Tiwary, and S. Srivastava, "Log periodic triangular patch array antenna with gap coupled feed," in *International Conference on Signal Processing and Communication*, Noida, India, Mar. 2015, pp. 99–104, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSPCom.2015.7150628>.
- [24] Y. A. Rayisiwi and T. Hariyadi, "Design of A 1:12 Power Divider at 5 GHz for Ground Surveillance Radar Application," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 384, Jul. 2018, Art. no. 012053, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/384/1/012053>.
- [25] R. N. Simons, *Coplanar Waveguide Circuits, Components, and Systems*. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 2001.
- [26] S. Tripathi, A. Mohan, and S. Yadav, "A Compact UWB Koch Fractal Antenna for UWB Antenna Array Applications," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 92, no. 4, pp. 1423–1442, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-016-3613-1>.
- [27] S. S. Kadam, N. S. Patil, P. B. Jadhav, and P. B. Kashid, "Formation of Fractal Antenna Array for Multiband Applications," *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3257–3263, Nov. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.D8048.118419>.
- [28] R. A. Pandhare, P. L. Zade, and M. P. Abegaonkar, "Miniaturized microstrip antenna array using defected ground structure with enhanced performance," *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 1360–1367, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jestech.2016.03.007>.
- [29] S. Palanisamy, B. Thangaraju, O. I. Khalaf, Y. Alotaibi, S. Alghamdi, and F. Alassery, "A Novel Approach of Design and Analysis of a Hexagonal Fractal Antenna Array (HFAA) for Next-Generation Wireless Communication," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 19, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 6204, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14196204>.
- [30] S. Nagaraju, B. V. Kadam, L. J. Gudino, S. M. Nagaraja, and N. Dave, "Performance analysis of rectangular, triangular and E-shaped microstrip patch antenna arrays for wireless sensor networks," in *International Conference on Computer and Communication Technology*, Allahabad, India, Sep. 2014, pp. 211–215, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCT.2014.7001494>.

The Influence of Base Layer Thickness in Flexible Pavements

Muhammed Abdul Sada Hadi
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
m.hadi1901m@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Mohannad H. Al-Sherrawi
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
dr.mohannad.al-sherrawi@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract-Flexible pavement design and analysis were carried out in the past with semi-experimental methods, using elastic characteristics of pavement layers. Due to the complex interferences between various layers and their time consumption, the traditional pavement analysis, and design methods were replaced with fast and powerful methods including the Finite Element Method (FEM) and the Discrete Element Method (DEM). FEM requires less computational power and is more appropriate for continuous environments. In this study, flexible pavement consisting of 5 layers (surface, binder, base, subbase, and subgrade) had been analyzed using FEM. The ABAQUS (6.14-2) software had been utilized to investigate the influence of the base layer depth on vertical stresses and displacements. Three different thicknesses were adopted (10, 20, and 30cm) with constant other pavement layer thicknesses. The results of this study showed that the stress levels at the top of the base layer increased by about 37% when the thickness of this layer increased from 10cm to 30cm, while the stress levels at the top of the subbase layer decreased by about 64%. When the base layer increased from 10 to 20, from 20 to 30, and from 10 to 30cm the vertical displacement decreased by 18%, 24%, and 37% respectively.

Keywords-flexible pavement; ABAQUS; base thickness; finite element method

I. INTRODUCTION

Standard flexible pavements with surface of Asphalt Concrete (AC) are used worldwide. The different layers of the flexible pavement structure have various strength and deformation properties, which make difficult to analyze the system layers [1]. Factors such as material properties, geometry of pavement structures, environment, traffic loading and construction practices affect the pavements. Furthermore, vehicle characteristics, load axle, and wheel configuration may cause damage to the pavements [2]. If the induced strains due to the external load are relatively small, stresses and deformations are usually estimated using the theory of elasticity. Semi-analytical and analytical solutions are available to analyze the behavior of elastic layered pavements subjected to surface loads. In solutions concerning the analysis of the pavement layer system under traffic load, the pavement layers are considered homogeneous, isotropic, and linear elastic [2].

Finite Element Method (FEM) is used to simulate several pavement problems that cannot be modelled using the elastic multi-layer theory. ABAQUS is commercial Finite Element (FE) modeling software. The ABAQUS (6.14-2) software package of engineering analysis is used world-wide to simulate the physical response from loading, contact, temperature, impact, and other conditions of the environment of structures and solid organisms [3]. The software can manage the assembly of parts (including flexible pavement layers, i.e. surface, binder, base-course, sub-base, and sub-grade layer) and define the interactions between these layers and the appropriate boundary conditions. Finally, it can find the value of maximum stress and the displacement for all pavement layers.

Several studies of the behavior of flexible floors in recent years have studied three-dimensional (3D) FE models. Authors in [4] employed the discretization of a 3-layer flexible pavement system subject to various loading types using the FE technique. Three layers of the same elastic module have been applied to turn the three layer systems into equivalent, simpler single-layer systems in the analysis. The utility of the 2-dimensional FE ANSYS program analytics has been described in [5], in order to examine the influence of the variation of thickness on crucial parameters of distinct component layers. It was observed that the tensile strain at the base of the asphalt layer and the compressive strain above the subgrade layer decline, when the depth of the asphalt layer increases. The authors also discussed the utility of FEM analysis for the exploration of the bituminous pavement characteristic sensitivity analysis. One aspect of the analysis was to check for the hypothesized trials of the sensitivity of the axis-symmetric horizontal dimension. Mesh refinement study was also conducted on the selected thickenings and material properties of various layers. Authors in [6] studied the effect of increasing axle load and the variation of pavement modulus on the overall pavement life. The results showed that tensile and compressive strain increased when the axle load increased and decreased when the asphalt layer modulus increased. Authors in [7] used ABAQUS to evaluate the stress and vertical displacement on the top of the surface layer in multi-layer flexible pavements under static loading. It was observed that raised thickness of the pavement surface layer led to reduction of the deformation and stress levels.

Corresponding author: Mohannad H. Al-Sherrawi

II. FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT

One of the most effective techniques used to simulate the response of different structural engineering challenges is the FEM. It has become the most extensively utilized technique in both academic and industrial numerical simulations [8]. Over the last three decades, substantial advancements in computer programs and FE techniques have made many commonly used 3D structural studies more affordable. The current research models and investigates the behavioral reaction of the pavement system using the ABAQUS 6.14-2 package [9]. Solid structural 3D pavement analysis utilizing the linear, general purpose brick element C3D8R has been adopted in the modeling process. Small elements are necessary to capture a stress concentrated at the structural limit [3].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Pavement Model

3D FE was used to model the surface, binder, base course, subbase, and subgrade, all of which may be considered as closed systems of numerous layers. In the present work, a conventional pavement section was considered, consisting of bituminous layers (surface, binder, base), subbase, and subgrade to study the effect of base layer thickness on the flexible pavement layers' performance, starting from 10cm with an increment of 10cm with fixed surface, binder, subbase, and subgrade depth thickness (4, 7.5, 20, and 250 cm respectively), as shown in Table I.

TABLE I. LAYER THICKNESSES

Layer	Layer name	Thickness (cm)		
		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
1	Surface	4	4	4
2	Binder	7.5	7.5	7.5
3	Base course	10	20	30
4	Subbase	20	20	20
5	Subgrade	250	250	250

The pavement geometry has the following dimensions: 500cm in the y- and the x-axes and 300cm in the z-axis. Only a quarter of the sample was used by using the 3D axis-symmetry property to reduce effort and time. The pavement geometry with the model can be seen in Figures 1, 2. A standard single axle load of a dual tire of 80kN was considered.

Fig. 1. Geometry model of the flexible pavement: (a) top view, (b) a quarter analytical model.

Fig. 2. The 3D multilayer model.

B. Material Properties

The layers' material characterizations listed in Table II were used in the FE program for flexible pavement models.

TABLE II. MATERIAL PROPERTIES FOR ROAD LAYERS [10]

Layer	Modulus of elasticity (E), kpa	Poisson ratio
Surface	2689000	0.35
Binder	2206000	0.35
Base	1655000	0.35
Subbase	110000	0.40
Subgrade	35000	0.499

C. Contact Area and Tire Pressure

The print area of the tire can be represented by two semicircles and a rectangle [11]. This shape is converted to a rectangle with an area of $0.5227 \times L^2$. The contact area has dimensions of 0.202m and 0.14m. In research and computing applications, even such a simple model is often applied as a uniformly distributed load over a circular or rectangular area [11].

D. Wheel Load Characterization

The wheel load is a standard axle loading simplified in a rectangular uniform surface charge treated as a single axis dual tire [11]. The standard has one axle, dual tires, and contact pressure equivalent to the pressure of the tire. The pressure of the tire is 750kPa and the overall load of the axle is 80kN [6]. The load zone established by the vehicle load is illustrated in Figure 3. The width of the print zone is 14cm for each tire, which is the same as the width of uniformly distributed surface loads and the length of the print tire is 20.3cm.

E. Boundary Conditions

Boundary conditions have a major effect on the prediction of the model response. The lower surfaces against all degrees of freedom are assumed to be entirely fixed for boundary conditions [12]. The edges can move in the vertical (y-) direction for all the geometry models of the pavement. In FE analysis, no movement is considered in the horizontal directions for the four sides of the model. These boundary

conditions were chosen in order to simulate the real boundary conditions [13] as shows in Figure 5.

Fig. 3. Standard axle load, critical loads, and loading form.

Fig. 4. The boundary conditions of the model.

F. Interaction Modeling Techniques

The Interaction module is employed to simulate the contact surface between the asphalt and the foundation layers [3]. The interaction between the sections of the model with ABAQUS needs to be established in order to define the interaction surfaces.

Fig. 5. The interaction layer used in the model.

There are numerous contact formulations and standards in ABAQUS, for the modeling of the interaction between layers. The contact between two flexible or deformable and rigid surfaces is referred to as surface-to-surface contact. The

degrees of freedom between the mode areas are utilized in the interaction module constraint and the limitations can be suppressed and repeated to alter the analytical model. The definition of contact is shown in Figure 5. Finally, the ABAQUS interaction module simulates the interaction of several layers of the pavement (surface and binder, binder and base, base and subbase, and subgrade and base) with the tire contact.

G. Mesh Size Distribution in The Model

Figure 6 presents the FE mesh of the model. The average mesh size under the wheel path is about 5cm and the total number of elements is more than 20000. Using a finer mesh near the load when modeling the pavement block as a FE model increases the accuracy of the results [14].

Fig. 6. Mesh size distribution for the 3D dual tire model.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stresses and displacements generated in pavement layers and interfaces due to the effect of wheel loads are some of the most primary considered elements in the design of flexible pavements. The obtained results of stresses and their vertical distribution from the FE model analysis adopted in this research are presented in Figures 7-12.

Fig. 7. Horizontal stress (σ_{xx}) distribution within pavement layers, case 1.

Fig. 8. Vertical displacement distribution within pavement layers, case 1.

Fig. 9. Horizontal stress (σ_{xx}) distribution within pavement layers, case 2.

Fig. 10. Vertical displacement distribution within pavement layers, case 2.

Fig. 11. Horizontal stress (σ_{xx}) distribution within pavement layers, case 3.

Fig. 12. Vertical displacement distribution within pavement layers, case 3.

The distribution of vertical stresses (σ_{22}) in the pavement system is shown in Table III. In case 1, a maximum vertical stress of 750kPa is concentrated on the top of the surface layer under the tire print. It is reduced to 579.91kPa at the top of the binder layer, which is about 77.7% of the applied pressure. At the top of the base layer, the stress is reduced to a value of 195.63kPa (about 26% of the applied tire pressure). It decreases to 40.547kPa and 20.071kPa (about 5% and 2.5% of the applied tire pressure) on the top of the subbase and the subgrade layer respectively.

In case 2, the vertical stress is reduced to 600.33kPa, 240.39kPa, 22.39kPa, and 13.14kPa at the top of the binder, base, subbase, and subgrade layers (about 80%, 32%, 2.9% and 1.6% of the applied pressure respectively).

In case 3, the vertical stress is reduced to 606.03kPa, 268.87kPa, 14.075kPa, and 9.4576kPa at the top of the binder, base, subbase, and subgrade layers (about 81%, 38%, 1.7% and 1.1% of the applied pressure respectively).

TABLE III. STRESS LEVELS BETWEEN THE INTERFACED LAYERS

Layer name	Vertical Stress (σ_{22}), kPa		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Top of binder	579.91	600.33	606.03
Top of base	195.63	240.39	268.87
Top of subbase	40.547	22.39	14.075
Top of subgrade	20.071	13.14	9.4576

The results of this study show that the stress levels at the top of the base layer increased by about 37% when the thickness of this layer increased from 10cm to 30cm, while the stress levels at the top of the subbase layer decreased by about 64%. By increasing the thickness of the base layer, the stress level was reduced, as shown in Figure 13. Also, the vertical stresses at shallow depths under the tire print slightly vary when the thickness of the base layer increases, but the difference is negligible at large horizontal distance and depth.

Fig. 13. Vertical stress vs depth.

Fig. 14. Vertical displacement on the top of the surface layer.

Figure 14 displays the vertical displacement on the top of the surface layer under the center of the inner wheel with horizontal distance for all cases. When the base layer is increased from 10 to 20cm, 20 to 30cm, and 10 to 30cm the vertical displacement decreases by 18%, 24%, and 37% respectively. The calculated results from this study are in accordance with those in [15], in which the authors used the ABAQUS to simulate flexible pavements and study the effect of increased base layer thickness on the response of the pavement. The results showed that when the base layer

thickness changed from 10 to 30cm, the deformation on the surface layer reduced by 41%. Authors in [16] studied the effect of the variation of the thickness of the base layer. It was observed that the number of rutting cycles increased by 4.48% with the change in the thickness of the base layer from 30cm to 45cm. However, the same increase was only 2.47% when the change in thickness was from 45cm to 60cm. Authors in [17] used the ABAQUS program to study the effect of four thicknesses of the base layer, namely 5, 8, 10, and 12cm to the elastic and elasto-plastic behavior. The result in the elastic behavior when the thickness of the asphalt changed from 5 to 12cm was that the deflection on the top of the layer reduced from 4.1 to 1.2mm.

V. CONCLUSION

The following are the main conclusions based on the results of this study:

- The percentage of the deformation decreases by 37%, 18%, and 24% when the thickness increases from 10 to 30cm, from 10 to 20cm, and from 20 to 30cm respectively, so the base layer plays the main role in reducing the deformation on the surface layer in the pavement structure.
- The vertical stress on the top of the base layer is 195, 240, and 268kPa for base layer thickness of 10, 20, and 30cm respectively. It decreases to 40.54, 22.39, and 14.07kPa on the top of the subbase layer corresponding to approximately 20%, 9%, and 5% of the applied stress on the top of the base layer. When the thickness of the base layer increases, the stresses in the layers below the base layer decrease, and thus the stresses above the sub layer decrease.
- It is clear from the study that the vertical stress decreases with the increase in the vertical depth of the all layers. Therefore, the upper layers must be of high quality.
- If the flexible paving layers are too thin, the overall structure of the pavement may disintegrate before the designed life time.
- ABAQUS gives high accuracy in the analysis of multi-layer flexible pavements in addition to the reduction of effort, time, and costs in comparison with the laboratory tests.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Kumela, "Evaluation of Flexible Pavement Deflections with Respect to Pavement Depths Using Software (A Case Study Jimma to Seka Road)," *American Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 141–146, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajce.20180605.11>.
- [2] E. M. Abd Alla, "The rational use of finite element method in the analysis of flexible pavements," *JES. Journal of Engineering Sciences*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 1185–1211, Jul. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.21608/jesaun.2006.110780>.
- [3] "Getting Started with ABAQUS/Explicit: Keywords Version (v6.5-1)," *Abacus Documentation*. <https://classes.engineering.wustl.edu/2009/spring/mase5513/abaqus/docs/v6.5/books/gsx/default.htm?startat=ch04s01.html> (accessed Nov. 16, 2021).
- [4] S. Helwany, J. Dyer, and J. Leidy, "Finite-Element Analyses of Flexible Pavements," *Journal of Transportation Engineering*, vol. 124, no. 5, pp. 491–499, Sep. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-947X\(1998\)124:5\(491\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-947X(1998)124:5(491)).
- [5] M. S. Ranadive and A. B. Tapase, "Parameter sensitive analysis of flexible pavement," *International Journal of Pavement Research and*

- Technology, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 466–472, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijprt.2016.12.001>.
- [6] A. E. A. E.-M. Behiry, "Fatigue and rutting lives in flexible pavement," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 367–374, Dec. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2012.04.008>.
- [7] F. Khodary, H. Akram, and N. Mashaan, "Behaviour of different pavement types under traffic loads using finite element modelling," *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 40–48, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.34218/IJCET.11.11.2020.004>.
- [8] A. Lazizi, H. Trouzine, A. Asroun, and F. Belabdelouhab, "Numerical Simulation of Tire Reinforced Sand behind Retaining Wall Under Earthquake Excitation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 605–611, Apr. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.427>.
- [9] A. S. Mahdi and S. D. Mohammed, "Experimental and Numerical Analysis of Bubbles Distribution Influence in BubbleDeck Slab under Harmonic Load Effect," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6645–6649, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3963>.
- [10] A. H. Abed and A. A. Al-Azzawi, "Evaluation of Rutting Depth in Flexible Pavements by Using Finite Element Analysis and Local Empirical Model," *American Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 163–169, Aug. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.3844/ajeassp.2012.163.169>.
- [11] Y. Huang, *Pavement Analysis and Design*, 2nd ed. Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA: Pearson, 2003.
- [12] P. C. Nguyen, D. D. Pham, T. T. Tran, and T. Nghia-Nguyen, "Modified Numerical Modeling of Axially Loaded Concrete-Filled Steel Circular- Tube Columns," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7094–7099, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4157>.
- [13] M. T. Rahman, K. Mahmud, and S. Ahsan, "Stress-Strain Characteristics of Flexible Pavement by Finite Element Method," *International Journal of Civil and Structural Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 233–240, Sep. 2011.
- [14] H. Wang and I. L. Al-Qadi, "Evaluation of Surface-Related Pavement Damage due to Tire Braking," *Road Materials and Pavement Design*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 101–121, Jan. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680629.2010.9690262>.
- [15] F. Khodary, H. Akram, and A. Othman, "Prediction of Flexible Asphalt Pavement Performances under Material Properties in Variation Influence," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science*, vol. 6, no. 12, pp. 11953–11963.
- [16] A. B. Tapase and M. S. Ranadive, "Performance Evaluation of Flexible Pavement Using the Finite Element Method," pp. 9–17, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784480090.002>.
- [17] G. Shafabakhsh, M. Motamedi, and A. Famili, "Influence of asphalt concrete thickness on settlement of flexible pavements," *EDJE*, vol. 18, pp. 473–483, Jan. 2013.

Efficiency Assessment of a Signalized Roundabout and a Traffic Intersection in Baghdad City

Hajir Hussein Mohammed
Civil Engineering Department
Baghdad University
Baghdad, Iraq

h.arkwazee1901m@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Mohammed Qadir Ismail
Civil Engineering Department
Baghdad University
Baghdad, Iraq

drmohammedismael@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract—In Baghdad city, Iraq, the traffic volumes have rapidly grown during the last 15 years. Road networks need to be reevaluated and decide if they are operating properly or not regarding the increase in the number of vehicles. Al-Jadriyah intersection (a four-leg signalized intersection) and Kamal Junblat Square (a multi-lane roundabout), which are two important intersections in Baghdad city with high traffic volumes, were selected to be reevaluated by the SIDRA package in this research. Traffic volume and vehicle movement data were abstracted from videotapes by the Smart Traffic Analyzer (STA) Software. The performance measures include delay and LOS. The analysis results by SIDRA Intersection 8.0.1 show that the performance of the roundabout is better than the signalized intersection but experiences high delay, and low LOS. Therefore, alternatives are proposed to improve the performance for current and future traffic volumes with low-medium delays.

Keywords—signalized intersection; multi-lane roundabout; delay; LOS

I. INTRODUCTION

Road traffic congestion comprises several complex procedures and incorporates numerous components cooperating simultaneously. In such a condition, a simulation modeler can be a very effective tool as it provides evaluations for various traffic conditions [1]. The increment in the demand for private transportation increases traffic congestion during peak hours [2, 3]. The streets are a key component and the vital arteries of a city, as well as an important timekeeper compass for the movement of the population in the city. Streets intersect with each other and intersections can be either controlled or uncontrolled. One of the best methods to facilitate the traffic at uncontrolled intersections is roundabouts. Frequently, the presence of a roundabout is inevitable because of its advantages such as reduced delays, improved traffic flow, safety, fewer conflicts, and economy. When rising rates of congestion and accidents are observed, there is a need to study this problem to find a solution. There is no doubt that the traffic problems whether congestion-related or accidents comprise crucial problems for most countries. However, the phenomenon of traffic congestion in the streets [4], especially in the streets which are not controlled by traffic control devices, has been exacerbated dramatically in recent years, especially in

Baghdad. The problem of increasing traffic volume is that the absorptive capacity of the roads is not able to accommodate the traffic flow at peak hours resulting in traffic congestion and accidents. Human factors account for 67% of the accidents, while road conditions account for 29%, and vehicle defects for 4% [5]. Many remedies have been proposed to prevent or reduce the accident rates, including proper driver education and sign boards and traffic signals wherever they are needed. Every highway should be made to have three lanes in each direction (two lanes would suffice for roads) and the roads should be properly maintained [6]. Variable Speed Limits (VSLs) are used to improve highway performance in terms of comfort and safety [7].

The operational performance evaluation will be conducted using the intelligent software SIDRA Intersection 5 which is a micro-analytical traffic evaluation tool that employs lane-by-lane and vehicle drive cycle models [8]. Its function is to compare different treatments of separate intersections as well as networks of intersections involving signalized and un-signalized intersection roundabouts. Authors in [9] studied the conversion option of 3-leg and 4-leg roundabouts to signalized 3-leg and 4-leg intersections. The performance of real existing roundabouts in Jeddah and Al-Madinah cities was evaluated. In terms of performance, the signalized intersection is the recommended option for the 3-leg roundabouts when the degree of saturation is over 80% and there is high left-turning volume. In [10], the authors studied the capacity and performance of the roundabouts in Nigeria, Makurdi, Wurukum using ARCADY and SIDRA Intersection. They suggested the use of fly-over bridges, the alteration of geometrical features, and the signalization of the roundabouts with road signs and proper pavement markings. Authors in [11] evaluated the performance of nested signalized roundabouts located in Niğde, Turkey, and compared the roundabout intersection solutions with the HCS6 method using the SIDRA Intersection software. The analysis showed that with the application of a modern roundabout, higher performance was observed. The average delay decreased by 72.8%, while the capacity increased by 67.8%. Their conclusion was that the use of roundabout control instead of a nested signal system might increase the performance of traffic flow. In [12], the authors

Corresponding author: Hajir Hussein Mohammed

used SIDRA Intersection to compare the operational performance evaluation of conventional signalized and non-signalized roundabouts and the potential replacement of conventional roundabouts with turbo ones. The delay time for the conventional signalized and non-signalized roundabouts was 407.2s and 337.6s respectively and LOS was F with forced or breakdown flows for both roundabouts. The authors concluded that the implementation of turbo roundabouts might reduce the risk of fatalities by 80% and increase the capacity by forcing the drivers to use inner lanes.

Authors in [13] used SIDRA to evaluate LOS and delays of the Al-Turkman Roundabout in Baghdad to improve its performance by proposing planning procedures to address the traffic jam and congestion problems in this area. In [14], the authors studied the performance of two signalized intersections in Bangi, Malaysia using the SIDRA software. The conclusion was that signalized intersection 2 performed better than the signalized intersection 1. Authors in [15] examined two signalized intersections using Sidra Intersection 5.1 based on the Australian, and American HCM methods and proposed new cycle times to improve their performance. The capacity values of Kule and Nalçacı-Sille signalized intersections according to the Australian method were higher than those obtained with the American method by about 7%. Similarly, the delay and the degree of saturation values according to the Australian method were lower by about 11% and 8% respectively. The Australian and the American methods proposed an optimum cycle time of 125s and 145s for Kule Intersection. Similarly, 70s and 85s were proposed respectively for the Nalçacı-Sille intersection. Therefore, the Australian method was considered better than the American method in terms of proposed cycle times because the traffic is affected negatively by long cycle times.

Authors in [16] studied the performance of three 4-leg signalized intersections and four roundabouts in Karbala city, Iraq using SIDRA Intersection and proposed alternatives for performance improvement. All the outputs were categorized by medium to high total delays, thus the level of service for most of the intersections was (F). Some alternatives were suggested: the performance of the intersection improved by about 50% with pavement remarking and lane designation and the MOE of the intersections improved by about 66% by pavement widening. In [17], the authors studied an optimization method of the factors that affect the signalized intersection operation. Three signalized intersections located in Al-Mansur, Baghdad were selected. The calibrated analysis results showed that after cycle time improvement application, the delay and queue length decreased.

Authors in [18] studied the operational performance of one highway, three intersections, and seventeen urban roads in Al-Kadhimiya, Baghdad, with the HCS2000 software and proposed performance improvement alternatives. The LOS of all intersections in existed conditions was (F). Increasing the number of lanes and selecting the best cycle time was suggested as the best alternatives for all signalized intersections and arterial roads. The LOS improved to (C), and in addition to the overpass alternative, the LOS was upgraded to (B) for signalized intersections. At the same time, the LOS of arterial roads improved and varied between (C) and (E). Total delay

was sufficiently decreased, and the operational performance improved for all intersections.

II. METHODOLOGY

Kamal Junblat Square (a 4-leg roundabout intersection) and Al-Jadriyah Intersection (a 4-leg signalized intersection) located in Baghdad city, Iraq (Figures 1-2) were selected to have their performance evaluated.

Fig. 1. Kamal Junblat square (Google Earth, © Maxar Technologies).

Fig. 2. Al-Jadriyah intersection (Google Earth, © Maxar Technologies).

The traffic data were collected for 10 regular working weekdays (from 17/01/2021 to 21/01/2021, and 07/02/2021 to 11/02/2021) with no holidays, no accidents, or unnatural security activities. The weather conditions on each video recording were normal without rain and the visual conditions were good. Two peak periods were acknowledged from the video observation. At least two hours are recommended to straddle the peak hour time since the traffic on various approaches usually vary, and it is necessary to ensure that the peak hour of each approach is included [19]. The morning period consists of 3 hours (from 7:00 AM to 10:00 AM) and the evening period consists of 2 hours (from 1:00 PM to 3:00 PM). The traffic data were extracted from videotapes with the use of the Smart Traffic Analyzer (STA) software as presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Collecting traffic volume and vehicle classification with the STA program.

Fig. 4. Traffic volume of the morning period (Al-Jadriyah intersection).

Fig. 5. Traffic volume of the evening period (Al-Jadriyah intersection).

Fig. 6. Traffic volume of the morning period (Kamal Junblat Square).

Fig. 7. Traffic volume of the evening period (Kamal Junblat Square).

Vehicle classifications and vehicle movements for the signalized intersection counted by the STA software are shown in Figures 8-11.

Fig. 8. Vehicle classification percentage for Al-Jadriyah intersection.

Fig. 9. Vehicle classification percentage for Kamal Junblat Square.

Fig. 10. Vehicle movement percentage for Al-Jadriyah intersection.

Fig. 11. Vehicle movement percentage for Kamal Junblat Square.

III. RESULTS

To discuss the current conditions of traffic operation and the geometry on traffic flow performance, the required actual

movement was acquired by applying SIDRA Intersection 8.0.1. The abstracted and collected data were fed to the program for each intersection separately. Many runs were implemented to exclude bias data. Table I presents the delay and the LOS of the roundabout. The delay of 14 Tamuz is 50.1s/veh and of Tow Stories Bridge is 120.6s/veh due to the high circulating volume (the biggest portion of vehicles from Karada Kharide and Jamia St.) in the entrance causing high conflict points leading to congestions with high delay. Although the traffic volumes of Karada Kharide and Jamia St. are high, the delays are 40.5s/veh, and 35.4s/veh respectively due to their geometry and low-medium circulating volume in their entrance (the result of the congestion in front of the other approaches). Delay is an important parameter to evaluate the LOS of a roundabout thus the LOS is D, E, D, and F for Karada Kharidge, 14 Tamuz St., Jamia St., and Tow Stories Bridge respectively. The control delay and LOS for individual lanes are illustrated in Figures 12, and 13.

All the output results are categorized by medium to high total delays. The total delay is 127.84veh-h/h, the average geometric delay is 2.7s/veh, and the average control delay of the roundabout is 57.2s/veh, thus the level of service for the roundabout is E according to the LOS categories of the software that are based on the SIDRA method. The LOS of four/five approach multi-lane roundabout suffering medium/high volumes and delays is ranging from E to F according to [10, 13, 22].

Fig. 12. Resulting average (control) delay of the individual lanes of Kamal Junblat Square.

Fig. 13. Resulting LOS of the individual lanes of Kamal Junblat Square

TABLE I. AVERAGE (CONTROL) DELAY AND LOS OF THE INDIVIDUAL LANES OF KAMAL JUNBLAT SQUARE

	Approaches				Intersection
	Karada Kharidge	14 Tamuz St.	Jamia St.	Two Stories Bridge	
Delay (control) (s.)	40.5	50.1	35.4	120.6	57.2
LOS	D	E	D	F	E
Control Delay (s) (SIDRA standard)	≤10	>10 – 20	>20 – 35	>35 – 55	>50 – 70
LOS (SIDRA standard)	A	B	C	D	E

Regarding the performance of the Al-Jadriyah intersection, the maximum cycle time according to [23] (120s) was inputted to SIDRA Intersection. The output phase sequence of each approach of the intersection is shown in Table II. Jamia St. phase time is considered as the reference phase. The reference phase merely indicates the phase that is coordinated in a SIDRA network model. Although of no significance for individual sites, one phase needs to be selected [24].

TABLE II. OUTPUT PHASE SEQUENCE FOR EACH APPROACH OF AL-JADRIYAH INTERSECTION

	Approaches				Remark
	Jamia St.	Barbi St.	Jadriyah Bridge	Sci Abduljabbar A. St.	
Phase A	R	R	G	R	-
Phase B	R	G	R	R	-
Phase C	G	R	R	R	REF
Phase D	R	R	R	G	-

The control delay is 285.2s, 140.1s, 197.9s, and 190.5s for Jamia St., Barbi St., Jadriyah Bridge, and Sci Abduljabbar A. St. respectively as shown in Table III. The average control delay of the signalized intersection is 228.5s, the total control delay is 542.96veh-h/h, and the average geometric delay is 2.6s. As previously mentioned, LOS is determined based on the delay for a signalized intersection, thus the LOS of all the approaches of Al-Jadriyah intersection and the intersection itself is F according to the HCM2010 method due to the high delay as the result of high traffic volume and the inadequate geometric dimensions of the intersection to discharge this high volume functionally [8, 25]. Control delay and LOS for the individual lanes are illustrated in Figures 14 and 15.

TABLE I. CONTROL DELAY AND LOS OF KAMAL JUNBLAT SQUARE

	Approaches				Intersection
	Karada Kharidge	14 Tamuz St.	Jamia St.	Two Stories Bridge	
Delay (control) (s.)	40.5	50.1	35.4	120.6	57.2
LOS	D	E	D	F	E
Control Delay (s) (SIDRA standard)	≤10	>10 – 20	>20 – 35	>35 – 55	>50 – 70
LOS (SIDRA standard)	A	B	C	D	E

Fig. 14. Resulting average (control) delay of the individual lanes of Al-Jadriyah Intersection.

Fig. 15. Resulting LOS of the individual lanes of Al-Jadriyah Intersection.

IV. ALTERNATIVES SUGGESTED TO IMPROVE THE PERFORMANCE OF THE INTERSECTIONS

An additional circulating lane improved the roundabout by about 18%. The control delay and LOS were about 57.2s and E and were improved to 46.8s and D respectively as shown in Table IV. Fly-over connection between 14 Tamuz Street and Two Stories Bridge approaches was the second suggested improvement and enhanced the roundabout by about 72%, improving control delay and LOS to 15.9s and B respectively as illustrated in Table V. A third proposal was the addition of another lane for each of the 14 Tamuz Street and Two Stories

Bridge approaches. LOS and control delay of the roundabout were enhanced to C and 27.8s respectively as presented in Table VI, therefore the improvement was about 51%.

TABLE II. AVERAGE (CONTROL) DELAY AND LOS OF KAMAL JUNBLAT SQUARE (ADDITIONAL CIRCULATING LANE PROPOSAL)

	Approaches				Intersection
	Southeast	Northeast	Northwest	Southwest	
Delay (control) (s)	51.8	48.5	8.3	92.3	46.8
LOS	E	D	A	F	D

TABLE III. AVERAGE (CONTROL) DELAY AND LOS OF KAMAL JUNBLAT SQUARE (FLY-OVER PROPOSAL)

	Approaches				Intersection
	Southeast	Northeast	Northwest	Southwest	
Delay (control) (s)	15.1	31.4	6.3	22.4	15.9
LOS	B	C	A	C	B

TABLE IV. AVERAGE (CONTROL) DELAY AND LOS OF KAMAL JUNBLAT SQUARE (ADDITIONAL LANE FOR 14 TAMUZ AND TWO STORIES BRIDGE PROPOSAL)

	Approaches				Intersection
	Southeast	Northeast	Northwest	Southwest	
Delay (control) (s)	45.0	22.5	12.8	26.7	27.8
LOS	D	C	B	C	C

Regarding the Al-Jadriyah Intersection, selecting the optimum cycle time (50s) with the fly over proposal was suggested as the first improvement alternative while the second was the use of the optimum cycle time (70s) with the addition of a lane for each approach of the intersection. The intersection was enhanced by about 91% with the first proposal and by 67% with the second proposal. Control delay time and LOS improved to 20.2s and C and 74.7s and D respectively with the first and second improvement proposal as shown in Tables VII and VIII.

TABLE V. AVERAGE (CONTROL) DELAY AND LOS OF AL-JADRIYAH INTERSECTION (FIRST PROPOSAL)

	Approaches				Intersection
	Southeast	Northeast	Northwest	Southwest	
Delay (control) (s)	23.3	26.9	14.6	20.7	20.2
LOS	C	C	B	C	C

TABLE VI. AVERAGE (CONTROL) DELAY AND LOS OF AL-JADRIYAH INTERSECTION (SECOND PROPOSAL)

	Approaches				Intersection
	Southeast	Northeast	Northwest	Southwest	
Delay (control) (s)	94.3	34.9	70.1	31.1	74.7
LOS	F	C	E	C	E

V. CONCLUSION

From field/video observations and simulation, the performances of the Kamal Junblat Square roundabout and the signalized Al-Jadriyah Intersection with high traffic volume

were compared. The roundabout shows better performance than the signalized intersection. The LOS and delay time of the roundabout were E and 57.2s and of the Al-Jadriyah Intersection were F and 228.5s. The signalized intersection suffers from a long cycle length (120s) that causes high delay time values. The increase of circulating volume causes a decrease in entry capacity, while the increase in the geometric feature dimensions (width of entry, entry radius, and inscribed circle diameter) increases the entry capacity, with one exception.

In the roundabout, domain approaches (Jamia St., and Karada Kharidge) cause high circulating volume in the sub-domain (14- Tamuz, and Two-Stories Bridge) entries, thus the LOS of these approaches (F) is worse than the domain approaches (D). Domain approaches in the roundabout operate properly in medium/high traffic situations, while the sub-domain approaches suffer from high delays due to the accommodation of high circulating volumes in their entries.

The addition of a circulating lane and of a lane to the sub-domain approaches improves the operation performance of the roundabout by an average of 18% and 51% respectively. The addition of one lane for each approach of the intersection enhances the performance of the signalized intersection by 67% in average.

A fly-over connection between sub-domain approaches enhances the roundabout performance by about 72% and a fly-over connection between Jamia St. and Jadriyah Bridge with optimum cycle time of 50s improves the operational performance of the Al-Jadriyah Intersection by about 91%. Thus, the fly-over is considered the best improvement alternative proposal.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Papageorgiou, P. Damianou, A. Pitsilides, A. Thrasos, and P. Ioannou, "A Microscopic Traffic Simulation Model for Transportation Planning in Cyprus," in *International Conference on Intelligent Systems And Computing: Theory And Applications*, Ayia Napa, Cyprus, Jul. 2006, pp. 157–166.
- [2] A. J. Essa, A. Ismail, A. E. Jehad, A. A. Adheem Hussein, A. H. Khalaf, and H. A. M. Yahia, "Development of Roundabout Delay Models Using Traffic Simulation Programs: A Case Study at Al-Mansour City, Iraq," *Jurnal Kejuruteraan*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 97–103, Dec. 2017, [https://doi.org/10.17576/jkukm-2017-29\(2\)-05](https://doi.org/10.17576/jkukm-2017-29(2)-05).
- [3] H. A. M. Yahia, S. Safinia, N. K. Al Musharfi, and S. S. I. A. Ali, "Car Driver Attitude towards Road Safety Measures," *Jurnal Kejuruteraan*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 57–61, Oct. 2017, [https://doi.org/10.17576/jkukm-2017-29\(1\)-08](https://doi.org/10.17576/jkukm-2017-29(1)-08).
- [4] M. M. Islam and A. Y. S. Al Hadhrami, "Increased motorization and road traffic accidents in Oman," *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 907–914, Dec. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.10520/EJC130254>.
- [5] M. Touahmia, "Identification of Risk Factors Influencing Road Traffic Accidents," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2417–2421, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1615>.
- [6] A. Detho, S. R. Samo, K. C. Mukwana, I. A. Memon, and U. A. Rajput, "Proposed Remedies to Prevent Road Traffic Accidents (RTAs) on Highways in Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3366–3368, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2128>.
- [7] M. Z. Hasanpour, M. R. Ahadi, A. S. Moghadam, and G. A. Behzadi, "Variable Speed Limits: Strategies to Improve Safety and Traffic Parameters for a Bottleneck," *Engineering, Technology & Applied*

- Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1535–1539, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.831>.
- [8] H. I. M. Irtema, A. Ismail, S. I. Albrka, M. A. Ladin, and H. A. M. Yahia, "Evaluating the Performance of Traffic Flow in Four Intersections and Two Roundabouts in Petaling Jaya and Kuala Lumpur Using Sidra 4.0 Software," *Jurnal Teknologi*, vol. 72, no. 4, pp. 1–5, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.11113/jt.v72.3906>.
- [9] M. Owais, O. Abulwafa, and Y. A. Abbas, "When to Decide to Convert a Roundabout to a Signalized Intersection: Simulation Approach for Case Studies in Jeddah and Al-Madinah," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 10, pp. 7897–7914, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-020-04479-6>.
- [10] P. T. Adeke, A. Etika, and A. A. Atoo, "Capacity and Performance Assessment of Wurukum Roundabout in Makurdi Metropolis: A Comparative Study using ARCADY and SIDRA INTERSECTION Software," *Arid Zone Journal of Engineering, Technology and Environment*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 309–320, Jun. 2020.
- [11] H. G. Demir and Y. K. Demir, "A Comparison of Traffic Flow Performance of Roundabouts and Signalized Intersections: A Case Study in Nigde," *The Open Transportation Journal*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 120–132, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874447802014010120>.
- [12] L.-S. Tey, M. S. Salim, S. M. R. Shah, and P. Ranjitkar, "Safety and Operational Performance of Roundabouts," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 8, no. 6S3, pp. 198–203, Nov. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.F1032.0986S319>.
- [13] G. M. Aboud, A. M. Abdulwahab, Q. S. Banyhussan, and H. A. Zubaidi, "A Case Study on Roundabout under Congestion: Proposal to Improve Current Traffic Operation," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 5, no. 9, pp. 2029–2040, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2019-03091391>.
- [14] J. Mohammed and A. A. M. D. O. Ali, "Traffic Flow Analysis for Intersection Using Computer Simulation Aasidra Software: A Case Study in Bangi Malaysia," *Tikrit Journal of Engineering Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 10–25, May 2014.
- [15] M. M. Akmaz and O. N. Celik, "Examination of Signalized Intersections According to Australian and HCM (Highway Capacity Manual) Methods Using Sidra Intersection Software," *Journal of Civil Engineering and Architecture*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 246–259, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.17265/1934-7359/2016.02.013>.
- [16] G. Sofia, A. Al-Haddad, and I. S. Al-Haydari, "Improvement of traffic performance at intersections in Karbala city," *MATEC Web of Conferences*, vol. 162, 2018, Art. no. 01032, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201816201032>.
- [17] M. K. Al-Obaidi, "Enhancement of the Traffic Operation Performance of Al-Mansour Signalized T-Intersection in Baghdad City," *Association of Arab Universities Journal of Engineering Sciences*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 190–210, 2018.
- [18] M. Q. Ismael and A. J. Mohammed, "Improvement of Traffic Movement for Roads Network in Al-Kadhimiya City Center," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 182–205, Sep. 2016.
- [19] L. J. Pignataro and E. J. Cantilli, *Traffic Engineering: Theory and Practice*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Prentice-Hall, 1973.
- [20] National Cooperative Highway Research Program, *Roundabouts: An Informational Guide*, Second Edition., no. Report 672. Washington, DC, USA: Transportation Research Board, 2010.
- [21] Federal Highway Administration, *Roundabouts : an informational guide*, no. FHWA-RD-00-067; Washington, DC, USA: US Department of Transportation, 2000.
- [22] M. R. Haque, M. A. Rahman, M. B. Hossain, and M. Roknuzzaman, "Capacity Evaluation of Roundabout Intersections in Khulna Metropolitan City by Using SIDRA," in *International Conference on Planning, Architecture and Civil Engineering*, Rajshahi, Bangladesh, Feb. 2017, Art. no. 6.
- [23] HCM, *Highway Capacity Manual 2010*. Washington, DC, USA: Transportation Research Board, 2010.
- [24] *Traffic Modelling Guidelines: SIDRA Intersection*. Adelaide, SA, Australia: Department for Infrastructure and Transport, 2021.
- [25] X. Chen, D. Li, N. Ma, and C. Shao, "Prediction of User Perceptions of Signalized Intersection Level of Service Based on Fuzzy Neural Networks," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 2130, no. 1, pp. 7–15, Jan. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.3141/2130-02>.

Removal of Multiplicative Gamma Noise from Images via SRAD Model Amelioration

Nacira Diffellah
Electronics Department
ETA Laboratory
Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi University
Bordj Bou Arréridj, Algeria
diffellahn@gmail.com

Rabah Hamdini
Automatics Department
SET Laboratory
Saad Dahlab University
Blida, Algeria
hamdinirabah@gmail.com

Tewfik Bekkouche
Electromecanics Department
ETA Laboratory
Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi University
Bordj Bou Arréridj, Algeria
bekkou66@hotmail.com

Abstract—In this paper, an improved Speckle Reducing Anisotropic Diffusion (SRAD), destined to remove multiplicative gamma noise applied to different images is proposed. The basic idea is to divide the image into several riddled areas and then calculate the Equivalent Number of Look (ENL) of each region. The largest value of the ENL is the best optimal homogeneous region of the image. This optimal choice allows us to solve the major problem of the SRAD algorithm articulated around a visual choice of the homogeneous region which is not satisfactory and causes non-uniformity in this area. To give more validity to the proposed method, several experimentations were conducted using different kinds of images and were approved by some quantitative metrics like PSNR, SNR, VSNR, and SSIM. The computer simulation results confirm the efficiency of the proposed method which outperforms the classical SRAD method.

Keywords—multiplicative gamma noise; SRAD; ENL; optimal homogeneous zone; speckle noise

I. INTRODUCTION

Images are not immune to contamination by noise that can degrade their visual quality. To deal with this problem, image denoising is the recommended solution. In this context, several restoration filtering algorithms have emerged. These algorithms are based on a variety of denoising techniques [1-8]. The noise in turn is divided into several forms. In this paper, we consider the gamma multiplicative noise. Among the existing techniques, we cite those that are based on anisotropic diffusion. Authors in [1] proposed an algorithm called SRAD, which consists in exploiting the instantaneous coefficient of variation which is a function of local gradient magnitude, and Laplacian operators. However, this method gave good performance in terms of the quality of the restored images, but has the disadvantage of the choice of the homogeneous area

determined by a simple subjective visual choice. SRAD [12] needs to know a homogeneous region in the processed image. Although it is not difficult for a user to select a homogeneous region in the image, it is non-trivial for a machine to do that. To remedy this problem an improved method, based on the calculation of the ENL [2], is proposed in this paper, which allows us to analytically determine the optimal homogeneous zone for any image type. Once this area is determined, we apply the SRAD algorithm itself, through simulations carried out on a set of images of different types. The obtained results confirmed the superiority of the proposed over the original SRAD method using several metrics such as: Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) [6], Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) [9], Visual Signal-to-Boise Ratio (VSNR) [10], and Structure Similarity Index Method (SSIM) [13].

II. THE SPECKLE NOISE MODEL

Multiplicative noise [5, 13] is generally more difficult to remove than additive noise [3]. The model is given by:

$$f(i, j) = u(i, j) \times \eta(i, j) \quad (1)$$

where the speckle image f is the product of the original image u and the non-Gaussian noise η . The indices i, j represent the spatial position over the image. In most applications involving multiplicative noise, the noise content is assumed to be stationary with unitary mean and unknown variance σ^2 . The Probability Density Function (PDF) of Erlang (Gamma) noise is given as [4]:

$$p(x; K, \theta) = \frac{x^{K-1} e^{-\frac{x}{\theta}}}{\theta^K \Gamma(K)} \quad (2)$$

For $x > 0$ and $K > 0$, $\theta > 0$ where K is the number of looks of the image (i.e. the number of independent values averaged) and $\Gamma(\square)$ is the classical Gamma function. $\bar{x} = K \cdot \theta$ is the mean and $\sigma^2 = K \cdot \theta^2$ is the variance. In this work, we assume that the images are corrupted by Gamma distributed noise:

$$\eta \sim \frac{\eta^{K-1} e^{-\frac{\eta}{\theta}}}{\theta^K \Gamma(K)} \quad (3)$$

III. THE SPECKLE REDUCING FAST VARIATIONAL RESTORATION METHOD

We consider an image f that corresponds to an unknown ground truth image u perturbed with a speckle multiplicative noise η . The objective is to denoise the available image f and recover an image as close as possible to u according to (1). The SRAD algorithm [1] for the speckle noise reduction in images is summarized as follows:

- Let u be the original image which is normalized on $[0,1]$. Define the smoothing time step and choose the homogeneous region within the original image.
- Compute the speckle scale from the delimited homogenous region which is depended on its variance and mean.
- Compute the Laplacian approximation of the image depending on the nearest-neighbor difference. Compute the nearest-neighbor difference.
- Compute the diffusion coefficient based on the instantaneous coefficient of variation.
- Compute the divergence by which we can update the SRAD function.

IV. THE PROPOSED METHOD

The ENL is used to evaluate the speckle noise reduction performance of the homogeneous regions in the image. The ENL is defined as:

$$ENL = \frac{\mu_u^2}{\hat{\sigma}_u^2} \quad (4)$$

where μ_u and $\hat{\sigma}_u$ are the estimated mean and standard deviation of the image.

Larger ENL values indicate excellent speckle noise removal ability. ENL is a well-known and effective metric for evaluating the regularization effectiveness on homogeneous areas. The proposed method is summarized in a process of 6 steps:

- Obtain the degraded image f from an imaging system which is the product of the true intensity u and draws from a Gamma distribution.
- Calculate the different evaluation metrics between the original and noisy images.

- Divide the noisy image into several overlapping regions according to the value of d . The total number of regions is equal to: $n = (2d - 1)^2$, where d is an integer $\neq 0$.
- Calculate the ENL for each region using (4) and choose the greatest value of ENL which corresponds to the most homogeneous region.
- Determine the coordinates of the previous optimal zone which has the greatest value of ENL. Then, apply the SRAD algorithm with the purpose to find the restored image.
- Calculate the metrics between the original image and the restored image and compare the obtained results, before and after restoration.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we will compare and discuss the results of the proposed method. The implementation has been tested against a set of images consisting of:

- Image 1: "Image union" [14] with a size of 1024×999 pixels by Kevin Dooley is licensed with CC BY 2.0 [15].
- Image 2: "First NAC Image Obtained in Mercury Orbit" [16] with a size of 1024×1020 by NASA Goddard Photo and Video, which is also licensed under CC BY 2.0.
- Image 3: "Transportation_airplane_on_lake" [17] with a size of 1289×1024. This image was acquired from Wikipedia. It was marked as Public Domain or CC0 and is free to use.

The images were corrupted with Gamma multiplicative noise having 1 mean and different standard deviation of 4%, 10%, 20%, and 60%. In Tables I-III we summarize the simulation results for a sample of given values. Figures 1-3 are composed of:

- The illustration of the position of the homogeneous zone within the noised image, automatically determined by the ENL metric.
- The number of the homogeneous zone, its coordinates as well as the value of the ENL which is estimated to be the largest by the proposed algorithm.
- The original and the restored images.
- In addition, in order to validate the illustration of these Figures, we also supported the assessment of our approach by all the metrics used.

Tables I-III summarize the results obtained concerning the different metrics used, namely PSNR, SNR, VSNR, and SSIM applied to the original and the noisy images and the real and restored images, by varying each time the number of looks $K = 4$, $K = 10$, $K = 20$, and $K = 60$.

In Tables I-III, we clearly notice that the metrics of the proposed method are significantly better than those of the original SRAD method for different noise levels, for the three images used in this paper.

(a) Noisy $K = 20$

Region [333.8000 800.2000 51.2000 49.9500], $d=20$
 PSNR=21.0963dB, SNR=9.0602, VSNR=29.9563dB, SSIM=0.9514

(b) $K = 20$, ENL= 471.0219, number=1262

(a) Noisy $K = 20, d = 15$

Region [786.0667 35.0000 68.2667 68.0000]
 PSNR=20.0851dB, SNR=0.4349, VSNR=10.5243 dB, SSIM=0.8115

(b) ENL= 83.4313, number=53

(c) Original

(d) Restored

PSNR=26.5126dB, SNR=13.7435,
 VSNR= 30.8696dB, SIM=0.9470

Fig. 1. Results of image 1.

(c) Original

(d) Restored

PSNR=24.9378dB, SNR=3.5459
 VSNR=12.4653, SSIM=0.8247

Fig. 2. Results of image 2.

TABLE I. PSNR, SNR, VSNR, AND SSIM OF NOISY AND DESPECKLED IMAGE 1 WITH DIFFERENT LEVELS OF K

	PSNR	SNR	VSNR	SSIM
$K=4$	15.1109	3.5008	26.4856	0.8231
Proposed	20.7247	7.3498	26.1100	0.8760
SRAD	18.8231	4.7549	26.1531	0.8270
$K=10$	17.6972	5.8270	27.9382	0.9040
Proposed	24.1607	11.3095	26.4329	0.9271
SRAD	23.5171	10.5614	26.0267	0.9195
$K=20$	21.0963	9.0602	29.9563	0.9514
Proposed	26.5126	13.7435	30.8696	0.9470
SRAD	23.5093	10.5496	29.9626	0.9193
$K=60$	32.8812	20.7208	33.5205	0.9955
Proposed	28.4062	15.9718	28.3802	0.9643
SRAD	26.4717	13.7056	26.0019	0.9464

TABLE II. PSNR, SNR, VSNR, AND SSIM OF NOISY AND DESPECKLED IMAGE 2 WITH DIFFERENT LEVELS OF K

	PSNR	SNR	VSNR	SSIM
$K=4$	13.9953	-4.5188	5.7907	0.6204
Proposed	19.5193	1.2013	11.9192	0.7196
SRAD	16.7190	-0.0049	11.5444	0.6345
$K=10$	16.6044	-2.6240	7.5992	0.7688
Proposed	22.9478	2.6145	12.3695	0.7944
SRAD	19.0560	0.9626	11.8564	0.7070
$K=20$	20.0851	0.4349	10.5243	0.8115
Proposed	24.9378	3.5459	12.4653	0.8247
SRAD	21.3566	1.9513	12.1517	0.7625
$K=60$	31.7254	11.7804	19.5227	0.9907
Proposed	27.3115	5.9811	14.1275	0.8929
SRAD	24.8388	3.3729	12.2072	0.8147

(a) Noisy $K = 20, d = 15$

Region [419.9250 717.8000 64.4500 51.2000]

PSNR=16.5447dB, SNR=2.3706, VSNR=12.1235d8, SSIM0=0.72320

(b) ENL= 4332.8337, number=1106

(c) Original

(d) Restored

PSNR=25.6970dB, SNR=11.4072
VSNR=16.4865, SSIM=0.8497

Fig. 3. Results of image 3.

TABLE III. PSNR, SNR, VSNR, AND SSIM OF NOISY AND DESPECKLED IMAGE 3 WITH DIFFERENT LEVELS OF K

	PSNR	SNR	VSNR	SSIM
$K=4$	10.5052	-2.6031	7.9086	0.4547
Proposed	16.8892	5.9958	16.0305	0.7133
SRAD	15.3289	6.3297	15.3680	0.7065
$K=10$	13.0901	-0.6873	9.5656	0.5802
Proposed	21.6008	9.0109	16.2655	0.7940
SRAD	18.6167	9.4196	15.7187	0.7807
$K=20$	16.5447	2.3706	12.1235	0.7232
Proposed	25.6970	11.4072	16.4865	0.8497
SRAD	22.2708	11.6397	16.0748	0.8280
$K=60$	28.2317	13.7751	17.4724	0.9661
Proposed	29.3506	14.8891	16.9263	0.9056
SRAD	29.2033	14.5952	15.9009	0.8875

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an efficient approach for image denoising when the image is corrupted by Gamma multiplicative noise was presented. The proposed approach is based on the

application of the ENL metric which consists of dividing the image successively in overlapping regions and then calculate automatically the largest value of ENL. The proposed method was applied to three different images and gave better and more satisfactory results than the classical SRAD algorithm. In the future, we plan to work on image denoising in the field of deep learning and compare it with the method presented in the current paper.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the General Directorate for Scientific Research and Technological Development of the Algerian Republic and the ETA laboratory of Bordj Bou Arreridj University.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Yu and S. T. Acton, "Speckle reducing anisotropic diffusion," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 1260–1270, Nov. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2002.804276>.
- [2] S. N. Anfinsen, A. P. Doulgeris, and T. Eltoft, "Estimation of the Equivalent Number of Looks in Polarimetric Synthetic Aperture Radar Imagery," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 47, no. 11, pp. 3795–3809, Nov. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2009.2019269>.
- [3] K. Kim, S. Jung, and J.-H. Kim, "Adaptive speckle filtering for real-time computing in low earth orbit satellite synthetic aperture radar," *ICT Express*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 187–190, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icte.2021.02.003>.
- [4] D. K. Nirmala, "A Brief Study on the Various Noise Models in Digital Image Processing," *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Engineering Research*, vol. 5, no. 10, pp. 17–23, Oct. 2017.
- [5] N. Diffellah, Z. E. Baarir, F. Derraz, and A. Taleb-Ahmed, "A Global Variational Filter for Restoring Noised Images with Gamma Multiplicative Noise," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4188–4195, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2737>.
- [6] A. Horé and D. Ziou, "Image Quality Metrics: PSNR vs. SSIM," in *2010 International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, Istanbul, Turkey, Aug. 2010, pp. 2366–2369, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPR.2010.579>.
- [7] M. V. Sarode and P. R. Deshmukh, "Image Sequence Denoising with Motion Estimation in Color Image Sequences," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 139–143, Dec. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.54>.
- [8] H. T. R. Kurmasha, A. F. H. Alharan, C. S. Der, and N. H. Azami, "Enhancement of Edge-based Image Quality Measures Using Entropy for Histogram Equalization-based Contrast Enhancement Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2277–2281, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1625>.
- [9] C. Plapous, C. Marro, and P. Scalart, "Improved Signal-to-Noise Ratio Estimation for Speech Enhancement," *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 2098–2108, Nov. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASL.2006.872621>.
- [10] D. M. Chandler and S. S. Hemami, "VSNR: A Wavelet-Based Visual Signal-to-Noise Ratio for Natural Images," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 16, no. 9, pp. 2284–2298, Sep. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2007.901820>.
- [11] Z. Wang, A. C. Bovik, H. R. Sheikh, and E. P. Simoncelli, "Image quality assessment: from error visibility to structural similarity," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 600–612, Apr. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2003.819861>.
- [12] A. Siddig, Z. Guo, Z. Zhou, and B. Wu, "An image denoising model based on a fourth-order nonlinear partial differential equation," *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, vol. 76, no. 5, pp. 1056–1074, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2018.05.040>.
- [13] R. Chan, H. Yang, and T. Zeng, "A Two-Stage Image Segmentation Method for Blurry Images with Poisson or Multiplicative Gamma

- Noise," *SIAM Journal on Imaging Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 98–127, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1137/130920241>.
- [14] K. Dooley, *Image union*. 2017.
- [15] "Attribution 2.0 Generic — CC BY 2.0," *Creative Commons*. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2.0/> (accessed Nov. 16, 2021).
- [16] NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, *First NAC Image Obtained in Mercury Orbit*. 2011.
- [17] "Transportation airplane on lake." https://free-images.com/display/transportation_airplane_on_lake.html (accessed Nov. 16, 2021).

Chaos Control and Stabilization of a PID Controlled Buck Converter Using the Spotted Hyena Optimizer

Derradji Bakria
LAADI Laboratory
Department of Sciences and Technology
Ziane Achour University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
bakriaderradji@gmail.com

Messaouda Azzouzi
Department of Sciences and Technology
Ziane Achour University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
Dr.Azzouzi@yahoo.fr

Djamal Gozim
Department of Sciences and Technology
Ziane Achour University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
gozimansour@gmail.com

Abstract-The voltage controlled buck converter by constant-frequency pulse-width modulation in continuous conduction mode gives rise to a variety of nonlinear behaviors depending on the circuit parameters values, which complicate their analysis and control. In this paper, a description of the DC/DC buck converter and an overview of some of its chaotic dynamics is presented. A solution based on the optimized PID controller is suggested to eliminate the observed nonlinear phenomena and to enhance the dynamics of the converter. The parameters of the controller are optimized with the Spotted Hyena Optimizer (SHO) which uses the sum of the error between the reference voltage and the output voltage as well as the error between the values of the inductor current in every switch opening instant to determine the fitness of each solution. The simulations results in MATLAB proved the efficiency of the proposed solution.

Keywords-buck converter; nonlinear behavior; optimized PID controller; spotted hyena optimizer

I. INTRODUCTION

DC-DC switched mode power converters have been widely used in many industrial and domestic applications such as hybrid cars, photovoltaic solar energy applications, cell phones chargers, etc. due to their high efficiency compared to the conventional linear regulators. To achieve the desired performance, the DC-DC converters can be either current controlled or voltage controlled. Controllers based on linear theory can be used due to their easy and low implementation cost and the good performance around the operating point [1, 2]. However, they do not take into consideration the nonlinear phenomena that can occur in the converter in high frequencies or when one of the parameters of the converter changes [3-6]. Recent research has proposed numerous solutions to address the above-mentioned problems. For instance, in [7], boost converter discrete-time models were used as an example to present an analytical solution that allows the prediction of

nonlinear phenomena in digital current mode controlled power converters. Meanwhile, in [8] the authors proposed a new method for the design of a stable and robust feedback control using the bifurcation analysis of the bilinear averaged model of boost converter and constrained stabilization principles. Another approach for designing a controller that guarantees the system's global stability was introduced in [9]. The approach is based on the principles of the contraction theory of switched systems. Nonetheless, the aforementioned works are based on analytical solutions and are a bit complex, and hard to implement in real plants. Fuzzy logic-based controllers have been used to control chaos in many studies [10-18]. However, the use of fuzzy logic complicates the control system and requires considerable computation time and a large memory space, while the use of the controllers based on metaheuristic algorithms ensure, at least, the same performance as the fuzzy controllers with less complexity and implementation cost [19-21]. Nonetheless, most of previous works that use this type of controller are using the Integral Absolute Error (IAE) as an adaptation coefficient which is insufficient to estimate the fitness of each solution during the search.

Nonlinear phenomena elimination in power converters is still an open research subject, although good results have been achieved in the literature. In this paper, we propose a method of shifting the nonlinear phenomena and expand the stability range of the converters without the need of complicated analysis methods or additional circuits. Using the powerful tools of MATLAB and the state-space model of the buck converter as an example, we designed a PID regulator that guarantees both global stability of the system and parameter disturbance rejection (load, input voltage, reference voltage). This design is based on the Spotted Hyena Optimizer (SHO) to determine the optimum gains of the controller using appropriate adaptation coefficients.

Corresponding author: Derradji Bakria

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

A. Buck Converter

A buck converter is a Switch Mode Power Supply (SMPS) that converts a DC voltage into a lower DC voltage through the commutation between different configurations [22, 23]. Buck converters are generally controlled via voltage mode control. In this control mode, the error ($\mathcal{E}(t)$) between the output voltage ($V_o(t)$) and the reference voltage (V_{ref}) is used to obtain the control signal ($Cm(t)$). The latter is compared with the sawtooth signal to generate the PWM signal needed to derive the switch. The proposed study circuit is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Voltage controlled buck converter.

The state of the system is expressed by the vector $X = [i_L, V_c]^T$ with:

$$\dot{X}_i = A_i X_i + B_i \quad (1)$$

where the state matrices A_i and B_i for each configuration are:

$$A_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{(R_{sw} + R_L + \frac{R_c R}{R_c + R})}{L} & \frac{-R}{L(R + R_c)} \\ \frac{R}{C(R + R_c)} & \frac{-1}{C(R + R_c)} \end{bmatrix}, B_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{V_g}{L} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$A_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{(R_D + R_L + \frac{R_c R}{R_c + R})}{L} & \frac{-R}{L(R + R_c)} \\ \frac{R}{C(R + R_c)} & \frac{-1}{C(R + R_c)} \end{bmatrix}, B_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$A_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{C(R + R_c)} \end{bmatrix}, B_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Equation (5) represents the solution of (1):

$$X_i(t) = e^{A_i(t-t_0)}(X_i(t_0) + A_i^{-1}B_i) - A_i^{-1}B_i \quad (5)$$

The behavior of the system is described in each configuration using (5) where the final state of the system in the current configuration is considered as the initial state $X_i(t_0)$ for the next one.

B. Spotted Hyena Optimizer

SHO imitates the natural hunting behavior of the spotted hyenas to find the optimum solution for an optimization problem [24, 25]. A pack of spotted hyenas follow an

organized group hunting technique that can be divided into three main behaviors:

1) Searching and Encircling Prey

When the hunt begins, the pack of the spotted hyenas has no information about the position of the prey, therefore the current fittest search agent will decide the possible location of the prey in the search space. Then, the rest of the pack will surround this position.

2) Hunting

The group hunting behavior of the spotted hyenas is based on a cluster of trusted friends that guide the members of the pack during the hunt.

3) Attacking

All search agents will be forced to move towards the position of the prey.

More details on the mathematical model of the SHO algorithm can be found in [24, 25].

C. SHO Application

In this study, the SHO algorithm was applied to determine the optimal parameters of a PID controller that would improve the dynamics of the converter. It is based on the minimization of the steady state error between the reference and the measured voltage, and the error between the successive values of the inductor current (measured in each switch opening instant) which are the peaks of the inductor current. Equation (6) represents the proposed objective function.

$$F(t) = w_1 F_1 + w_2 F_2 \quad (6)$$

$$F_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^N (p_i - \mu)^2}{N}} \quad (7)$$

$$F_2 = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} |\epsilon(t)| dt \quad (8)$$

where F_1 is the standard deviation of inductor current values measured in each switch opening instant, and F_2 represents the Integral Absolute Error (IAE).

Fig. 2. Closed loop system with SHO.

Figure 2 presents the control block diagram of the system, where K_p , K_i and K_d are respectively the proportional, the integral, and the derivative gains obtained by the SHO.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mathematical model of the proposed circuit presented in Figure 1 was simulated in MATLAB using (2)-(5). The converter and controller parameters are presented in Table I.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE PROPOSED CIRCUIT

Converter	V_g	24 Ω
	F	2500 Hz
	$R_{sw} = R_D$	0.0177 V
	L	0.02 H
	R_L	2 Ω
	C	47 μF
	R_C	0.2 Ω
Optimizer	w_1	100
	w_2	1
	Iterations	100
	Search agents	20
Controller	K_p	8
	K_i	800
	K_d	0.0001

A. Original Behavior

In this study, the input voltage was chosen for study and observation while the other parameters had fixed values. As shown in Figure 3, the converter dynamics clearly changed from Period 1, to Period 2, to Period 4, and then to chaotic dynamic behavior.

Fig. 3. (a) Bifurcation diagram varying V_g . (b) Phase plan diagram $V_o - i_L$ and the inductor current $i_L(t)$ of Period 1 when $V_g = 24V$. (c) Phase plan diagram $V_o - i_L$ and the inductor current $i_L(t)$ of Period 2 when $V_g = 30V$. (d) Phase plan diagram $V_o - i_L$ and the inductor current $i_L(t)$ of Period 4 when $V_g = 34V$. (e) Phase plan diagram $V_o - i_L$ and the inductor current $i_L(t)$ of chaos when $V_g = 40V$.

The input voltage V_g was set to start from 20V, and then it increased gradually to 80V. The converter exhibits the stable Period 1 behavior when $V_g \leq 26V$ followed by the unstable period 2 behavior when $26 < V_g \leq 33.25V$. Afterwards, the converter exhibits the unstable Period 4 when $33.25 < V_g \leq 34.75V$. Finally, the converter shows irregular behavior (chaos) when $V_g > 34.75V$. Figures 3(b), 3(c), 3(d) and 3(e) show the phase plan diagram $V_o - i_L$ and the inductor current $i_L(t)$ of the aforementioned behaviors respectively.

B. Optimized Behavior

As shown in the convergence curve in Figure 4, the SHO algorithm finds the optimal gains of the controller after a few iterations. Figure 5 is the voltage wave diagram obtained before and after the optimized PID controller was implemented, where the latter begins after 0.06s. It is clear from the wave form of the output voltage and the phase plan diagram $V_o - i_L$ that the converter returns to the stable Period 1 behavior at 0.067s.

Fig. 4. Convergence curve.

Fig. 5. V_o after applying the optimized parameters.

The bifurcation diagram in Figure 6 proves that the optimized controller is able to extend the stability range of the converter up to 80V of V_g . For more efficiency evaluation, the robustness of the control to the sudden changes in the parameters of the converter has been tested. The response of the output voltage V_o to a sudden change in the input voltage, the reference voltage and load are presented in Figure 7.

Fig. 6. Bifurcation diagram varying V_g using the optimized PID.

Fig. 7. System response to changes in: (a) Input voltage, (b) reference voltage, (c) load.

In the first 40ms, the system is subject to the parameters given in Table I, as shown in Figure 7(a). Steady state is

reached in 6ms with no overshoot. At $t=40ms$, the input voltage is increased to 30V, as it is remarked, and the controller was able to stabilize the system. At the same instant as before, we repeated the same scenario by inducing a sudden change in the reference voltage. At $t=40ms$, the reference voltage changed to 5V, and the controller adapts with the change and stabilizes the system to the new operating point. The results are shown in Figure 7(b). The same scenario is repeated again to test the response of the system to the change in load. At $t=40ms$ we changed the load to 35Ω . From Figure 7(c), it can be seen that the system remains stable and tracks the reference voltage.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, PI D controller gain tuning for a voltage controlled DC-DC buck converter is formulated as an optimization problem. This optimization is aimed to produce gains for the controller that would guarantee a robust closed loop. In addition, the objective function used to evaluate the fitness of the gains during the optimization is based on the sum of the error between the reference voltage and the output voltage as well as the error between the values of the inductor current in every switch opining instant. The SHO was used to solve this problem.

To evaluate the efficiency of the designed controller to shift nonlinear phenomena, the bifurcation diagram obtained using the optimized controller is compared to that presented in the literature. We also tested the capability of the controller to reject the disturbance in the parameters of the converter (load, input voltage, and reference voltage). The obtained results prove the efficiency of the proposed solution to shift the nonlinear phenomena and to expand the range of the desired period 1 behavior. In addition to its high efficiency, this solution offers a simple control circuit and low implementation cost without the need of additional circuits.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. G. Perry, G. Feng, Y.-F. Liu, and P. C. Sen, "A Design Method for PI-like Fuzzy Logic Controllers for DC-DC Converter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 54, no. 5, pp. 2688-2696, Oct. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2007.899858>.
- [2] M. Saoudi, A. El-Sayed, and H. Metwally, "Design and implementation of closed-loop control system for buck converter using different techniques," *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 30-39, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MAES.2017.150261>.
- [3] M. M. Al-Hindawi, A. Abusorrah, Y. Al-Turki, D. Giaouris, K. Mandal, and S. Banerjee, "Nonlinear Dynamics and Bifurcation Analysis of a Boost Converter for Battery Charging in Photovoltaic Applications," *International Journal of Bifurcation and Chaos*, vol. 24, no. 11, Nov. 2014, Art. no. 1450142, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218127414501429>.
- [4] A. Ghosh and S. Banerjee, "Study of complex dynamics of DC-DC buck converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 323-348, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJPELEC.2017.085200>.
- [5] S. Banerjee, A. Ghosh, and S. Padmanaban, "Modeling and analysis of complex dynamics for dSPACE controlled closed-loop DC-DC boost converter," *International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems*, vol. 29, no. 4, 2019, Art. no. e2813, <https://doi.org/10.1002/etep.2813>.
- [6] S. Demirbas, H. Fidanboy, and E. Kurt, "Exploration of the Chaotic Behaviour in a Buck-Boost Converter Depending on the Converter and Load Elements," *Journal of Electronic Materials*, vol. 8, no. 45, pp. 3889-3899, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11664-016-4450-4>.

- [7] A. K. Singha, S. Kapat, S. Banerjee, and J. Pal, "Nonlinear Analysis of Discretization Effects in a Digital Current Mode Controlled Boost Converter," *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 336–344, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JETCAS.2015.2462151>.
- [8] C. Yfoulis, D. Giaouris, F. Stergiopoulos, C. Ziogou, S. Voutetakis, and S. Papadopoulou, "Robust constrained stabilization of boost DC–DC converters through bifurcation analysis," *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 35, pp. 67–82, Feb. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conengprac.2014.11.004>.
- [9] D. Angulo-Garcia, F. Angulo, G. Osorio, and G. Olivar, "Control of a DC-DC Buck Converter through Contraction Techniques," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 11, Nov. 2018, Art. no. 3086, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11113086>.
- [10] K. Guesmi, N. Essounbouli, A. Hamzaoui, J. Zaytoon, and N. Manamanni, "Shifting nonlinear phenomena in a DC–DC converter using a fuzzy logic controller," *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*, vol. 76, no. 5, pp. 398–409, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matcom.2007.04.008>.
- [11] K. Guesmi, N. Essounbouli, and A. Hamzaoui, "Systematic design approach of fuzzy PID stabilizer for DC–DC converters," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 49, no. 10, pp. 2880–2889, Oct. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2008.03.012>.
- [12] K. Mehran, D. Giaouris, and B. Zahawi, "Stability Analysis and Control of Nonlinear Phenomena in Boost Converters Using Model-Based Takagi–Sugeno Fuzzy Approach," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 200–212, Jan. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSI.2009.2019389>.
- [13] W. Hu, B. Zhang, and R. Yang, "Bifurcation Mechanism and Stabilization of V2C Controlled Buck Converter," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 77174–77182, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2918297>.
- [14] G. Djamal, G. Kamel, and M. Djiali, "On the elimination of nonlinear phenomena in DC/DC converters using type-2 fuzzy logic controller," *Diagnostyka*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 73–80, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.29354/diag/93139>.
- [15] M. Ayati, A. Bakhtiyari, and A. Gohari, "Chaos control in buck converter using fuzzy delayed-feedback controller," in *4th International Conference on Control, Instrumentation, and Automation*, Qazvin, Iran, Jan. 2016, pp. 362–365, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIAutom.2016.7483189>.
- [16] Y. Yuan, C. Chang, Z. Zhou, X. Huang, and Y. Xu, "Design of a single-input fuzzy PID controller based on genetic optimization scheme for DC-DC buck converter," in *International Symposium on Next-Generation Electronics*, Taipei, Taiwan, May 2015, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISNE.2015.7131965>.
- [17] Z. B. Duranay, H. Guldemir, and S. Tuncer, "Fuzzy Sliding Mode Control of DC-DC Boost Converter," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 3054–3059, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2116>.
- [18] K. Behih, K. Benmahammed, Z. Bouchama, and M. N. Harmas, "Real-Time Investigation of an Adaptive Fuzzy Synergetic Controller for a DC-DC Buck Converter," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4984–4989, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3172>.
- [19] H. Abderrezek, A. Ameer, and M. N. Harmas, "Robust DC/DC converter controllers using PSO," *Electrotehnica, Electronica, Automatica*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 31–37, Jan. 2017.
- [20] C.-B. Fu, A.-H. Tian, K.-N. Yu, Y.-H. Lin, and H.-T. Yau, "Analyses and Control of Chaotic Behavior in DC-DC Converters," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2018, Nov. 2018, Art. no. e7439137, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/7439137>.
- [21] H. Abdelgawad and V. Sood, "Boost Converter Controller Design Based On Particle Swarm Optimization," *International Journal on Power Engineering and Energy*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 647–659, 2016.
- [22] R. W. Erickson and D. Maksimovic, *Fundamentals of Power Electronics*. Netherlands, Amsterdam: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2001.
- [23] K. Jayaswal and D. K. Palwalia, "Performance Analysis of Non-Isolated DC-DC Buck Converter Using Resonant Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3350–3354, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2242>.
- [24] G. Dhiman and V. Kumar, "Spotted hyena optimizer: A novel bio-inspired based metaheuristic technique for engineering applications," *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 114, pp. 48–70, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advensoft.2017.05.014>.
- [25] G. Dhiman and A. Kaur, "Spotted Hyena Optimizer for Solving Engineering Design Problems," in *International Conference on Machine Learning and Data Science*, Noida, India, Dec. 2017, pp. 114–119, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MLDS.2017.5>.

Enhancement of the Properties of Compressed Stabilized Earth Blocks through the Replacement of Clay and Silt with Fly Ash

S. N. Malkanthi

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering
University of Ruhuna
Sri Lanka
snmalkanthi@cee.ruh.ac.lk

Harsha Galabada

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Moratuwa
Sri Lanka
hyasasiri@yahoo.com

A. A. D. A. J. Perera

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Moratuwa
Sri Lanka
asoka@uom.lk

P. Dhammika Dharmaratne

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Moratuwa
Sri Lanka
makway.cons@gmail.com

Abstract—The use of earth as a building material, in different forms, such as unburnt and burnt bricks, rammed earth, mud blocks, and soil blocks, is a common practice globally. This study is focused on soil blocks stabilized with cement which are referred to as Cement Stabilized Earth Blocks (CSEBs). The strength and durability of CSEBs are primarily governed by the amount of silt and clay content (finer) in the soil. Many researchers have shown that low finer content improves the properties of CSEB and they have altered the finer content by adding different additives. The current study used a washing method to reduce the finer content and fly ash was utilized as finer to re-fill the soil to the required finer content amount. Also, soil grading was modified by adding larger particles that were separated from the same soil to fit the soil grading to the optimization curves mentioned in the literature. The finer content was changed to 5%, 7.5%, and 10%. Blocks were made by stabilizing the soil with 6%, 8%, and 10% cement and with the size of 150mm×150mm×150mm. The results revealed that fly ash addition up to 10% improves the properties of CSEBs and compressive strength changes from 4.28N/mm² to 13.43N/mm².

Keywords—cement stabilized earth blocks; fly ash; reduced silt and clay; improved properties

I. INTRODUCTION

Earth is one of the oldest and most widespread construction materials [1]. Raw earth as a building material has many advantages [2–5]. Soils in their natural state lack in strength, durability, and dimension stability. Authors in [6] showed the mechanical weakness and the absence of standard procedures to measure strength and stiffness as some demerits of earth-based constructions. These deficiencies can be overcome by stabilizing the soil to produce building materials [7]. Compressed Stabilized Earth Blocks (CSEBs) are one such building material. Authors in [8] used soil to produce mud

concrete blocks. Authors in [9], on their extensive literature survey, have shown the advantages and disadvantages of using earth-based building materials. They have the inherent advantages of being eco-friendly, having low thermal conductivity, while they are abundantly available in nature. However, the loss of strength and dimensional stability when in contact with water for a long time, is a serious disadvantage. Due to these disadvantages, the use of CSEBs as a common building material is not as expected. The use of burnt bricks and cement blocks is popular in Sri Lankan housing construction also. As per statistics, the construction industry consumes a huge cost for burnt bricks and soil blocks usage is not even mentioned in the statistics [10]. The two main challenges of CSEBs are durability and compressive strength. The main variable for both these critical parameters is related to the amount of silt and clay (finer) in CSEBs. Past research work established the optimum finer in the region ranging from 5% to 20% related to compressive strength but no firm indication of the range was associated with the durability of CSEBs. Lateritic soil is used for the production of CSEBs and the content of silt and clay in lateritic soils is generally around the range from 20 to 35% [11].

CSEBs can be used to overcome the problems associated with burnt bricks such as material availability and the economic viability. Generally, many researchers have shown the effect of finer content to the properties of CSEBs. The effect of soil grading to enhance the CSEB properties was examined in [12]. The authors showed that the particle size distribution of soil can be modified to fit into the theoretical distribution suggested by particle packing theories. Based on that, particle packing concepts suggested in [13–15] are valid for CSEB production. Crushed construction waste also can be used to modify the particle size distribution of the soil [16]. For

Corresponding author: S.N. Malkanthi

other soil-based products like mud concrete also, particle percentages in the different ranges need to be controlled [8].

The current research examined the reduction of finer content by washing the soil for the production of CSEBs. Removing finer content to a certain extent may improve durability. Production practicability is another concern. With high clay content, the production process may face problems. Therefore, removing finer may help the production process and lower its cost. With this finer reduction, there can be more voids in the soil mix. Therefore, the study suggests the addition of fly ash to act as finer. With this background, the objective of the study is to check the suitability of using fly ash as a replacement for finer content in the soil to produce CSEBs.

II. USE OF FLY ASH FOR CSEB PRODUCTION

Fly ash is a fine, glass-like powder recovered from gases created by coal-fired electric power generation and its particles are generally spherical in shape and range in size from 0.5 μ m to 100 μ m [17]. SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, and occasionally CaO are the main chemical components present in fly ash [18]. It has a long history of use as an engineering material and has been successfully employed in geotechnical applications [19]. Additionally, the use of fly ash to enhance the properties of concrete is not rare. Authors in [20] have used fly ash/rice husk ash mixture to enhance the properties of concrete. Authors in [21] showed the effect of using fly ash on the compressive strength of green concrete. Most of the times, fly ash is classified as secondary binder and cannot induce the desired effect by itself. However, with the presence of activators can form a cementitious compound which can improve the strength of the soil [22]. Highest compressive strength of CSEBs can be achieved when they were incorporated with 10% fly ash. The lowest water absorption was experienced by CSEBs when the fly ash percentage was 15% [23]. Authors in [24] have used high carbon fly ash for compressed earth blocks. As per their studies, they have varied the fly ash content from 0% to 50% in 10% intervals keeping the cement content constant. Blocks with 0% fly ash have shown the maximum compressive strength and the lowest water absorption. They concluded that 25% fly ash content gives the optimum compressive strength. Authors in [25] used lime and fly ash for soil blocks. Their study showed that the unconfined compression strength of the laterite soil with 5% fly ash and 15% lime was found to be around 2.5 times more than the strength of natural laterite soil. Also, they have shown that the average compressive strength of the blocks tested after 28 days of curing was more than the minimum compressive strength of fired bricks as per IS: 1077 (1992). The water absorption value obtained for 28 days of curing was below the minimum value as specified in IS: 1077(1992).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Soil is the dominant part of CSEBs. Geotechnical analysis was carried out to analyze the characteristics of the soil. Wet sieve analysis as per [26] was conducted to identify the silt and clay content accurately. Atterberg test was conducted as per [27]. Specific gravity test also was performed to identify the physical properties of the soil. Wet sieve analysis showed that the soil contains 28% silt and clay. Therefore, to reduce the silt

and clay content, the soil was washed. The washed soil consisted of nearly 5% silt and clay content.

This particle size distribution of the soil revealed that modification is needed to get its particle distribution to fit into the optimization curves as described by the particle packing theories. Also, finer content was changed to 5%, 7.5%, and 10% by adding fly ash. This fly ash was taken from Norechcholai Lakvijaya Power Plant, Sri Lanka. Fly ash was tested for its particle size distribution and chemical composition. Table I shows the chemical composition of the fly ash. Earlier separated larger particles in the range of 2.0-6.0mm and 6.0-12.0mm as in Figure 1(a) and 1(b) were also added to get the soil particle size distribution as per optimization curves. As per the objective of the study, cement was used as stabilizer in 6%, 8%, and 10% proportions.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF FLY ASH

Constituents determined	Content %	Test method
Calcium as CaO	5.63	Acid digestion and atomic absorption spectrometry
Magnesium as MgO	1.59	
Iron as Fe ₂ O ₃	3.35	
Aluminum as Al ₂ O ₃	19.74	
Potassium as K ₂ O	0.47	
Sodium as Na ₂ O	0.95	
Manganese as MnO	0.05	Acid digestion and UV/VIS
Phosphorus as P ₂ O ₅	1.89	
Titanium as TiO ₂	1.98	Gravimetry
Silicon as SiO ₂	47.48	
Loss on ignition	16.79	

Fig. 1. (a) Gravel 2.0-6.0mm, (b) Gravel 6.0-12.0mm.

Since the mixture of soil has more gravel parts and the casting was carried out using a cement sand block-making machine, the water requirement was comparatively less. For the practical easiness of casting 8-10% water (by soil weight) was sufficient. For each combination, 10 blocks were cast resulting to a total of 90 blocks. The 150mm×150mm×150mm blocks were prepared using the cement sand block-making machine shown in Figure 2. Both vibration and compaction were applied to block casting. Vibration time was regulated based on the preliminary conducted test. Casted blocks were cured using wet gunny bags and water for 7 and 28 days. Cast blocks were tested to determine their dry and wet compressive strengths, dry density, and water absorption, as per SLS 1382 (Part 2) [28] as strength-related tests. Each block was placed carefully in the testing machine below the center of the upper bearing block and load was added until failure. The compressive strength was determined using the load at failure. Figure 3 shows the testing procedure and the cast blocks.

Fig. 2. Use of block making machine for CSEB production.

Fig. 3. Cast blocks and compressive test procedure.

The dry density of the blocks was determined after keeping the blocks in the oven for more than 24 hours at 105°C. Each specimen was oven-dried to a constant mass, weighed and measured to determine its dry density which was calculated by:

$$D_d = \frac{\text{Dry mass (Kg)}}{\text{Volume (m}^3)} \times 10^6 \quad (1)$$

To determine the water absorption of the blocks, oven-dried test specimens were immersed in water for 24 hours, and the increase in the mass of each specimen was calculated and expressed as a percentage of the specimen's initial dry mass.

$$W = \frac{\text{Saturated surface dry mass (g)} - \text{Oven dry mass (g)}}{\text{Oven dry mass (g)}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The used original soil consists of 5% finer and its grading shows it as a fine-grained soil. So, gravel had to be added to fit the grading into the optimization curve. Then, finer content got to be reduced, hence separated finer should be added. Fly ash

was added to the mix as finer, and the prepared CSEBs were tested. The fly ash used for the blocks was sieved through a 0.425mm sieve. In this study, the purpose of using fly ash is to replace finer particles. Other than that, its binding properties were not considered. The specific gravity of fly ash is 2.2 and it is less than that of original soil (2.7) resulting in reduced specific gravity for the soil-fly ash mix. When mixing the soil and fly ash, the expected final particle size distribution was determined as per the power line. A maximum density line has been proposed in [29]. It gives a direction to select a correct proportion of aggregates to get the maximum density. So, to match with the power line, other than the fly ash, different size larger particles were also added to the mixture. These larger particles were earlier extracted from the same soil. Figure 4 shows the particle size distribution for fly ash, used soil, reconstitute soil and its comparison to the power line.

Fig. 4. Comparison of particle size distribution.

A. Properties of CSEBs with Fly Ash Replacement

Finer content was changed to 5%, 7.5%, and 10% by adding fly ash. Blocks were made with 6%, 8%, and 10% cement stabilizer. The dry compressive strength (at 7 and 28 days) and the wet compressive strength (at 28 days) of blocks made with fly ash as finer are shown in Figures 5-7. Considering the compressive strength results of blocks with fly ash replacement, when the cement content is 10%, high compressive strength can be achieved, irrespective of the finer content. Among the tested samples, 7.5% finer with fly ash replacement has given the highest compressive strength. The test results were compared with SLS 1382 specification for CSEBs and SLS 855 specification for cement blocks. According to the test results shown in Table II, when the cement content is 10% for all the selected finer contents, compressive strength values are above the limiting value for grade 1 CSEB (6.0N/mm² and 2.4N/mm² for dry and wet compressive strength respectively). For 5% and 7.5% finer and 8% cement, compressive strength values reached grade 2 CSEB (4.0 - 6.0N/mm² for dry compressive strength and 1.6 - 2.4N/mm² for wet compressive strength). Even with 6% cement, 7.5% finer can produce grade 3 CSEB (2.8 - 4.0N/mm² for dry compressive strength and 1.2 - 1.6N/mm² for wet compressive strength).

Fig. 5. 7-day dry compressive strength results of soil blocks with fly ash.

Fig. 6. 28-day dry compressive strength results of soil blocks with fly ash.

Fig. 7. 28-day wet compressive strength results of soil blocks with fly ash.

Also, the density and water absorption values (Table III) are satisfied with the specified value (1750kg/m³ and 15% respectively) in SLS 1382 Part 1. Out of all the finer contents,

7.5% finer replacement has the highest density and lowest water absorption when the cement replacement is 10%.

TABLE II. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH RESULTS

Cement %		6	8	10
5% finer with fly ash	Dry	2.72	4.57	9.8
	Wet	1.85	2.6	5.25
	Dry/wet	0.680	0.569	0.536
7.5% finer with fly ash	Dry	2.79	4.76	13.43
	Wet	1.67	3.16	7.35
	Dry/wet	0.599	0.664	0.546
10% finer with fly ash	Dry	2.43	3.76	8.75
	Wet	1.45	2.85	4.28
	Dry/wet	0.597	0.758	0.489

TABLE III. DENSITY AND WATER ABSORPTION RESULTS

Cement %		6	8	10
5% finer with fly ash	Density (kg/m ³)	1968	1903	1943
	Water absorption %	10.33	11.28	9.34
7.5% finer with fly ash	Density (kg/m ³)	1865	1833	2074
	Water absorption %	11.40	12.40	6.32
10% finer with fly ash	Density (kg/m ³)	1761	1778	1912
	Water absorption %	13.89	13.77	11.54

V. CONCLUSIONS

The current study used the abundantly available soil with high silt and clay (finer) content. The reduction of excessive finer was done by washing the soil. Then, the study focused on replacing the silt and clay content in the soil with fly ash for CSEB production. Also, soil grading was modified to fit into the optimization curves as explained in particle packing theories. The use of the washing method for finer reduction and the use of traditional cement sand block making machines for block production do not require highly technical skills. Hence, the local construction industry can use this method easily. The most notable findings of the present study are:

- With 10% cement stabilization, CSEBs with all fly ash addition achieved high values of dry and wet compressive strengths, satisfying the Grade 1 requirements.
- 8% cement stabilization gives compressive strength values of Grade 2 blocks for all fly ash addition percentages.
- Even with 6% cement stabilization, 7.5% fly ash addition gives compressive strength in the Grade 3 range.
- All the blocks, irrespective of the cement and fly ash content, have densities and water absorption values that satisfy the SLS 1382 requirements.

The studies [12, 16] showed similar behavior of blocks' compressive strengths. Both studies showed that 10% cement usage for block production leads to high compressive strength. Authors in [7] also recommended 10% as the highest cement percentage considering the financial aspect. Further, 7.5% finer contained soil contributes to improved properties compared to

5% and 10% finer contributions. Based on the obtained results, this study suggests the washing of soil as a novel method to reduce its finer content for soil block production. Finally, it can be concluded that the addition of fly ash as finer results to the improvement of the properties of CSEBs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. The authors would like to acknowledge the support given by Mr. D. M. N. L. Dissanayaka, technical officer of the Structural Testing Laboratory, Mr. H. T. R. M. Thanthirige, technical officer of the Building Materials Laboratory, and Ms. W. U. B. Rukma, technical Officer of the Construction Engineering and Management Division, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Silveira, H. Varum, A. Costa, T. Martins, H. Pereira, and J. Almeida, "Mechanical properties of adobe bricks in ancient constructions," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 36–44, Mar. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2011.08.046>.
- [2] J. C. Morel, A. Mesbah, M. Oggero, and P. Walker, "Building houses with local materials: means to drastically reduce the environmental impact of construction," *Building and Environment*, vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 1119–1126, Dec. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1323\(00\)00054-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1323(00)00054-8).
- [3] D. Allinson and M. Hall, "Hygrothermal analysis of a stabilised rammed earth test building in the UK," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 845–852, Jun. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2009.12.005>.
- [4] F. Pacheco-Torgal and S. Jalali, "Earth construction: Lessons from the past for future eco-efficient construction," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 29, pp. 512–519, Apr. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2011.10.054>.
- [5] F. McGregor, A. Heath, E. Fodde, and A. Shea, "Conditions affecting the moisture buffering measurement performed on compressed earth blocks," *Building and Environment*, vol. 75, pp. 11–18, May 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2014.01.009>.
- [6] J. E. Aubert, P. Maillard, J. C. Morel, and M. Al Rafii, "Towards a simple compressive strength test for earth bricks?," *Materials and Structures*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 1641–1654, May 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-015-0601-y>.
- [7] P. J. Walker, "Strength, durability and shrinkage characteristics of cement stabilised soil blocks," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 301–310, Jan. 1995, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465\(95\)00019-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465(95)00019-9).
- [8] G. H. Galabada, M. Rajapaksha, F. R. Arooz, and R. Halwatura, "Identifying the Impact of Concrete Specimens Size and Shape on Compressive Strength: A Case Study of Mud Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4667–4672, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3020>.
- [9] A. L. Murmu and A. Patel, "Towards sustainable bricks production: An overview," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 165, pp. 112–125, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.01.038>.
- [10] *Annual survey of construction industries*. Battaramulla, Sri Lanka: Department of Census and Statistics, 2015.
- [11] S. N. Malkanthi and A. Perera, "Durability of Compressed Stabilized Earth Blocks with Reduced Clay and Silt," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 431, Nov. 2018, Art. no. 082010, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/431/8/082010>.
- [12] S. N. Malkanthi and A. A. D. A. J. Perera, "Particle Packing Application for Improvement in the Properties of Compressed Stabilized Earth Blocks with Reduced Clay and Silt," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4538–4542, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3002>.
- [13] S. A. A. M. Fennis and J. C. Walraven, "Using particle packing technology for sustainable concrete mixture design," *Heron*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 73–102, 2012.
- [14] M. N. Mangulkar and S. S. Jamkar, "Review of Particle Packing Theories Used For Concrete Mix Proportioning," *International Journal Of Scientific & Engineering Research*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 143–148, 2013.
- [15] S. V. Kumar and M. Santhanam, "Particle packing theories and their application in concrete mixture proportioning: A review," *Indian Concrete Journal*, vol. 77, pp. 1324–1331, Sep. 2003.
- [16] S. N. Malkanthi, W. G. S. Wickramasinghe, and A. A. D. A. J. Perera, "Use of construction waste to modify soil grading for compressed stabilized earth blocks (CSEB) production," *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, vol. 15, Dec. 2021, Art. no. e00717, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2021.e00717>.
- [17] *Techno Economic Feasibility Report on Flyash Bricks*. New Delhi, India: Building Materials & Technology Promotion Council.
- [18] "Fly ash suppliers in India | Fly ash Manufacturers & Exporters in india - Cementation." <https://cementationindia.com/fly-ash.html> (accessed Nov. 20, 2021).
- [19] A. A. Landman, "Aspects of solid-state chemistry of fly ash and ultramarine pigments," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa, 2005.
- [20] N. Bheel, M. A. Jokhio, J. A. Abbasi, H. B. Lashari, M. I. Qureshi, and A. S. Qureshi, "Rice Husk Ash and Fly Ash Effects on the Mechanical Properties of Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5402–5405, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3363>.
- [21] S. A. Chandio, B. A. Memon, M. Oad, F. A. Chandio, and M. U. Memon, "Effect of Fly Ash on the Compressive Strength of Green Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5728–5731, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3499>.
- [22] G. P. Makusa, *State of the art review: Soil stabilization methods and materials in engineering practice*. Luleå, Sweden: Luleå University of Technology, 2012.
- [23] A. A. Sofi, T. A. Sheikh, R. A. Wani, and A. Manzoor, "Cement stabilized earth blocks (CSEB): An economic and eco-friendly building material," *IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 6–11, 2016.
- [24] C. Egenti, J. Khatib, and D. Oloke, "High Carbon Fly ash and Soil in Shelled Compressive Earth Masonry Units," *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 61–65, Dec. 2015.
- [25] T. Shetty, B. K. Rao, and J. B. Pai, "A Feasibility Study on the Compressive Strength of Flyash and Lime Stabilized Laterite Soil Blocks," *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 5, no. 9, pp. 73–80, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.15680/IJIRSET.2016.0505512>.
- [26] ASTM C117 (2003), *Standard Test Method for Materials Finer than 75- μ m (No . 200) Sieve in Mineral*. West Conshohocken, PA, USA: ASTM International, 2003.
- [27] ASTM D4318-10, *Standard Test Methods for Liquid Limit, Plastic Limit and Plasticity Index of Soils*. West Conshohocken, PA, USA: ASTM International, 2010.
- [28] *Specification For Compressed Stabilized Earth Blocks: Part 2 Test Methods*. Colombo, Sri Lanka: Sri Lanka Standard Institution.
- [29] T. C. Powers, *The Properties of Fresh Concrete*, First Edition. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 1968.

Producing Green Concrete with Plastic Waste and Nano Silica Sand

Mohammed Fadhil Qasim
Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
m.qasim1901m@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Zena K. Abbas
Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
dr.zena.k.abbas@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Suhair Kadhém Abed
Building Research Directorate
Baghdad, Iraq
suhairkah@yahoo.com

Abstract-Industrial and urban development has resulted in the spread of plastic waste and the increase in the emissions of carbon dioxide resulting from the cement manufacturing process. The current research aims to produce green (environmentally friendly) concrete by using plastic waste as coarse aggregates in different proportions (10% and 20%) and nano silica sand powder as an alternative to cement in different proportions (5% and 10% by weight). The results showed that compressive strength decreased by 12.10% and 19.23% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement and increased by 12.89% and 20.39% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement respectively at 28 days. Flexural strength decreased by 12.95% and 19.64% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement and increased by 11.16% and 19.86% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement. Splitting tensile strength decreased by 12.74% and 20.22% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement and increased by 10.86% and 19.66% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement. Dry density decreased by 4.51% and 7.83% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement and increased by 2.78% and 4.10% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement respectively at 28 days.

Keywords-green concrete ; plastic waste; silica sand

I. INTRODUCTION

Green concrete was first produced in Denmark in 1998. The term green concrete refers to the environmental concept in which waste is utilized and thus recycled in its production. The production of green concrete is usually cheap because of the use of waste as a partial substitute for cement and aggregates, reducing energy consumption and causing less harm to the environment [1, 12, 13]. The emission of carbon dioxide (CO₂) is an environmental problem. The cement manufacturing process produces about 8 to 10% of the total CO₂ emissions globally, so researchers resorted to the production of green concrete, which utilized recycled materials, e.g. pozzolanic materials, which are used to reduce the amount of cement in the mixture, thus reducing cement production and CO₂ emissions

from cement factories. Waste plastic, glass, ceramics, rubber, etc. have also been used as aggregates in the production of green concrete [2, 17]. The process of disposing of plastic waste causes major environmental problems due to the large disposed quantities and their low biodegradability, so research has focused on the disposal of plastic waste through its use in concrete [3, 14, 16]. Plastic waste consisting of Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE), such as plastic bags, has become a major environmental problem due to the difficulty of its eco-friendly disposal. Often plastic bags are burned, contributing to air pollution [4, 15]. Green concrete developed with waste materials is an active area of research. Fly ash has been used as cement replacement in green concrete made with partial replacement of conventional coarse aggregates with coarse aggregates from demolishing waste [5]. Portland cement is considered a product most involved in environmental pollution. It is responsible for about 10% of global CO₂ emissions. Limestone dust is a by-product of limestone plants and it is produced in thousands of tons annually as waste [6]. For sustainable development construction, recycle or reuse of waste materials is utilized. Many researches tried to create an innovative green concrete, utilizing waste materials [7].

II. MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

A. Cement

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) 42.5 R from the Al-mass company was used in all concrete mixes. The physical and chemical properties in accordance with the Iraqi specification No. 5/2019 as shown in Tables I and II.

B. Fine Aggregates

Using natural sand in Saturated Surface Dry (SSD) condition was used as fine aggregates. It is conformable with the Iraqi specification No.45/1984 zone three (Tables III and IV).

TABLE I. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF OPC

Physical properties	Test result	IQS No.5/2019 requirements for OPC
Fineness (Blaine method) m ² /Kg	386	≥ 280
Initial setting (min)	165	≥ 45 min
Final setting (min)	260	≤ 600 min
Soundness (autoclave method), %	0.12	≤ 0.8
Compressive strength (MPa) at 2 days	28	≥ 20
Compressive strength (MPa) at 28 days	46	≥ 42.5

TABLE II. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND MAIN COMPOUNDS OF THE CEMENT USED

Oxide composition and chemical properties	Test results	IQS No.5 /2019 limits for OPC
Lime (CaO)	62.77	-
Silica (SiO ₂)	20.65	-
Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	4.87	-
Iron oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	3.43	-
Magnesia (MgO)	4.35	≤ 5%
Sulfate (SO ₃)	2.50	≤ 2.8% for C ₃ A > 3.5%
Loss on Ignition (L.O.I.)	1.36	≤ 4%
Insoluble residue (I.R.)	0.91	≤ 1.5%
Main Compounds (Bogue's equation)		
Tri calcium silicate (C ₃ S)	53.77	-
Di calcium silicate (C ₂ S)	18.72	-
Tri calcium aluminate (C ₃ A)	7.10	-
Tetra calcium aluminate - ferrite (C ₄ AF)	10.43	-

TABLE III. FINE AGGREGATE GRADING TEST

Sieve size (mm)	Passing%	IQS No.45/1984 zone 3 requirements
10	100	100
4.75	100	90-100
2.36	93.8	85-100
1.18	80.8	75-100
0.6	61	60-79
0.3	21.8	12-40
0.15	1.8	0-10

TABLE IV. CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF FINE AGGREGATES

Property	Test result	IQS No.45/1984 requirements
Sulfate content, %	0.101	≤ 0.5
Fine materials Passing from 75µm sieve, %	3.9	≤ 5
Specific gravity	2.58	-
Fineness modulus, %	2.4	-
Dry rodded density, kg/m ³	1694	-
Absorption, %	0.8	-

C. Coarse Aggregates

Crushed gravel in SSD, of nominal maximum size of 14mm and conformable with the Iraqi specification No.45/1984 was used as coarse aggregates. Sieve analysis, and chemical and physical properties are shown in Tables V-VI respectively.

TABLE V. COARSE AGGREGATE GRADING TEST

Sieve size (mm)	Passing %	IQS No. 45/1984 5-14mm requirements
20	100	100
14	94	90 - 100
10	52.66	50 - 85
4.75	1.0	0-10

TABLE VI. CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COARSE AGGREGATES

Property	Test result	IQS No. .45/1984 requirements
Sulfate content as a SO ₃ , %	0.08	≤ 0.1
Specific gravity	2.62	-
Impact value, %	2.405	≤ 45
Abrasion test (Los Angeles), %	17.4	≤ 35
Crushing value, %	17.77	-
Dry rodded density, kg/m ³	1688	-
Absorption, %	0.7	-

D. Waste Plastic Aggregates

The plastic waste used as coarse aggregates had nominal maximum size of 14mm obtained from cutting vegetable boxes, garbage containers, shampoo, and detergent bottles. Sieve analysis, and the results of chemical and physical tests of the waste plastic aggregates are presented in Tables VII and VIII respectively.

TABLE VII. PLASTIC WASTE AGGREGATES GRADING TEST

Sieve size (mm)	Passing %	IQS No. 45/1984 5-14mm requirements
20	100	100
14	96	90-100
10	63	50-85
4.75	4.5	0-10

TABLE VIII. CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF PLASTIC WASTE AGGREGATES

Property	Test result	IQS No. .45/1984 requirements
Sulfate content as a SO ₃ , %	Nile	≤ 0.1
Specific gravity	0.95	-
Impact value, %	0.00	≤ 45
Abrasion test (Los Angeles), %	0.00	≤ 35
Crushing value, %	0.00	-
Dry rodded density, kg/m ³	455	-
Absorption, %	0.00	-
Thickness, mm	Max3	-

E. Mixing and Curing

The water used for mixing and curing conforms to the Iraqi specification No. 1703/1992. The chemical properties of the water used are shown in Table IX.

TABLE IX. PROPERTIES OF THE WATER USED

Required tests	Test result	Iraqi specification No.1703/1992
Sulfur salts SO ₃ ⁻² , ppm	316	≤ 1000
Total Dissolved Salts (TDS), ppm	978	≤ 3000
Chlorides, ppm	118	≤ 500
Carbonate and bicarbonate, ppm	307	≤ 1000

F. High Range Water Reducing Admixture (Superplasticizer)

Hyperplastic PC200 complying with ASTM C494-04 type A and G was used in this research. The dosage recommended by the manufacturer is 0.5 - 2.5lt/100kg of cement weight in the mix.

G. Silica Sand Powder

Local silica sand was used in the form of powder. The particle size analysis test is presented in Figure 1. Chemical and physical tests for nano silica sand were carried out and were compared with ASTM C 618 as shown in Tables X and XI respectively.

Fig. 1. Practical size analysis for silica sand powder.

TABLE X. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF NANO SILICA SAND POWDER

Property	Test result	Chemical requirements for Class N natural Pozzolan, ASTM C618-19
SiO ₂ plus Al ₂ O ₃ plus Fe ₂ O ₃ , %	90.04	70.0 Min.
SO ₃ , %	2.10	4.0 Max.
Loss on ignition, %	7.41	10.0 Max.
Moisture content, %	1.8	3.0 Max
Calcium oxide (CaO), %	4.66	-
Magnesium oxide (MgO), %	1.23	-

TABLE XI. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF NANO SILICA SAND POWDER

Property	Test result	Physical requirements for Class N natural Pozzolan, ASTM C618-19
Amount retained when wet sieved on 45 μm, %	0	34 Max.
Strength activity index with Portland cement at 7 days, percentage of control	87.46	75 Min.
Strength activity index with Portland cement at 28 days, percentage of control	92.54	75 Min.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PART

A. Mixtures

ACI 211.1 code design was used to achieve compressive strength of 30MPa at 28 days for cylinder and 37.5MPa for cube specimens as the reference mix. The plastic waste was replaced in different proportions of the volume of the coarse aggregates (natural gravel), and the silica sand replaced cement in different proportions as shown in Table XII.

B. Molds Preparation

Cube steel molds having dimensions of 100×100×100mm were utilized for compressive strength tests, cylinder steel molds of 100×200mm for splitting tensile strength tests, and 100×100×400mm prisms for flexural strength tests.

TABLE XII. MATERIAL CONTENT FOR THE DESIGNED CONCRETE

Materials kg/m ³	Ref.	10% PL*	20% PL	5% SS**	10% SS
Cement	400	400	400	380	360
Fine aggregates	727	727	727	727	727
Coarse aggregates	1020	918	815	1020	1020
Plastic waste	0	27.5	55	0	0
Silica sand	0	0	0	20	40
Water	171	171	171	171	171
S.P. L/100Kg cement	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.80	0.85

*PL: Plastic coarse aggregates, **SS: Silica Sand

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Compressive Strength Measurements

Compressive strength test was conducted according to BS EN 12390-3:2019 (E) as shown in Figure 2. The compressive strength was tested for three cubes at the age of 7, 28, and 90 days.

Fig. 2. Compressive strength test machine.

The results for the reference mix and the concrete containing plastic aggregates are plotted in Figure 3. It was found that the compressive strength decreased by 10.84, 12.10, and 13.62% and by 18.18, 19.23, and 20.15% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement, respectively, at 7, 28, and 90 days. A possible reason for the decrease in the compressive strength is the weakness of the bonding strength between the smooth surface of the plastic aggregates and the cement paste, which leads to a weakening of the transition zone [21-23]. Plastic waste (high density polyethylene) in concrete mixtures as aggregate replacement was studied in [8]. The authors used plastic waste in the concrete mixture with proportions of 10, 20, and 30% of the volume of coarse aggregates. The compressive strength decreased with increasing plastic waste proportion [8].

Fig. 3. Relationship between compressive strength and age for different percentages of plastic waste as coarse aggregates.

The compressive strength test results for the reference mix and the concrete containing the silica sand powder are plotted in Figure 4. The compressive strength increased by 10.20, 12.89, and 12.64% and by 19.46, 20.39, and 19.11% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement, respectively, at 7, 28, and 90 days. The reason for the increase in compressive strength is the reaction of calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂), which is a product of the reaction of cement and water with silica sand, which leads to the formation of a secondary gel (C-S-H) [20]. The mechanical properties of concrete using silica sand as partial (5, 10, 15, 20 and 25% by weight) replacement of cement were studied in [9]. It was found that the best replacement ratio was 15% [9].

Fig. 4. Relationship between compressive strength and age for deferent percentages of silica sand powder.

B. Flexural Strength

Flexural strength was determined according to ASTM C293-16 as shown in Figure 5. The flexural strength average of three models per mixture was examined at the age of 7, 28, and 90 days.

Fig. 5. Flexural strength test machine.

The results of the flexural strength measurements for the reference mix and the concrete containing plastic aggregates are plotted in Figure 6. Flexural strength decreased by 12.26, 12.95, and 10.81% and by 21.63, 19.64 and 19.10% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement, respectively, at 7, 28, and 90 days. The reason is the same with the one mentioned in compressive strength analysis [24]. Some properties of sustainable concrete with mixed plastic waste aggregates can be seen in [10]. When replacing aggregates with plastic waste at proportions of 5, 25, and 45% of volume, a decrease in flexural strength was observed with an increase in the replacement ratio. The flexural strength test results for the reference mix and the concrete containing the silica sand powder are plotted in Figure 7. Flexural strength increased by 11.1, 11.16, and 11.6% and by 17.78, 19.86, and 18.64% for 5% and 10% of silica sand replacement, respectively, at 7, 28,

and 90 days. The reason is the one mentioned in compressive strength analysis [9, 19]. The use of silica sand in partial replacement of the fine material (sand) in concrete was studied in [20]. The best replacement ratio was found to be 15% [20].

Fig. 6. Relationship between flexural strength and age for deferent percentages of plastic waste as coarse aggregates.

Fig. 7. Relationship between flexural strength and age for deferent percentages of silica sand powder.

C. Splitting Tensile Strength

Splitting tensile strength test was determined according to ASTM C496/C496M-17 at the age of 7, 28, and 90 days (Figure 8). The average of three measurements was considered the final value of each mixture.

Fig. 8. Splitting tensile strength test.

The results of the splitting tensile strength tests for the reference mix and the mixtures containing plastic aggregates are plotted in Figure 9. Splitting tensile strength decreased by 11.77, 12.74, and 13.76% and 19.34, 20.22, and 20.63% for 10% and 20% of plastic waste replacement, respectively, at 7, 28, and 90 days. The reason is the same mentioned in compressive strength analysis [10, 25]. The use of plastic waste (high density polyethylene) in concrete mixture as aggregate

replacement was studied in [8]. Plastic waste was utilized in concrete mixtures with proportions of 10, 20, and 30% of the volume of coarse aggregates. It was found that splitting tensile strength decreased by increasing percentage of plastic waste [8]. Splitting tensile strength for the reference mix and the concrete containing silica sand powder is plotted in Figure 10. Splitting tensile strength increased by 10.71, 10.86, and 11.37% and by 17.60, 19.66, and 18.50% for 5% and 10% of silica sand replacement, respectively, at 7, 28, and 90 days. The reason mentioned in compressive strength analysis [9, 18] also applies here. The use of silica sand as partial replacement of fine materials in concrete was studied in [20]. The best replacement ratio was proved to be 15% of cement weight [20].

Fig. 9. Relationship between splitting tensile strength and age for different percentages of plastic waste as coarse aggregates.

Fig. 10. Relationship between splitting tensile strength and age for different percentages of silica sand powder.

D. Dry Density

Dry density test was found by taking the average density of three cubes of $100 \times 100 \times 100$ dimensions at the age of 28 days according to BS 1881-114: 1983. The cubes were drying in the oven at 105 ± 5 °C until constant mass. Dry density decreased by 4.51% and 7.83% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement, respectively, at 28 days. This decrease in the dry density of concrete is caused by the decrease in the plastic density compared to the density of the natural coarse aggregate [26-28]. Experimental investigation on recycled plastics as aggregates in concrete was conducted in [11]. It was found that dry density decreased with increasing plastic waste percentage [11].

Silica sand powder was utilized at proportions of 5% and 10%. It was found that the density of dry concrete increases by 2.78% and 4.10% respectively at 28 days. The reaction of

calcium hydroxide $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ with silica sand powder leads to the formation of a secondary gel (C-S-H) that fills the voids in concrete, making the mixture more denser [9]. The effect of nanomaterials on the properties of limestone dust green concrete was studied in [6]. It was found that dry density increased with the increase in nano Al_2O_3 percentage [6]. The dry density for the reference mix and the concrete containing plastic and silica sand powder are plotted in Figure 11

Fig. 11. Relationship between dry density and different percentages of plastic waste and silica sand powder.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the obtained experimental results, the most notable outcomes of the current study are:

- Compressive strength decreased by 10.84, 12.10, and 13.62% and by 18.18, 19.23, and 20.15% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement, and increased by 10.20, 12.89, and 12.64% and 19.46, 20.39, and 19.11% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement, respectively, at 7, 28, and 90 days.
- Flexural strength decreased by 12.26, 12.95, and 10.81% and 21.63, 19.64, and 19.10% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement, and increased by 11.1, 11.16, and 11.6% and 17.78, 19.86, and 18.64% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement, respectively, at 7, 28, and 90 days.
- Splitting tensile strength decreased by 11.77, 12.74, and 13.76% and 19.34, 20.22, and 20.63% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement and increased by 10.71, 10.86, and 11.37% and 17.60, 19.66 and 18.50% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement, at 7, 28, and 90 days respectively.
- Dry density decreased by 4.51% and 7.83% for 10% and 20% plastic waste replacement, respectively, at 28 days. It increased by 2.78% and 4.10% for 5% and 10% silica sand replacement, respectively, at 28 days.
- The cost of concrete was reduced by using local and recycled materials.
- The concrete production had reduced pollution by using plastic waste as coarse aggregates.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Agarwal and N. Garg, "A Research on Green Concrete," *IJIRMPMS - International Journal of Innovative Research in Engineering & Multidisciplinary Physical Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 4, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9MBZN>.

- [2] B. Suhendro, "Toward Green Concrete for Better Sustainable Environment," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 95, pp. 305–320, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.12.190>.
- [3] B. Rai, S. T. Rushad, B. Kr, and S. K. Duggal, "Study of Waste Plastic Mix Concrete with Plasticizer," *ISRN Civil Engineering*, vol. 2012, May 2012, Art. no. e469272, <https://doi.org/10.5402/2012/469272>.
- [4] P. S. Patil, J. R. Mali, G. V. Tapkire, and H. R. Kumavat, "Innovative techniques of waste plastic used in concrete mixture," *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 3, no. 9, pp. 29–32, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.15623/ijret.2014.0321008>.
- [5] S. A. Chandio, B. A. Memon, M. Oad, F. A. Chandio, and M. U. Memon, "Effect of Fly Ash on the Compressive Strength of Green Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5728–5731, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3499>.
- [6] S. M. Alsaedy and N. Aljalawi, "The Effect of Nanomaterials on the Properties of Limestone Dust Green Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7619–7623, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4371>.
- [7] M. T. Lakhiar, S. Sohu, I. A. Bhatti, N. Bhatti, S. A. Abbasi, and M. Tarique, "Flexural Performance of Concrete Reinforced by Plastic Fibers," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 3041–3043, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2084>.
- [8] N. L. Rahim, S. Sallehuddin, N. M. Ibrahim, R. Che Amat, and M. F. Ab Jalil, "Use of Plastic Waste (High Density Polyethylene) in Concrete Mixture as Aggregate Replacement," *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 701, pp. 265–269, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.701.265>.
- [9] S. Pachipala, "A Study on Mechanical Properties of Concrete using Silica Sand as Partial Replacement of Cement," *International Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 34–39, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.14445/23488352/IJCE-V4I5P111>.
- [10] W. I. Khalil and H. M. Mahdi, "Some properties of sustainable concrete with mixed plastic waste aggregate," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 737, no. 1, Feb. 2020, Art. no. 012073, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/737/1/012073>.
- [11] D. Y. Osei, "Experimental investigation on recycled plastics as aggregate in concrete," *International Journal of Civil and Structural Engineering Research*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 168–174, 2014.
- [12] C. Garg and A. Jain, "Green concrete: Efficient & eco-friendly construction materials," *International Journal of Research in Engineering & Technology*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 259–264, 2014.
- [13] C. V. Nielsen and M. Glavind, "Danish Experiences with a Decade of Green Concrete," *Journal of Advanced Concrete Technology*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 3–12, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.3151/jact.5.3>.
- [14] M. Raghatate Atul, "Use of plastic in a concrete to improve its properties," *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Studies*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 109–111, 2012.
- [15] M. Karthikeyan, K. Balamurali, V. B. Kumar, S. M. Prabakar, and R. Janarthanan, "Utilization of waste plastic in concrete," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1400–1405, 2019.
- [16] M. Lokeshwari, N. Ostwal, K. H. Nipun, P. Saxena, and P. Pranay, "Utilization of Waste Plastic as Partial Replacement of Fine and Coarse Aggregates in Concrete Blocks," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 6, no. 9, pp. 378–382, 2019.
- [17] K. P. Mehta, "Reducing the Environmental Impact of Concrete," *Concrete International*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 61–66, Oct. 2001.
- [18] J. L. Chaudhary, A. Harison, and V. Srivastava, "Use of Silica Sand as Cement Replacement in PPC Concrete," *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, no. 11, pp. 55–58, Nov. 2015.
- [19] K. Jignesh and S. R. Vaniya, "Effect of use of Silica Sand as Fine Material in Concrete," *International Journal for Innovative Research in Science & Technology*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 266–271, 2015.
- [20] P. Hemanth and A. S. N. Manikantha, "Use of silica sand partial replacement of fine material(sand) in concrete," *International Journal For Advanced Research In Science and Technology*, vol. 10, no. 12, pp. 100–106, 2020.
- [21] H. M. Abdelmotti and M. A. Mustafa, "Use of Polypropylene Waste Plastic Pellets as Partial Replacement for Fine Aggregate in Concrete," *University Of Khartoum Engineering Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 37–43, Feb. 2019.
- [22] A. I. Al-Hadithi and M. F. A. Alani, "Mechanical Properties of High Performance Concrete Containing Waste Plastic as Aggregate," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 21, no. 8, pp. 100–115, Aug. 2015.
- [23] Y. Ghernouti, B. Rabehi, B. Safi, and R. Chaid, "Use of Recycled Plastic Bag Waste in the Concrete," *Journal of International Scientific Publications: Materials, Methods and Technologies*, vol. 8, pp. 480–487, 2011.
- [24] S. Arivalagan, "Experimental Study on the Properties of Green Concrete by Replacement of E-Plastic Waste as Aggregate," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 172, pp. 985–990, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.05.145>.
- [25] S. Needhidasan, B. Ramesh, and S. Joshua Richard Prabu, "Experimental study on use of E-waste plastics as coarse aggregate in concrete with manufactured sand," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 22, pp. 715–721, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2019.10.006>.
- [26] M. M. Ahmed and S. S. Raju, "Properties of Concrete by the Addition of Plastic Solid Waste," *International Journal of Science and Research*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 1170–1173, 2013.
- [27] V. Kathe, A. Gangurde, and A. Pawar, "Green Concrete using Plastic Waste," *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 214–216, 2015.
- [28] A. S. M. Sayem, A. Hasnat, M. J. Islam, and T. Tafsirojjaman, "A Study of Green Concrete using Waste Plastic and Stone Dust," in *International Conference on Recent Innovation in Civil Engineering for Sustainable Development*, Gazipur, Bangladesh: Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, 2015, pp. 110–115.

Analysis of Factors Affecting Road Traffic Accidents in North Cyprus

Mehmet Angin
Department of Civil Engineering
Near East University
Nicosia, Cyprus
mehmet.angin@neu.edu.tr

Shaban Ismael Albrka Ali
Department of Civil Engineering
Near East University
Nicosia, Cyprus
shabanismael.albrka@neu.edu.tr

Abstract-Road traffic accidents are a global issue. North Cyprus exhibits a similar trend to the rest of the world. Urbanization and the increasing number of vehicles come along with the increase of road traffic accidents. The objectives of the current study are to draw attention to the issue of road traffic accidents and to identify which factors are the main causes of road traffic accidents in North Cyprus. This article follows a two-stage study to examine the causes of this critical issue. In the first stage, a survey was conducted to determine local public opinions. The participants were asked about how environmental factors, vehicle factors, human factors, and road factors impact accidents. According to the survey outcomes, human factors and road factors have the most significant impact. In the second stage of the study, official data from official statistics were considered. The number of accidents, fatalities, and injured people are indicated initially followed by the causes of accidents. Negligent driving and speeding were identified to be the most frequent causes within the studied period. At the end of the study, the common causes of accidents in official statistics and in survey results were specified. Negligent driving and over-speeding were the major causes of road traffic accidents according to the results.

Keywords-accidents; environmental factors; vehicle factors; human factors; road factors

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Road Traffic Accidents (RTAs) represent an important and well-known global problem. They are considered a substantial public health threat in terms of injuries, disabilities, and fatalities. Deaths caused by RTAs have increased to 1.35 million a year, while up to 50 million injuries are caused by such incidents. In other words, approximately 3,700 people lose their lives every day in RTAs. RTAs are the eighth leading cause of death for people of all ages and the leading cause of death for children and young adults between 5 and 29 years of age. The death rates are three times higher in low-income countries than in high-income countries according to a global status report on road safety published in 2018 [1]. Globally, the total number of vehicles has increased during the last decade [2]. The increase in vehicle numbers and growth in urbanization have led to traffic congestion in urban centres and subsequently to the occurrence of more RTAs. The importance of traffic safety measures has emerged as a result of the increasing number of vehicles as well as the growth in

urbanization [3]. Moreover, the problem of improving road quality and all concerned traffic safety equipment is a key factor of minimizing RTAs [4]. On the other hand, it has been proven that stress and environmental factors play a vital role in causing RTAs. Other important factors such as vehicle age, human error, safety measures and place and time of accident decide the seriousness of the accidents [5]. Another previous study presents an alternative solution that smartphone-based road accident determination and reporting systems can improve drivers' awareness on road safety and save lives in road accidents [6].

In North Cyprus, 478 people lost their lives and 12,551 were injured as a result of RTAs between 2007 and 2018 [7-12]. This study aimed to discover the main causes of RTAs in North Cyprus. The research aim was addressed by taking into consideration a combination of local public opinions and real data. The current article includes three main sections. The first section introduces the status of RTAs globally and provides different examples of past studies about RTAs. In the second section, the study area and the acquisition of data are defined. The concluding aspects are presented in the last section, in which all human and road factors were identified to have a significant impact on RTAs in the survey. On the other hand, the individual, vehicle, and environmental factors were found to have variable impact. Negligent driving and over-speeding came to the fore according to the official statistics. Most of the RTAs were recorded in 2008 and most of the accidents that caused fatalities and injuries happened in 2012 based on the same statistics.

Authors in [13] conducted a study in Turkey in which they used multinomial logit analysis to determine the risk factors that influence the severity of traffic injuries. The results showed that factors such as primary-educated drivers, single-vehicle accidents, drivers over the age of 65, accidents occurring on provincial roads, highways, or state routes and the existence of pedestrian crosswalks increase the likelihood of fatal injuries. Moreover, accidents with private vehicles or cars reach a peak level in the evenings. Fatal injuries decrease in the presence of traffic lights or under clear weather conditions on local city streets. Authors in [14] found that general driving errors and casual pedestrian behavior cause deaths or injuries as a result of RTAs. However, they emphasized in the

Corresponding author: Mehmet Angin

importance of road safety education. Authors in [15] analyzed both severe and non-severe RTAs on dry and wet highways. They used crash records of the 2010-2014 period. They used four different sets of crash data obtained from urban highways and four-lane rural roads in the state of Alabama. The four datasets include severe crashes on wet pavements, non-severe crashes on wet pavements, severe crashes on dry pavements and non-severe crashes on dry pavements. It was found that the rate at which younger drivers were involved in crashes was higher than the one of older drivers, except for non-severe crashes that occurred on wet pavements. In terms of the correlation between non-severe and severe crashes and gender, crash involvement rates for younger and older female drivers were found to be higher on wet pavement surfaces than dry pavement surface conditions.

Authors in [16] examined the relationships between drunk driving or being under the influence of drugs and driver-related risk factors, which are known as factors that contribute to fatal road traffic crashes. Norwegian road traffic crash registries and forensic toxicology databases were utilized. The relation between impairment and driver-related risk factors according to specific substance groups was calculated. According to the study, drug/alcohol use among car or van drivers is associated with speeding, not having a valid driver license, and not using a seatbelt. Moreover, a relationship was found between motorcycle/moped drivers and not having a valid driver license as well as not using a helmet.

Authors in [17] analyzed RTAs involving young drivers in urban areas. The study aimed to demonstrate measures that would reduce the number of RTAs involving young drivers. The authors stated the importance of starting to instill knowledge of traffic culture from an early age in order to develop safe, defensive, and attentive drivers. The educational process results in the creation of responsible drivers, which will also reduce the frequency of RTAs and indirectly the number of fatalities and casualties.

Authors in [18] studied the impact of various risk factors on RTAs. The authors aimed to identify the impact of different risk factors on RTAs in the city of Shenyang, China and discuss the different common factors that affect non-motor vehicle and pedestrian accidents. Time of year, administrative division, and age were the three most common factors for pedestrian and non-motor vehicle accidents. Factors affecting pedestrian and non-motor vehicle accidents also had different orders of importance. The authors used data from 1,227 traffic crashes in which pedestrians and drivers of non-motor vehicles were victims in Shenyang between 2015 and 2017. Administrative division, age, and season were the most common influencing factors. For pedestrian accidents, the season was the most important influencing factor, whereas for non-motor vehicle accidents, the administrative division was the most important influencing factor. Authors in [19] published an article about public health issues connected to road traffic crashes. The study analyzed the factors that contribute to road traffic crashes and made some recommendations.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Study Area and Data Collection

Cyprus is an island situated in the Eastern Basin of the Mediterranean Sea [20]. North Cyprus amounts to around one third of the island, and is divided into six districts: Nicosia, Famagusta, Kyrenia, Morphou, Trikomo, and Lefka [21]. Official statistics books were used to determine the actual number of accidents, number of injured people and number of fatalities. Additionally, a survey was conducted via Google Forms to obtain the thoughts of the local community regarding RTAs. The survey included personal information, trip characteristics, and suggested accident reasons. The evaluation of the survey results and then the compiled official data are presented in this research paper. At the end of the study, the compatibility between public opinion and the actual data is presented.

B. Questionnaire Design

The survey was conducted using an online method and questions were asked to members of the local community including pedestrians, passengers, and drivers. A total of 114 people participated in the survey. Three different groups of questions were included in the survey, which included personal information, daily trip characteristics and causes of RTAs above. The first two sections of the survey include short answers or multiple-choice type questions. The third part of the survey asked the respondents to state the degree of impact (1=no impact, 2=impact, 3=great impact) of the RTA causes. The last part of the survey is divided into four sections, namely human factors, vehicle factors, road factors, and environmental factors. Each section has its own specific questions. Participants were asked to choose the most appropriate impact factor based on their aspects.

C. Personal Information

The personal information section is the first step of the survey. It includes questions about age, gender, job, education level, and workplace location. The respondents were in different age categories. The youngest respondents were 19 years old, and the oldest was 69 years old. The majority of the respondents were 22 years old (9.50%). On the other hand, in terms of the gender of the participants, 68.80% of the respondents were males and 31.20% of them were females. The respondents were from different occupational fields and educational levels. The last question of the personal information part is about the workplace location. This question is a multiple-choice question with the possible choices of Nicosia, Famagusta, Kyrenia, Morphou, Trikomo, or Lefka, and not towns or villages. Although the majority of the participants worked in Nicosia, people who worked in other cities also participated in the survey, except for Trikomo, see Figure 1. Therefore, the opinions of people working in different districts were obtained through this study.

D. Trip Characteristics

This section includes workdays per week, time taken to drive to the workplace, and driving experience. Each participant wrote his/her own answers. Afterwards, all the provided responses were reviewed and clarified with the

following distributions. The majority of the respondents stated that they worked 5 days per week with a ratio of 45.20%. This may be a sign that many of the participants constantly encounter traffic. The second question of the trip characteristics was about trip time. It was a short-answer type of question. Thus, each person wrote a different duration. According to the responses, the maximum duration was seven and a half hours and the minimum was a minute. In the last part of the trip characteristics section, the driving experience of the respondents was examined. The driving experience distribution of the respondents is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Workplace distribution of the respondents.

Fig. 2. Driving experience distribution of the respondents.

E. Road Traffic Accident Causes

This part of the survey is directly related to the detection of the causes of RTAs. The survey participants chose the impact factor that suited their views. Each cause has three different types of options, namely no impact, impact, and great impact, as mentioned in the questionnaire section. The first part of this subsection is about human factors, which includes negligent driving, drunk driving, inexperienced drivers, over-speeding, driving while sleepless and tired, and using a mobile phone while driving. All these reasons were considered to be risk factors that may cause RTAs and were regarded by the respondents as having a significant impact on RTAs. It should be noted that this category achieved the highest vote ratio. The distribution of these reasons is shown in Figure 3. Negligent driving has the highest percentage with 80.20%. Therefore, this demonstrates the awareness among the local community about the risks of negligent driving effect in terms of crashes. Despite negligent driving having the highest percentage, over-speeding,

and using a mobile phone while driving have an effect on RTAs. Over-speeding was selected by 78% and using a mobile phone while driving was chosen by 76.6% of the respondents with regard to having a significant impact. Furthermore, drunk driving and driving while sleepless or tired worsened the human-induced risk factors on RTAs. The effect of inexperience on road traffic accidents received the least percentage.

Fig. 3. Human factors distribution of the respondents.

The second part of the causes of the accidents in the survey considers vehicle factors. Those factors include bad tire usage, insufficient lighting, breakdown of engines, breakdown of gearboxes, and poor brakes. Three types of impact factors were observed for different reasons in this section. Figure 4 describes the moderate impact distribution of bad tyre usage and insufficient lighting. The bad tyre usage had the highest percentage with 50%. On the other hand, insufficient lighting had a moderate impact on RTAs with 44.1%.

Fig. 4. Moderate impact vehicle factors.

Fig. 5. No impact vehicle factors.

Furthermore, the breakdown of engines and gearboxes were considered to be factors that have no impact on RTAs according to the results. The results displayed in Figure 5 show

the distribution of these factors. The breakdown of gearboxes has the highest percentage with 50.50% while the breakdown of engines received 50% with regard to having no impact. Lastly, poor brakes was the only factor that had a great impact for vehicles in RTAs according to the survey with a percentage 42.70%.

The third part of the survey was based on road factors. The great impact choice was selected for all the reasons. Poor road surface, poor road lighting, poor road signing, speed humps and roadway geometry, are included in this part. With 68.50%, poor road lighting had the highest impact percentage among these reasons. The distribution of the answers is shown in Figure 6. The last part of the survey is concerned with environmental factors. The participants were asked about the impact degree of slick road surfaces and weather conditions. According to the results, slick road surfaces have a great impact with 49.10% and weather conditions have a moderate impact with 50%.

Fig. 6. Distribution of road factors.

F. Road Traffic Accident Data

In this section of the study, the actual data of the North Cyprus collected via official statistics are presented. The data period is from 2007 to 2018. The official accident reasons are presented to be compared with the survey outcomes. Regarding the data, the number of RTAs, number of fatalities and injuries were obtained. Most of the traffic accidents occurred in 2008, whereas most of the fatal accidents and most injuries happened in 2012, as shown in Figures 7 and 8. There are fluctuations across the time period.

Fig. 7. Number of RTAs and injuries between 2007-2018.

Figures 9-11 exhibit all the factors that contributed to RTAs in North Cyprus with consideration of the actual data of the

2007 - 2018 period. Negligent driving, speeding, and drunk driving are dominant factor, as were and in the survey part of the study. Figures 8-10 also show the striking effect of lack of compliance with traffic signs and not keeping a safe distance while driving on RTAs.

Fig. 8. Number of fatalities between 2007-2018.

Fig. 9. Accident reasons between 2007-2010.

Fig. 10. Accident reasons between 2011-2014.

Fig. 11. Accident reasons between 2015-2018.

III. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The current study explores different factors to determine the reasons for RTAs in North Cyprus. The necessary information was obtained by conducting an online survey and researching official statistics. As a result of the evaluation of these two sources, the main risks that cause RTAs have been identified. The fact that the statistical data and the results of the survey are in accordance shows the awareness of the local community about RTAs. In addition, this situation increases the reliability of the study. The opinions of 114 respondents who answered the survey's questions were presented with charts. Human and road factors are the primary reasons for RTAs based on the conducted online survey. Human factors such as negligent driving, over-speeding, and using a mobile phone while driving were selected as primary. Other factors like poor road surface and poor road lighting are seen as the most important road factors. Furthermore, poor brakes under vehicle factors and slick roads under environmental factors were evaluated as the main causes of RTAs in North Cyprus.

According to the recorded data, RTAs increased in 2018 compared to 2007, and the number of accidents causing injuries and fatalities decreased. When we examine the distribution of accident causes in the graphs, we see that the major factors that cause accidents are negligent driving, non-compliance with traffic signs, over speeding and not keeping a safe distance while driving.

When both aspects are examined, it is observed that negligent driving and over-speeding, are common. These are the main factors that cause RTAs in North Cyprus. The results of this study can be used by policy makers to ensure traffic safety.

Based on the study findings, the following conclusions can be made:

- Human factors are the major causes of RTAs.
- Consistency of the survey and real data has been observed. Negligent driving and over speeding were major reasons in

both parts of the research. Thus, the main causes of traffic accidents in North Cyprus are negligent driving and over speeding.

- Vehicle factors have 3 types of impact factors on RTAs based on the conducted survey result.
- Road factors have a great impact on the RTAs from the perspective of the North Cyprus society.
- Environmental factors have great or moderate impact on RTAs from the perspective of the local public.
- The number of RTAs increases continuously since 2014.
- There was a decrease in RTA-related fatalities and injuries in 2018 compared to 2007 in North Cyprus.
- This study could be used for developing new mitigation strategies about RTAs in North Cyprus. These strategies can achieve success via education, awareness, and engineering solutions.

REFERENCES

- [1] *Global status report on road safety 2018*. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2018.
- [2] M. U. Farooq, A. Ahmed, S. M. Khan, and M. B. Nawaz, "Estimation of Traffic Occupancy using Image Segmentation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7291–7295, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4218>.
- [3] A. C. Igboanugo and E. F. Ekhuemelo, "Intervention Analysis of Road Traffic Accidents in Nigeria," *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 18–19, pp. 375–382, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.18-19.375>.
- [4] M. Touahmia, "Identification of Risk Factors Influencing Road Traffic Accidents," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2417–2421, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1615>.
- [5] P. Muthusamy, M. Rajendran, R. Kasimani, and P. Sivaprakash, "A Review on Road Traffic Accident and Related Factors," *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, vol. 10, no. 11, pp. 28177–28183, Jan. 2015.
- [6] I. J. Mrema and M. A. Dida, "A Survey of Road Accident Reporting and Driver's Behavior Awareness Systems: The Case of Tanzania," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6009–6015, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3449>.
- [7] *Statistical Yearbook 2018*. Nicosia, Cyprus: North Cyprus Statistical Institute, 2019.
- [8] *Statistical Yearbook 2011*. Nicosia, Cyprus: North Cyprus Statistics and Research Department, 2015.
- [9] *Statistical Yearbook 2016*. Nicosia, Cyprus: North Cyprus Statistics and Research Department, 2017.
- [10] *Statistical Yearbook 2015*. Nicosia, Cyprus: North Cyprus Statistics and Research Department, 2017.
- [11] *Statistical Yearbook 2017*. Nicosia, Cyprus: North Cyprus Statistics and Research Department, 2018.
- [12] *Statistical Yearbook 2014*. Nicosia, Cyprus: North Cyprus Statistics and Research Department, 2016.
- [13] A. K. Çelik and E. Oktay, "A multinomial logit analysis of risk factors influencing road traffic injury severities in the Erzurum and Kars Provinces of Turkey," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 72, pp. 66–77, Nov. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2014.06.010>.
- [14] J. Singh, M. K. Sahni, S. Bilquees, S. M. S. Khan, and I. Haq, "Reasons for road traffic accidents victims' perspective," *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*, vol. 5, no. 4, Jan. 2016, Art. no. 1, <https://doi.org/10.5455/ijmsph.2016.07112015357>.

- [15] A. Kassu and M. Anderson, "Analysis of severe and non-severe traffic crashes on wet and dry highways," *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, vol. 2, Sep. 2019, Art. no. 100043, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2019.100043>.
- [16] A. Valen *et al.*, "Driver-related risk factors of fatal road traffic crashes associated with alcohol or drug impairment," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 131, pp. 191–199, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2019.06.014>.
- [17] P. Brlek, L. Krpan, I. Cvitković, and K. Lukačić, "Analysis of traffic accidents of young drivers in urban areas and measures to increase safety," *Put I Saobraćaj*, vol. 66, no. 1, pp. 25–28, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.31075/PIS.66.01.05>.
- [18] J. Wang, H. Lu, Z. Sun, T. Wang, and K. Wang, "Investigating the Impact of Various Risk Factors on Victims of Traffic Accidents," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 9, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 3934, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093934>.
- [19] J. Kulharni, "Public Health Issue Related to Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs)," *International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1–6, 2020.
- [20] "Geography of Cyprus," *Wikipedia*. Nov. 18, 2021, Accessed: Nov. 23, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Geography_of_Cyprus&oldid=1055817966.
- [21] "Cyprus," *Wikipedia*. Nov. 05, 2021, Accessed: Nov. 23, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Cyprus&oldid=1053625350>.

Anti-Phishing Awareness Delivery Methods

Abdulbasit Darem

Computer Science Department
Northern Border University
Arar, Saudi Arabia
basit.darem@nbu.edu.sa

Abstract-Phishing attacks are increasingly exploited by cybercriminals, they become more sophisticated and evade detection even by advanced technical countermeasures. With cybercriminals resorting to more sophisticated phishing techniques, strategies, and different channels such as social networks, phishing is becoming a hard problem to solve. Therefore, the main objective for any anti-phishing solution is to minimize phishing success and its consequences through complementary means to advanced technical countermeasures. Specifically, phishing threats cannot be controlled by technical controls alone, thus it is imperative to complement cybersecurity programs with cybersecurity awareness programs to successfully fight against phishing attacks. This paper provides a review of the delivery methods of cybersecurity training programs used to enhance personnel security awareness and behavior in terms of phishing threats. Although there are a wide variety of educational intervention methods against phishing, the differences between the cybersecurity awareness delivery methods are not always clear. To this end, we present a review of the most common methods of workforce cybersecurity training methods in order for them to be able to protect themselves from phishing threats.

Keywords-anti-phishing awareness; phishing; phishing attack; awareness delivery methods; cybersecurity threats

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in technology have transformed the way people work, communicate, and socialize quite dramatically. This has also exposed people and companies to various threats, one of which is phishing. Phishing attacks form one of the most common cybersecurity threats that individuals and businesses face around the world, costing victims billions of dollars. Phishing is described as a potent attack vector by which cybercriminals gain access to networks and systems to deliver malicious payloads (e.g. ransomware) or siphon off valuable and sensitive information (e.g. login credentials for online banking or e-commerce sites) from potential victims. Phishing primarily depends on the perception of authenticity normally enacted through authentic-looking emails and spoofed websites purportedly from a legitimate and trusted source. It also masquerades hidden malicious payloads, such as ransomware, as authentic products or services. Figure 1 shows the unique fake websites and phishing emails detected by APWG just in the first quarter (Q1) of 2020, which are significantly higher than during the previous years [1]. Many fake websites are exact copies of the genuine websites, which make it difficult

for people to recognize them as illegitimate websites. These malicious websites usually remain on-line for a short time only.

Fig. 1. Unique phishing websites and emails in Q1 of 2020.

In addition to the usual fake websites and phishing emails, cybercriminals rely on social engineering techniques to exploit human psychology to deceive people. The prevalent human weaknesses cybercriminals exploit include the inability of the people to differentiate real enterprise websites from spoofed ones, the way people interact with systems, the way people understand various alert messages and clues, and so forth. In addition, the attackers frequently use factors such as urgency or intimidations to compel the potential victims. The unsuspecting users are lured to click on a malicious link embedded in emails, which may activate a trustworthy looking spoofed website to disclose sensitive personal or financial information. Cybercriminals use sensitive information illegally harvested from victims for illicit purposes that include identity theft, financial fraud, and corporate espionage [2].

II. PHISHING THREAT LANDSCAPE

With the advances in technical countermeasures making penetration of corporate networks quite difficult, cybercriminals are shifting their focus to exploiting the easier human vulnerability to perpetrate an attack. This shift has made phishing threats prevalent and costly. According to the Anti-Phishing Working Group (APWG), phishing attacks have consistently increased over the last ten years [1]. As phishing threats are gaining prominence and techniques to prevent them are developing, phishers are getting more creative by coming up with new tactics and crafting sophisticated messages to

evade detection by both people and the anti-phishing measures in place.

Until recently, phishing attacks were largely dependent on spoofed websites and emails. Currently, the phishers are also taking advantage of varied channels, in addition to the conventional email messages, such as social media, SMS/text phishing (smishing), Business Email Compromise (BEC), and voice phishing (vishing). Figure 2 shows the recent phishing attack distribution based on specific channels [3]. The study is based on approximately 50 million simulated phishing attacks. It showed BEC-based and social media-based phishing attacks taking prominence over other platforms [3]. For example, with a 176% perennially increase in phishing Uniform Resource Locator (URL), Facebook has become the favor platform for phishing attacks [4]. Recently, social network sites with malicious links masked as fake news are used [5]

Fig. 2. Phishing attack channels.

Another channel being quietly exploited by cybercriminals is the HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) protocol. Exiting web browsers use the HTTPS protocol to alert users when they are attempting to access an "unsecure" website. An increasing practice by cybercriminals is to set up phishing sites that use the HTTPS protocol. Currently, almost 60% of phishing websites use HTTPS [1] to give a false sense of security to unsuspecting victims. Since the fake websites use HTTPS protocol, the web browsers may not flag the fake website as unsecured to the end users. This makes it very difficult for the end users to recognize it as fake. Therefore, fake HTTPS-based websites have become so prevalent that solely relying on conventional representations of Internet security is no longer trusted. Mobile-based [6] and USB-based [7] phishing attacks are other channels that are increasingly exploited by cybercriminals. For example, SMS phishing that targets consumers (e.g. major bank customers) and enterprises is on the rise. With 84% of the customers reporting SMS/text phishing attacks [7], smishing volume is clearly on the rise. A study was carried out in [8] in order to see if people would take a USB flash drive left on various locations of a university campus and plug it to their computer. They found that 45% of people did plug them into their device, as well as opened a file on that USB. This problem is becoming a concern as a recent study shows that 81% of businesses in the study had suffered from malicious USB drops [7].

Cybercriminals are introducing innovative techniques to increase the success rate of phishing attacks and defeat the anti-phishing tools and the effectiveness of intervention programs. The growth of the phishing attack variety and techniques further highlights the shift of the burden of action from an automated exploit or tool to a human intelligence.

III. PHISHING THREAT CHALLENGES

The main challenge cybersecurity professionals face is finding ways to defend enterprise networks effectively and efficiently against attacks that manipulate human frailty. Addressing this challenge is very important for several reasons. In particular, with phishing attacks known to be the most frequent first step in penetrating the defenses of a firm network, the sooner a phishing attempt is detected in the attack chain, the higher the chances of stopping, containing and responding to the attack are. Normally, corporations have technical defenses in place to detect and stop phishing messages before they reach the inboxes of the employees. However, cybercriminals are innovating new tactics and are refining their attack techniques. As a result, phishing attacks are becoming more sophisticated and evading detection even by advanced technical countermeasures [9-11]. The literature discusses several possible ways to identify phishing attempts based on various clues that are visible with the naked eye. These clues include the absence of HTTPS in browsers URL, the content of web browsers, the warning signs displayed by browser toolbars, the various signs for valid certificates (e.g. VeriSign certificates), and the content and the context of the email message. Unfortunately, many people are unaware of security warnings and clues that are displayed on web browsers, or simply disregard them [12]. In addition, it is not easy for average online users to recognize phishing signs or visually identify a spoofed website [13]. Phishing attacks can be identified just by looking at the Uniform Resource Locator (URLs), even though recognizing an impersonated URL from a real one just by looking is not easy [14].

Fig. 3. Reasons for acting on phishing emails.

There are various reasons for the reaction of people to phishing messages, which make dealing with phishing threats very challenging. For example, curiosity, anti-phishing countermeasures, knowledge of the sender, and interest in validating the message are some of the reasons that compel users to act on phishing emails [15] (Figure 3). Authors in [15]

found that 34% of the participants opened emails because they were curious about the content of the message followed by 27% by the urge to find out the validity of the email message. The appearance of a name known to the receiver in the email body impersonating as the sender (even though the sender addresses are different) as well as the trust on the existence of technical anti-phishing measures are some of the reasons that make users to act on phishing emails.

To summarize, with cybercriminals resorting to more sophisticated phishing techniques, strategies, and different channels, phishing is becoming a harder and harder problem to solve. Therefore, the main objective is to minimize the success of phishing and the consequences through complementary means to advanced technical countermeasures. Specifically, phishing threats cannot be controlled by technical controls alone, thus it is imperative for businesses to complement their cybersecurity with awareness programs that successfully fight against phishing attacks.

IV. DELIVERY METHODS' COMPARISON

In this section, we analyze the various delivery methods along with various factors as shown in Table I. Regarding face-to-face delivery methods such as lectures and workshop-based methods, the training time, place, and topic of training are well known in advance. In the self-based class of delivery methods, such as the web-based, the time and place are decided by the trainee while the topic of the training may be known in advance.

Lecture and workshop-based delivery methods are generally moderated by an expert with different levels of involvement. The training is conducted onsite (e.g. classroom) thus the learners and the instructors are required to be physically present in the classroom. All other delivery methods are conducted in a virtual classroom without the physical presence of the instructors and learners. Normally the content in the self-directed delivery methods tends to be generic often developed with a one-size-fits-all scenario. On the other hand, the content in lecture-based training can be adjusted by the instructors to cater to the requirements of the learners. The instructors can also adapt lesson plans to the specific requirements of the learners. The main difference between the story-based method and the other methods, is that the content of the lesson is always written from the perspective of real experiences on an individual, whereas in the other methods, it is written from the perspective of experts. Embedded training is an ongoing real-time training and thus does not require allocation of training timetable [16-17]. As the lecture and workshop-based training methods are highly customizable, it is possible to tailor them to meet the needs of a workforce in a specific division. The trainers in the lecture-based and workshop-based training have an active presence while the instructor is passive in self-directed approaches. A marked difference between the lecture-based and workshop-based methods is the way the knowledge is transferred. In the lecture-based method, the transfer is from the instructor to the trainees, while, in workshop-based training, the knowledge is generated and shared by the participants with occasional contribution from the instructors. Also, the instructor in the lecture-based training has an active involvement in the delivery of the

training content, whereas the involvement of the instructor in the workshop-based training is restricted almost to an observer level. Because employees have to be away from their regular work for the duration of the training, lecture-based and workshop-based trainings tend to be held infrequently. Additionally, both may require more time to complete than the other delivery methods. In the lecture-based training, the communication between the instructor and the learners is one-way. In contrast, the communication in the workshop-based delivery method is many-to-many because the method is based rather on dialogue than on instructions. Communication in all other methods is one-to-one, meaning there is no direct instructor involvement but the communication with the content prepared by the lectures. The problem with the later delivery methods is that if the learners want to apply what they have learnt to specific examples, they must do so on their own. Another obvious drawback is the absence of interaction with other learners and instructors, which means that learners must research and find out on their own what is not clear to them. With the provision to start studying at a time of their choice and proceed at their own pace, learners in self-directed methods must be able to self-motivate in order to finish the lesson.

As learners advance through their training program, it is necessary to track a range of metrics (e.g. participation rate, course completion rate), monitor progress, and reporting. All delivery methods except story-based and embedded-based are capable of tracking the participation rate and the completion rate. Note that in the story-based and embedded-based, an intervention for the end-users who fail the simulated phishing test is prescribed. There is no mechanism to ensure that the end users successfully complete the recommended intervention. But the end-users may or may not follow the recommendations. Only the web-based training method and the video-based and game-based delivery methods have real time reporting to answer queries regarding how many employees have completed the lesson and how many are in the progress.

The lessons in the lecture-based and workshop-based delivery methods have a fixed time to start and end, and thus they are not self-paced. The lecture-based training runs approximately 45 minutes in a classroom. For example, it run for 45 minutes in [18] and for 30 to 45 min in [13]. Since the lecture-based and workshop-based delivery methods are generally moderated by an expert, the pace is determined by the lecturer. In the story-based and the embedded-based delivery methods, the training must be done immediately after the instantiation of the lesson, and thus there is no specific time limit. The self-directed delivery methods allow the learners to choose the pace, sequence, and content of their training material. Video-based learning is flexible, and users could watch and rewatch the videos as they wish [31]. This is generally true for game-based learning. Some game-based learning progresses are controlled in such a way that the learner must achieve certain threshold in terms of correctly identifying phishing and genuine URLs [18].

Feedback is a core component in providing an effective learning experience to learners. The lecture-based delivery method, due to the active presence of the instructor during the training, offers real-time feedback [19]. The workshop-based

and the game-based [20] delivery methods also offer real-time feedback for the same reason. The embedded delivery method provides quick and useful feedback to the end users at the very moment when they make mistakes [21]. The story-based delivery method that implements the embedded training [22] also provides instant feedback. However, text-based delivery does not offer feedback or other interactive elements due to the static nature of the content format. Video-based delivery also does not provide feedback.

V. ANALYSIS OF THE DELIVERY MODELS

The current research suggests that different training delivery methods have different outcomes on the learners' ability to recognize and mitigate phishing threats [18, 21]. With this in mind, we reviewed some of the user studies with a focus on those that consider two or more delivery methods. This will shed some light on the delivery methods that are most effective in enabling learners to identify and mitigate phishing threats. Table I summarizes the various research results we considered.

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE DELIVERY METHODS

Reference	Delivery Method								Satisfaction				Communication tracking				
	Lecture	Workshop	Story	Text	Web	Video	Game	Embedded	Preference	Click rate	False negative	False positive	Self-efficacy	Many-many	Participate	Completed	Reporting
[27]	x	√	√	x	x	√	√	x	√	x	x		√	√	√	√	x
[2]	x	x	x	√	x	√	√	x	√		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
[16]	x	x	x	√	√	√	√	√	√	x	√	√	x	x	√	√	x
[28]	√	x	x	√	x	√	√	x	x	√	x		√	√	x	x	√
[29]	x	x	x	x	√	x	√	x	x	√	x		√	√	x	x	√
[30]	√	x	x	√	x	√	√	x	x	√	x		√	√	x	x	√
[31]	x	x	√	x	√	x	x	x	x	√	x		√	√	x	x	x
[32]	x	x	√	x	√	x	x	x	x	√	x		√	√	x	x	x

Authors in [23] tested the efficacy of embedded phishing with a web-based training page to see if it improves the phishing awareness of the users. The study considered 1,359 corporate employees. The authors organized the outcome of the evaluation in terms of click rate as: people who always clicked (Always) irrespective of previous training about phishing, people who clicked at least once (Once), people who clicked after training (Trained), and people who never clicked (Never). The result showed that anti-phishing education works as demonstrated by nearly 63% reduction of the click rate after the training. This study revealed that there are people who ignore security training and advice. The main reasons for the end user's decision to accept or ignore security advices are investigated in [24-25]. The authors revealed that perceived trust of the security advice sources as the main reason for accepting it while factors such as inconvenience, privacy concerns, and excessive information are grounds for rejecting the security advice. Authors in [26] determined that fear of consequences of clicking or not clicking as the main driver for people to act on phishing emails. A summary of the results of the works of Wash and Cooper [31], Marsden et al. [32] and Caputo et al. [23] in terms of click rate by the study subjects is shown in Figure 5. The results of these studies show that there is a correlation between the performance of the training and the different class of subjects. Therefore, it is paramount to consider the demographic information of the subjects when designing and delivering intervention training.

trained with game-based delivery method were able to recognize a fake site with a higher rate of accuracy than the participants who were trained using a website.

Fig. 4. Participants click rate characteristics.

Several user studies that measure the efficacy of game-based training method as compared to other delivery methods exist. Authors in [29] evaluated the effectiveness of game-based delivery method in raising phishing attack awareness. They compare it to a web-based delivery method (i.e. tutorial information given in APWG website on phishing). In terms of recognizing fake websites, the result showed that the end-users

Authors in [16] evaluated the efficacy of embedded training to improve end user susceptibility to phishing threats using the False Positive (FP) and False Negative (FN) metrics. A FP happens if a user identifies a genuine website as a phishing one while a FN occurs if a user wrongly identifies a phishing website as a genuine website. Different training delivery methods, namely game-based, web-based/video-based, and text-based were considered. The participants received several simulated phishing emails. A remedial training is randomly offered from the list of the four embedded training methods to the end users who clicked on the embedded link in the simulated emails. After the training, another set of simulated phishing emails were sent to the same end users and then it was behaviorally measured whether they fell victims to

the phishing attacks or not. The outcome of the study is summarized in Table II. The overall result shows that the end users correctly recognize phishing links in a significantly better rate after the training. Participants trained with game-based delivery method performed better overall. This may be due to the fact that they performed the post-training test immediately after training. The result also shows that training with game-based methods is as good as the web-based in regard to FN but better in terms of FP. Although the game-based delivery method is able to decrease FP from an original 30% to 14%, as well as FN from the original 34% to 17%. Unfortunately, the result shows that a significant number of end users are still susceptible to phishing threats.

TABLE II. EMBEDDED TRAINING PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Evaluation	Text-based		Game-based		Web-based	
	FP	FN	FP	FN	FP	FN
Pre-training	27%	43%	30%	34%	30%	38%
Post training	21%	19%	14%	17%	41%	12%

Authors in [27] conducted a user study of game-based delivery method and compared it against web-based [33] using 39 students at Cornell. The game used in study was What.Hack [27] and the web-based training material [33]. The participants were given a pretest, training, and a posttest, in that sequence. The effectiveness was measured using the correctness percentage (click rate). The result of the experiment shows a significant improvement for game-based delivery method from 65% before training to 89% after training (about 37% improvement) in correctly recognizing phishing attempts. The performance of the web-based delivery methods of Wash et al. [31] and Wen et al. [27] is compared in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Web-based delivery method outcome.

The result shows that training reduces the susceptibility to phishing threats but incorporating lecture-based training does not have significant changes. Following training, both groups substantially reduced the threat. The authors also considered the confidence level of the participants after training. The learners' self-confidence based on self-assessment showed that the learners showed strong confidence in their ability to recognize phishing emails. The result also suggested that preference for lecture-based delivery method is higher than the other methods.

TABLE III. COMBINED TRAINING PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Evaluation	Group A		Group B	
	Click rate	Data divulge	Click rate	Data divulged
Pre-training	13.2% (9/68)	77.77% (7/9)	3.1% (2/56)	50% (1/2)
Post training	1.5% (1/68)	100% (1/1)	1.6% (1/56)	100% (1/1)
Reduction	11.4%		51.6%	

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a review of the delivery methods of cybersecurity training programs aimed at improving personnel's awareness and behavior of information security in the context of phishing. The phishing landscape and challenges were addressed. The delivery methods were analyzed to shed some light on the delivery that is most effective in enabling learners to identify and mitigate phishing threats. The delivery methods along with their various factors were analyzed. In face-to-face delivery methods, such as lecture and workshop-based methods, training time, place, and topic of training are well known in advance. In the self-based class of delivery methods such as the web-based, the time and place are decided by the trainee while the topic of the training may be known in advance. The web-based delivery method performance for several studies was compared to observe that after training, the click rate decreases by 21% which suggests that training does decrease susceptibility to phishing threat to certain extent. The result also suggested that the preference for the lecture-based delivery method is higher than for the other methods.

REFERENCES

- [1] APWG, *Phishing Activity Trends Report*, 1st Quarter. Anti-Phishing Working Group, 2020.
- [2] J. Abawajy, "User preference of cyber security awareness delivery methods," *Behaviour & Information Technology*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 237–248, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2012.708787>.
- [3] "2021 Report on Phishing Attacks - State of the Phish," *Proofpoint*, Mar. 30, 2021. <https://www.proofpoint.com/us/resources/threat-reports/state-of-phish> (accessed Nov. 23, 2021).
- [4] "Facebook Phishing: Why Social Media is a New Phishers' Favorite," *Vade Secure*. <https://www.vadeseure.com/en/blog/facebook-phishing-is-exploding> (accessed Nov. 23, 2021).
- [5] E. D. Frauenstein and S. Flowerday, "Susceptibility to phishing on social network sites: A personality information processing model," *Computers & Security*, vol. 94, Jul. 2020, Art. no. 101862, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2020.101862>.
- [6] D. Goel and A. K. Jain, "Mobile phishing attacks and defence mechanisms: State of art and open research challenges," *Computers & Security*, vol. 73, pp. 519–544, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2017.12.006>.
- [7] *2021 Report on Phishing Attacks - State of the Phish*. Proofpoint, 2021.
- [8] M. Fischer et al., "Users Really Do Plug in USB Drives They Find," in *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, San Jose, CA, USA, May 2016, pp. 306–319, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SP.2016.26>.
- [9] S. Nasiri, M. T. Sharabian, and M. Ajami, "Using Combined One-Time Password for Prevention of Phishing Attacks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2328–2333, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1510>.
- [10] A. Al-Marghilani, "Comprehensive Analysis of IoT Malware Evasion Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7495–7500, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4296>.

- [11] D. K. Singh and M. Shrivastava, "Evolutionary Algorithm-based Feature Selection for an Intrusion Detection System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7130–7134, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4149>.
- [12] M. Alsharnouby, F. Alaca, and S. Chiasson, "Why phishing still works: User strategies for combating phishing attacks," *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, vol. 82, pp. 69–82, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2015.05.005>.
- [13] R. M. Mohammad, F. Thabtah, and L. McCluskey, "Tutorial and critical analysis of phishing websites methods," *Computer Science Review*, vol. 17, pp. 1–24, Aug. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2015.04.001>.
- [14] J. S. Tharani and N. A. G. Arachchilage, "Understanding phishers' strategies of mimicking uniform resource locators to leverage phishing attacks: A machine learning approach," *Security and Privacy*, vol. 3, no. 5, 2020, Art. no. e120, <https://doi.org/10.1002/spy2.120>.
- [15] Z. Benenson, "Exploiting curiosity and context: How to make people click on a dangerous link despite their security awareness," presented at the Black Hat USA 2016, 2016.
- [16] P. Kumaraguru, S. Sheng, A. Acquisti, L. F. Cranor, and J. Hong, "Teaching Johnny not to fall for phish," *ACM Transactions on Internet Technology*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 7:1-7:31, Jun. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1754393.1754396>.
- [17] J. Hong, "The state of phishing attacks," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 74–81, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2063176.2063197>.
- [18] K. RaniSahu and J. Dubey, "A Survey on Phishing Attacks," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 88, pp. 42–45, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.5120/15392-4007>.
- [19] P. Kim, J. V. Homan, and R. L. Metzger, "How long do employees remember information security training programs? A study of knowledge acquisition and retention," *Issues in Information Systems*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 197–207, 2016.
- [20] B. B. Gupta, A. Tewari, A. K. Jain, and D. P. Agrawal, "Fighting against phishing attacks: state of the art and future challenges," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 28, no. 12, pp. 3629–3654, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-016-2275-y>.
- [21] "The Art of Deception in Social Media Phishing." <https://www.vadesecond.com/en/blog/the-art-of-deception-in-social-media-phishing> (accessed Nov. 23, 2021).
- [22] I. Qabajeh, F. Thabtah, and F. Chiclana, "A recent review of conventional vs. automated cybersecurity anti-phishing techniques," *Computer Science Review*, vol. 29, pp. 44–55, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2018.05.003>.
- [23] D. D. Caputo, S. L. Pfleeger, J. D. Freeman, and M. E. Johnson, "Going Spear Phishing: Exploring Embedded Training and Awareness," *IEEE Security Privacy*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 28–38, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MSP.2013.106>.
- [24] E. M. Redmiles, S. Kross, and M. L. Mazurek, "How I Learned to be Secure: a Census-Representative Survey of Security Advice Sources and Behavior," in *ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, Vienna, Austria, Oct. 2016, pp. 666–677, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2976749.2978307>.
- [25] E. M. Redmiles, A. R. Malone, and M. L. Mazurek, "I Think They're Trying to Tell Me Something: Advice Sources and Selection for Digital Security," in *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, San Jose, CA, USA, May 2016, pp. 272–288, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SP.2016.24>.
- [26] K. Greene, M. Steves, and M. Theofanos, "No Phishing beyond This Point," *Computer*, vol. 51, no. 6, pp. 86–89, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2018.2701632>.
- [27] Z. A. Wen, Z. Lin, R. Chen, and E. Andersen, "What.Hack: Engaging Anti-Phishing Training Through a Role-playing Phishing Simulation Game," in *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, Scotland, UK, May 2019, pp. 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300338>.
- [28] K. F. Tschakert and S. Ngamsuriyaroj, "Effectiveness of and user preferences for security awareness training methodologies," *Heliyon*, vol. 5, no. 6, Jun. 2019, Art. no. e02010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02010>.
- [29] N. A. G. Arachchilage, S. Love, and K. Beznosov, "Phishing threat avoidance behaviour: An empirical investigation," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 60, pp. 185–197, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.02.065>.
- [30] S. Stockhardt *et al.*, "Teaching Phishing-Security: Which Way is Best?," in *International Conference on ICT Systems Security and Privacy Protection*, Ghent, Belgium, Jun. 2016, pp. 135–149.
- [31] R. Wash and M. M. Cooper, "Who Provides Phishing Training? Facts, Stories, and People Like Me," in *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, Montreal, QC, Canada, Apr. 2018, pp. 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3174066>.
- [32] J. Marsden *et al.*, "Facts and Stories in Phishing Training: A Replication and Extension," in *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, New York, NY, USA, Apr. 2020, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3334480.3381435>.
- [33] Barracuda Networks Inc, "Click Thinking Content," *Barracuda Campus*. <https://campus.barracuda.com/product/phishline/doc/79463828/click-thinking-content/> (accessed Nov. 23, 2021).

Design and Evaluation of Transmitting Antennas for Solar Power Satellite Systems

Abdullah Alogla

Department of Electrical Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Ha'il
abdullahogla@gmail.com

Mohamed Abdelaziz Hassan Eleiwa

Department of Electrical Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Ha'il
ma.eleiwa@uoh.edu.sa

Hammad Alshortan

Department of Electrical Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Ha'il
en.hh2010@hotmail.com

Abstract-This study attempts to identify, design, and evaluate transmitting antennas for Solar Power Satellite (SPS) systems. The design approach aimed at meeting the SPS operational requirements at ISM bands, namely 2.4-2.5GHz for the NASA and 5.725-5.875GHz for the JAXA models. The primary attributes of SPS antennas for transmitting Beamed High-Power Microwaves (BHPMs) are high power handling capability, efficiency, and directivity with narrow beamwidth and lower sidelobe levels. Using a planar end-fed 20×20 SWA module, the whole planar Slotted Waveguide Antenna Arrays (SWAAs) were designed for both the NASA and JAXA reference models having 1km diameter antenna aperture, peak power level over 1GW, directivity over 80dBi, Side Lobe Level (SLL) less than 20dB, and pencil beam with HPBW less than 0.01°. The proposed slotted waveguide transmitting antenna arrays fulfilled the operational requirements for both the NASA and JAXA SPS reference models. Due to the higher operating frequency, the results showed that the proposed planar SWA array performs better on the JAXA than on the NASA SPS model.

Keywords-solar power satellites; microwave power transmission; slotted waveguide antenna arrays

I. INTRODUCTION

Solar Power Satellites (SPSs), or Space-Based Solar Power (SBSP) systems are used to collect the solar power and convert it into microwave energy to be beamed to a ground station antenna on earth [1, 2]. Several SPS proposals have been introduced since the first SPS concept, proposed by Peter Glaser in 1968. NASA with the US Department of Energy (DOE) presented the first SPS reference model in 1978. The second reference SPS model was introduced by the Japanese Aerospace eXploration Agency (JAXA) in 2000, featuring electronic beam steering instead of mechanical antenna rotation. Recently, NASA and JAXA introduced improved models, while other agencies in different countries became interested and proposed several SPS models to be launched in

different orbits. The latest SPS concept is the smaller SPS constellations, devised to overcome challenges such as weight, cost, and launching problems. Overviews of the recent international SPS models and research are presented in [3-5]. The specifications of NASA and JAXA reference models are presented in Table I, as published in [6].

TABLE I. REFERENCE SPS MODELS' PARAMETERS

Model	Old JAXA	JAXA 1	JAXA 2	NASA
Frequency	5.8GHz	5.8GHz	5.8GHz	2.45GHz
Transmitting antenna diameter	2.6Km	1Km	1.93Km	1Km
Transmitted power	1.3GW	1.3GW	1.3GW	6.72GW

An SPS system consists of the space and the ground stations. The space station consists of a solar energy collector, a microwave generator, and a transmitting antenna array, while the ground station mainly consists of the receiving antenna (rectenna). The major SPS benefits are the permanent transfer of solar power from space to earth wirelessly, without cables, grids, towers, and carbon emissions. The main drawbacks of the SPS technology are interferences and biological effects associated with the wireless transmission of electricity using High Power Microwave (HPM) signals [7-9]. Efficiency improvement is one of the main challenges of SPS systems, as it can reduce cost, interferences, and biological effects. The SPS efficiency is a combination of DC-RF conversion efficiency, RF-DC conversion efficiency [10], and beam efficiency. Beam efficiency depends on the transmitting and receiving antenna specifications, the wavelength, and the separation distance between the space and ground stations [11].

To improve beam efficiency, the transmitting antenna should be designed to radiate a narrow and controllable beam with suppressed sidelobes to concentrate the power on the receiving antenna aperture. Therefore, a phased array antenna with retro-directive beam control is usually used for beaming high-power microwaves to the receiving antenna on earth [12-

15]. Tapered excitation is also commonly used to suppress the sidelobes, and thence more concentrated microwave power will be collected by the receiving antenna aperture area. The most famous excitation tapering techniques are Chebyshev, Taylor, Villeneuve, Gaussian, and binomial distributions. The radiating elements of the phased antenna system might be dipole, microstrip patch, reflector, horn, or Slotted Waveguide Antenna (SWA).

Due to their planar and rigid construction with low loss, high power handling capability, and high efficiency, SWAAs are more attractive candidates for application in microwave systems such as wireless communications, radars, and SPS systems [16-21]. The general principles and components of microwave power transmission systems and their space applications are outlined in [16], while several SWA arrays were designed in [17] with different tapered distributions for high power microwave applications. A slotted waveguide linear antenna array with 16 elements was designed at 9.4GHz for radar applications and simulated using HFSS in [18]. Subarraying techniques were applied in [19] with conventional longitudinal slot arrays to increase the relative bandwidth up to 15% at X-band for SAR applications. A procedure based on Elliott's model was proposed in [20] to design shaped beam planar arrays. An analytical procedure was introduced in [21], based on Babinet's principle, to design and construct a slotted waveguide antenna array at 2.45GHz.

Recently, trapezoidal-shaped slots were used for increasing the bandwidth of SWAAs on 5G applications [22]. Slots were cut on the surface of the circular waveguide WC69 and filled with Teflon. A 4.54% of fractional bandwidth of the 24GHz center frequency was achieved with gains up to 14.71dBi over the operating bandwidth. A planar resonant SWAA of 24×24 longitudinal slots on the broad surface of a rectangular waveguide was designed and simulated for satellite communications within the 29.5-31GHz frequency band in [23], using the sub arraying technique, but without achieving the required 5% fractional bandwidth. Moreover, the simulated SLL was found to be higher than the predicted 20dB. The simulation results produced approximately the designed gain of 30dBi and 3° beamwidth in both azimuth and elevation planes. An antenna with a metasurface placed inside at an optimized location was proposed in [24] for an efficient DC-RF SPS module at 2.45GHz center frequency, without stating any further design details or parameters. The presented antenna patterns showed that the H-plane beamwidth was wider than the E-plane. Simplified closed-form equations were used in [25] to calculate the slots' lengths, widths, and their distribution along the length of the radiating and feeder SWAs. This method was applied to design an 8×8 planar SWAA at 3.952GHz for maritime applications. The obtained HPBWs were 9.6° and 11.4° with SLRs of 22.3dB and 28.1dB for E and H planes, respectively.

Slots are ideal radiating elements that can be easily cut into the waveguide walls incorporating their waveguide feeding structures without the need for special matching networks. Such integrated and robust antenna structures are conducive for the space stations of SPS systems. The radiating slots may be cut on the waveguide walls in longitudinal (shunt), transversal

(series), or inclined shapes. The slotted waveguide antenna arrays can be resonant (standing) or non-resonant (traveling) waves. The traveling wave array has larger bandwidth but lower efficiency due to the power absorbed by the terminating matched loads. Also, the main beam direction of the traveling wave SWAA depends on the operating frequency. On the other hand, resonant SWAA has a narrower beamwidth with higher efficiency, its main beam direction is frequency independent, and it is always perpendicular to its array axis (broadside). Due to these attractive features, this study adopted the resonant SWAA for SPS systems.

To the best of our knowledge, no published papers have yet discussed an SWAA design to meet the operational requirements of the reference SPS models, apart from the scientific reports of NASA [26, 27] and JAXA [28, 29]. Therefore, this study aims to analyze, design, and simulate operable SWA arrays for the NASA and JAXA SPS reference models using closed-form equation, Babinet's principle, and different software packages such as PCADE, Antenna Magus, and CST Microwave Studio.

II. SWAA PARAMETERS AND DESIGN PROCEDURES

The main objective of this study was to design SWA arrays as radiating elements for SPS transmitting antenna systems. The designed SWA arrays were simulated, and their performance was evaluated on the operational requirements of NASA and JAXA SPS models shown in Table II.

TABLE II. TYPICAL TRANSMITTING ANTENNA PARAMETERS FOR NASA AND JAXA SPS MODELS

Parameter	NASA Model	JAXA Model
Frequency bandwidth [GHz]	2.4-2.5	5.8-5.9
Operating frequency [GHz]	2.45	5.8
HPBW beamwidth [degrees]	<4°	<4°
Directivity [dBi]	>30	>30
Antenna diameter	1Km	1Km
Sidelobe level (SLL) [dB]	<20	<20
Output power (beamed to earth)	>1.3GW	>1.3GW

The first step in designing an SWA array is to choose the proper waveguide based on the frequency band. Figure 1 shows the rectangular waveguide and its cross-sectional dimensions.

Fig. 1. Rectangular waveguide geometry and cross-sectional dimensions.

Assuming the dominant mode TE₁₀ is propagating, the waveguide parameters are:

$$\lambda_{cm} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{m}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n}{b}\right)^2}}; \lambda_g = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{1 - \lambda^2 / \lambda_{cm}^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$Z_{gTE} = \frac{\omega\mu}{\beta} = \eta \frac{\lambda_g}{\lambda}, \quad P = \frac{1}{4} \frac{|E_m|^2}{Z_{gTE10}} \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha_c = \frac{P_L}{2P} = \frac{1}{\sigma\delta b\eta} \frac{f_{c10} \left[\left(\frac{f}{f_{c10}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{2b}{a} \right)^2 \right] \left[\frac{Nep}{m} \right]}{\sqrt{(f/f_{c10})^2 - 1}}, \delta = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\omega\mu\sigma}}, \eta = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}} \quad (3)$$

where λ_c is the cutoff wavelength, λ_g is the guide wavelength, Z_{gTE} is the guide impedance for TE mode, and E_m and P are the electric field amplitude and power propagating into the waveguide, respectively. The attenuation constant due to power losses (P_L) in the waveguide conducting walls is α_c . Based on the frequency bands of both NASA and JAXA SPS models, the appropriate rectangular waveguides were chosen, their parameters were calculated using the above equations, and the results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III. WAVEGUIDES PARAMETERS FOR SPS MODELS

Parameter	NASA Model	JAXA Model
SPS frequency range [GHz]	2.4-2.5	5.8-5.9
Operating frequency [GHz]	2.45	5.8
Free space wavelength (λ) [mm]	122.45	51.72
Proper rectangular waveguide	WR340	WR159
Waveguide frequency range [GHz]	2.2-3.3	4.9-7.05
Waveguide dimensions [mm]	$a=86.36,$ $b=43.18$	$a=40.39,$ $b=20.19$
Cutoff wavelength (λ_c) for TE10 [mm]	172.72	80.77
Cutoff frequency (f_c) for TE10 [GHz]	1.737	3.714
Guide wavelength (λ_g) [mm]	173.62	67.34
Propagation constant (β) for TE10 [rad/m]	36.206	93.323
Attenuation coefficient (α_c) [dB/m]	0.01	0.04
Waveguide impedance (Z_{gTE10}) [Ω]	534.5	490.8

Figure 2 represents the sketch of a linear resonant SWAA of N slots (a) and its equivalent circuit (b). The slots are cut longitudinally on the rectangular waveguide broad wall. The waveguide ends are terminated with short circuits, a quarter guide wavelength ($\lambda_g/4$) apart from the centers of last slots. The slot elements' centers are placed half guide wavelength ($d_s = \lambda_g/2$) apart and are offset on the opposite side of the waveguide centerline to ensure uniform phase excitation. The slot length was chosen to be resonant, approximately equal to half wavelength ($L_s = \lambda/2$), and thus the longitudinal slot was equivalent to a shunt conductance g , as shown in Figure 2(b).

Fig. 2. (a) Resonant shunt slotted waveguide array and (b) its equivalent circuit.

An equation was developed in [30] for calculating the normalized slot conductance ($g_n = G_n/g_w$) of the n -th narrow slot

radiating into a half-space, which accounts for the actual slot length. This can be used to calculate each slot displacement x_n , $n=1, 2, \dots, N$:

$$g_n = 2.09 \frac{\lambda_g}{\lambda_0} \frac{a}{b} \left(\cos\left(\frac{0.464\pi\lambda_0}{\lambda_g}\right) - \cos(0.464\pi) \right)^2 \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x_n}{a}\right) \quad (4)$$

For perfect matching, the waveguide normalized input conductance should be equal to the total equivalent normalized conductance of the shunt slots for the end-fed linear SWA array, i.e.:

$$\sum_{n=1}^N g_n = 1 \quad (5)$$

The slot conductance is proportional to its radiated power, according to:

$$g_n = C a_n^2 \quad (6)$$

where a_n is the excitation coefficient of the n -th slot. The excitation coefficients are adjusted to yield the required pattern. Equation (6) was substituted into (5) to get the constant C . Then substituting C into (6) to get the normalized n -th slot's conductance g_n , and hence the n -th slot offset x_n can be calculated from (4). For a center-fed linear SWA array terminated by short circuits at both ends, the matching condition provided by (5) will be:

$$\sum_{n=1}^N g_n = 2 \quad (7)$$

For the end-fed linear uniform array of N identical shunt slots, the normalized slot conductance is simply computed from (5) to be $g_n = 1/N$ for all n . Accordingly, the offset x_n will be the same. Alternatively, Babinet's principle could be used directly to design the SWA array in terms of its dual dipole array, where the (thin) slot admittance Y_s is related to its complementary thin wire dipole impedance Z_w by:

$$Y_s = G_s + jB_s = 4Z_w/\eta^2 \quad (8)$$

where $\eta = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}}$ is the intrinsic impedance of the surrounding medium. Substituting resonant conditions in free space ($\eta=377$, $Z_w=73.2$) into (8) gives the resonant slot conductance as:

$$G_s = \frac{(4 \times 73.2)}{377^2} = 2.06mS \quad (9)$$

The power radiated by a slot is $P_s = V_s^2 G_s$. Assuming a uniform electric field distribution across the slot aperture, $E_s(x,z) = E_s$, and slot voltage $V_s = E_s W_s$, where W_s is the slot width. The minimum slot width W_s^{min} is determined from the maximum power handling capability of the slot (P^{max}), which corresponds to applying the breakdown electric field E_{bd} . Substituting by the slot conductance G_s from (9), and the free space breakdown electric field $E_{bd} = 3MV/m = E_s$, the minimum slot width will be equal to:

$$W_s^{min} = \left(\frac{1}{E_{bd} \sqrt{G_s}} \sqrt{P^{max}} \right) = 0.00735 \sqrt{P^{max}} \quad (10)$$

For a thin slot, the length to width slot ratio (L_s/W_s) should be kept larger than 10.

The required number of slots N in the SWA array can be estimated based on the maximum power handling capability,

specified voltage standing wave ratio VSWR, bandwidth, and the required beamwidth and directivity. The required transmitting antenna diameter is approximately 1Km for both NASA and JAXA models, as shown in Table II. The equivalent square aperture array shall have approximately equal x and y dimensions as $L_x=L_y=886.41\text{m}$. For a center-fed linear array, its waveguide length is $L_g = (N_s - 1) d + \lambda_g/4 + \lambda_g/4$, where d is the inter-element spacing from slots' centers equal to $g/2$ for a resonant array. Thus, the number of slot elements in x or y dimensions is $N_s=N_x=N_y=1772.82/\lambda_g$, and the total number of slots N_t required to a 1Km diameter SPS transmitting antenna area with a planar square array of slotted waveguides is calculated as:

$$N_t = (N_s)^2 = \left(\frac{1772.82}{\lambda_g}\right)^2 \quad (11)$$

III. SWA DESIGN AND SIMULATION

Based on the previous design procedures, several linear SWA arrays having different numbers of slots with uniform and tapered distributions were designed and simulated using software packages such as PCAAD, Antenna Magus, and CST Microwave Studio. Linear uniform resonant SWA arrays with 10 elements were designed for 2.45GHz and 5.8GHz frequencies. Figure 3 shows the field pattern of its equivalent half-wave dipoles array for 2.45GHz, where 3dB beamwidth was 7.05° , directivity was 11.6dB, and SLL was -13dB. Chebyshev excitations were used for the same array to get its field pattern, where the 3dB beamwidth was 7.790° , which was slightly wider than its uniform excitation counterpart, but the SLL was largely suppressed to -20dB. Similar patterns with approximately the same pattern parameters were obtained for the arrays designed for 5.8GHz.

Fig. 3. The field patterns of a linear uniform array having 10 uniform excitation half-wave dipoles at 2.45GHz.

Other linear SWA arrays, having 20 elements, were designed for 2.45GHz and 5.8GHz, and Figure 4 shows the field patterns for 5.8GHz. HPBW was narrower and decreased by more than a factor of half the 10-element arrays for both uniform and Chebyshev excitations. Similar patterns were obtained for the designed array at 2.45GHz.

Fig. 4. The field patterns of linear uniform array of 20 Chebyshev excitation half wave dipoles at 5.8 GHz.

Planar arrays of 20×20 equivalent half-wave dipoles with the same dual-slot dimensions ($L_s=\lambda/2$, $d_x=g/2$, and $d_y=\text{waveguide width } a$) were designed for 2.45GHz and 5.8GHz. The obtained patterns for both frequencies were quite similar. Figures 5(a) and 5(b) show the array patterns with uniform and Chebyshev excitations at 2.45GHz, where a pencil beam was obtained with 3° HPBW in both planes.

Fig. 5. The field patterns for a planar uniform array of 20×20 half-wave dipoles at 2.45 GHz. (a) Uniform and (b) Chebyshev excitation.

Linear and planar resonant SWA arrays having 10 and 20 slots with uniform and Villeneuve distributions were simulated for 2.45GHz and 5.8GHz.

Fig. 6. Simulated resonant SWA arrays. (a) Linear center-fed array, (b) end-fed planar array.

The simulated SWA arrays are shown in Figures 6(a) and (b) for linear and planar structures respectively. The SWA arrays' parameters were obtained by plugging the data of Table II into (4)-(11). Table IV shows the results for the 10-element linear SWAAs on 2.45GHz and 5.8GHz.

TABLE IV. DESIGN PARAMETERS OF LINEAR 10-ELEMENT UNIFORM RESONANT SWA ARRAYS FOR SPS MODELS

Parameter	NASA Model	JAXA Model
No. of slot elements	10	10
Slot length (L_s) [mm]	61.22	25.86
Slot spacing (d_s) [mm]	86.81	33.67
Slot width (W_s) [mm]	6	2.8
Slot offset (x_s) [mm]	8.85	5.41
Ratio (L_s/W_s)	10.2	9.24
Short circuit end spacing	43.41	16.84
Distance from feed slot to feed termination [mm]	79.36	33.52
Feed waveguide length [mm]	158.7	67.05
Feed slot length [mm]	57.9	24.46
Feed slot width	6.118	2.584
Feed slot angle [degrees]	45	45
SWAA Z-dimension [mm]	793.6	335.2
SWAA X-dimension [mm]	158.7	67.05
SWAA Y-dimension [mm]	96.06	40.52

Fig. 7. Radiation patterns of linear resonant center-fed 10-element uniform SWA arrays at 2.45GHz (blue) and 5.8 GHz (red).

The optimized array patterns for SWA arrays with Villeneuve distributions are shown in Figure 7. The blue line refers to 2.45GHz and the red to 5.8GHz. Their reflection coefficients (S11) are plotted versus frequency in Figure 8. Similarly, more linear resonant 10- and 20-slot element SWAAs with uniform and Villeneuve distributions were designed and simulated. Such arrays were designed to be used as subarrays for the required planar SWAA arrays by NASA and JAXA SPS models. The radiation patterns of a 20-slot linear uniform array with uniform and Villeneuve distributions are shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 8. Reflection coefficients (S11) of linear resonant center-fed 10-elements uniform SWA arrays for NASA (blue) and JAXA (red) SPS models.

Fig. 9. Radiation patterns of linear resonant 20-element uniform SWA arrays for uniform (blue) and Villeneuve (red) excitations.

IV. SWA PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The parameters of the previously described designs are summarized and presented in Tables V-VII. Tables V and VI show the pattern parameters for the slot complementary (dipole) linear and planar arrays of 10 and 20 element with uniform and Chebyshev distributions for both models. Table VII presents the antenna parameters of the linear SWA arrays with uniform and Villeneuve excitations. Studying and comparing the antenna parameters for the uniform SWA arrays concludes to:

- The HPBW and SLL of linear uniform arrays are approximately the same in Tables V and VI, and are very

close to those produced by the simulation of actual SWA arrays (Table VII).

- The pattern parameters for linear uniform arrays in Tables V and VII with tapered distributions are approximately the same for both Chebyshev (Table V) and Villeneuve (Table VII).
- The calculated pattern parameters, specifically the directivity D_o (maximum directive gain) and the 3dB HPBW in Table V, are compatible with the classical array theory, which states that for a linear uniform broadside array, if $N_d \gg \lambda$, then, $D_o = 2N_d/\lambda$, and $HPBW = 101.5\lambda/N_d$.
- The obtained relative bandwidth, shown in Table VII, is decreased to half when the number of elements is doubled from 10 to 20 for both uniform and Villeneuve

distributions, while the HPBW is getting narrower and halved when the number of elements is doubled.

- The planar SWA arrays presented in Table VI are exhibiting narrow beams in both principal planes and thus the overall directivity was increased and found to be slightly larger than the summation of directivities of their constituting linear arrays in dB scale, which is again compatible with the classical array theory.
- The bandwidth of all designed arrays in Table VII satisfied the bandwidth operational requirements for both SPS models (BW=100MHz), except the 20 element arrays at 2.45GHz, where the bandwidth was found to be approximately equal to 50MHz for both uniform and Villeneuve distributions.

TABLE V. LINEAR SLOT COMPLEMENTARY (DIPOLE) ARRAYS' SPECIFICATIONS

Pattern Parameters	NASA Model				JAXA Model			
	N=10		N=20		N=10		N=20	
	Uniform	Chebyshev	Uniform	Chebyshev	Uniform	Chebyshev	Uniform	Chebyshev
Half power beamwidth (HPBW) [deg]	7.05	7.79	3.42	3.68	7.76	8.40	3.8	4.05
Sidelobe level (SLL) [dB]	-13.3	-20.00	-13.4	-20.00	-13.14	-20.00	-13.28	-20.00
Directivity (Do) [dB]	11.6	11.4	14.6	14.4	11.3	11.1	14.2	14.1

TABLE VI. PLANAR SLOT COMPLEMENTARY (DIPOLE) ARRAYS' SPECIFICATIONS

Parameters	NASA Model				JAXA Model			
	10x10		20x20		10x10		20x20	
	Uniform	Chebyshev	Uniform	Chebyshev	Uniform	Chebyshev	Uniform	Chebyshev
Half power beamwidth (HPBW) [deg]	7.05x6.02	7.79x7.50	3.42x3.01	3.68x3.52	7.67x6.34	8.4x6.92	3.80x2.99	4.05x3.20
Sidelobe level (SLL) [dB]	-13.01	-20.30	-13.25	-20.31	-13.30	-20.40	-13.40	-20.33
Directivity (Do) [dB]	24.8	24.6	31	30.8	24.70	24.5	30.90	30.7

TABLE VII. SWAA SPECIFICATIONS

Specification	NASA Model				JAXA Model			
	N=10		N=20		N=10		N=20	
	Uniform	Villeneuve	Uniform	Villeneuve	Uniform	Villeneuve	Uniform	Villeneuve
Half power beamwidth (HPBW) [deg]	7.75	8.51	3.87	4.21	7.76	8.49	3.87	4.21
Sidelobe level (SLL) [dB]	-13.01	-20.61	-13.25	-20.51	-13.14	-20.40	-13.28	-20.37
Directivity (Do) [dB]	16.78	16.62	19.70	19.60	16.77	16.62	19.73	19.59
Bandwidth (below the -10 dB level) [MHz]	104.1	97.20	50.32	47.34	246.4	230.1	119.1	112.1
Relative bandwidth (%)	4.25	3.97	2.05	1.93	4.25	3.97	2.05	1.93

Practically, weight, dimensions, and gain are more critical than the bandwidth for SPS operations. Therefore, this study recommends the 20-element linear uniform SWAA to be the subarray of the planar square array for SPS transmitting antennas. Equation (11) can be used to calculate the total number of slots N_t on the proposed planar square arrays for both SPS models and the total number of 20x20 planar array modules required to cover the whole transmitting antenna area, whose diameter is 1Km for both SPS models. These calculations show that the required number of 20x20 planar array modules is approximately 260,658 modules for the NASA and 1,732,699 modules for the JAXA models. Accordingly, and due to the classical array theory calculations, the 3dB beamwidth (HPBW) was found to be approximately 0.007° and 0.003° for the transmitting antennas of NASA and JAXA SPS models, respectively, and the overall directivity (Do) was found to be approximately equal to 83.22dB and 90.7dB for the NASA and JAXA SPS models, respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the SPS operational requirements, several linear and planar uniform SWA arrays with uniform and tapered excitation distributions were designed and simulated using different software packages. The antenna patterns and parameters of the designed SWA arrays obtained from the slot complementary (dipoles) elements, based on Babinet's principle, were found to be quite similar to those obtained by the simulation of actual SWA arrays having the same parameters. Based on extensive calculations, a planar array of 20x20 slot elements was proposed to be a module for the completely planar SWA array to cover the 1Km diameter area of the transmitting antennas for both NASA and JAXA SPS models. The proposed transmitting antennas' parameters were found to fulfill the operational requirements for both SPS models. However, the antenna specifications of the proposed planar SWA array for the JAXA are better than for the NASA SPS model. Such transmitting antennas achieve pencil beam with very narrow HPBW in the principle planes, which is

approximately 0.007° and 0.003° for NASA and JAXA SPS models, respectively. Moreover, the achieved overall directivity was found to be approximately 83.22dB, and 90.7dB for NASA and JAXA SPS models, respectively. Experimental verification is planned for the future. Due to the higher operating frequency, the results confirmed that the antenna specifications of the proposed planar SWA array for the JAXA were better than for the NASA SPS model. Several SPS geometrical and technical challenges such as size, weight, cost, assembly, and launching are still under investigation. Smaller satellite constellations are some latest proposals to overcome some of these challenges.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. O. McSpadden and J. C. Mankins, "Space solar power programs and microwave wireless power transmission technology," *IEEE Microwave Magazine*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 46–57, Dec. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MMW.2002.1145675>.
- [2] D. M. Flounoy, *Solar Power Satellites*, 2nd edition. New York: Springer, 2011.
- [3] J. D. Dakora, I. E. Davidson, and G. Sharma, "Review of Modern Solar Power Satellite and Space Rectenna Systems," in *2020 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Computing and Data Communication Systems (icABCD)*, Aug. 2020, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/icABCD49160.2020.9183884>.
- [4] S. DebBarman, S. Gupta, and O. P. Das, "A Review: Space Based Solar Power (Sbsp) in Development of Smart City," *Social Science Research Network*, Rochester, NY, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 3621435. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3621435>.
- [5] J. A. Vedda and K. L. Jones, "Space-based Solar Power: A near-term Investment Decision," Center for Space Policy and Strategy, Oct. 2020.
- [6] "URSI White Paper on Solar Power Satellite (SPS) Systems and Report of the URSI Inter-Commission Working Group on SPS," URSI Inter-commission Working Group on SPS.
- [7] T. Hatsuda, K. Ueno, and M. Inoue, "Solar power satellite interference assessment," *IEEE Microwave Magazine*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 65–70, Dec. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MMW.2002.1145677>.
- [8] M. E. Bendib and A. Mekias, "Solar Panel and Wireless Power Transmission System as a Smart Grid for Electric Vehicles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5683–5688, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3473>.
- [9] H. Matsumoto, "Numerical estimation of SPS microwave impact on ionospheric environment," *Acta Astronautica*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 493–497, Aug. 1982, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0094-5765\(82\)90095-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0094-5765(82)90095-9).
- [10] J. O. McSpadden, L. Fan, and K. Chang, "A high conversion efficiency 5.8 GHz rectenna," in *1997 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest*, Jun. 1997, vol. 2, pp. 547–550, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWSYM.1997.602852>.
- [11] R. B. Vaganov, "Maximum power transmission between two apertures with the help of a wave beam," *Journal of communications technology & electronics*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 397–402, 1997.
- [12] N. Shinohara, J. Fujiwara, and H. Matsumoto, "Development of Active Phased Array with Phase-controlled Magnetrons," in *Proceedings of ISAP2000*, Fukuoka, Japan.
- [13] M. C. Hatfield and J. G. Hawkins, "Design of an electronically-steerable phased array for wireless power transmission using a magnetron directional amplifier," in *1999 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest (Cat. No.99CH36282)*, Jun. 1999, vol. 1, pp. 341–344, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWSYM.1999.779489>.
- [14] M. M. Nahas and M. Nahas, "Bandwidth and Efficiency Enhancement of Rectangular Patch Antenna for SHF Applications," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4962–4967, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3014>.
- [15] K. Hashimoto, K. Tsutsumi, H. Matsumoto, and N. Shinohara, "Space solar power system beam control with spread-spectrum pilot signals," *URSI Radio Science Bulletin*, vol. 2004, no. 311, pp. 31–37, Dec. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.23919/URSIRSB.2004.7909631>.
- [16] W. C. Brown and E. E. Eves, "Beamed microwave power transmission and its application to space," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 1239–1250, Jun. 1992, <https://doi.org/10.1109/22.141357>.
- [17] H. M. E. Misilmani, M. Al-Husseini, and M. Mervat, "Design of Slotted Waveguide Antennas with Low Sidelobes for High Power Microwave Applications," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research C*, vol. 56, pp. 15–28, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.2528/PIERC14121903>.
- [18] S. Murugaveni and T. Karthick, "Design of Slotted Waveguide Antenna for Radar Applications at X-Band," *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, vol. 3, no. 11, Nov. 2014.
- [19] S. Sekretarov and D. M. Vavriv, "A Wideband Slotted Waveguide Antenna Array for SAR Systems," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research M*, vol. 11, pp. 165–176, 2010, <https://doi.org/10.2528/PIERM10010606>.
- [20] G. A. Casula, G. Mazzarella, and G. Montisci, "Design of Shaped Beam Planar Arrays of Waveguide Longitudinal Slots," *International Journal of Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 2013, Feb. 2013, Art. no. e767342, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/767342>.
- [21] A. A. Eyadeh and M. N. Al-Ta'ani, "Performance Study of Wireless Systems with Switch and Stay Combining Diversity over α - η - μ Fading Channels," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5047–5055, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3100>.
- [22] H. R. D. Filgueiras, J. R. Kelly, P. Xiao, I. F. da Costa, and A. Cerqueira Sodré, "Wideband Omnidirectional Slotted-Waveguide Antenna Array Based on Trapezoidal Slots," *International Journal of Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 2019, Oct. 2019, Art. no. e3792980, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/3792980>.
- [23] L. Ripoll and L. Valdez, "Design and Simulation of a Slot Waveguide Array Antenna (SWAA) for Satellite Communications," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 519, no. 1, May 2019, Art. no. 012035, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/519/1/012035>.
- [24] A. K. Baghel, S. S. Kulkarni, and S. K. Nayak, "Efficient Modeling of DC-RF module of Space Solar Power Satellite with Improved Antenna design and Metasurface," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Microwaves, Antennas, Communications and Electronic Systems (COMCAS)*, Nov. 2019, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMCAS44984.2019.8958029>.
- [25] H. M. El Misilmani, M. Al-Husseini, and K. Y. Kaban, "Design procedure for planar slotted waveguide antenna arrays with controllable sidelobe level ratio for high power microwave applications," *Engineering Reports*, vol. 2, no. 10, 2020, Art. no. e12255, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eng2.12255>.
- [26] H. Benson and M. Jenkins, "Satellite Power System Concept Development and Evaluation Program Volume VI Construction and Operations," National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), Technical Memorandum 58233, 1981.
- [27] R. H. Dietz, G. D. Arndt, J. W. Seyl, L. Leopold, and J. S. Kelley, "Satellite power system: Concept development and evaluation program. Volume 3: Power transmission and reception. Technical summary and assessment," National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), Technical Memorandum 58238, Jul. 1981.
- [28] H. Matsumoto, "Research on Solar Power Station and Microwave Power Transmission in Japan: Technology and Strategy (invited)," presented at the 2001 Asia-Pacific Radio Science Conference (AP-RASC '01), Tokyo, Japan, Jan. 2001.
- [29] "Outline of the Basic Plan on Space Policy (Provisional Translation)," National Space Policy Secretariat, Cabinet Office, Japan, Jun. 2020.
- [30] R. Elliott, "An improved design procedure for small arrays of shunt slots," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 48–53, Jan. 1983, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.1983.1143002>.

Investigation of a Digital Hydraulic Valve Operated by Servo Motors

Adem Fatih Ozalp
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Karabuk University
Karabuk, Turkey
ademfatihozalp@karabuk.edu.tr

Refik Polat
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Karabuk University
Karabuk, Turkey
refikpolat@karabuk.edu.tr

Celalettin Cetinkaya
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Karabuk University
Karabuk, Turkey
c.cetinkaya06@hotmail.com

Muhammet Huseyin Cetin
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Konya Technical University
Konya, Turkey
mhcetin@ktun.edu.tr

Abstract-This paper describes a new type of digital hydraulic valve run by two servo motors. Digital hydraulics is a cutting-edge technology, which saves more exhausted energy than conventional hydraulic valves. It includes conventional valves, but its working principle is different. Similar or different size valves constitute a digital hydraulic valve assembly. When the assigned valves are opened, a certain amount of flow is obtained from the output of the valve assembly. To control a digital hydraulic valve, Pulse Number Modulation (PNM) Control technique is used for equal valve flow rates, while Pulse Code Modulation (PCM) is used for different valve flow rates. Valves are exerted by independently launched electric coils. Previous studies used controller board and external power booster circuits for coils. In this study, a new type of digital hydraulic valve is designed, manufactured, and tested with the PNM method. The studied valve body has two different valve groups. Every group includes 16 equal valves and 1 camshaft rotated by 1 servo motor. The servo motors are controlled by a PLC. The calculated performance index is found to be 5.1ms which is similar to the results of previous studies. The experimental results showed that the cam and servo motor controlled digital hydraulics is applicable to variable speed control hydraulic systems.

Keywords-hydraulic control; digital hydraulics; position control; valve design

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydraulic cylinders and hydraulic motors are used for lifting and turning heavy loads. Elevators, presses, excavators, buckets, and dams are common areas of use. When precise position control is required for lifting heavy or light loads, and the lifting system has limited space, hydraulic systems are applied instead of electric actuators. Proportional and servo valves are used for precise position control with a hydraulic cylinder. However, these high cost valves can easily break down due to contamination in the oil. This paper presents a hydraulic valve which can be used in precision position control

applications, can work in the performance of servo and proportional valves, is resistant to oil contamination, and saves more energy than the conventional valves. The proposed valve is tested for speed and position control with a hydraulic cylinder.

Pressurized flow valves have been highly investigated in order to increase the performance of a system. Pressure and flow rate change during the operation greatly affect the behavior of the system [1, 2]. On-off directional valves, proportional valves, servo valves are often used for a single hydraulic cylinder or a single motor. Authors in [3] used two independent proportional valves each for one port of a hydraulic cylinder, reducing the energy losses by 15%. Authors in [4] increased the controllability of the system by running the inlet and outlet ports of a hydraulic cylinder by 5 separate proportional valves. In addition, the efficiency of the system has increased. The lines to and from the cylinder were controlled by 4 proportional valves. Another valve saves the potential load energy that the cylinder lifts and increases the system efficiency by connecting the return line of the hydraulic cylinder to the system. Authors in [5] proved that parallel-connected on-off valves can be used as servo valves in the digital hydraulic method. In this method, the hydraulic system using water as fluid is operated with valves located in parallel. The valves have different flow rates and are controlled by the binary coding method. The data obtained in the experiment showed that velocity and position graphs are similar to the servo valve actuated system. However, it was found that the pressure shocks in the system are high.

Proportional and servo valves alone are generally used with a hydraulic cylinder, and a spool of the valve regulates the amount of flow through the valve. However, in digital hydraulics, the on-off valves just open and close and are more than one. The flow rate of each valve is a small amount of the total flow of the system. The flow rate of each valve may be

different or equal to the others'. If the valve flow rate is desired to be the same, valves with a very small flow rate are required in order to increase their accuracy, so the number of valves increases. If the valve flow rate is selected in multiples of 2 by the binary coding method, four valves will be sufficient instead of sixteen equal valves. The sensitivity will be 1/16 times. The Fibonacci (1: 1: 2: 3: 5) method is similar to the binary coding method and the flow rates are chosen using different coefficients. In this way, when the valve flow rate is selected as a coefficient of some numbers, pressure shocks occur during the opening and closing of the valves at system pressure. These pressure shocks cause undesirable results in system control, hydraulic system parts and make it difficult for the system to operate linearly [6].

Authors in [7] evaluated the hydraulic systems required in the ITER fusion reactor. They stated that the hydraulic system to be used in the reactor would take a narrow space, work in high radiation, and should carry high reliability and high sensitivity. They mentioned that the digital hydraulic method would be suitable for this because the system is capable of tolerating errors. When they compared the servo hydraulic system to the digital hydraulic system, they obtained similar position tracking results. However, the digital hydraulic system made oscillation movements when servo systems gave more linear results at low speeds. They stated that using more on-off valves should be used to solve the pressure fluctuation causing oscillations. When separate valves are placed differentially in the A and B pressure and tank lines to the system, all four flow lines can be controlled independently. Controller systems using 2-5 independent proportional valves instead of only one proportional valve are called programmable, multifunctional, independent line, and distributed line. Since the valve system is used differentially, these systems are energy efficient, and their losses are minimized. When a single proportional valve is used, the valve spool regulates the flow to the pressure line and tank line equally [8-10]. Digital hydraulic control method is superior compared to proportional and servo systems. In the case of a digital hydraulic system, when a valve fails, the system is capable of continuing operation.

Digital hydraulics systems are cheaper compared to proportional and servo systems and can cost even less if they are mass manufactured. They have the advantages of not requiring spool feedback as the proportional or servo valves [11-13]. The model-based controller system is used to control the digital hydraulic system. The controller operates based on a steady-state model and does not require dynamic modeling, so it does not make many calculations during the operation of the system. In this method, the control technique is based on reducing the previously calculated estimates in an optimal way by using the cost function method. During the operation of the system, the best reference command is determined by comparing the measurements taken from the position, pressure, and flow sensors with the estimated data to be operated with minimum energy, and the system is controlled according to [14-15]. Authors in [16, 17] conducted the experiments of a hydraulic system powered by a fixed displacement pump, working with a four-zone secondary controller and variable displacement hydraulic motor. In this system, it is not possible to produce a hydraulic cylinder with a

variable piston similar to its variable displacement motor in today's conditions. Instead, authors in [16] used telescopic independent pistons and cylinders. The cylinder is connected to a boom arm and has loads of 200kg, 150kg, 100kg, and 50kg on the arm. The system shows 60% reduction in energy losses compared to systems operated by proportional and servo valves. This system is well controlled at high speeds but faces problems at low speeds. In contrast to the previous systems, a safety valve and a second flow sensor outside the pump line are installed to measure energy efficiency. It was found that the energy saving of this experimental system is increased by reducing the energy loss in the pressurized flow to the tank. Authors in [18] operated a three-part hydraulic cylinder with 3 digital hydraulic control units including 8 on-off valves each. This system is operated by digital hydraulics and its energy loss is reduced by 66%. In the experimental system, the hydraulic cylinder is connected to a single degree of freedom lever, and the lever is required to keep fixed permanently.

Authors in [19] tested a lever mechanism with an electronic load sensing pressure system, a distributed digital hydraulic control unit, and a pressurized tank line. The system had a hydraulic accumulator connected to the tank line. The flow from the system to the tank was pressurized by a relief valve. The studied system's energy losses decreased by 53% to 71% compared to the proportional valve systems. Authors in [20] examined a system of miniature valves to lift a load of 50kg. Their system worked successfully for 15mm, 50mm, and 100mm position displacement. The coefficient found by dividing the derivative of the position error over time by velocity was determined as a success. Their obtained coefficient was 1.7ms which is much better than the 5.3ms found in [21]. In the newly developed digital hydraulic method, instead of a servo valve, simple on-off poppet valves with equal fluid flow rate are used. The total number of the poppet valves is at least 2. In order to reduce the total number of poppet valves, valves with different flow rates are selected in multiples of two (binary coding). Thus, instead of 16 open-close valves, the same process can be applied with 4 on-off valves. In the digital hydraulic control method, when one of the valves breaks down, the system continues to operate, and the operation of the system is not disrupted at all [19].

Controlling four or more valves at the same time with binary coding in PCM method causes undesired pressure fluctuations in the system. Other PNM methods use equal flow rate commercial valves that require more valves and more space in digital valve assembly. To solve that, custom made miniature valves are produced. This type of assembly is smaller compared to the commercially used valve assembly. Either commercial or custom-made valves require high performance electronic control cards and additional valves are added to the system to show a damping effect. Therefore, the complexity of the system increases [19, 21-24].

The above mentioned digital hydraulic valves involve independent control components for each small valve flow rate and that makes it even more complicated. The proposed valve has one camshaft and a servo motor for 16 same flow rate valves, which is better coordinated to control the valves.

II. CONTROL PRINCIPLE

The steady state model and the cost function presented in [5] are used to control the suggested valve. For the extending movement of the steady state, the equations of the system are:

$$Q_{N,P} = \sum_{i=1}^{np} u_{Pi} Q_{N,Pi} \quad (1)$$

$$Q_P = Q_{N,P}(u_P) \sqrt{P_S - P_A} = A_A \quad (2)$$

$$Q_T = Q_{N,T}(u_T) \sqrt{P_B} = A_B \quad (3)$$

$$F = A_A P_A - A_B P_B \quad (4)$$

$$z = [Q_{N,P}(u_P)] / [Q_{N,T}(u_T)] \quad (5)$$

$$\gamma = A_A / A_B \quad (6)$$

$$P_A = \frac{z^2 P_S + \gamma^2 F / A_B}{z^2 + \gamma^3} \quad (7)$$

$$P_B = \frac{\gamma z^2 P_S - z^2 F / A_B}{z^2 + \gamma^3} \quad (8)$$

$$v = \frac{Q_{N,P}(u_P)}{A_B} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma P_S - F / A_B}{z^2 + \gamma^3}} \quad (9)$$

$$W = Q_P \cdot P_S \quad (10)$$

For the retracting movement of the steady state, the equations of the system are:

$$P_A = \frac{\gamma^2 P_S + \gamma^2 F / A_B}{z^2 + \gamma^3} \quad (11)$$

$$P_B = \frac{\gamma^3 P_S - z^2 F / A_B}{z^2 + \gamma^3} \quad (12)$$

$$v = - \frac{Q_{N,T}(u_T)}{A_B} \sqrt{\frac{P_S + F / A_B}{z^2 + \gamma^3}} \quad (13)$$

where $Q_{N,P}(u_P)$ and $Q_{N,T}(u_T)$ are the nominal flow coefficients of the tank side and the pressure side that change with u_P and u_T which are the element vectors of $Q_{N,P}$ and $Q_{N,T}$. F is the force applied by the cylinder, P_S is the supply pressure, P_A is the piston side pressure of the hydraulic cylinder, P_B is the rod side pressure of the hydraulic cylinder, W is system energy and v is the hydraulic cylinder velocity.

Every poppet valve has an equal flow rate. Also, the elements of vectors of $Q_{N,P}$ and $Q_{N,T}$ consist of the flow rates of these valves. The system is controlled with the steady state equations and the cost function. The least error control input calculated from the cost function is applied to the servo motors. This function can be written as:

$$J(k) = [v_r(k) - \hat{v}(k)]^2 + K_{pd} [p_{dr}(k) - \hat{p}_d(k)]^2 + K_1 [\hat{p}_A(k-1) - \hat{p}_A(k)]^2 + K_2 [\hat{p}_B(k-1) - \hat{p}_B(k)]^2 \quad (14)$$

where $J(k)$ represents the calculated error for the given combination of input, v_r is the reference velocity, $\hat{\quad}$ circumflex is used to represent the calculated values of the below symbol, p_{dr} represents the downstream reference

pressure, K_{pd} is the weight of downstream pressure error, and K_1 and K_2 are the weights of pressure variation for the A and B sides of the cylinder.

The least error combination shows us the best control switch to achieve less error output. This combination has error vectors that correspond to the vector of $Q_{N,P}(u_P)$ and $Q_{N,T}(u_T)$ in the same row and column. Thus, less calculated error for the given reference value is applied to the system. Hydraulic systems are sensitive to disturbance and a closed-loop controller is efficient to obtain better results [26]. A closed-loop controller is used which can be written as:

$$v_{rc} = v_r + K_p (y_r - y) \quad (15)$$

where v_{rc} is closed-loop velocity reference, K_p is closed-loop gain, y_r is position reference, and y is the actual position.

A closed-loop controller is used to decrease velocity error (Figure 3). The studied valve is not able to change the direction of the piston, therefore a commercial directional valve is added to the system as shown in Figures 1, 4. The direction signal is shown as u_{dir} in Figure 3.

III. DESIGN OF THE VALVE

The studied hydraulic valve has two camshafts, and each one is driven by 1 servo motor. Each camshaft has 16 cams and is used to actuate the valve spools instead of 16 different coils independent of each other. Its rod and piston ports are connected to a commercial 4-way valve to channel the pressurized flow to the pump and tank ports of the used digital hydraulic valve. The studied digital valve has 2 groups of valves. Each group includes 16 equal rate poppet valves and 1 servo motor to exert the spool of the poppets. The studied valve cannot use the binary coding method because the camshaft is able to open the valves one after another while the binary coded method needs to open different flow rate valves independently. For example, the PCM method might run 4 valves, and these are placed as 1x, 2x, 4x, and 8x flow rate valves in a line. It will open 1x, 2x, 4x, and 8x flow rate valves to have 15x flow rate or will open 1x and 8x flow rate valves to have 9x flow rate. However, the used camshaft will open 16 pieces of 1x flow rate valves respectively to supply the 16x flow rate to the system, and the studied valve cannot be used for binary coding method. In addition, for binary coding method, a hydraulic system has a lot of pressure fluctuations while different flow rate poppets are opened. Instead, the studied valve will open the equal flow rate poppets successively by the servo motor with camshaft and the pressure shocks which are produced with the opening and closing of different flow rate valves will be decreased. Thus, pressure shocks that reduce the life and operating accuracy of the system will be prevented.

Two servo motors through camshafts exert the poppet spools in the valve group one by one and each camshaft has 16 different angled cams mounted. As shown in Figure 2, each cam makes an angle of 11,25° with the next cam. So, for every 11,25° turn of the camshaft, one poppet in the valve group opens. The valve poppet is pressed down by a running cam lobe and is lifted by spring force.

Fig. 1. Test setup.

Fig. 2. The valve assembly.

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the closed loop control system.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fifth-order polynomial is used for reference generation. Three different trajectories are chosen, namely 25mm, 50mm, and 100mm back and forth displacement with 2s movement time. Each trajectory is performed 4 times and Integral of Square Error (ISE) and maximum position error measurements are compared to see the performance of the system as shown in Table I. After several tests to acquire better cost function parameters K_{pd} , K_1 , and K_2 , they were found to be 5×10^{-16} . Nominal flow coefficients $Q_{N,PI}$ and $Q_{N,TI}$ are $1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3/(\text{s}\sqrt{\text{Pa}})$

In Figure 2, each camshaft faces two identical valve bodies, below and above. The left sides of the upper and lower body are for the pressure line and the right sides are for the tank line. Each valve body has 2 plates and spools fitted into them. The red color valve plate houses the higher pressurized line, and the orange color plate houses the lower pressurized line. Plates are connected to each other with bolts. Also, two plates hold up each valve body, camshafts, and servo motors from the sides with bolts. To minimize the valve, two opposite valve bodies are used.

IV. TEST SETUP

The test setup is shown in Figure 1. Loads are placed on the plate, which is attached to the vertical cylinder rod end. Steel frame houses the manufactured valve on the right side and a directional valve on the left side. The vertical hydraulic cylinder is set in the middle of the steel frame. Pressure transducers are connected to the hydraulic cylinder end ports and a linear position sensor is attached to the hydraulic cylinder rod end. A hydraulic pressure supply unit is connected to the valve with hydraulic hoses. The schematic of the hydraulic circuit is shown in Figure 4. The studied valve body (8, 9) and an on-off valve (10) are attached side by side on a frame. A double-acting hydraulic cylinder ($\text{Ø}40 \text{ mm} / \text{Ø}25 \text{ mm} \times 400 \text{ mm}$) is placed in the center of the frame to lift up loads. Its ports are from the pump and tank ports of the studied valve manifold. Hydraulic hoses are used to connect valves, cylinder, and hydraulic supply to each other. A separate hydraulic supply unit includes a 5.5kW electric motor and a 32.5lt/min fixed displacement pump (1) is used. Servo motors are run by an OMRON PLC unit. Measurements are taken by the same PLC unit. Two pressure transducers (6) are added to the rod pressure line and piston pressure line of the hydraulic cylinder (11) to measure the pressure of the cylinder chambers. To see the flow rate of the pump, a flowmeter (4) is used. Hydraulic cylinder displacement is measured with a linear position sensor (7). Tank (12), check valves (2), relief valve (3), and mechanic pressure gauge (5) are the other system components.

and $0.9 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3/(\text{s}\sqrt{\text{Pa}})$ respectively. Replaceable orifice cavity is designed on the valve manifold and the flow rate of the valve can be changed by using different diameter bores inside the orifices. However, it is hard to find the desired diameter commercial orifices, so commercial setscrews are drilled and used for the required orifices. It is highly difficult to drill the desired bore below $\text{Ø}1\text{mm}$ diameter in high strength commercial setscrews. Closed-loop gain is $K_p = 35/\text{s}$ and the used load mass is 50kg. Output data are filtered with a low-pass filter. For each position tracking experiment, position, position error, velocity, cylinder port pressures, and states of valve

openings are measured. Figure 5 depicts that 25mm position error is bigger than in longer distance trajectories. Both pressure outputs oscillate at maximum speed peak point. Maximum position error is 0.29mm at the speed stop point on back forward movement.

Fig. 4. Hydraulic circuit diagram.

Figure 6 presents the 50mm position tracking. The position error is better than the 25mm error. There are some pressure fluctuations at extending movement. Retracting movement makes more valve openings than the 25mm retracting movement. To decrease cavitation, the T port flow rate is smaller than the P port flow rate. Due to the area difference between the rod and piston side, more valve openings occur with a larger speed. Figure 7 shows the pressure fluctuations with both extending and retracting movement of 100mm displacement results. These fluctuations happen when it is getting closer around maximum speed peak point. Moreover, the valve opening number increases with speed. Besides, the best maximum position error by speed is 0.51mm. Previous studies compared their experiments with a performance index method calculated by dividing maximum position error by speed.

Fig. 5. 25mm displacement tracking results.

TABLE I. VALUES OF ISE AND MAXIMUM ERROR FOR POSITION

Trajectory	ISE (mm ² /s)	Δx (mm)
25 mm	0.14	0.29
50 mm	0.19	0.38
100 mm	0.26	0.51

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, a cam operated digital hydraulic valve is designed, manufactured, tested, and discussed. It is proven to be applicable to solenoid operated digital hydraulic valves, proportional, and servo operated valves.

Fig. 6. 50mm displacement tracking results.

Fig. 7. 100 mm displacement tracking results.

The results show promising values: the 100mm trajectory performance index is 5.1ms, which is similar to the value of 5.3ms found in [21]. On the other hand, the 25mm trajectory position error is not as good as the 100mm trajectory response because valve flow rates are chosen with a wide range which affects the speed and the position error. However, the valve is self-designed and manufactured allowing orifice change, and hence proper flow rates can be applied to the desired systems.

The 50mm tracking response error can also be tolerated by changing orifices. Also, by increasing valve number and using smaller flow rate valves, 25, 50, and 100mm tracking responses can give good results. On the other hand, the studied valve uses a vertically placed cam, and this results in a wider valve manifold with more valves. Cam operated valves cannot be placed crosswise like solenoid operated digital hydraulic valves. It can be concluded that the valve can present great

performance for bigger systems due to manufacturing limits. An essential result is achieved because cheaper components than the solenoid-operated digital hydraulic valves are used.

It is possible to obtain smoother movement with smaller flow rate of valves. This comes with a larger volume, but with a smaller price.

In summary, our first digital hydraulic valve is not as superior as the previously studied digital hydraulic valves due to the used cam and servo motor, but it can be improved with a smaller design and more valves while it has already showed its potential with inexpensive components.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study was funded by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) ARDEB 1002 Grant No 218M256.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. A. Venkataraman, K. Kanthavel, and B. N. Kumar, "Investigations of Response Time Parameters of a Pneumatic 3/2 Direct Acting Solenoid Valve Under Various Working Pressure Conditions," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 502–505, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.360>.
- [2] A. Gupta, N. Bokde, D. Marathe, and K. Kulat, "Leakage Reduction in Water Distribution Systems with Efficient Placement and Control of Pressure Reducing Valves Using Soft Computing Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1528–1534, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1032>.
- [3] J. Mattila and T. Virvalo, "Energy-efficient motion control of a hydraulic manipulator," in *Millennium Conference. IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation. Symposia Proceedings*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Apr. 2000, vol. 3, pp. 3000–3006 vol.3, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ROBOT.2000.846483>.
- [4] Bin B. Yao and S. Liu, "Energy-saving control of hydraulic systems with novel programmable valves," in *4th World Congress on Intelligent Control and Automation*, Shanghai, China, Jun. 2002, vol. 4, pp. 3219–3223 vol.4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WCICA.2002.1020129>.
- [5] M. Linjama, K. T. Koskinen, and M. Vilenius, "Accurate Trajectory Tracking Control of Water Hydraulic Cylinder with Non-Ideal on/off Valves," *International Journal of Fluid Power*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 7–16, Jan. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14399776.2003.10781151>.
- [6] M. Linjama, "Digital fluid power-state of the art," in *12th Scandinavian International Conference on Fluid Power*, Tampere, Finland, May 2011.
- [7] M. Linjama, J. Seppala, J. Mattila, and M. Vilenius, "Comparison of digital hydraulic and traditional servo system in demanding water hydraulic tracking control," in *Fluid Power and Motion Control*, 2008, pp. 393–403.
- [8] S. Liu and B. Yao, "Energy-Saving Control of Single-Rod Hydraulic Cylinders with Programmable Valves and Improved Working Mode Selection," in *SAE Transactions*, vol. 111, 2002, pp. 51–61.
- [9] H. Hu and Q. Zhang, "Realization of Programmable Control using a Set of Individually Controlled Electrohydraulic Valves," *International Journal of Fluid Power*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 29–34, Jan. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14399776.2002.10781135>.
- [10] A. Shenouda and W. J. Book, "Selection of Operating Modes of a Multi-Functional Hydraulic Device," in *International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition*, Orlando, FL, USA, Nov. 2005, pp. 99–109, <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2005-81687>.
- [11] M. Linjama, A. Laamanen, and M. Vilenius, "Is it time for digital hydraulics?," in *The Eight Scandinavian International Conference on Fluid Power*, Tampere, Finland, May 2003, pp. 347–366.
- [12] L. Siivonen, M. Linjama, and M. Vilenius, "Analysis of fault tolerance of digital hydraulic valve system," in *Power Transmission and Motion Control*, 2005, pp. 133–146.
- [13] A. Laamanen, L. Siivonen, M. Linjama, and M. Vilenius, "Digital flow control unit - An alternative for a proportional valve?," in *Bath Workshop on Power Transmission and Motion Control*, 2004, pp. 297–308.
- [14] M. Linjama and M. Vilenius, "Energy-efficient motion control of a digital hydraulic joint actuator," in *6th JFPS International Symposium on Fluid Power*, Tsukuba, Japan, Nov. 2005, vol. 2005, pp. 640–645, <https://doi.org/10.5739/isfp.2005.640>.
- [15] M. Linjama, M. Huova, O. Karhu, and K. Huhtala, "High-Performance Digital Hydraulic Tracking Control of a Mobile Boom Mockup," in *10th International Fluid Power Conference*, Dresden, Germany, Mar. 2016, pp. 37–48.
- [16] M. Linjama, H.-P. Vihtanen, A. Sipola, and M. Vilenius, "Secondary controlled multi-chamber hydraulic cylinder," in *11th Scandinavian International Conference on Fluid Power*, Linköping, Sweden, Jun. 2009.
- [17] H. Berg and M. Ivantysynova, "Design and testing of a robust linear controller for secondary controlled hydraulic drive," *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part I: Journal of Systems and Control Engineering*, vol. 213, no. 5, pp. 375–386, Aug. 1999, <https://doi.org/10.1243/0959651991540223>.
- [18] M. Huova, A. Laamanen, and M. Linjama, "Energy Efficiency of Three-Chamber Cylinder with Digital Valve System," *International Journal of Fluid Power*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 15–22, Jan. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14399776.2010.10781011>.
- [19] M. Huova and M. Linjama, "Energy efficient digital hydraulic valve control utilizing pressurized tank line," in *Proceedings of the 8th International Fluid Power Conference*, Dresden, Germany, Mar. 2012, pp. 111–122.
- [20] M. Paloniitty and M. Linjama, "High-linear digital hydraulic valve control by an equal coded valve system and novel switching schemes," *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part I: Journal of Systems and Control Engineering*, vol. 232, no. 3, pp. 258–269, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959651817750519>.
- [21] M. Linjama and M. Vilenius, "Improved Digital Hydraulic Tracking Control of Water Hydraulic Cylinder Drive," *International Journal of Fluid Power*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 29–39, Jan. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14399776.2005.10781209>.
- [22] T. Lantela and M. Pietola, "High-flow rate miniature digital valve system," *International Journal of Fluid Power*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 188–195, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14399776.2017.1358025>.
- [23] M. Linjama, M. Paloniitty, L. Tiainen, and K. Huhtala, "Mechatronic Design of Digital Hydraulic Micro Valve Package," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 106, pp. 97–107, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.06.013>.
- [24] S. Chekurov and T. Lantela, "Selective Laser Melted Digital Hydraulic Valve System," *3D Printing and Additive Manufacturing*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 215–221, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1089/3dp.2017.0014>.
- [25] M. Paloniitty, M. Linjama, and K. Huhtala, "Equal Coded Digital Hydraulic Valve System – Improving Tracking Control with Pulse Frequency Modulation," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 106, pp. 83–91, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.06.011>.
- [26] S. Babesse, "Design of Two Optimized Controllers of a Hydraulic Actuator Semi-Active Suspension: A Comparison Study," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4561–4565, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2836>.

Low Cost High Gain 8×8 Planar Array Antenna for 5G Applications at 28GHz

Hammad H. Alshortan
Department of Electrical Engineering
University of Hail
Hail, Saudi Arabia
en.hail1411@gmail.com

Abdullah S. Alogla
Department of Electrical Engineering
University of Hail
Hail, Saudi Arabia
abdullahogla@gmail.com

Mohamed A. H. Eleiwa
Department of Electrical Engineering
University of Hail
Hail, Saudi Arabia
mohamed.eleiwa@yahoo.com

Muhammad I. Khan
Department of Electrical Engineering
University of Hail
Hail, Saudi Arabia
mu.khan@uoh.edu.sa

Abstract- In next-generation mobile networks, hundreds of diverse devices aim to be interconnected, posing huge challenges in capacity, coverage, efficiency, reliability, and connectivity. These and other challenges are addressed at Radio Frequency (RF) parts such as several radiating unit antennas, with very fine beamforming capabilities along with the requirements of high gains and minimized size. This work presents an 8×8 Aperture Coupled Microstrip Patch Antenna (AC-MPA) in the form of a planar array modeled for the 28GHz frequency band with high gain and compact size, making it suitable for 5G networks. The antenna is designed using a substrate with overall dimensions of $74.6 \times 85.648 \times 0.107 \text{mm}^3$ and relative permittivity of $\epsilon_0 = 4.3$.

Keywords- 5G; microstrip patch antenna; planar array

I. INTRODUCTION

Moving towards 5G means increased data rate needs in order to meet the requirements of high quality applications such as video streaming, endless connectivity, and maximum capacity and coverage with reduced cost [1-3]. Antenna arrays in next generation networks for mobile communication at higher frequency spectra, such as the mm-Wave band, have received attention to meet and support the growing higher data rates with greater throughput and improved performance [4-6]. Very precise and proper consideration is needed regarding the antenna design of future wireless devices due to increased operating frequency [7-10]. It is very challenging to put more antenna elements in a confined specific space. Apart from design issues in terms of physical geometry, designing 5G broadband antennas, operating at multiple frequencies as candidates for 5G bands is a challenging issue. A number of array designs for 5G broadband communication have been proposed [11-13]. Almost all these antennas occupy large space in mobile phone devices operating at very few 5G bands. In this work, a high gain, compact size, and wider band antenna has been proposed. The structure of the antenna contains 64 elements in an 8×8 array arrangement. At different scanning

angles, it provides quite considerable radiation beams. The antenna has been modeled, simulated, and analyzed with the CST software [14]. Geometry and structure of the antenna are discussed in detail below.

The need of enhanced communication is essential due to the advancement and exponential growth of new technologies such as the massive Internet of Things (IoT), which are less power demanding and low-cost. These technologies consist of connections among hundreds of small size sensors, with specific application such as agriculture, smart cities, smart home, etc.. Services with specific purpose need very high throughput, lower latency, improved security, and reliability. Therefore, communication needs wide coverage and faster service [15]. The proposed spectrum for 5G by 3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project) consists of two bands, one below 6GHz (also known as the sub-six band) and one above 6GHz, typically from 26GHz to 40GHz (also known as millimeter wave) [15-16].

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

In order to fulfill the requirements of 5G networks in terms of flexibility, usefulness, proficiency, and integration, microstrip antennas are a considerable solution as they put together all the required characteristics. They are compacted and easy to develop on PCBs (Printed Circuit Boards) cost-effective solutions [17]. The primary structure of these antennas consists of a dielectric material both sides of which contain conducting sheets, one known as the radiating element (patch) and the other as the ground plane. An antenna array must be properly designed so that beam-forming and beam-steering abilities can be achieved. Each element in the array must be separately fed. The proposed antenna is a planar array with 64 elements formed with single elements of dimensions $9.4 \times 10.75 \times 0.107 \text{mm}^3$. Figure 1 depicts the diagram of the proposed 5G array antenna.

Corresponding author: Hammad Alshortan

Fig. 1. Single element patch antenna. (a) Top view, (b) side view.

III. SINGLE ELEMENT ANTENNA

Figure 2 shows the schematic diagram of the single element of antenna and Figure 3 shows its S11 result. These elements are further combined to form an antenna array. From the results it can be observed that return loss below -26dB is achieved at 28GHz and a bandwidth around 4GHz is obtained. The values of the parameters affect the performance of the antenna in terms of its matching and band. The optimized antenna parameters are shown in Table I.

Fig. 2. Array antenna single element multiple views: (a) top, (b) bottom, (c) side, and (d) end.

TABLE I. ANTENNA ELEMENT PARAMETER DESCRIPTION

Name	Parameter Value (mm)
Frequency	27.89
Port width	2.305
Port height	0.967
Wavelength center	10.749
Groundplane width	10.749
Groundplane length	9.352
Groundplane feed extension	-1.702
La	2.799
Wa	0.107
Lf	2.973
Wf	0.209
Lp	3.978
Wp	5.374
Eb	4.3
Et	1
Ls	0.478
Hb	0.107
Ht	0.859
Tanδb	0
Tanδt	0

IV. THE PROPOSED 5G ANTENNA ARRAY

The proposed design of the 5G antenna array with 64 elements formed using the discussed above single element is illustrated in Figure 4. The design has overall dimensions of 74.6×85.648×0.107mm³. As can be seen, 64 compact antenna components with distance d are used to make an array in the top segment of the PCB. The antenna is constructed on the FR-4 as bottom substrate and vacuum as the top part.

Fig. 3. S11 of the single element antenna.

Fig. 4. Array arrangement of the 8×8 (64 elements) antenna.

The antenna array was simulated in CST and the obtained values of S11 are shown in Figure 5. It can be observed that the designed antenna provides wide bandwidth more than 4.5GHz with an acceptable value of return loss at 28GHz, i.e. -28.5dB. Similarly, after the simulation of the antenna, a gain of 10.34dBi is achieved. Figure 6 gives the graphical representation of the 3D radiation pattern plot.

Fig. 5. S11 graph of the antenna array.

Fig. 6. 3D Radiation pattern (gain) at 28GHz.

The results obtained for the s-parameter of the 64-element antenna, simulated and analyzed in this work are shown in Figure 7. It can be observed that a very consistent and directional response is obtained and radiation with a very acceptable s-parameter is attained. Figures 8-9 show the E-plane and H-plane patterns in polar and Cartesian coordinates at 28GHz.

Fig. 7. S-parameter of the array arrangement in an 8x8 manner.

Fig. 9. H-plane pattern in (a) polar and (b) Cartesian coordinates.

The elements of the proposed array exhibit great performance. The efficiencies (radiation and total) of the proposed planar antenna array are exhibited in the related Figures. It can be observed that adequate efficiency outcomes are achieved at 25-30GHz. Higher than 97% radiation efficiency is gained. Likewise, more than 70% total efficiency has been attained for the introduced array elements [18-19]. It can also be observed that the proposed 5G antenna design offers steady radiation (patterns/beams) with enough gain [20].

V. COMPARISON WITH STATE OF THE ART ANTENNAS

A comparison with known related antennas is shown in Table II. It can be understood that the presented antenna is a low-cost antenna with much improved impedance bandwidth and acceptable peak gain in comparison with other known, state of the art antennas. The antenna has efficient planar structure, it is easy to implement and has a high directive gain. The presented antenna achieves an impedance bandwidth of 29% and a peak gain of 10.5dBi which outperforms the other antennas, and is adequate for millimeter-wave communication. It has a much wider bandwidth of 4.5GHz.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA WITH PREVIOUS WORKS

Ref./Year	Freq. band (GHz)	Bandwidth (GHz)	Peak gain (dBi)	Type
[21]/2021	24.25-29.5	6	0-5	Phased array
[22]/2018	39-49.3	2.0	5.5	Reflector, omni
[23]/2017	24-32	3.5	9	SIW/tapered slot
[24]/2016	57-67	-	2.2	Micro-strip
This work	25-30	4.5	10.5	Planar array

Fig. 8. E-plane pattern in (a) polar and (b) Cartesian coordinates.

VI. CONCLUSION

The aim of this work was to present a new and compact array with WB function for 5G mobile communication. Its arrangement includes 64 compact antennas in an 8×8 planar form, positioned at the top edge of the FR4-material mainboard. The fundamental properties of the proposed antenna were examined. The introduced array shows satisfactory features over its operation band, which can be appropriate for multi-mode communications in 5G systems. This antenna has a considerable bandwidth over 4.5GHz, a gain of about 10.5dBi and is offered as a solution for beamforming application scenarios. Moreover, not only it has small dimensions but also it possesses a modular structure that can be simply scalable for a greater number of ports and elements.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Osseiran *et al.*, "Scenarios for 5G mobile and wireless communications: the vision of the METIS project," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 52, no. 5, pp. 26–35, May 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2014.6815890>.
- [2] P. Gupta, "Evolution of mobile generations: 1G to 5G," *International Journal For Technological Research In Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 152–157, 2013.
- [3] W. Roh *et al.*, "Millimeter-wave beamforming as an enabling technology for 5G cellular communications: theoretical feasibility and prototype results," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 106–113, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2014.6736750>.
- [4] Y. Wang, J. Li, L. Huang, Y. Jing, A. Georgakopoulos, and P. Demestichas, "5G Mobile: Spectrum Broadening to Higher-Frequency Bands to Support High Data Rates," *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 39–46, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MVT.2014.2333694>.
- [5] N. Ojaroudi Parchin, M. Alibakhshikenari, H. Jahanbakhsh Basherlou, R. A. Abd-Alhameed, J. Rodriguez, and E. Limiti, "MM-Wave Phased Array Quasi-Yagi Antenna for the Upcoming 5G Cellular Communications," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 5, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 978, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9050978>.
- [6] N. Ojaroudi Parchin *et al.*, "Frequency Reconfigurable Antenna Array for MM-Wave 5G Mobile Handsets," in *Broadband Communications, Networks, and Systems*, Cham, 2019, pp. 438–445, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-05195-2_43.
- [7] N. Amitay, V. Galindo, and C. P. Wu, *Theory and analysis of phased array antennas*. New York, NY, USA: Wiley-Interscience, 1972.
- [8] N. Ojaroudiparchin, M. Shen, and G. F. Pedersen, "Multi-layer 5G mobile phone antenna for multi-user MIMO communications," in *2015 23rd Telecommunications Forum Telfor*, Belgrade, Serbia, Nov. 2015, pp. 559–562, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TelFOR.2015.7377529>.
- [9] W. Hong, K. Baek, Y. Lee, and Y. G. Kim, "Design and analysis of a low-profile 28 GHz beam steering antenna solution for Future 5G cellular applications," in *2014 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium (IMS2014)*, Tampa, FL, USA, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWSYM.2014.6848377>.
- [10] N. Ojaroudiparchin, M. Shen, S. Zhang, and G. F. Pedersen, "A Switchable 3-D-Coverage-Phased Array Antenna Package for 5G Mobile Terminals," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 15, pp. 1747–1750, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LAWP.2016.2532607>.
- [11] S. Zhang, I. Strytsin, and G. F. Pedersen, "Compact Beam-Steerable Antenna Array With Two Passive Parasitic Elements for 5G Mobile Terminals at 28 GHz," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 66, no. 10, pp. 5193–5203, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2018.2854167>.
- [12] R. Rodriguez-Cano, S. Zhang, and G. F. Pedersen, "Beam-steerable multi-band mm-wave bow-tie antenna array for mobile terminals," in *12th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP 2018)*, London, UK, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1049/cp.2018.0418>.
- [13] N. O. Parchin, R. A. Abd-Alhameed, and M. Shen, "Design of Low Cost FR4 Wide-Band Antenna Arrays for Future 5G Mobile Communications," in *2019 International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation (ISAP)*, Xi'an, China, Oct. 2019.
- [14] *CST Studio Suite 3D EM simulation and analysis software*. Simula.
- [15] *Making 5G NR a reality*. San Diego, CA, USA: Qualcomm, 2016.
- [16] G. A. Akpakwu, B. J. Silva, G. P. Hancke, and A. M. Abu-Mahfouz, "A Survey on 5G Networks for the Internet of Things: Communication Technologies and Challenges," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 3619–3647, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2779844>.
- [17] C. A. Balanis, *Antenna Theory: Analysis and Design*, 4th ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2016.
- [18] M. O. Dwairi, "Increasing Gain Evaluation of 2×1 and 2×2 MIMO Microstrip Antennas," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7531–7535, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4305>.
- [19] M. R. Rezoug, M. Benaouadj, D. Taibi, and R. Chenni, "A New Optimization Approach for a Solar Tracker Based on an Inertial Measurement Unit," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7542–7550, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4330>.
- [20] H. V. T. Chi, D. L. Anh, N. L. Thanh, and D. Dinh, "English-Vietnamese Cross-Lingual Paraphrase Identification Using MT-DNN," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7598–7604, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4300>.
- [21] X. Gu *et al.*, "Antenna-in-Package Integration for a Wideband Scalable 5G Millimeter-Wave Phased-Array Module," *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 682–684, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LMWC.2021.3071917>.
- [22] K. Fan, Z.-C. Hao, Q. Yuan, J. Hu, G. Q. Luo, and W. Hong, "Wideband Horizontally Polarized Omnidirectional Antenna With a Conical Beam for Millimeter-Wave Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 66, no. 9, pp. 4437–4448, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2018.2851363>.
- [23] B. Yang, Z. Yu, Y. Dong, J. Zhou, and W. Hong, "Compact Tapered Slot Antenna Array for 5G Millimeter-Wave Massive MIMO Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 6721–6727, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2017.2700891>.
- [24] M. H. Ghazizadeh and M. Fakhrazadeh, "60 GHz Omni-directional segmented loop antenna," in *2016 IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation (APSURSI)*, Fajardo, PR, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 1653–1654, <https://doi.org/10.1109/APS.2016.7696533>.

Photometric Ligature Extraction Technique for Urdu Optical Character Recognition

Majida Kazmi

Faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
majidakazmi@neduet.edu.pk

Fauzia Yasir

Faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
fyasir@neduet.edu.pk

Samreen Habib

Neurocomputation Lab, NCAI
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
habib@cloud.neduet.edu.pk

Muhammad Saad Hayat

Department of Electrical Engineering
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
hayat@cloud.neduet.edu.pk

Saad Ahmed Qazi

Faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering
Neurocomputation Lab, NCAI
NED University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
saadqazi@neduet.edu.pk

Abstract-Urdu Optical Character Recognition (OCR) based on character level recognition (analytical approach) is less popular as compared to ligature level recognition (holistic approach) due to its added complexity, characters and strokes overlapping. This paper presents a holistic approach Urdu ligature extraction technique. The proposed Photometric Ligature Extraction (PLE) technique is independent of font size and column layout and is capable to handle non-overlapping and all inter and intra overlapping ligatures. It uses a customized photometric filter along with the application of X-shearing and padding with connected component analysis, to extract complete ligatures instead of extracting primary and secondary ligatures separately. A total of ~2,67,800 ligatures were extracted from scanned Urdu Nastaliq printed text images with an accuracy of 99.4%. Thus, the proposed framework outperforms the existing Urdu Nastaliq text extraction and segmentation algorithms. The proposed PLE framework can also be applied to other languages using the Nastaliq script style, languages such as Arabic, Persian, Pashto, and Sindhi.

Keywords-ligature; holistic; Urdu OCR; Nastaliq; photometric filter; Urdu printed text images

I. INTRODUCTION

OCR technology is used to obtain machine editable text from text images. It allows the digitization of valuable printed and handwritten data covering cultural and historical milestones [1]. The commercial OCR systems that are now available report near to 100% recognition rates for languages

using the Latin alphabet, such as English, German, and French. Arabic and Chinese OCR systems are also well-developed. Despite the significant research interest in this area, OCR systems for many languages, including Urdu, are still in the development stage [2-3]. Urdu is Pakistan's official language having a large collection of valuable printed and handwritten data in the form of books, novels, magazines, and newspapers. Most of these valuable data are not accessible digitally. The Urdu language has 39 basic characters, 28 of which are Arabic. It is mostly written in the Nastaliq script style, which is a complex calligraphic style, written diagonally from right-to-left with varying inter and intra word spaces, overlapping of characters and strokes, incorrect or filled loops and lack of fixed baseline [4-5] as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Major challenges in Nastaliq text: Intra overlapping ligatures (red), inter overlapping ligatures (green), false and filled loops (blue) and missing baseline (yellow).

Urdu OCR is primary composed of five stages: Image acquisition, pre-processing, segmentation, classification and recognition, and post-processing [6]. Image acquisition collects digital images through camera shots, scanned text images, or

Corresponding author: Majida Kazmi

generated synthetic images [6]. Pre-processing aims to enhance the quality of an acquired image [6]. Noise and skew removal, binarization, contrast enhancement, etc. are mainly performed in this step with the use of classic image processing techniques. Segmentation decomposes a source image into characters, ligatures, or words [7-8]. This step usually employs projection profile and Connected Component Analysis (CCA). Classification aims to correctly classify the extracted/segmented features (ligatures, characters, words, etc.). The most common classifier methods are Decision Tree (DT), Statistical Classifier (SC), Neural Networks (NNs) [9, 10], Hidden Markov Models (HMMs), and Support Vector Machines (SVMs). Finally, post-processing corrects the recognition errors in the obtained text [10]. The techniques used for OCR post-processing include manual error correction, dictionary-based error correction, and context-based error correction [12-13].

Among the above stages, segmentation at character, ligature, or word level is the most challenging stage in Urdu OCR. Based on these levels, Urdu OCR can be divided into two categories: analytical approach at character level [14-15] and holistic approach at ligature level [7, 16-17]. The analytical approach segments text at character level either explicitly or implicitly. The explicit segmentation requires an extensive knowledge of characters as it explicitly divides handwritten or printed text into characters. Many researchers have adopted the explicit character segmentation [17-21]. On the other hand, implicit segmentation is an integration of the segmentation and recognition processes. Successful work has been reported by researchers for implicit segmentation [22-26] due to the smaller number of segments. However, both algorithms require a massive amount of training data for better results. The holistic approach is also referred to as segmentation-free method. It extracts at ligature or word level. Groups of isolated (non-joiner) characters and non-isolated (joiner) characters (Figure 2(a)) are termed as ligatures. These ligatures are grouped to form words. Ligatures are further classified as primary and secondary ligatures. Primary ligatures represent the main body of a word, while dots or diacritic marks are the secondary ligatures (Figure 2(b)).

Fig. 2. Word breakdown. (a) Ligatures in an example word, (b) ligature components.

Avoiding character level segmentation has made the holistic method extremely popular [3, 27-32]. Authors in [27] followed the projection technique for text line extraction. The main body and diacritics were identified based on the distance between the horizontal base and the average line. The

technique was tested on a small data set that was not specific to Nastaliq script, consisting of 1050 single characters and ligatures, with 98.86% accuracy. Authors in [28] used the horizontal projection technique. CCA was applied before text segmentation. The horizontal span of each secondary component on the baseline was calculated for the re-association of diacritics to their respective primary ligature. However, this approach assumed to work on text files instead of text images to extract complete ligatures. Similarly, authors in [29] applied the vertical projection profile method for the association of secondary ligatures by calculating the start and end point of diacritics. The proposed method reported 100% and 99% accuracy in baseline identification and ligature extraction respectively on scanned images with 48 font size but this technique ignores intra-overlapping ligatures and is also font size dependent.

Authors in [3] employed the horizontal projection method along with dilation to merge secondary and primary ligatures before line separation from the image. Authors in [30] used only 300 ligature samples to evaluate their proposed method, reporting 91.3% accuracy in segmentation and 78% in diacritics association. Authors in [31] proposed an extraction ligature technique based on 6 heuristic conditions reporting an accuracy of 99.02% on 45 images. Authors in [32] proposed the line segmentation technique with the connected component analysis method on images to collect width, height and centroids of ligatures reporting 99.80% accuracy. However, this technique does not segment multi-column scripts and overlapped inter and intra ligatures. Many recognition techniques carry out separate classifications of primary and secondary components [3, 27-32] to reduce the number of distinct recognizable classes. Such techniques face significant challenges in re-associating the secondary components with their primary components to recognize the entire ligature. The complexity at character segmentation has shifted the focus towards the holistic approach, i.e. the recognition of words or ligatures in the text. Segmenting text at the character level is more complex than the recognition of words and ligatures due to character overlapping, varying inter and intra word spaces, context sensitivity, different forms of characters according to their position in a word or a ligature, and the cursive script style. The literature review reveals that Urdu OCR is an open field for the researcher to design a system capable of incorporating factors such as intra and inter ligature overlapping, multi-column text images with borders, font variation, and mass data of ligatures for classification.

An efficient ligature extraction technique for Urdu OCR is proposed in this paper. The proposed method is capable to extract complete ligatures efficiently unlike separating primary and secondary components. The proposed technique is independent of font size and column layout, and is capable to handle all overlapping and non-overlapping ligatures by addressing the issue of intra overlapped ligatures as well as the complex association of the secondary components. It extracts complete ligatures, rather than separating primary and secondary components, thus secondary ligatures do not need to reassociate with their primary ligature in the classification and recognition steps. The proposed framework is designed for

Urdu but is applicable to other languages that follow the Nastaliq style, such as Arabic, Persian, Pashto, and Sindhi.

II. THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed framework for ligature extraction is depicted in Figure 3. It consists of 3 steps: image acquisition, image binarization, and PLE. Urdu printed text images from novels, religious books written in Nastaliq style, in single and double columns and varying font sizes were downloaded from different sources [33] and are referred to as I_{img} . First, the I_{img} is converted into binarized images I_{th} by using hard thresholding. The resultant I_{th} is a mono-chrome image with white background and black text (Figure 4). Then, an efficient process of PLE is applied on each I_{th} .

Fig. 3. Framework for Urdu ligature extraction.

A. Photometric Ligature Extraction (PLE)

The proposed PLE used a customized photometric filter which is specifically designed to decompose an image based on the photometric similarity. The stepwise description of PLE process follows:

- In the first step, PLE deploys a photometric filter to extract text lines (L_{lines}) from the image (I_{th}). The algorithm in Figure 4 demonstrates the working of the photometric filter. This filter scans the binarized image from top to bottom to detect text using the logical AND operator. The size of the photometric filter is adjusted with the width (W) of the image as $(1 \times W)$. The output of the photometric filter is then saved in an array. The resultant array is a stream of zeroes and ones, on which unary AND operation is performed to get a single bit value, i.e. 0 or 1. The 0 value indicates the presence of black pixel/s in the row, otherwise the value will be 1.
- In the second step, the image L_{lines} is first rotated counterclockwise by 90° . The photometric filter is then applied to each line of L_{lines} to extract both overlapped and non-overlapped ligatures.
- The overlapped ligatures are corrected in this step by applying X-shear transformation and padding simultaneously on each L_{lig} to overcome the most

challenging issue of inter and intra ligatures overlapping. The output of this step consists of the sheared and padded ligatures $L_{sheared-lig}$.

- In this step, the $L_{sheared-lig}$ images are classified into two classes based on the extent value of the first encountered ligature in image using CCA. Height, width, centroid, etc. are major properties obtained through the CCA method. The developed methodology utilized another component property termed as extent which is defined as the ratio of contour area to the bounding rectangle area. The extent value is a key feature in distinguishing secondary and primary ligatures with 99% accuracy. If the extent value of ligature is less than the hard threshold value, then dilatation operation is carried out on the encountered ligature producing $L_{ligs, dilated}$. This process reduces the distance between the primary and the secondary component of a ligature.
- In the last step, the photometric filter is again applied to all dilated and non-dilated ligatures $L_{ligs,dilated}$ and $L_{ligs,non-dilated}$ to extract complete ligatures as final output $L_{extracted-ligs}$.

```

Input: UrduPrintedTextImages { $I_{img}$ }
Output: SegmentedLines { $L_{lines}$ }
for each image do
    Rows=height of image, Set Index=0
    Apply thresholding & saved as binarized image
    Construct Photometric filter [ $1 \times W$ ] size
    Background pixel values are co-efficient of filter
    while Index < Rows do
        Apply AND operation on each row
        res=resAND.getAND(Filter, thresholdedImg,)
        if res==0 then
            startLine=getRowvalue(i)
            Index++
            while res!=0 do
                endLine=getRowvalue(i)
                Index++
            end
            cropLine=thresholdedImg[startLine:endLine]
            Append to the list of extracted line (Lline)
        end
        Index++
    Return extracted lines from image
    
```

Fig. 4. The photometric filter algorithm.

Fig. 5. The result of image binarization (I_{th}) on the input image I_{img} .

B. Demonstration of the Proposed PLE

The stepwise demonstration of the proposed PLE technique is shown in Figure 6. The input of the PLE technique is a mono-chrome image with white background and black text (Figure 5).

Fig. 6. PLE framework illustration. (a) An extracted line (L_{line}). (b) Segmented ligatures from the sentence in (a). The red encircled ligatures are overlapped. (c) The overlapping issue of ligatures obtained in (b) is resolved by X-shearing of ligatures encircled as green. (d) List of ligatures ($L_{lig,dilated}, L_{lig,non-dilated}$) after morphological operation (dilation). (e) Correctly extracted ligatures ($L_{extracted-ligs}$) after PF applied on ($L_{lig,dilated}, L_{lig,non-dilated}$).

In the first step, text lines are extracted one by one from the text image by applying the photometric filter (Figure 6(a)). In the next step, each extracted line is first rotated counterclockwise and then again passes through the photometric filter to extract both overlapped (marked as red circle) and non-overlapped ligatures (Figure 6(b)). The issue of inter and intra overlapping is resolved (see Figure 6(c), marked as green circles) by applying X-shearing and padding simultaneously on each ligature. Figure 6(d) depicts the list of

dilated and non-dilated ligatures. The dilation process reduces the distance between the primary and secondary component of a ligature. Finally, the photometric filter is again applied on these ligatures to get the final output as shown in Figure 6(e). This step will further enhance the correct separation of ligatures.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The proposed Urdu ligature extraction framework was evaluated on downloaded Urdu printed text images. The technique was tested on a total of 600 novel and book images. The working dataset mainly comprised of non-overlapping lines with no boundary across images. First, the photometric filter was applied on the images and extracted lines with an accuracy of 99.6%. A total of 13,200 lines were extracted from 600 images. These lines were then segmented into ligatures. A total of 267,800 ligatures were extracted after the complete execution of all the steps of the proposed PLE with an overall accuracy of 99.4%. Table I compares the proposed ligature extraction framework with previously reported methods. Authors in [27] evaluated their approach on 1050 ligatures with 98.86% accuracy in primary and secondary stroke extraction. Authors in [29] achieved 99% accuracy in ligature and diacritics extraction. Authors in [30] tested their system on 300 sample images out of which 274 were segmented correctly with 91.3% accuracy. Authors in [30] analyzed 45 Urdu images to classify and associate the connected components with 99.02% accuracy. Authors in [32] used 10,063 text lines to test their algorithm and reported an accuracy of 99.8%.

However, as discussed above, due to the limited data set of ligatures, researchers have mostly deployed algorithms on their own datasets to check the accuracy of ligature segmentation/extraction. Therefore, the accuracy depends upon the complexity of the text images used for segmentation and re-association of primary and secondary components. Segmentation algorithms achieving segmentation accuracy near 99% apply CCA for primary and secondary component segmentation in [28, 31-32] and projection profile method in [3, 27, 29-30] and then reassociate the secondary components. These studies also ignore the extraction of inter overlapped ligatures. The last row of Table I presents the findings of the proposed technique. The proposed solution resolved the problem of inter ligature overlapping with an accuracy of 99.4%. However, the efficiency of the proposed method is reduced due to the redundant use of the word جو . This complete ligature remains unaffected even after X-shearing because the primary component Alif "ا" lies in the region of the second main component 'ک' and the diacritics also overlap with the neighboring primary components. It was observed that spacing between diacritics that lie below the main body sometimes leads to incorrect line segmentation.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an efficient ligature extraction technique for the extraction of Urdu ligatures in Nastaliq fonts. The technique used a customized photometric filter along with the application of X-shearing and padding with CCA that result in the efficient extraction of overlapped and non-overlapped ligatures. The proposed framework achieves an accuracy of

99.4%. The efficiency of PLE technique can be enhanced by overcoming the association of secondary ligatures to respective main component before the extraction of text lines. This work

can also be deployed for other Nastaliq script-based languages like Persian, Pashto, Saraiki, Panjabi, etc..

TABLE I. COMPARISON WITH RELEVANT HOLISTIC APPROACHES

Work	Ligature Extraction		Limitations	Accuracy (%)	Extracted overlapped ligatures
	Technique	Result			
[32]	CCA	Separate primary and secondary components	Declares the secondary ligature as primary ligature when the size exceeds the threshold value	99.8	No
[30]	PP	Separate primary and secondary components	- Extracted only 300 ligatures - Low diacritics association accuracy	91.3	No
[31]	CCA	Separate primary and secondary components	- Relies on zonal information - Tested on only 45 images	99.02	No
[29]	PP	Separate primary and secondary components	- Cannot extract overlapped ligatures - Dependent on font size of 48	99.0	No
[27]	PP	Separate primary and secondary components	- Did not specify the script style - The system was tested on 1050 ligatures	98.86	No
[28]	CCA	Separate primary and secondary components	The proposed method was directly tested on text files	97.4	No
Proposed PLE	Photometric filter, X-shearing and stretching, CCA, and dilation	Complete ligature extraction	- Uneven baseline recognition - Narrow spacing between the ligatures of the word which reduces efficiency	99.4	Yes

CCA: Connected Component Analysis, PP: Projection Profile

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Wali and S. Hussain, "Context Sensitive Shape-Substitution in Nastaliq Writing System: Analysis and Formulation," 2007, pp. 53–58, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-6268-1_10.
- [2] S. T. Javed and S. Hussain, "Segmentation Based Urdu Nastaliq OCR," in *Progress in Pattern Recognition, Image Analysis, Computer Vision, and Applications*, 2013, pp. 41–49, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-41827-3_6.
- [3] I. U. Din, Z. Malik, I. Siddiqi, and S. Khalid, "Line and Ligature Segmentation in Printed Urdu Document Images," presented at the 3rd International Conference on Computational and Social Sciences, Oct. 2015.
- [4] S. Naz, A. I. Umar, S. B. Ahmed, S. H. Shirazi, M. Imran Razzak, and I. Siddiqi, "An Ocr system for printed Nasta'liq script: A segmentation based approach," in *17th IEEE International Multi Topic Conference 2014*, Dec. 2014, pp. 255–259, <https://doi.org/10.1109/INMIC.2014.7097347>.
- [5] H. R. Khan, M. A. Hasan, M. Kazmi, N. Fayyaz, H. Khalid, and S. A. Qazi, "A Holistic Approach to Urdu Language Word Recognition using Deep Neural Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7140–7145, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4143>.
- [6] N. H. Khan and A. Adnan, "Urdu Optical Character Recognition Systems: Present Contributions and Future Directions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 46019–46046, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2865532>.
- [7] S. Chanda and U. Pal, "English, Devnagari and Urdu Text Identification," in *Proc. international conference on document analysis and recognition*, 2005, pp. 538–545.
- [8] A. Rana and G. S. Lehal, "Offline Urdu OCR using Ligature based Segmentation for Nastaliq Script," *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 35, pp. 1–9, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2015/v8i35/86807>.
- [9] M. Alghobiri, "A Comparative Analysis of Classification Algorithms on Diverse Datasets," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2790–2795, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1952>.
- [10] S. R. Basha, J. K. Rani, and J. J. C. P. Yadav, "A Novel Summarization-based Approach for Feature Reduction Enhancing Text Classification Accuracy," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5001–5005, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3173>.
- [11] I. A. Doush, F. Alkhateeb, and A. H. Gharaibeh, "A novel Arabic OCR post-processing using rule-based and word context techniques," *International Journal on Document Analysis and Recognition (IJ DAR)*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 77–89, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10032-018-0297-y>.
- [12] Y. Bassil and M. Alwani, "OCR Post-Processing Error Correction Algorithm using Google Online Spelling Suggestion," *arXiv:1204.0191 [cs]*, Apr. 2012, Accessed: Dec. 01, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1204.0191>.
- [13] K. Kukich, "Techniques for automatically correcting words in text," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 377–439, Dec. 1992, <https://doi.org/10.1145/146370.146380>.
- [14] S. Naz, K. Hayat, M. Imran Razzak, M. Waqas Anwar, S. A. Madani, and S. U. Khan, "The optical character recognition of Urdu-like cursive scripts," *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 1229–1248, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patcog.2013.09.037>.
- [15] S. A. Husain, "A multi-tier holistic approach for Urdu Nastaliq recognition," in *International Multi Topic Conference, 2002. Abstracts. INMIC 2002.*, Karachi, Pakistan, Dec. 2002, pp. 84–84, <https://doi.org/10.1109/INMIC.2002.1310191>.
- [16] S. T. Javed, S. Hussain, A. Maqbool, S. Asloob, S. Jamil, and H. Moin, "Segmentation Free Nastaliq Urdu OCR," *International Journal of Computer and Information Engineering*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 1514–1519, Oct. 2010.
- [17] U. Pal and A. Sarkar, "Recognition of printed Urdu script," in *Seventh International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition, 2003. Proceedings.*, Edinburgh, UK, Aug. 2003, pp. 1183–1187, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDAR.2003.1227844>.
- [18] Z. Ahmad, J. K. Orakzai, and I. Shamsheer, "Urdu compound Character Recognition using feed forward neural networks," in *2009 2nd IEEE International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology*, Beijing, China, Aug. 2009, pp. 457–462, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSIT.2009.5234683>.
- [19] S. A. Sattar, S. Haque, and M. K. Pathan, "A Finite State Model for Urdu Nastaliq Optical Character Recognition," *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 116–122, 2009.
- [20] S. T. Javed, "Investigation into a segmentation-based OCR for the Nastaleeq writing system," M.S. thesis, National University of Computer and Emerging Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan, 2007.
- [21] S. Mir, S. Zaman, and M. W. Anwar, "Printed Urdu Nastaliq Script Recognition Using Analytical Approach," in *2015 13th International*

- Conference on Frontiers of Information Technology (FIT), Islamabad, Pakistan, Dec. 2015, pp. 334–340, <https://doi.org/10.1109/FIT.2015.65>.
- [22] S. B. Ahmed, S. Naz, M. I. Razzak, S. F. Rashid, M. Z. Afzal, and T. M. Breuel, "Evaluation of cursive and non-cursive scripts using recurrent neural networks," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 603–613, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-015-1881-4>.
- [23] R. P. Thakkar Mitesh, "Handwritten Nastaleeq Script Recognition with BLSTM-CTC and ANFIS method," *International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology*, vol. 11, no. 3, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.14445/22312803/IJCTT-V11P128>.
- [24] S. Naz *et al.*, "Offline cursive Urdu-Nastaliq script recognition using multidimensional recurrent neural networks," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 177, pp. 228–241, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2015.11.030>.
- [25] S. Naz *et al.*, "Urdu Nastaliq recognition using convolutional–recursive deep learning," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 243, pp. 80–87, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2017.02.081>.
- [26] S. Naz, A. I. Umar, R. Ahmad, S. B. Ahmed, S. H. Shirazi, and M. I. Razzak, "Urdu Nastaliq text recognition system based on multi-dimensional recurrent neural network and statistical features," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 219–231, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-015-2051-4>.
- [27] S. Sardar and A. Wahab, "Optical character recognition system for Urdu," in *2010 International Conference on Information and Emerging Technologies*, Karachi, Pakistan, Jun. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIET.2010.5625694>.
- [28] N. Sabbour and F. Shafait, "A segmentation-free approach to Arabic and Urdu OCR," *Proc. SPIE*, vol. 8658, p. 86580N, Feb. 2013.
- [29] S. Nazir and A. Javed, "Diacritics Recognition Based Urdu Nastalique OCR System," *The Nucleus*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 361–367, Sep. 2014.
- [30] A. F. Ganai and A. Koul, "Projection profile based ligature segmentation of Nastaleeq Urdu OCR," in *2016 4th International Symposium on Computational and Business Intelligence (ISCBI)*, Olten, Switzerland, Sep. 2016, pp. 170–175, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCBI.2016.7743278>.
- [31] G. S. Lehal, "Ligature Segmentation for Urdu OCR," in *2013 12th International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition*, Washington, DC, USA, Aug. 2013, pp. 1130–1134, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDAR.2013.229>.
- [32] I. Ahmad, X. Wang, R. Li, M. Ahmed, and R. Ullah, "Line and Ligature Segmentation of Urdu Nastaleeq Text," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 10924–10940, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2703155>.
- [33] "Kutubistan," *Kutubistan*. <https://kutubistan.blogspot.com/> (accessed Dec. 01, 2021).